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Special issue: Empirical translation and interpreting studies

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Introducing the special issue: Empirical translation and interpreting studies

This special issue of the *SKASE Journal of Translation and Interpretation* is a thematic issue devoted to empirical translation and interpreting studies. It brings together a selection of eleven papers originally presented at the *Translation in Transition 2024* conference in Batumi, Georgia.

The special issue places particular emphasis on two directions: on the one hand, low-resourced and less-researched language pairs, which present unique challenges due to the scarcity of data and limited existing research, and, on the other hand, an interplay between different methods and data types. This special issue combines corpus-based product research with experimental process research in translation studies. Together, these directions aim to push the boundaries of translation studies by integrating innovative research methodologies.

The contributions of this special issue are grouped into four thematic sections. The first section, Machine Translation and further AI tools in Translation Studies, includes three studies that explore the role of machine translation and artificial intelligence in translation processes and outputs. They address questions of evaluation, simplification, and tool use across different groups of translators and learners.

Longhui Zou and **Ali Saeedi** compare GPT-4o and Google Translate using the American Translators Association (ATA) certification framework for English–Chinese and English–Arabic. Combining automatic evaluation with human assessment, their study shows how performance varies across systems and languages and highlights the value of human judgment in capturing nuanced issues such as idiomaticity and rhetorical expression.

Sarah Ahrens, **Silvana Deilen**, **Sergio Hernández Garrido**, **Ekaterina Lapshinova-Koltunski** and **Christiane Maaß** evaluate intralingual machine translation into Plain German in the health domain. By comparing MT outputs with human translations and original texts, they demonstrate that domain- and task-specific fine-tuning improves quality, while general-purpose systems such as ChatGPT perform less reliably.

Athanasios Breskas, **Silvia Hansen-Schirra** and **Dimitrios Kapnas** investigate how school pupils and university students use machine translation tools and AI systems like ChatGPT in translation tasks. Collecting keylogging data, they show that students deploy tools more strategically and effectively than pupils, underlining that language competence remains essential for evaluating and using AI outputs.

The studies in the second section, Cognitive Studies of Translation, examine how translators' behaviour, ideology, and directionality shape cognitive load and translation processes.

Michael Carl, **Takanori Mizowaki**, **Aishvarya Ray** and **Masaru Yamada** introduce the concept of a Behavioural Translation Style Space (BTSS), a hierarchical structure that maps observable behaviour such as gaze and keystroke patterns to higher-level cognitive and affective processes. The model also serves as a foundation for computational agents that simulate the temporal dynamics of human translation.

Fatemeh Parham and **Mina Mirzaee** investigate the potential effect of translators' ideology and cognitive abilities on cognitive load during the translation process. Using eye-tracking and pupil-diameter measures, they show both ideology and cognitive ability significantly influence average pupil diameter, suggesting that translators experience higher cognitive load when their ideological stance aligns with the translation brief, and when they possess higher cognitive capacity.

Zoë Miljanović, Fabio Alves, Celina Brost and Stella Neumann study directionality effects in English–German translation using keystroke-logged data. Their results reveal that translations into the L1 involve more extensive editing procedures than translations into the L2, while pause patterns vary by register.

The third section of this special issue consists of three corpus-based studies of translation.

Khatuna Beridze analyses image metaphors in two English translations of Shota Rustaveli’s 12th-century Georgian poem. Drawing on, amongst others, cognitive linguistics and anthropology, she frames translation as cultural-cognitive evolution. The study contributes to Cognitive Metaphor Studies, as well as corpus-based Cognitive Translation Studies, situating translation as an act of cultural and cognitive evolution.

Mirela Imamovic, Silvana Deilen, Dylan Glynn and Ekaterina Lapshinova-Koltunski examine the translation of evaluative expressions from English to German in TED talk subtitles. Using Appraisal Theory and manual annotation, they find a general preference for equivalence in the translation of evaluative expressions, alongside signs of both “shining-through” from English and adaptation to German linguistic norms. Their study contributes to understanding the role of evaluative language in translation and complement existing research on translation strategies of evaluative language.

Olga Davis, Muhammad Ahmed Saeed, Dimitris Asimakoulas and Sabine Braun explore the under-researched practice of extended audio description. Combining natural language processing, qualitative user research, and think-aloud protocols, they show how so-called paused commentaries has the potential to offer a more informative viewing experience to conventional user groups and an opportunity to repurpose audio description as assistive commentaries for a wider range of audiences.

The special issue concludes with a section on interpreting.

Christina Pollkläsener, Maria Kunilovskaya and Elke Teich investigate the occurrence of filler particles in English–German interpreting. Their findings show that surprisal of following words is a good predictor of filler particles in interpreting.

The special issue winds up with a contribution by **Adeleh Mirzaee, Razavi Mousavi, Saeed Mir, Fatemeh Parham and Mehrdad Dadgostar**, who examine the impact of automatic speech recognition (ASR) on interpreters’ cognitive load using fNIRS measures. Their results indicate that using ASR reduces processing effort compared to unaided interpreting, though interpreters’ subjective perceptions do not always align with neural data.

The guest editors

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Directionality in translation: Throwing new light on an old question

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Abstract

Investigating directionality in translation from an empirical-experimental perspective has long occupied translation studies scholars. Most empirical studies about translating from L1 into L2 or from L2 into L1 use the time spent on the task as an indicator of processing effort. Whyatt (2019) is a notable exception which investigates not only time spent on the task but also the impact of text type on translation directionality. However, a combined focus on translation directionality and editing patterns observed over the course of the translation process as an indicator of processing effort has been rarely analysed (Alves & Gonçalves 2013). Against this background, two research questions guide the rationale of this experimental study: (1) Is there a difference in translation task execution when translating from L2 into L1 than when translating from L1 into L2?, (2) Does it differ in terms of text register, editing patterns, pause length or time spent on the task? To answer these questions, we investigated L1>L2 and L2>L1 translation task execution in the language pair English/German by means of keystroke-logged data. The results show that translations into the L1 in our data set involve a higher proportion of editing procedures as opposed to unchallenged translations than translations into the L2. Furthermore, results for inter-word pauses are register-specific. These findings suggest that the effect of directionality on translation behaviour is complex and requires a research design that accounts for this complexity.

Keywords: translation process research; directionality in translation; editing patterns; processing effort; register effect

1. Introduction

Investigating directionality in translation from an empirical-experimental perspective has long occupied translation studies scholars. While many empirical studies about translating from the first language (henceforth L1) into a second language (henceforth L2) or from an L2 into the L1 use the time spent on the task as an indicator of processing effort (Pavlović & Hvelplund Jensen 2009; Ferreira et al. 2016; Schmaltz et al. 2016), we propose that a combined focus on time-based *and* text editing patterns observed in the course of the translation process may provide a more robust account of the impact of directionality on task execution. Even though translation into the L2 is neither uncommon in many speech communities nor necessarily ‘worse’ than translation into the L1 (Pokorn 2005; Pavlović 2013), it is not the preferred translation direction in many cultures including Germany, where translation programmes focus primarily on teaching L2>L1 translation. Translation competence in both directions is, therefore, not necessarily comparable. That is why there is a need to understand effects of translation direction on the translation process more comprehensively. This paper offers a new perspective on the issue by answering the following primary research question: (1) Is there a difference in translation students’ task execution when translating from an L2 into the L1 than when translating from the L1 into an L2? To specify this guiding question, we further ask:

(2) Does it differ in terms of text register, editing patterns, pause length and/or time spent on the task?

Research on the effect of translation direction has gained popularity in recent years. Yet the terminology is still not entirely standardised within the field. Directionality is typically used to denote whether a translation task demands translating into the first language, or into a second language and this is also how it will be used in this study. This already displays two of the main approaches to this issue. Translations into the second language are often called “inverse” or “reverse”, which, however, implies some sort of judgment on what would be the “right” direction, namely *direct* translation into the first language. To avoid assumptions yet to be proven empirically we will adopt the more neutral terminology also employed by others referring to the L1 as the first, or most frequently used language, and L2 for the second, or lesser used language (cf. Pavlović 2007; Stewart 1999). Note that Evert & Neumann (2017) refer to a different type of directionality in their investigation of asymmetries between the languages involved in translation in their role as source or target language. What they investigate is independent of translating into the L1 or L2 and might be called *language pair directionality* to distinguish it from the L1-L2 directionality we are interested in here, which is in turn independent of relationships between specific languages.

In the remainder of the paper, we will first review the literature and then describe our innovative remote elicitation procedure and data processing in the method section. The subsequent discussion and conclusion of our results offer potential explanations for our findings while remaining critical of their overall implications for the question of translation directionality and processing behaviour.

2. Literature review

Empirical research on the effect of translation direction is rather scarce and presents a somewhat divided field of observations, especially regarding the translation process (Whyatt 2019: 80). Findings also diverge as far as the translation product is concerned. While some studies do not report on any textual differences regarding directionality (Rodríguez-Inés 2013), other studies have found directionality to have an effect on translation quality in grammar, punctuation or even readability of the target text in both directions (Whyatt 2019: 89). Furthermore, Whyatt also reports a modulating effect of text type on said directionality effect, which suggests a significant influence of the source text register on translation depending on the direction. Specific typographical differences corresponding to translation direction have further been reported by Rodríguez-Inés (2017: 257), who found a general tendency of translators to use more brackets to add information or provide equivalent terms in translations into the L2 than into the L1.

Differences in syntactic and lexical complexity in L2 translations from French into English have been found by Penha-Marion et al. (2024). They report a tendency toward lower lexical density due to a reduced vocabulary range with more high-frequency words and increased syntactic complexity by means of longer sentences in L1>L2 translations than in L2>L1 translations and in original English texts. Penha-Marion et al. (2024) attribute this to the effect of translation experience, or rather the lack thereof, as their participants were translation students. An influence of the source texts as well as idiosyncratic translation behaviour was also observed.

More generally, many studies elicit data from translation students or inexperienced translators (Pavlović 2007, 2010, 2017; Cao et al. 2023), and it has been shown that the translators' L2 proficiency and general linguistic knowledge might have more of an impact on translation quality than the direction of the translation task (Elston-Güttler et al. 2005; Pokorn et al. 2019). This suggests that translator training should include second language competence training, but also that studies on translation directionality need to be aware of the individual capabilities of their participants.

These findings concerning the effect of language proficiency as well as the prominence of specific features depending on the translation direction have informed the discussion about the supposed difference in difficulty and cognitive demand of translating into the L1 or into the L2. Difficulty in either translation direction is suggested to be linked to time spent on the task or the cognitive effort needed to complete it. For this, translators' behavioural patterns during the translation task are frequently consulted. This often involves the use of eye-tracking software and/or keystroke logging tools in combination with self-reports after or even during the translation task, to enable a more comprehensive understanding of the cognitive processes involved in translation (Alves et al. 2009).

Previous studies investigating said difference in cognitive effort respective of the translation direction have produced inconclusive results. Investigations of gaze and pause behaviour during translating show that translations into the L2 demand more cognitive effort, hence corroborating the so-called *translation asymmetry* (Pavlović & Hvelplund Jensen 2009; Chang & Chen 2023; Jia et al. 2023). This effect also holds true when language specific features are investigated (Jensen et al. 2009). Furthermore, the total time spent on the translation task has been shown to be indicative of the cognitive effort applied. Yet even though participants sometimes spend perceivably more time on translations into their L2, this difference was not proven to be statistically significant (Ferreira et al. 2021: 115). In other studies, no difference in terms of time spent is found at all (Whyatt 2019: 88). Fonseca (2015: 123) further claims that the supposed higher cognitive demand might rather be the result of strategic translation behaviour than a sign of increased difficulty. Ferreira et al. (2018), in contrast to Whyatt (2019), find higher metalinguistic self-monitoring in L2>L1 translation with more explicit critical appraisal of the choices made in the participants' L1. These two studies also contrast in terms of the difficulties in L1>L2 translation, which may be of lexical (Ferreira et al. 2018) or grammatical nature (Whyatt 2019). This indicates a lack of conclusive evidence concerning cognitive effort in translation depending on L1-L2 directionality, as multiple factors are at play (cf. Pavlović & Hvelplund Jensen 2009).

Pavlović (2007: 13) also shows that only 44% of translators indicate L1>L2 translation to be more difficult, while 33% claim it to be the other way around, although these preferences could very likely be due to differences in training and proficiency (Pietryga 2022: 105). These findings suggest that language proficiency, individual differences and especially the source text intricacy might impact the perceived difficulty and general outcome of the translation task even more than the directionality of the translation, in terms of both process and product (Ferreira et al. 2016: 61; Ferreira et al. 2018: 111–112). Concerning revision behaviour as well, individual preferences between translators seem to have a larger impact than L1-L2 directionality (Alves & Vale 2011/2017; Alves & Gonçalves 2013), although this remains to be confirmed by studies with larger numbers of participants.

As shown above, translation research has employed many different methods over the years. The most promising and meaningful approach appears to be a multi-methods research design that combines the investigation of the translation process and product. There have been

a few attempts to take on this task on a larger scale through compiling a translation process corpus. The project TransComp (Göpferich et al. 2008) conducted a longitudinal study that investigated the development of translation competence of translation students in comparison to professional translators. By using the keystroke logger Translog, and a screen recording tool, they provide insight into the translation process as well as the translation product of their comparably small corpus. A similar approach has been taken by a team at the Zürich University of Applied Sciences with the Capturing Translation Processes (CTP) project (Ehrensberger-Dow 2013: 7). They collected translation process data of translation students and professional translators at different points in their careers, employing a multi-methods research design. Their data shows that especially students employ different strategies when translating into the L2 like, for example, longer contemplation times with fewer revisions.

Keystroke logging the translation process involves analysing latencies between the specific computer activities such as all kinds of keystrokes, mouse clicks etc. and segmentation patterns, which have been used as operationalisations of cognitive processing effort. According to Alves & Vale (2011/2017), editing patterns can be mapped onto micro and macro translation units (TUs). Micro TUs correspond to translational text production segments delimited by pauses of a pre-defined length. In this, the concept is comparable to the concept of the production unit by Carl et al. (2016). However, we are interested in the editing operations on these units (see below). Note that Alves & Vale’s micro TU is not equivalent to Carl’s (2021) notion, which he also calls micro unit, although he defines it differently.

Once a translator revisits an initial micro TU and edits it, it will become part of a macro unit, which thus consists of all micro TUs (still separated by pauses) that involve edits of the initial one and make changes to some of its wording (Alves & Vale 2009). This includes all interim changes such as deletions, insertions and revisions that lead to the final translation solution. Alves & Vale (2011/2017) differentiate between different types of macro units depending on whether text production and edits occur in the drafting and/or end revision phase. A P1 is produced and possibly changed across multiple micro units during the drafting phase only, while P2 exhibits straightforward text production during the drafting phase and is then only edited during the end revision phase. The last type of macro unit, P3, consists of multiple micro units in the drafting and at least one editing pattern in the end revision phase, therefore having undergone multiple editing procedures across translation phases. To those macro units, Alves & Gonçalves (2013: 113) add a P0 category which equals a micro unit that does not undergo any editing procedures whatsoever. They also annotate the distance between the micro units that together make up one macro unit. Table 1 summarises the different editing patterns characterising translation units proposed by Alves & Gonçalves (2013).

Table 1: Overview of the editing procedures described by Alves & Gonçalves (2013)

Procedure	Characterisation
P0	continuous text production only, no edits
P1	edits of the produced unit during drafting phase only
P2	edits of the produced unit only during the end revision phase
P3	edits of the produced unit during drafting and end revision phase

Against the background of the conflicting findings of previous studies, for example in relation to time spent on the translation task or different foci of cognitive effort (Ferreira et al. 2021; Whyatt 2019), we tentatively formulate the following expectations. Since we are working with translation students, and language proficiency was shown to be a significant

factor, participants might need time to look up more words when translating into the L2 than into the L1, resulting in longer pauses in this direction. Furthermore, a difference in editing behaviour might become visible, as translation into the L1 has been shown to exhibit more complex editing procedures. Moreover, the strong influence of register on linguistic choice has been widely reported generally in linguistics. In particular, Whyatt (2019) also identifies an interaction between register and directionality.

3. Method

3.1. Experimental design

We designed an experiment in which translation students (L1 speakers of German) translated four texts, two from English into their L1 German and two from German into English, their L2. To account for the expected influence of register on directionality we included texts from the registers of popular scientific writing and product review respectively. The source texts thus cover both translation directions as well as two different registers. In order to delimit the amount of translation units to be included in the subsequent manual analysis (see below), we identified cohesive chains in the four texts. Throughout the text, different items refer back to an antecedent, thus establishing a cohesive chain. Drawing on Halliday & Hasan (1976), they consist of elements linked through lexical cohesion or cohesive reference. These items naturally occur in any text and therefore require little manipulation. Their analysis in the translations grants insight into the participants' translation and editing strategies. While they work through the source text and encounter more items belonging to the cohesive chain, the field of sense relations unfolds and reveals a clearer meaning of each individual item. This means that the translators might be prompted to go back in their target text production to revise choices they initially made or to adapt their subsequent translation choices to produce a more cohesive target text. We identified one cohesive chain in each text, starting from the antecedent representing the text's topical focus in the title or, in the case of the German product review, in the first line. The chains consist of sense related items, such as repetitions, synonyms, hyponyms or meronyms, as well as lexically related items belonging to the same semantic space and pronominal reference items. These pronouns are co-referential with the antecedent as well as with the other cohesive items in the chain.

The texts (see Appendix A) were edited such that they were comparable in length and in number of the different cohesive items and proofread by native speakers of English and German. Moreover, the experimental design (see below) was tested in two pilot studies with students from RWTH Aachen University. The second pilot study was necessary because of issues with the first set of source texts. Table 2 provides a comparative characterisation of the final set of source texts including the distribution of cohesive items in the source texts. In order to access translational behaviour, we analysed linear representations of the unfolding target texts produced in Translog-II (Carl 2012) rather than the source or target text products (see below for further detail on preprocessing Translog's log files).

Table 2: Overview of length and cohesive items of the source texts

	DE_POP	EN_POP	DE_REV	EN_REV
Words	237	253	242	241
Characters	1,804	1,651	1,629	1,233
Lexical cohesion	16	9	15	18
Reference	3	1	5	3
Total number of cohesive items	19	10	20	21

Previous experimental studies of directionality in translation used small cohorts of participants with process data elicited on-site in a laboratory. To allow for a larger cohort of participants and consequently more statistical power, we collected data remotely. The experimenter met the participant via video call using the video chat environment Zoom (Version 5.17.7) and gave the participant remote access to their computer on which the translation task was displayed and recorded in the keystroke logging environment Translog-II. The fact that keystroke logging was recorded remotely is likely to have an unavoidable impact on the accuracy of the recordings. In the worst case, accuracy varies between participants due to differences in the hardware and/or internet speed. Keller et al. (2009) report a replication study for self-paced reading, which also involves keystroke logging. Their web-based replication of a lab experiment yielded a close match between the original and the web-based results. While these findings cannot simply be applied to our setting involving a different software, it at least gives us some confidence in the validity of the recordings. Needless to say that future work will have to include a replication study for Translog-II similar to the study reported by Keller et al. (2009).

During the experiment, cameras and microphones were switched off on both ends of the call. All participants were given an individual ID to pseudonymise the elicited data and ensure confidentiality. Prior to the experiment, the participants gave their informed consent to participating voluntarily in the study, and they were debriefed afterwards. Participants received 45 Euros as remuneration.

On the screen next to the Translog window, there was an internet browser with four open tabs, including two bilingual online dictionaries (<https://www.dict.cc/> and <https://www.leo.org/>) as well as two monolingual thesauri (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/> for English and <https://www.dwds.de/> for German), which the participants could switch between. The participants were asked to only use these resources and neither other resources on their own devices nor print dictionaries. In some cases, we encountered Zoom or internet-related issues, but they could all be resolved rather quickly and were noted in the experiment protocols. Some participants were unable to use the umlauts (ä, ö, ü) on their keyboards for the German translations, which could not always be fixed during the experiment but was noted in the protocols as well.

After they completed each translation, participants notified the experimenter, who saved the recording and opened the next source text to be translated in Translog. This experimental setup ensures sufficient experimental control while increasing ecological validity in comparison to a laboratory setting by allowing the participants to work at their own pace in a familiar physical environment. Nevertheless, awareness of being recorded as well as the constraint imposed on access to resources clearly make this an experimental setting with consequences on the participants' behaviour. Participants first performed a copy task and then translated all four texts. The order in which the texts were presented was randomised. After

completing all translation tasks, participants were asked to fill in a survey adapted from the Translation and Interpreting Competence Questionnaire (Schaeffer et al. 2020). As part of the survey, we asked participants to take the English and German LexTALE tests (Lemhöfer & Broersma 2012) and enter their results.

A total of 38 students (29 female, 8 male, 1 diverse; ages 19–30, SD 2.736534; 18 undergraduate, 20 graduate students) enrolled in translation degree programmes at four German universities¹ who had successfully completed at least two translation modules participated in the study. They were required to have German as (one of) their L1(s) and English as their first L2. The mean scores for the German and English LexTALE tests were 85.62% (SD 8.808537) and 81.46% (SD 10.76115) respectively.

3.2. Mapping translation units (annotation)

The resulting 152 keystroke log files (38 participants x 4 texts) were subsequently processed. In a first step, the XML files generated by Translog-II were automatically segmented into micro units using individual pause thresholds and represented as text files with the help of a Python script. The thresholds were determined individually per participant based on the median pause duration between pressing alphanumeric keys (as these are more likely to be used when typing words). To this median, we added two standard deviations of this duration in order to capture 95 percent of the variance in inter-key pause duration (see Martín & Apfelthaler (2022) for a similar approach using two times the median value as an arbitrary threshold to identify segments). In this way, we obtained an individual measure of a participant's typical typing speed that captures individual sensorimotor specifics (e.g. whether someone is a touch typist or not) and helps mitigate the influence of any challenges posed by the technical infrastructure. Any pause duration longer than this thus represents an extreme value that cannot be explained by sensorimotor or technical considerations and is likely to be caused by processing-related factors.² In addition to symbols representing mouse clicks or keystroke operations such as backspacing or deletion, the linear representations produced by our Python script represent each micro unit in one line, thus tracking the sequential order of text production. They also include an indication of the micro unit's position in the translation product: Each line starts with the cursor position in the unfolding target text at the current stage. The pause length dividing the current from the next micro unit is given in milliseconds at the end of each line.

These pre-segmented files representing the processes of target text production were uploaded to the annotation platform INCEpTION (Klie et al. 2018), where seven students enrolled in the MA programme Cognitive, Digital and Empirical English Studies at RWTH Aachen University annotated the files for course credits under the supervision of the first author on the basis of detailed annotation guidelines. The students were first trained in the annotation and practised it in a trial round, after which potential issues were addressed and the annotation guidelines refined. The student annotators were made familiar with the source texts and their cohesive chains and additionally had access to Translog in order to be able to replay the

¹ We gratefully acknowledge support from Oliver Czulo (University of Leipzig), Silvia Hansen-Schirra (University of Mainz/Germersheim), Kerstin Kunz (Heidelberg University) and Ekaterina Lapshinova-Koltunski (University of Hildesheim) in finding participants.

² We are indebted to Florian Frenken for this reasoning and for writing the Python scripts required for the automatic segmentation of the Translog-II logfiles and for exporting the INCEpTION annotation to a data table for further analysis.

translation process. All annotations were performed on the linear representations of the target texts, which were not aligned with the source texts.

The annotation proceeded in three steps. First, translations of the cohesive items in the source texts were identified and labelled in the target texts, including 1) the cohesive relation to their antecedent and 2) the type of text production operation involved (that is, full or partial production or deletion, or a mixed category for both production and deletion operations within one micro unit). Furthermore, any subsequent revision, such as an addition to or editing of these items, during the course of translation was also categorised. In the case where an item belonging to a cohesive chain was edited but that edit did not establish a (different) cohesive relation to the target antecedent, we added an escape label for the category ‘cohesive relation’, as it would not apply. Figure 1 shows a linear representation of the target text in INCEPTION annotated for cohesive items in step 1.

	Reference	Production	
69	[503]	Sie	sind robust [•14.422]
70	[519]	und ich habe	[•02.078]
71	[531],	[•813]	
72	[533]	wenn ich etwas zum	[•03.375]
73	[552]	Tisch trage	[•03.640]
74	[563],	nicht das Gef	[•985]
75	[578]	ühl	[•04.329]
76	[581],	dass sich der	Griff [•984]

Figure 1: Example of an annotation of the linear representation in INCEPTION, including the pronominal reference *sie* (‘it’) and the meronym *Griff* (‘handle’) referring to the antecedent *Pfanne* (‘pan’)

Next, each production segment containing a cohesive item identified in step 1 and any subsequent micro units where each such item was edited were linked and labelled as macro units. This involves a first annotation of the segment containing the item as a micro unit representing (in the case of P0) or belonging to a macro unit as well as a link of that segment to its related micro units, which together form the macro unit (P1-3). These comprise the initial production of the segment containing a cohesive item and any subsequent segments including an editing operation on that item, so that all micro units belonging to one macro unit are connected. The links between the micro units are labelled with a running number. The number of the link between the last two micro units of the macro unit is thus also the number of times the item was picked up again and worked on during the translation process. Figure 2 shows an example of a macro unit consisting of three micro units, in which the item initially produced in segment number 164 was immediately deleted in the following segment number 165 and produced again later in the translation process in segment 170. This example represents a P1 type of translation unit, in which the item was produced and edited only during the drafting phase. The numbers attached to the links between the micro units count the number of revisions of the initially produced item. In this case, the initial item *extension* was deleted in the first linked revision and produced again in the second linked revision. The number in square brackets at the start of each line represents the cursor position, and the number in square brackets at the end of each line is the pause length in ms.

Figure 2: Example of a meronym produced and edited across several micro units in the drafting phase

In the third and last step, the translation phases orientation, drafting and end revision (Jakobsen 2002) were determined with another span layer in INCEpTION. The orientation phase describes the phase before any translating in terms of actual text production takes place. Possible keystrokes in that phase may for example include noting down vocabulary in the Translog editor during source text reading in preparation of translating. Drafting includes all text production from the first key press to produce the target text until a first version of the entire source text has been transferred into the target language. After that final full stop, the end revision phase begins (Jakobsen 2002: 91–92).

After each step, the students' annotations were checked and corrected first by the students themselves and finally by the first author before proceeding to the next step of the annotation. These annotations were exported from the INCEpTION platform in the form of XML files, which were then processed to result in a data table containing each annotated item in a micro unit, its position in the text approximated by the cursor position at the beginning of the processing segment, its position in the translation process as the number of the line of the segment in the linear representation, and the annotated information, that is the cohesive relation of the item in the segment, the text production operation, and the translation phase the segment occurs in. Based on the macro units established in the second step of the annotation and the translation phase, the macro units were determined and classified into one of the editing procedures presented in Table 1 (Alves & Vale 2011/2017; Alves & Gonçalves 2013). The data table furthermore contains the register, translation direction, source text and participant ID as metadata information.

On the basis of the data thus obtained, we analysed two indicators claimed to be linked to directionality: inter-word pause length as a time-related indicator of processing effort (potentially linked to lexical retrieval) and the distribution of editing procedures across micro and macro units as an indicator of the strain of text production.

4. Results

4.1. Pause length

As to pause length, we focus on all inter-word pauses as these are more likely to be linked to lexical retrieval. These are extracted automatically as latencies from a non-alphanumeric key such as white space or a punctuation mark (representing the end of one word) to the next alphanumeric key (representing the start of the next word). This information was automatically

extracted for the entire data set and can therefore be analysed in more statistical detail, whereas the examination of editing procedures required manual annotation and will therefore only be characterised with the help of descriptive statistics (see below).

We fitted a mixed linear regression model to analyse the relationship between translation direction and inter-word pause length. Table 3 gives an overview of the variables included in the analysis. In addition to our response variable total inter-word pause length (“interword_pauses_sec_c”) and our main predictor of interest, translation direction (“direction_sum”), we included register as a predictor, as this has been shown in multiple studies to be an important factor influencing linguistic choice (“register_sum”). Since Whyatt (2019) also discussed an interaction with directionality, we include an interaction term between these two variables in our model.

We assumed above that proficiency in the L2 could influence the process. We therefore included the score of the English LexTale test as the variable “LexTale_EN_c”. Pause behaviour could be influenced by the participants’ typing abilities. To account for this, we include a measure of typing speed during the copy task as the individual baseline (“keystroke_time_copy_sec_c”). The last predictor is “no_activity_sec_c”: The length of pauses during translating could be moderated by whether the participants took time to familiarise themselves with the source text at the beginning of the task and reviewed the product for a last time before ending it. This information is captured by the variable “no_activity_sec_c”.

As each participant contributes four data points, these are not independent. Each person might introduce idiosyncratic patterns across tasks. We therefore include a random intercept for “participantID”. Note that we do not include a random effect for source text, although all participants translated the same four texts, as the levels map entirely on the combined fixed effects of translation direction and register.

Table 3: Overview of the variables included in the regression model

Type	Variable	Scaling	Levels	Description
Response	interword_pauses_sec_c	Continuous	-	The overall time without computer activity between words (centred)
Predictor	direction_sum	Binary	L1>L2, L2>L1	Direction of translation into the L2 or the L1 (sum-coded)
	register_sum	Binary	REV, POP	The two registers from which the source texts were taken (sum-coded)
	LexTale_EN_c	Continuous	-	The score of the English LexTale test (centred)
	keystroke_time_copy_sec_c	Continuous	-	The number of characters typed per second in the copy task (centred)
	no_activity_sec_c	Continuous	-	Time spent on the task before the first and after the last computer activity (centred)
Random effect	participantID	Categorical	[participant ID]	The unique identifier of each participant

Table 4 provides descriptive statistics of the pause-related variables for all 152 data points. The variable “interword_pauses_sec_c” is computed by subtracting the total word-internal pause lengths (used in the calculation of typing speed, see above) from the sum of all pause lengths per text in seconds. As can be seen in Table 4, the median sum of inter-word pause lengths per text is 1,935.1 seconds (the median overall task time is 2,333.2 seconds). The measure of typing speed in the copy task per participant was obtained by dividing the length of the copy text in characters by the time participants needed for the task (given in seconds). This gives us the average number of letters a participant types per second. Recordings of the copy task were missing for four participants. The median number of letters typed per second across the remaining 34 participants is 2.757.³ The variable “no_activity_sec_c” is the result of subtracting the time elapsed between the first and the last computer activity from the overall time spent on the task. One extreme data point (1521.3 seconds of no activity) was more than double the length of the second-longest value. We removed this data point, as there may have been an unrelated interruption in task completion.⁴ The median time without activity is 85.125 seconds (SD 103.6124), that is, roughly 4 percent of the overall task time. Descriptive statistics for “no_activity_sec_c” are given with and without the extreme data point in Table 4. We took the decision to continue without this extreme data point (leaving us with 151 data points for the regression analysis).

Table 4: Descriptive summary of pause-related variables

	tasktime_ sec	interword_ pause_sec⁵	LexTale _EN_c	keystroke_ time_ copy_sec⁶	no_activity_ _sec	no_activity_ sec⁷
n	152	152	152	34	152	151
Min.	952.9	733.6	54.00	1.491	9.563	9.563
1 st qu.	1,875.1	1513.2	76.56	2.114	36.937	36.828
Median	2,333.2	1935.1	82.50	2.757	85.805	85.125
Mean	2,426.7	2014.3	81.46	2.700	124.225	114.973
3 rd qu.	2,954.2	2486.5	88.75	2.932	162.969	159.899
Max.	5,037.6	4192.0	96.25	4.079	1521.297	624.734
SD	826.0031	737.1506	10.76115	0.6718379	153.8698	103.6124

A regression model in R (R Core Team 2024) with all above predictor variables retrieved no significant effects of L2 proficiency and typing speed in the copy task on pause behaviour (see Appendix B). We therefore ran a second model without the variables “LexTale_EN_c” and “keystroke_time_copy_sec_c”, which allowed us to include data from

³ As an alternative perspective on typing speed, we also calculated the time required to type a key, for ease of understanding given in ms (after removing the NAs for participants without a copy task): Min. = 245.1, 1st qu. = 341.1, Median = 362.7, Mean = 395.6, 3rd qu. = 473.1, Max. = 670.6, SD = 106.9926

⁴ The survey filled in by participants after completion of the four translation tasks also included questions about interruptions, but the participant’s respective answers don’t provide definite information.

⁵ For comparison, word-internal pauses per second: Min. = 134.5, 1st qu. = 220.6, Median = 281.6, Mean = 288.1, 3rd qu. = 340.1, Max. = 541.4, SD = 78.3733

⁶ After removing the NAs for participants without a copy task

⁷ After removing one influential data point (textID “BACHMCBDAL07_A”)

all 38 participants. The regression model yielded the outcome summarised in Table 5. Recall that data for one text was removed because of an extreme value for “no_activity_sec_c”.

Table 5: Summary of the mixed linear regression model

	Estimate Std.	Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)	
(Intercept)	18.7922	63.7631	37.9403	0.295	0.76982	
direction_sum1	95.5683	32.6844	113.1476	2.924	0.00418	**
register_sum1	360.4499	33.7880	117.5891	10.668	< 2e-16	***
no_activity_sec_c	2.0692	0.4546	143.5747	4.552	1.13e-05	***
direction_sum1:register_sum1	-183.2756	33.3175	117.1153	-5.501	2.25e-07	***
Random effect for participant (151 observations, 38 groups): Variance = 113667, SD 337.1						

Model diagnostics reveal that the residuals are somewhat right-skewed, meaning that the error is not entirely normally distributed. Moreover, there is a weak tendency for residuals to fan out when moving along the fitted values, suggesting that variance of the residuals is not entirely homogeneous. There is no indication of collinearity, as the variance inflation factors for all predictors are all below 2 and thus well below the conservative threshold suggested by Winter (2019: 114). Model comparison was carried out with the *afex* package (Singmann et al. 2018) for nested mixed models using likelihood ratio tests. It yielded significant effects for all three predictors and the interaction, showing that the model with all factors captures the variance best (see Appendix B for the complete model output).

All predictors are significantly associated with the sum of inter-word pauses per text, and this effect is complex, characterised by a strong interaction effect between translation direction and register. In both registers, when translating into the L1, overall inter-word pause length is predicted to decrease by 191.1 seconds⁸ compared to the opposite translation direction. In both directions, when the register is popular-scientific, the difference in inter-word pause length to reviews is 720.9 seconds. However, the interaction effect reveals that the directionality effect is actually register-specific: When participants translate reviews into the L1, the overall inter-word pause length is predicted to be 912.0 seconds shorter than when translating a popular-scientific text into the L2 and even 1,087.4 seconds shorter than popular-scientific translation into the L1. Consequently, L2>L1 translation is characterised by shorter inter-word pause lengths only in the register of reviews. In the popular-scientific register, translating into the L2 actually appears to have a facilitating effect: A participant is predicted to require roughly 175 seconds less in inter-word pauses than in the other translation direction. Last but not least, each additional second without a computer activity before or after text production turns out to increase the overall inter-word pause length by 2.07 seconds.

Including a random intercept for participants reveals a great deal of variation between participants accounted for by the model: Variation for 95% of participants (+/- two standard deviations of the random effect) around the intercept (i.e. sum of inter-word pauses per text) ranges roughly from -655 to +693 seconds.

⁸ Recall that the regression model uses sum coding so that the estimates in Table 5 for both binary predictors only specify half of the actual difference between the two levels.

The conditional R^2 of 0.70 suggests a very good model fit, where the conditional R^2 captures the variance described by both fixed and random effects. The marginal R^2 for the fixed effects only is 0.49, suggesting that accounting for the effect of participants substantially adds to the described variance. As R^2 is actually a measure of effect size measuring the strength of the relationship between variables (Winter 2019: 77), this suggests a medium and, when accounting for the participants' effect, even strong effect.

4.2. Editing procedures

The annotation of the above-mentioned production segments for editing procedures yielded the characterisation of the four texts summarised in Table 6. It should be noted that the overall number of translation units involving the cohesive items identified in the STs diverges strikingly across texts. Translations into English of the German popular-scientific text yield a total of 936 relevant macro units, whereas translations of the English popular-scientific text only yield less than half that amount (435 macro units). This latter result is not surprising as this is also the source text with the lowest number of cohesive devices (see Table 2), which will naturally reflect in the distributions in the translations. The German original review results in 852 relevant macro units in the translations and the English review yields slightly more with 873 relevant macro units. This skewed distribution means that only the proportions of the different editing procedures per text can be compared at all and even these need to be interpreted very cautiously. A comprehensive analysis and discussion of editing procedures would require annotation of *all* macro units in the INCEPTION interface, which is outside the scope of this paper.

Table 6: Proportions of editing procedures in segments of interest across translation directions (by register) in per cent

	L1 > L2			L2 > L1		
	Popsci	Review	Combined	Popsci	Review	Combined
P0	56.52	68.66	62.30	43.45	62.31	56.04
P1	40.92	29.69	35.57	53.79	33.33	40.14
P2	1.39	1.17	1.29	0.46	2.63	1.91
P3	1.18	0.47	0.84	2.30	1.72	1.91
Macro units involving edits (= P1+P2+P3)	43.48	31.34	37.70	56.55	37.69	43.96

Table 6 reveals a difference between the translation directions with translation into the L1 requiring overall more edits per translation unit, with overall 43.96% of the translations into the L1 requiring edits and only 37.70% of translations into the L2. The table also shows that this difference is carried mainly by the review register. Around two thirds of the translation units are unchallenged productions (P0) in both directions, whereas the popular-scientific texts force the participants to edit more. In L2>L1 translation, less than half of the translation units examined here remain unchallenged. Whether the difference between the two types of texts can be interpreted as a register effect or is actually simply a reflection of the specific linguistic characteristics of the four source texts cannot be reliably decided.

5. Discussion

This study set out to investigate two related research questions, namely (1) whether there is a difference in translation task execution depending on the translation direction and, more specifically, (2) whether it differs with respect to editing and temporal patterns as well as by register. The above results show that, indeed, there is an effect of directionality in terms of both editing and required time as measured by inter-word pauses, but this effect is complex and driven by the source text and its register. Overall pause length is affected by the translation direction, but even more so by the variable of register. Inter-word pause lengths, which we linked to issues of lexical retrieval above, are indeed shorter for the review text in L2>L1 translation than in the opposite direction. While we cannot entirely rule out other explanations, individual factors such as keyboard-related issues are not highly likely, as participants worked in their own working environment, and are additionally accounted for by the random effect in the mixed model. The non-specialised wording of the register means that participants do not have to contemplate the wording in the potentially more familiar translation direction. When translating into the L2, more pauses are required, and this effect does not depend on L2 proficiency. By contrast, when the register is popular-scientific writing, the overall task appears more effortful, requiring more pauses between words in both directions, and there is no advantage of translating into the L1 anymore. Apparently, making sense of the source text now requires so much more time that text production takes much longer into the L1. Following Whyatt's (2019) reasoning, it may actually be more important for the participants to understand the source text well. So, the source text being in the L1 actually has a facilitating effect in this register. As a result, slightly less time is required for contemplating translation in the L2 than in the opposite direction. It should be kept in mind, though, that this study is based on only one source text per register and translation direction. The effect observed here could be entirely due to the specific challenges of the four texts. As Penha-Marion et al. (2024) report, a small set of source texts can be quite influential. This means that future work should involve a much-increased data set with a sufficiently high number of source texts that mitigates the influence of individual texts on the overall results.

We can tentatively interpret the significant effect of time without computer activity on inter-word pause length, both increasing together, as suggesting that those participants who take more time familiarising themselves with the source text and re-reading their target text may also take longer in general in decision-making (compare Lehka-Paul (2020) for a different observation and discussion of various behavioural preferences of translators). At the same time, the high variance between our participants as revealed by the random intercepts in the regression model indicates larger individual differences in their translation behaviour. This concerns not only their overall translation strategy, that is, how much time they spend outside of actual text production and whether they revise at all, but also individual differences in the time spent on translation and production speed. The participant metadata also indicates a wide range in language proficiency based on their LexTALE results for both German and English.

Concerning the editing strategies, P0 is overall the most frequent category. This observation based on the descriptive statistics (see Table 6) is even more pronounced in the direction L1>L2 with straightforward, continuous production of the micro unit. The overall prevalence of P0 corresponds to the findings reported by Alves & Gonçalves (2013: 115–16), who link P0 to routinised translation behaviour. While this result may suggest competent decision-making, participants may on the other hand have found fewer options in the less familiar language. P1 and P2 strategies, which represent more complex macro units involving

editing of the produced item either in the drafting or in the end revision phase, are comparably more frequent in the translation direction L2>L1. The participants may have been more critical of their target texts and may draw on a wider range of possible translation solutions in their L1. At the same time, this result may reflect that the antecedents in the English source texts allow more variation in how they are subsequently referred to in the text. These are *pans* and *bacteria*. The former, for example, is ambiguous, in that it could mean both or either *Töpfe* or *Pfannen* in German. This ambiguity is frequently not recognised from the start but only throughout the text, which led participants to change their first translation solution, sometimes multiple times. The antecedent in the English popular-scientific source text, *bacteria*, also grants access to various synonyms in German. The antecedents and references to them in the German source texts seem to be more specific in comparison, though this might also reflect a lower range of vocabulary or less familiarity with diversifying lexis in the participants' L2.

The reviews seem to require less editing or production of cohesive items spread across several micro units in translation, as reflected by the higher proportion of the P0 type of text production pattern in this register. In contrast, an interrupted production frequently occurs in the case of unfamiliar and highly specific terminology in the popular-scientific texts, where participants may more frequently pause during the production of an item, resulting in a higher number of P1 patterns in that register. This kind of P1 pattern can be distinguished from P1 macro units that are characterised by text operations other than production, i.e., those that involve editing the produced item at a later stage in the drafting phase. It will be worthwhile to extend the categorisation and make this distinction in future analyses, because the two patterns reflect different behaviours under the same P1 label. The unfamiliar subject matter and lexis of the popular-scientific register seem to slow down the participants as well as trigger more editing. Some participants also seemed to perceive the more scientific or technical texts as more difficult and remarked upon this after the experiment. Some noted that they would have found background information or reference texts helpful or would have usually done research to produce a target text they are more confident in. On the other hand, at least one participant remarked that they worked with both of these registers, i.e., product reviews and popular-scientific texts, in their translation programme.

P2 and P3 editing strategies were overall very infrequent. Both of these patterns are defined by including editing in the end revision phase. This last phase during the translation process was frequently very short or even completely missing in many text productions, which might reflect the student participants' limited translation experience or their lack of a strategy involving editing of a rough draft (cf. Ehrensberger-Dow 2013).

That said, the proportions of the more complex editing procedures P1–P3 are higher in translation into the L1 than into the L2. However, it must be kept in mind that this study only uses one text each for each register and translation direction combination. This means that the results are affected by source-text specific features. Translating from the English popular-scientific source text, for example, more uncertainty with certain items regarding their spelling could be observed in the translation process, such as recursive variations of *Kolibakterien*. The German source text seems to allow less variation in its translation solutions in comparison, with a higher frequency of P0 overall. It can also be argued that, despite careful selection of the source text and pilot-testing (both texts describe certain chemical and physical processes in a somewhat narrative order), the English source text is more technical in nature. Though we do not consider the translation quality in this study, one sentence in that text (see Example (1) below) seemed to pose a particular challenge syntactically and was frequently misunderstood by the translation students.

- (1) Then, to transform the muconic acid into adipic acid, they used a second type of *E. coli*, which produced hydrogen gas, and a palladium catalyst.

The majority of participants translated this sentence in such a way that the last nominal group *a palladium catalyst* was understood to be part of the non-defining relative clause. Their translations thus suggest that the *E. coli* bacteria also produced the palladium catalyst instead of that catalyst also being used to transform the acid. Expressing complex methods such as described in this sentence poses a particular challenge when translators are unfamiliar with the subject matter.

6. Conclusion

The results presented above, and the regression analysis in particular, throw new light on the question of directionality in translation by revealing the complex influence of register on translational behaviour across translation directions (bearing in mind that this influence is currently at least partly due to specific characteristics of the source texts). The results suggest that time-related measures shed some light on processing effort in the performance of translators working from L1 into L2 or from L2 into L1. Nevertheless, they also show that factors like register (cf. Whyatt 2019) and idiosyncratic behaviour (cf. Penha-Marion et al. 2024) have a significant effect on task execution. Considering the specific measures such as pause length and editing strategies reveals that participants produce translations of reviews in less time as reflected by shorter overall sums of inter-word pauses and require less revision with fewer complex macro units, when looking at specific cohesive items. This is especially the case when translating in the more familiar direction L2>L1. In the popular-scientific register, on the other hand, more time is taken overall and specifically in the translation direction L2>L1. In that register, the source text seems to pose more of a challenge, and participants may also spend more time on their target text with higher metalinguistic critical awareness of their target text in this more specialised register. Future studies must include a larger number of source texts to mitigate potential source text-specific effects. Collecting more translations from more participants will also help reduce the influence of individual participants' preferences and translation strategies, though a wide range of variation with regard to their behavioural measures can still be expected. More generally, extending the classification discussed here for only the editing procedures of elements in the identified cohesive chains in the source texts to *all* translation units in the translations will permit statistically analysing associations of editing procedures with the various predictor variables as demonstrated for inter-word pause length.

In addition to the mentioned limitations concerning the textual material, the experimental set-up also comes with certain constraints. The remote solution and lack of eye-tracking means that phases of inactivity on the participants' side cannot reliably be attributed to source or target text reading or understood to indicate cognitive effort. Though the processing of the translation process data was handled individually, technical issues such as delays during remote access or keyboard incompatibilities will nevertheless affect the results. The set-up allows some control, for example over the use of resources during the experiment, though the consultation of additional sources cannot be completely eliminated, as the participants worked 'behind closed cameras' for reasons of privacy and creating a more natural situation. Participants were mostly not accustomed to the working environment of Translog.

One participant remarked that they found it unfamiliar not to be able to edit the source text, which made orienting themselves in the text more difficult. Two participants also commented on the order of the texts: This order was randomised but one participant perceived the two popular-scientific as particularly difficult as they followed the two easier reviews while another said the vocabulary from the English source texts was helpful when translating the German ones into English.

Since the participants in the experiment had little or no professional experience in translation, the next step will be to replicate the study using the same methodology with professional translators. Furthermore, the annotated data also allows an investigation of how the different translation units and cohesive relations differ in terms of their complexity as captured by the number of editing procedures performed as well as their complexity in terms of distance measures. A longer distance between the micro units within a macro unit potentially means that processing effort is higher for items that need to be recalled in comparison to items revised immediately or in close proximity to their initial production (Alves & Gonçalves 2013). Which editing strategy is triggered by the cohesive relation in the source text is also of interest: Depending on whether, for example, the item is a repetition or stands in a hyponymy relation to the antecedent, the translator may have more options to revise their solution and therefore edit the item more or less frequently. This also has to do with different stylistic preferences in what the translation students were taught in their programme. For example, some translator trainers – at least in a German context – might maintain the stylistic instruction to avoid repetition (arguably depending on the context). The translators may deviate from the source text choice in this case, whereas a hyponym, for example, is already a more specific choice made from the possible types of the antecedent, which is why a deviation might be less likely in this case unless there is linguistic ambiguity in the source or target language.

In sum, we hope to have shown that our experimental design involving remote data collection results in larger data sets. The use of mixed regression modelling of inter-word pause length involving multiple predictor variables as well as an interaction term sheds new light on the complex interplay of various factors affecting linguistic choice in the two translation directions. Future work that addresses the above points while using larger numbers of participants and considering a more complex set of variables demonstrated here can lead to a more comprehensive understanding of the intricacies of directionality in translation.

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Appendix A: Source texts

EN_POP (from the online research news source *ScienceDaily*; <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2023/11/231101134747.htm>)

Plastic-eating bacteria turn waste into useful starting materials for other products
Mountains of used plastic bottles get thrown away every day, but microbes could potentially tackle this problem. Researchers in ACS Central Science report that they have recently developed a plastic-eating *E. coli* that can efficiently turn polyethylene terephthalate (PET) waste into adipic acid, which is used to make nylon materials, drugs and fragrances. Previously, a team of researchers had engineered a strain of *E. coli* to transform the main component in old PET bottles, terephthalic acid, into something tastier and more valuable: the vanilla flavor compound vanillin. At the same time, other researchers had engineered microbes to metabolize terephthalic acid into a variety of small molecules, including short acids. A new team from the University of Edinburgh wanted to further expand *E. coli*'s biosynthetic pathways to include the metabolism of terephthalic acid into adipic acid. The team developed a new *E. coli* strain that produced enzymes that could transform terephthalic acid into compounds such as muconic acid and adipic acid. Then, to transform the muconic acid into adipic acid, they used a second type of *E. coli*, which produced hydrogen gas, and a palladium catalyst. The team found that attaching the engineered microbial cells to alginate hydrogel beads improved their efficiency, and up to 79% of the terephthalic acid was converted into adipic acid. Using real-world samples of terephthalic acid from a discarded bottle and a coating taken from waste packaging labels, the newly engineered *E. coli* system efficiently produced adipic acid.

EN_REV (from the SFU Review Corpus; Taboada & Grieve 2004)

Pans that are worth buying

I have finally found a set of pans that are worth the money I paid for them. I thought I needed a new stove; instead a new set of pans was a better deal. I researched all of the different sets available and decided that these were the best fit for the money I had available. I absolutely love how fast the copper core bottom pans heat up. I can now boil water in half the time and at a much lower setting than before. They are sturdy and I don't feel like the handle is going to come loose when I carry something to the table. I also enjoy the fact that the handles are welded to the outside of the frying pan; this ensures that there are no rough surfaces on the interior for food to stick to. I also enjoy being able to cook at high temps without the sides of the skillet heating up. The heat source is concentrated at the base of the pan instead of in the handle and sides. This is safer and more efficient. The only disadvantage I have found so far is the clean-up. The instructions say the pans are dishwasher safe but it is not recommended due to possible cosmetic changes. My wife once used a metal spoon to stir and this left scratches on the surface. It did not affect the use, only the appearance.

DE_POP (from the online science news site *Wissenschaft-aktuell*; https://www.wissenschaft-aktuell.de/artikel/Mikroplastik_in_Wolken1771015591004.html)

Mikroplastik in Wolken

Mikroplastik hat viele Quellen von Fleece-Jacken über Kunststoffverpackungen und Reifenabrieb bis zu Kosmetika. Diese winzigen Partikel belasten die Umwelt auf dem gesamten Globus und konnten sogar schon in den Schneeproben der Arktis nachgewiesen werden. Nun

analysierte eine chinesische Forschergruppe ihren Anteil in Wolken. Tatsächlich fanden sie so beachtliche Mengen, dass ein Einfluss der Partikel auf die Wolkenbildung selbst nicht ausgeschlossen werden kann. Die Arbeitsgruppe an der Shandong University in Qingdao fing die Feuchtigkeit der Wolken über dem Berg Tàì Shān mit einer speziellen Apparatur ein. Insgesamt enthielten 24 der 28 gesammelten Proben Mikroplastik. Jeder Liter des Kondensats enthielt im Durchschnitt 463 Plastikpartikel. Das entspricht einem Teilchen Mikroplastik auf etwa fünf Kubikmeter feuchter Luft. Die meisten Mikroplastikteilchen waren nicht größer als 100 Mikrometer und konnten dadurch leicht durch die Atmosphäre über weite Strecken transportiert werden. Sie bestanden aus einer Vielzahl verschiedener Kunststoffe wie Polypropylen, Polyethylen und Polyamid. Mit Wettermodellen rekonstruierten die Forschenden den Ursprung dieser Luftverschmutzung. So gelangte das meiste Mikroplastik aus dicht besiedelten Regionen im Süden Chinas bis zum Tàì Shān. In weiteren Analysen entdeckten sie, dass viele Plastikpartikel durch Verwitterung eine raue Oberfläche hatten. An dieser Oberfläche konnten sich leichter weitere Umweltgifte wie Blei oder Quecksilber anlagern. Zudem sei es wahrscheinlich, dass Mikroplastik in der Atmosphäre als Kondensationskeime für Tropfen dienen, also direkt die Bildung von Wolken und Niederschlag unterstützen. Diese Funktion des Mikroplastiks könnte einen Einfluss auf Wettervorhersagen und sogar Klimamodelle haben.

DE_REV (from the USAGE review corpus; Klinger 2014)

Schönes Design mit durchdachter Funktionalität

Nachdem man den Toaster ausgepackt hat, fällt einem als Erstes sein Gehäusedesign angenehm ins Auge. Die schlanke Bauform und der verwendete Edelstahl verleihen ihm ein schönes und hochwertiges Aussehen. Was mir am Gehäuse am besten gefällt, ist, dass dieses wärmeisoliert ist. Wie ich finde ein wichtiges Kriterium für Haushalte mit Kindern. Der Toaster beherrscht neben dem Rösten auch das Aufwärmen und Auftauen von Toast beziehungsweise Brotscheiben. Einen gewissen Seltenheitscharakter hingegen hat die Möglichkeit, Toast einseitig zu rösten. Wozu ich das gebrauchen kann, weiß ich zwar noch nicht, aber die Funktion funktionierte beim Toastbrot sehr gut. Die Auswahl seiner Röstgrade erfolgt über einen Drehschalter an der Seite, und mit 7 Stufen ist die Auswahl zwar nicht außergewöhnlich, aber allemal ausreichend. Klasse finde ich, dass der Brötchenaufsatz im Toaster integriert ist und man somit keine weiteren Teile in der Küche verstauen muss, bis sie gebraucht werden. Bei Bedarf wird dieser einfach nach oben geklappt und schon kann es losgehen. Durch die längliche Form des Toasters kann man locker 3 Brötchen auftauen und der Aufsatz hatte damit auch keine Probleme. Was mich als Einziges an dem Gerät stört, ist der Piep-Ton nach Beendigung des Toastens. Wobei der Ton mich an sich nicht stört, sondern nur die Lautstärke. Für meinen Geschmack hätte man die Lautstärke verringern können. Fazit: Alles in allem summieren sich die einzelnen Ausstattungsmerkmale des Philips zu einem runden Gesamtprodukt, das Funktionalität und Design wunderbar unter einen Hut bringt.

Appendix B: R script

Descriptive stats

Key participant information

```
# age
summary(bachMeta$age)

##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## 19.00  22.25  24.00  24.39  25.00  30.00

# age, standard deviation
sd(bachMeta$age)

## [1] 2.736534

# gender
table(bachMeta$gender)

##
##      Divers Männlich Weiblich
##          1         8         29

# education
table(bachMeta$gender) # 18 BA students, 20 MA students

##
##      Divers Männlich Weiblich
##          1         8         29

# L1
table(bachMeta$B005_01) # 34 German, 4 list an additional L1

##
##                deutsch                Deutsch
##                   2                   31
## Deutsch, Finnisch, Ungarisch Deutsch, Polnisch
##                   1                   1
##                Deutsh Hochdeutsch und Plautdietsch
##                   1                   1
##                Türkisch & Deutsch
##                   1

#LexTale test results for German
summary(bachMeta$LexTale_DE)

##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## 66.25  79.06  87.50  85.62  92.50  98.75

# Lextale German, standard deviation
sd(bachMeta$LexTale_DE)

## [1] 8.808537

# Lextale test results for English
summary(bachMeta$LexTale_EN)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##      54.00   76.56   82.50   81.46   88.75   96.25
```

Lextale English, standard deviation

```
sd(bachMeta$LexTale_EN)
```

```
## [1] 10.76115
```

Pause measures

Inter-word pauses

```
summary(bachMain$interword_pauses_sec)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##      733.6 1513.2 1935.1 2014.3 2486.5 4192.0
```

Inter-word pauses, standard deviation

```
sd(bachMain$interword_pauses_sec)
```

```
## [1] 737.1506
```

Word-internal pauses

```
summary(bachMain$pauses_wordinternal_sec)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##      134.5  220.6  281.6  288.1  340.1  541.4
```

Word-internal pauses, standard deviation

```
sd(bachMain$pauses_wordinternal_sec)
```

```
## [1] 78.3733
```

no. of keystrokes per second in copy task

```
summary(bachMain$keystroke_time_copy_sec, na.rm = TRUE)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.   NA's
##      1.491  2.114  2.757  2.700  2.932  4.079    16
```

no. of keystrokes per second in copy task, standard deviation

```
sd(bachMain$keystroke_time_copy_sec, na.rm = TRUE)
```

```
## [1] 0.6718379
```

time required per keystroke in ms in copy task

```
summary(bachMain$time_keystroke_copy_ms, na.rm = TRUE)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.   NA's
##      245.1  341.1  362.7  395.6  473.1  670.6    16
```

time required per keystroke in ms in copy task, standard deviation

```
sd(bachMain$time_keystroke_copy_ms, na.rm = TRUE)
```

```
## [1] 106.9926
```

time without an activity before and after text production

```
summary(bachMain$no_activity_sec)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##      9.563  36.937  85.805 124.225 162.969 1521.297
```

```
# time without an activity before and after text production, SD  
sd(bachMain$no_activity_sec)  
## [1] 153.8698
```

Visual summaries main experiment

Sums of inter-word pause lengths per text

Times without any activity before and after text production

The boxplot clearly shows an extreme data point. Let's therefore inspect the data set without the extreme value. First, descriptive stats without the data point:

```
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   9.563 36.828  85.125 114.973 159.899 624.734
## [1] 103.6124
```

Now, the boxplot without the data point:

Regression analysis for inter-word pause length

We saw above that there is one extreme value for no activity. All data for this particular text looks ok except for its value for no activity. It is possible that there was simply a gap at the end of the task.

Let's visually check how the distribution of `interword_pauses_sec` looks with and without the extreme data point.

The interquartile range for L1>L2 reviews becomes slightly wider. Otherwise the data looks ok. We will therefore run the model without the extreme data point.

```

## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood . t-tests use Satterthwaite's
## method [lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula:
## interword_pauses_sec_c ~ direction_sum * register_sum + LexTale_EN_c +
##   keystroke_time_copy_sec_c + no_activity_sec_c + (1 | participantID)
## Data: bachMain135_s
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
##  2074.4  2100.5 -1028.2  2056.4    126
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.3634 -0.5780 -0.0503  0.5301  3.6245
##
## Random effects:
## Groups           Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## participantID (Intercept) 122935   350.6
## Residual                172178   414.9
## Number of obs: 135, groups: participantID, 34
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error    df t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)      12.651    70.163  34.163  0.180  0.85798
## direction_sum1    98.438    35.941 101.475  2.739  0.00728 **
## register_sum1    347.147    37.289 106.005  9.310 2.01e-15 ***
## LexTale_EN_c     -3.839     6.628  34.847 -0.579  0.56613
## keystroke_time_copy_sec_c 13.788   104.942  34.138  0.131  0.89624
## no_activity_sec_c  2.174     0.500 127.593  4.349 2.77e-05 ***
## direction_sum1:register_sum1 -177.019   36.440 104.300 -4.858 4.19e-06 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) drctn_1 rgst_1 LT_EN_ ky____ n_ct__
## directn_sm1  0.013
## registr_sm1 -0.026 -0.038
## LexTal_EN_c -0.018 -0.008  0.035
## kystrk_t____ -0.012 -0.002  0.016  0.054
## n_ctvty_sc_  0.077  0.104 -0.285 -0.145 -0.075
## drctn_s1:_1  0.010  0.011 -0.046 -0.035 -0.020  0.194

```

As neither L2 proficiency nor typing speed in the copy task turn out to have an effect on pause behaviour, we fit another model with all 38 participants (but without the extreme data point) without these variables.

Final model

```

# Complete data set minus the extreme case
bachMainCompl <- bachMain_s |>
  filter(textID != "BACHMCBDAL07_A")

pause_md1_compl <- lmer(interword_pauses_sec_c ~ direction_sum * register_sum +
  no_activity_sec_c + (1|participantID), data = bachMainCompl, REML = FALSE)
summary(pause_md1_compl)

```

```
## Linear mixed model fit by maximum likelihood . t-tests use Satterthwaite's
## method [lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula:
## interword_pauses_sec_c ~ direction_sum * register_sum + no_activity_sec_c +
## (1 | participantID)
## Data: bachMainCompl
##
##      AIC      BIC   logLik deviance df.resid
## 2302.8 2324.0 -1144.4  2288.8    144
##
## Scaled residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.3840 -0.5618 -0.0401  0.5598  3.6973
##
## Random effects:
## Groups      Name          Variance Std.Dev.
## participantID (Intercept) 113667   337.1
## Residual          159956   399.9
## Number of obs: 151, groups: participantID, 38
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##              Estimate Std. Error      df t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)      18.7922    63.7631   37.9403  0.295 0.76982
## direction_sum1    95.5683    32.6844  113.1476  2.924 0.00418
## register_sum1     360.4499    33.7880  117.5891 10.668 < 2e-16
## no_activity_sec_c  2.0692     0.4546  143.5747  4.552 1.13e-05
## direction_sum1:register_sum1 -183.2756    33.3175  117.1153 -5.501 2.25e-07
##
## (Intercept)
## direction_sum1          **
## register_sum1           ***
## no_activity_sec_c       ***
## direction_sum1:register_sum1 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Correlation of Fixed Effects:
##              (Intr) drct_1 rgst_1 n_ct__
## directn_sm1  0.009
## registr_sm1 -0.019 -0.030
## n_ctvty_sc_  0.058  0.082 -0.266
## drctn_s1:_1  0.008  0.009 -0.048  0.210
```

Coefficients

```
# random effect coefficients for each participant
# coef(pause_mdL_compl)$participantID
summary(coef(pause_mdL_compl)$participantID[1])

## (Intercept)
## Min.      :-652.06
## 1st Qu.   :-174.06
## Median    :  44.28
## Mean      :  18.79
## 3rd Qu.   : 186.23
## Max.      : 721.37
```

Check for collinearity

```
vif(pause_md1_compl)

##           direction_sum           register_sum
##           1.006929           1.076071
##           no_activity_sec_c direction_sum:register_sum
##           1.129798           1.046316
```

Model comparison

```
pause_md1_compl_afex <- mixed(interword_pauses_sec_c ~ direction * register + no_a
ctivity_sec_c + (1|participantID), data = bachMainCompl, method = "LRT")

## Contrasts set to contr.sum for the following variables: direction, register, pa
rticipantID

## Numerical variables NOT centered on 0: no_activity_sec_c
## If in interactions, interpretation of lower order (e.g., main) effects difficul
t.

## REML argument to lmer() set to FALSE for method = 'PB' or 'LRT'

pause_md1_compl_afex

## Mixed Model Anova Table (Type 3 tests, LRT-method)
##
## Model: interword_pauses_sec_c ~ direction * register + no_activity_sec_c +
## Model:      (1 | participantID)
## Data: bachMainCompl
## Df full model: 7
##           Effect df      Chisq p.value
## 1           direction 1    8.26 **    .004
## 2           register 1   78.54 ***   <.001
## 3 no_activity_sec_c 1   19.08 ***   <.001
## 4 direction:register 1   26.83 ***   <.001
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '+' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

R2

```
r.squaredGLMM(pause_md1_compl_afex$full_model)

##           R2m           R2c
## [1,] 0.4877996 0.7005753
```

Is the error normally distributed?

```
hist(residuals(pause_md1_compl))
```

Histogram of residuals(pause_mdl_compl)

There is somewhat of a right-skew in the model, which is also visible in the q-q plot:

```
qqnorm(residuals(pause_mdl_compl))  
qqline(residuals(pause_mdl_compl))
```

Normal Q-Q Plot

Check for homoskedasticity

```
plot(fitted(pause_md1_compl), abs(residuals(pause_md1_compl)))
```


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Evaluation of translations into Plain German produced by humans and MT systems including ChatGPT

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Abstract

In this paper, we present the results of a study evaluating intralingual machine translations of health information texts into Plain German. In our study, we compare machine-translated simplified texts with those simplified manually by human translators, as well as with the original, unsimplified texts. We compare the output of four different machine translations systems and assess the translation quality using various criteria, including translation errors, readability, and syntactic complexity. The study reveals that from the four analysed machine translation systems, ChatGPT performed worst. Our results also suggest that fine-tuning a model with task-specific and domain-specific data improves the translation quality.

Keywords: Plain Language; simplified German; text simplification; health communication; Large Language Models; ChatGPT

1. Introduction

This paper focuses on the analysis of human and machine translations of health information texts into Plain German. As a form of accessible communication, Plain Language has become increasingly significant in health communication (Schaeffer et al. 2018; Deilen et al. 2024a; Ahrens 2025; Maaß 2024a). Translating a text from standard German into Plain Language belongs to the field of intralingual translation (Hansen-Schirra et al. 2020), which is defined as “an interpretation of verbal signs by means of other signs in the same language” (Jakobson 1959: 233).

Despite the urgent need for Plain Language translations, there is a shortage of qualified and experienced human translators as well as a lack of computer-aided translation (CAT) tools and high-quality machine translation (MT) systems for this type of intralingual translation. Even though more and more MT systems are currently being developed and released, there is limited information on the performance of existing systems for translating texts into Plain Language, particularly in the context of health communication.

Recent studies have revealed that over half of Germany’s population have low health literacy, i.e., find it difficult to access, understand, appraise, and apply health information (Schaeffer et al. 2021). Consequently, enhancing health literacy has become a crucial aim for the German healthcare system (Schaeffer et al. 2018). Almost 75% of the general population show low health literacy in the dimension “appraise” (Schaeffer et al. 2021: 26), and digital health literacy is particularly low (Schaeffer et al. 2021: 68). Research shows that accessible communication is relevant to promote health literacy. Accessible communication helps patients to navigate the health system and to better comprehend, engage with, and adhere to medical advice (Schaeffer et al. 2021).

The emergence of MT tools that use Large Language Models (LLMs) that are readily available to the public enhances the importance of digital health literacy. While understanding health information may become easier, its appraisal becomes harder, knowing that such translation tools may present false and even harmful information. Therefore, in this study, we analyse machine-translated texts in Plain German, comparing them with human translations. The goal is to show how the different models perform and what types of problems they show. We also demonstrate that methods of translation error analysis from interlingual translation can also be applied to intralingual translation. In doing so, we contribute to the methodological development of research on intralingual MT. Apart from looking into compliance with the rules of Plain Language (such as readability and syntactic simplicity), we specifically pay attention to the correctness of the content and the errors that occur in machine translations. We evaluate the machine-generated translations produced by four different models and compare them with the professional human gold-standard translations. Additionally, we also compare all translations with the original source texts written in standard German. Both the source texts and human gold standard translations (text in Plain Language) were taken from the website of the German health magazine *Apotheken Umschau*¹.

The following sections provide an overview of our findings. Section 2 reviews related research. Section 3 outlines our research design, including the corpus and methods used. Section 3.3. details the results of our analyses, and in Section 4, we discuss these results along with their limitations and potential avenues for future research.

2. Related work

2.1. Plain Language

Plain Language is a means to make expert information accessible to lay readers (Maaß 2020, 2024a). The target audience of Plain Language texts are non-experts with average or slightly below average language or reading skills (Maaß 2020). Intralingual translation is often required in settings with asymmetric knowledge distribution or knowledge gaps between the communication participants, for example in the field of medical and health communication. Even though in intralingual translation, there is “no classical language change in the sense of interlinguality, which is typically regarded as a criterion for the definition of translation” (Hansen-Schirra et al. 2020: 199), we agree with researchers such as Schubert (2013), Bredel & Maaß (2016), or Hansen-Schirra et al. (2020), who propose a broader definition of translation (including intralingual, interlingual and intersemiotic translation).

Plain Language is flexible. Its linguistic features can be adapted to the presumed reading skills of the intended audience (Maaß 2020). Easy Language, on the other hand, is maximally reduced on all language levels (i.e. on the morphological, lexical, phrasal, syntactic and textual level) and therefore characterized by a more fixed set of linguistic rules (Bredel & Maaß 2016; Maaß 2020). It is mainly intended for people with communication impairments and disabilities (Bredel & Maaß 2016; Maaß 2020). In contrast to Easy Language, Plain Language has no stigmatising features but is also much less comprehensible. Therefore, situated between the

¹ For the source texts, see: <https://www.apotheken-umschau.de> (accessed 2025-03-14) and for the human gold standard translations, see <https://www.apotheken-umschau.de/einfache-sprache/> (accessed 2025-03-14).

varieties Easy and Plain Language, Maaß (2020) models Easy Language Plus, which balances comprehensibility and acceptability.

In the area of natural language processing, translation into Plain Language can be linked to the studies on automatic text simplification. This area of research has focused on automatically converting complex lexical and syntactical constructions in a text into simpler ones (see, for instance, Saggion 2017; Martin et al. 2020; Sheang & Saggion 2021; Maddela et al. 2021, Ebling et al. 2022, Weiss & Meurers 2022, amongst others). Most existing approaches have focused on the differences based on language command or educational level. However, the differences between readers of Easy and Plain Language and further differentiation within the subgroups have not been addressed so far. At the same time, it is known that target audience-oriented data helps to build better automatic text simplification models (as stated by Scarton & Specia 2018). One method to perform text simplification is by using machine translation tools. Specific problems of automatic systems for intralingual translation have been described by Säuberli et al. (2020) and Spring et al. (2023). Overall, with the emergence of generative language models, there has been a considerable improvement in performance for the task of intralingual translation, e.g., translation from standard German into Easy or Plain German.

At the same time, despite the improvements in the intralingual MT systems, studies revealed that target groups are not yet safe to use the outputs (Anschütz et al. 2023; Maaß 2024b). Still, the tools can be used to provide professional translators with a draft that is post-edited in a next step. Further studies (Deilen et al. 2023; Deilen et al. 2024a, 2024b) also show that intralingual MT systems can be useful for professional translators to reduce their workload, but that they cannot be used safely without post-editing. Deilen et al. (2024a, 2024b) evaluated the performance of the MT system SUMM AI. SUMM AI is an intralingual translation tool that not only uses an LLM but also employs Easy and Plain Language parameters. The authors analysed the output of three SUMM AI models: baseline model, model 1 and model 2. The baseline model was a generically trained LLM while model 1 and model 2 used LLMs *and* were fine-tuned using the texts from *Apotheken Umschau* (see 3.1.). The baseline model and model 1 used the same LLM; however, unlike the baseline model, model 1 was also fine-tuned (Deilen et al. 2024b). Fine tuning was done with 170 texts from the *Apotheken Umschau* website. Both source texts and human gold standard texts were used to fine tune the LLM. Model 2 was fine-tuned in the same manner but is based on a different LLM. They compared the models' output with the existing human translations and the underlying source texts. Their study revealed that even though the fine tuning improved the output, the evaluation of the correctness revealed severe misinformation and content-related mistakes for all models (Deilen et al. 2024a: 47, 2024b: 473).

Similarly to Deilen et al. (2023), who tested ChatGPT for German Easy Language translations, Madina et al. (2024) investigated the feasibility of using ChatGPT to create Spanish Easy-To-Read (E2R) texts. Their study revealed that the generated output does not follow the E2R text rules (for example the rule regarding sentence splitting) and that the tool did not anticipate the knowledge of users, for example by adding examples and explanations when necessary. Therefore, they conclude that the output is still not suitable for the target audience, in this case users with cognitive disabilities.

2.2. Accessibility in the medical domain

Studies existing in the area of health literacy show that readers have trouble appraising the quality, trustworthiness, commercial interest, and applicability of health information to their own situation (Schaeffer et al. 2021: 69). The German *National Action Plan Health Literacy* (Schaeffer et al. 2018) suggests using Plain Language to make health information more accessible to large portions of the population. Health information in Plain Language may address population groups whose health literacy is measured to be particularly low, i.e., population groups with lower socio-economic status, lower education level, higher age, or migration experiences. People with chronic illnesses and disabilities, too, can benefit from health information in Plain Language, as they need to navigate the health system more extensively than the average person. Plain Language may alleviate some of the complexity in the health system. To translate more health texts into Plain Language, translators may leverage intralingual MT tools, such as those using LLMs, to speed up the translation process. This may make it feasible to meet the demand for accessible health information.

However, the use of LLM-based tools to translate health information into Plain Language is not without risks. Language models predict the likelihood of an utterance, but do not assess its accuracy in a given context. Weidinger et al. (2022) therefore identify the risk area “misinformation harms”. Generating false information may threaten a person’s autonomy, increase their trust in false beliefs, amplify distrust in “society’s shared epistemology” (Weidinger et al. 2022: 218), and even cause bodily harm (Weidinger et al. 2022: 219), so that LLM-based tools are unsafe for users (Maaß 2024b).

Wilhelm et al. (2023) compare the health information output of four LLMs (for example GPT-3.5-Turbo) in terms of the criteria of completeness, correctness, and harmfulness. The models were asked “How to treat [disease]”. The four models showed promise, for example in presenting balanced and unbiased information, but did not usually present the risks and potential harms of suggested treatments (completeness) and usually presented also incorrect and harmful information. The authors thus conclude that professional proof-reading is needed. GPT-3.5-Turbo performed best in terms of correctness and was the only MT-tool to not present any harmful health information.

2.3. Error analysis in the field of text simplification

Automatic text simplification aims to make given texts easier to read and understand while preserving its original meaning. Even though there is a large amount of work on text simplification, the evaluation of the simplification output still remains understudied (Grabar & Saggion 2022). Grabar & Saggion (2022) discuss the current state of the evaluation of automatic text simplification, including some crucial factors such as the role of end users, the domain of source documents, and the evaluation measures. They point out that one of the main challenges in the field of text simplification is the fact that the output is subjective, which makes it difficult to evaluate. The main reasons for this lack of objective measures are that there are no native simplified-language speakers, the guidelines for simplification are often vague, and the simplification requirements often vary depending on the target group of the text. With the rise of Large Language Models, more and more studies have been conducted that investigated the feasibility of using LLMs for text simplification and evaluation tasks in different languages. Most studies conclude that LLMs show great potential for text simplification, especially after

prompting and fine-tuning (see for example Klöser et al. 2024 for German; Martínez et al. 2024 for Spanish; or Nozza & Attanasio 2023 for Italian).

The only studies known to us that deal with intralingual (i.e. Plain Language) translation evaluation are Deilen et al. (2023) and Deilen et al. (2024a, 2024b). In Deilen et al. (2023), the researchers used ChatGPT-3.5 as a MT tool to translate administrative texts into German Easy Language. Two linguists trained in Easy and Plain Language manually checked the ChatGPT-output independently of one another. In case of discrepancies, the errors were discussed by six Easy Language experts. The authors followed a similar approach in Deilen et al. (2024a, 2024b). Here, the focus was on health communication in German Plain Language. Standard language texts from the *Apotheken Umschau* website were machine translated using the intralingual translation tool SUMM AI² and two researchers conducted the same manual error-check. When specialised knowledge of the medical domain was needed, Deilen et al. consulted the editorial team of the *Apotheken Umschau*. Deilen et al. (2023, 2024a, 2024b) report only whether the outputs were correct or incorrect. If one content-related error was found, the output was considered incorrect. This was done to first evaluate the suitability of machine-translated Plain Language output for end users. In health communication, texts are unsafe if they contain any content-related mistakes as health literacy is low – especially considering the dimension *appraisal*. From the baseline model, 29 translations were incorrect; model 1 performed similarly, having translated only two out of 30 texts correctly; model 2 had the best performance with 15 correct translations (Deilen et al. 2024b). None of the ChatGPT-4o translations were correct. The authors do not provide any information on error categories nor error severity.

Established schemes for error analysis in interlingual (machine) translation are widely used (see, e.g., multidimensional quality metrics – MQM, Lommel et al. 2014). They normally describe error typology with various linguistic categories, as well as error scoring and severity levels. However, to the best of our knowledge, an error evaluation scheme for intralingual translation is still missing. We chose the translation error framework MQM. Relevant criteria are chosen from this framework to assess the translation quality in a given project. For example, using the harmonised Dynamic Quality Framework and Multidimensional Quality Metrics (DQF-MQM), Rodríguez Vázquez et al. (2022) compared three interlingual MT tools for various language pairs. Easy Language texts regarding the legal, medical, and political domain were translated from French to German, English, Spanish, and Farsi. The authors compared adherence to Easy Language rules and translation quality according to DQF-MQM. The translations from French into German Easy Language most notably contained translation errors regarding linguistic conventions (like spelling, punctuation, or grammar) and accuracy (like mistranslations, over-, or under-translation, Rodríguez Vázquez et al. 2022). Translation of health information texts, too, contained most notably errors in linguistic conventions, but also style errors (i.e. awkward, unidiomatic, or inconsistent style, Rodríguez Vázquez et al. 2022). Concerning Easy Language rules, German texts contained most rule violations on the word level (for example choice of words and numbers) and the rule to segment compounds was not implemented at all (Rodríguez Vázquez et al. 2022: 40). In all domains, most rules on the word level contained errors. In health information texts, errors on the phrase level (for example negation and use of present tense) were also common (Rodríguez Vázquez et al. 2022: 39). The

² summ-ai.com. (accessed 2025-03-14). SUMM AI is a machine translation tool for translating texts into Easy German and Plain German. The company SUMM AI offers different licenses for freelancers, authorities and companies.

authors conclude that their results can be used to devise rules for the pre- and post-editing processes that aim to solve the most prominent accessibility issues in the MT-generated texts. Other studies utilise LLMs to automatically apply MQM for translation evaluation (Fernandes et al. 2023; Kocmi & Federmann 2023). Since application of MT for Easy and Plain Language is growing, there is a need for studies and frameworks focusing on error typology in intralingual translation.

3. Research design

3.1. Data collection

We use the dataset from Deilen et al. (2024b), which is based on the 30 texts from the *Apotheken Umschau* website. The texts cover various topics ranging from long COVID, diabetes to birth control. The 30 texts were chosen randomly out of the 200 texts for which a Plain Language translation was available, with the only condition that they cover as many different categories as possible (medication, diseases, therapies, first aid, contraception). For each of these 30 texts, the dataset contains a professional human translation into Plain Language and three machine-translated outputs produced with three different SUMM AI models (see 2.3.). The human translations were produced by Plain Language experts who were translation students at the University of Hildesheim and who professionally translated health information at the Research Centre for Easy Language (University of Hildesheim). The human translations underwent a three-stage proof-reading process. The rough translations were proofread by a peer. The translator then improved the translation according to the feedback. A project manager proofread the translation again before sending it to the *Apotheken Umschau* editorial team that ensured the correctness of the content. If the translation contained any mistakes, the translations were again improved by the project manager. Consequently, these translations can be considered as reference, i.e., a human gold standard.

In our study, we add a ChatGPT-4o corpus and compare the machine translations (four for each text) with the existing human translations and the source texts. The main difference between ChatGPT and SUMM AI is that the latter was specifically developed for Easy and Plain German translation (see above), while ChatGPT is a generic tool. In addition, ChatGPT is a chatbot that can be prompted whereas SUMM AI does not contain any prompting functions. Translations with ChatGPT were generated after a two-step prompt. The prompt was developed based on findings from Deilen et al. (2023), stating that assigning a role, setting a context and asking for background information seemed to improve the output. First, ChatGPT was asked to define *Plain Language* in the field of accessible communication and inclusion: “ChatGPT, wie wird im Bereich der Barrierefreien Kommunikation und der Inklusion ‘Einfache Sprache’ definiert?” (“ChatGPT, how is *Plain Language* defined in the field of Accessible Communication and inclusion?”). Then, ChatGPT was prompted to take on the role of a Plain Language expert:

ChatGPT, du bist jetzt ein Experte für Einfache Sprache. Wir brauchen Unterstützung in der Übersetzung eines Textes der Gesundheitskommunikation in Einfache Sprache. In dem Text geht es um [hier Thema einfügen]. Die Übersetzung soll für Menschen mit Leseschwierigkeiten leicht verständlich sein. Übersetze bitte den folgenden Text:

‘ChatGPT, you are now an expert in Plain Language. We need help translating a health communication text into Plain Language. The text is about [insert topic]. The translation should be easily comprehensible for people who have difficulty reading³. Please translate the following text:’.

As a result, for each source text we have one human gold standard and four machine translations produced with four different models that are labelled as baseline, model 1, model 2 and ChatGPT in the analysis below⁴.

3.2. Data analysis

We follow Deilen et al. (2023, 2024a, 2024b) to evaluate the machine translated outputs in terms of readability, syntactic complexity, and correctness. Easy Language and Simple Language have specific characteristics at all linguistic levels. We will limit ourselves here to the example of syntactic complexity because it provides a good indication of the profiles of the target texts. We add to the results reported in Deilen et al. (2024b) by comparing them with the ChatGPT-4o corpus. We will also add an analysis of error typology, not only for the ChatGPT-4o outputs, but also for the SUMM AI outputs. This analysis is described in section 3.2.2., and preliminary results from the current stage of error analysis are presented in 3.3.3.

3.2.1. Readability

We automatically evaluated readability using the Hohenheim Comprehensibility Index (HIX). The HIX, which is commonly used in German Easy Language Research, takes into account the four major readability formulas validated for the German language (Bredel & Maaß 2016: 61–62): the Amstad index, the simple measure of gobbledygook (G-SMOG) index, the Vienna non-fictional text formula (W-STX), and the readability index (LIX). A HIX of 0 indicates extremely low comprehensibility and a HIX of 20 means extremely high comprehensibility⁵. At a HIX of 18, a text can be classified as Easy German, i.e. the least complex variety of German (Rink 2020; Maaß 2024). The benchmark for Plain German is at 16 points (Kröger et al. 2025).

3.2.2. Syntactic complexity

We use dependency parsing (using the Stanford NLP Python Library Stanza (v1.2.1)⁶) to automatically measure the distribution of specific syntactic relations with the goal to assess syntactic complexity. Syntactic relations include adnominal clauses or clausal modifiers of noun (acl), adverbial clause modifiers (advcl), clausal components (ccomp), clausal subjects (csubj), open clausal elements (xcomp), and parataxis relation (parataxis). The higher the number of these syntactic relations in the corpus, the more complex the texts. The distribution frequencies of these syntactic relations are calculated for each corpus: source texts, human translations, and the four machine translated outputs.

³ We used “people who have difficulty reading” as an umbrella term for the different Plain Language target groups (see Maaß 2020).

⁴ The labels for the SUMM AI systems were taken from Deilen et al. (2024b).

⁵ see <https://klartext.uni-hohenheim.de/hix> (accessed 2025-03-14)

⁶ <https://stanfordnlp.github.io/stanza/index.html> (accessed 2025-03-14)

3.2.3. Correctness and error typology

Correctness as a criterion for automatic intralingual Easy and Plain Language translation was reported in Deilen et al. (2024a, 2024b). In Plain Language translation, a text can be classified as correct if it does not contain any errors, neither in terms of content nor in terms of language (i.e. spelling, grammar). Common errors in the corpus of Deilen et al. (2024a, 2024b) were redundancies, unreasonable and incorrect statements, lexico-semantic errors, missing segmentation signs, as well as missing reflective pronouns. However, in Deilen et al. (2024a, 2024b), the researchers simply mentioned the errors they encountered but they did not employ a structured error analysis, as is done in this study.

To check the correctness in a more structured manner that allows for a later quantitative error analysis, we first adapted and chose between relevant parts of the MQM to fit the present intralingual translation study. We then analysed the four main error categories: terminology, accuracy, linguistic conventions, and audience appropriateness. Table 1 presents and defines these four categories (in bold letters) and its error types in more detail.

As stated before, the error typology is based on the categories proposed by MQM, expanded and adapted with error types fitting intralingual translation analysis. For instance, the typology “wrong or missing explanation” was added under accuracy: if an explanation was present and relevant but did not reflect the information from the source text, it constitutes a “wrong addition”. If an explanation was needed, but not present, it was a “missing addition”. The adapted MQM is used as a coding frame to manually analyse the translation errors within the MT output.

An initial analysis using the coding frame focused on the ChatGPT-4o output. Here, researchers compared the source texts with the ChatGPT-4o output. They annotated any errors according to the coding frame. This initial analysis was useful to evaluate which parts of the coding frame were usable and which parts needed further adaptation. Definitions for each error category were specified to fit the present corpora, and examples were added to make the coding frame more usable. The initial analysis was also needed to train the researchers in error analysis. At this stage, errors were documented thoroughly in each text and the number of errors was added up according to the four main categories of terminology, accuracy, linguistic conventions, and audience appropriateness (see Section 3.3.3.).

In a next step, the improved coding frame was used to again analyse three texts in the ChatGPT-4o subcorpus and to analyse three texts in the model 1 subcorpus. Again, the MT output was compared with the source texts, and any errors were annotated according to the coding frame. The researchers who had previously analysed the ChatGPT-4o output now analysed the model 1 output. The researchers discussed cases in which they disagreed. Due to time constraints, this was completed for one of the model 1 texts and for all three ChatGPT-4o texts which are much shorter than the SUMM AI generated texts. After this process, the coding frame was again adapted: definitions were written more clearly and more distinctly from each other (see Table 1), examples were corrected, clarified, or added. Errors were again documented thoroughly. After this second step, the coding frame was finalised and is currently used to analyse all MT outputs.

Table 1: Overview of the MQM error categories from the current project stage⁷

Error type	Definition
Terminology	The use of a term does not fit to the field conventions, is incorrectly used in the target text or is not equivalent to the term in the source text.
Inconsistent terminology	Multiple terms are used to describe the same concept when just one term is needed or appropriate.
Wrong term	Multiple terms are used to describe the same concept when just one term is needed or appropriate.
Accuracy	Content in the target text does not match the propositions from the source text.
Mistranslations	Target content does not accurately represent the source content.
Ambiguous content	Ambiguity is introduced where specification is needed.
Hallucination	Machine translation produces an output that is totally decoupled from the source text.
Wrong or missing explanation	Explanation is necessary and added but does not represent the information from the source text (<i>wrong</i>) or an explanation is needed but is not present in the target text (<i>missing</i>).
Incomplete information	Relevant information from the source text is missing in the target text.
Linguistic conventions	Errors related to the linguistic level of the source text.
Grammar	Grammatical rules are violated in the source text.
Punctuation	Punctuation is used incorrectly.
Spelling	Words are misspelled.
Cohesion and coherence	Connectors necessary to understand the text as a whole are missing or incorrect (<i>cohesion</i>). Semantic relationships within the text are not clear (<i>coherence</i>)
Audience appropriateness	Content in the target text is not valid, appropriate or acceptable for the target audiences.
Inaccurate advice	Target text contains advice that is not in the source text or that is not suitable for the situation in question.
Stigmatising content	Content can lead to stigmatization of end users.

⁷ Current project stage refers to the fact that we are currently working on adapting the MQM error categories to the field of intralingual translation and that these are the categories used for the presented analyses. However, this work can be regarded as work in progress, i.e. while analysing the errors, we also adapt the scheme accordingly.

3.3. Results

3.3.1. Readability

Figure 1 illustrates the HIX values for each corpus. As expected, the source text corpus scored the lowest HIX values of the six corpora (mean: 10.46, SD: 2.76). Model 2 achieved the highest HIX values, with a mean HIX value of 19.5 (SD: 0.76). The ChatGPT-4o texts yielded the lowest HIX value among all machine translations (mean: 16.1, SD: 3.26). Figure 1 also shows that the ChatGPT translations had a much greater variation in the HIX values than all other texts.

Figure 1: HIX values of the four machine translations, the human translations, and the source texts

All texts in the baseline corpus and in the model 2 corpus could be classified as Plain German – meaning all texts reached a HIX value of at least 16 points. 93% of the model 1 corpus and 83% of the human translation corpus reached this benchmark. Only 57% of texts in the ChatGPT-4o corpus could be classified as Plain German. Thus, in terms of readability, ChatGPT-4o performed worse than the other MT systems.

Still, it is important to keep in mind that the HIX value is only a quantitative measure that focuses purely on readability features on the text surface (i.e. overt complexity). This means that the textual level and aspects like cohesion, coherence, or information structure are not assessed. Consequently, HIX values can only be regarded as a first step in the analysis and have to be supplemented with further qualitative analysis. For example, how is the complexity of the text contents reflected in the very homogeneously high HIX values of model 2?

3.3.2. Syntactic complexity

Figure 2 shows the distributions of complex dependency relations in all the subcorpora under analysis. Similarly to the results reported by Deilen et al. (2024b), none of the machine-translated outputs is syntactically as simple as the human translations.

Figure 2: Distribution of syntactically complex dependency relations in the source texts, human and the four machine translations (normalised frequencies per 10000)

The best performing system in terms of syntactic simplicity was model 1 with the only exception of the parataxis relation. This type of relation was automatically assigned to sentential parenthetical or a clause after a colon or a semicolon placed side by side without any explicit coordination or subordination. This type of construction, especially the one with colon, is frequently used in Plain German, as shown in the human translation in example (1): *Sie glauben* ('You think') is followed by a colon and the verb *haben* ('have') is tagged as a parataxis relation to the verb *glauben* ('think') by the parser.

- (1) **Sie glauben:** Ich habe eine seelische Erkrankung? (**You think:** I have a mental illness?)

This demonstrates the appropriateness of the use of this relation in translations into Plain Language and also explains why we observe an opposite tendency here if compared to other syntactically complex relations. Since syntactic embedding depth in particular poses a risk to comprehension, parataxis in Plain Language texts to a moderate extent does not pose a problem. Accordingly, it also appears frequently in the human-translated gold standard texts, which supports once more that parataxes are not difficult to process and can therefore be used in Plain Language texts. Interestingly, translations with ChatGPT-4o were similar to human translations in terms of the use of parataxis relations.

However, this is not the case for the other syntactic relations. The ChatGPT-4o outcomes are positioned between the performance by baseline and the models 1 and 2, with the exception of complement clauses, where ChatGPT-4o achieved a similar performance as the most successful model 2. An example of a complement clause is illustrated in example (2).

- (2) a. Ein gesundes Gelenk hat eine Schicht aus Knorpel und Gelenkflüssigkeit. Diese sorgen dafür, dass die Knochen nicht aneinander reiben. (ChatGPT-4o)
'A healthy joint has a layer of cartilage and synovial fluid. These ensure that the bones do not rub against each other.'

- b. Zwischen den Knochen sind Knorpel und Gelenkflüssigkeit. Sie dienen dem Schutz der Knochen: So reiben die Knochen nicht aneinander. (Human)
‘Between the bones are cartilages and synovial fluid. They serve to protect the bones: This way the bones do not rub against each other.’

The translation with ChatGPT-4o in (2a) contains the complement clause introduced with the complementizer *dass* (‘that’). The human gold standard translation in (2b) contains a parataxis construction with a colon instead.

3.3.3. Correctness and Error Typology

The initial MQM-based error analysis of the ChatGPT-4o translation corpus shows several issues along all four main categories (see section 3.2.2.), indicating that most of the texts have to be professionally post-edited to be functional and action-oriented. In this first analysis, a total amount of 244 errors were found in 30 ChatGPT-4o generated texts, averaging 8.13 errors per text (SD: 7.3; mode: 2). Most errors were found in the main categories *accuracy* (110 errors) and *linguistic conventions* (109 errors). A “mistranslation” is illustrated in the following example from our MQM coding frame:

- (3) a. Zudem gibt es eine Früherkennungsuntersuchung, die ab einem Alter von 35 Jahren alle zwei Jahre von den Krankenkassen bezahlt wird. (source text)
‘Additionally, there is a screening that from age 35 onward is paid by health insurance.’
- b. Ab 35 Jahren kannst du alle zwei Jahre eine Hautuntersuchung bei deiner Krankenkasse machen lassen. (ChatGPT-4o)
‘From the age of 35 onward, you can get a skin examination at your health insurance.’ (using the informal *you*)

The correctness and error typology analysis indicates the utmost importance of post-editing by professional translators or domain experts. Classifying error severity and thus also the resulting post-editing workload remains an open question, which will be addressed in future phases of this research project.

4. Summary and future work

ChatGPT-4o generated texts displayed the lowest and the most varied HIX values. The three SUMM AI models were better able to produce readable text that reached the Plain Language benchmark more often. While ChatGPT-4o did not perform as well as model 1 in terms of syntactic complexity, it resembled human translation in its use of parataxis. In other syntactic relations, it mostly performed better than the baseline model, but worse than models 1 and 2. All 30 ChatGPT-4o generated texts contained errors.

The SUMM AI models outperform ChatGPT-4o in almost all analysed criteria. This suggests that fine-tuning both with task-specific data (baseline system), meaning the task of intralingual translation into Plain Language, and with domain-specific data (health texts from *Apotheken Umschau*), improves MT into Plain German. Fine-tuned models that are trained specifically for intralingual translation tasks outperform the general model that uses prompting. In the case of ChatGPT-4o, we did not use all the prompting strategies proposed in

Deilen et al (2023): In addition to the holistic model that was used in this paper, they chose a second approach that they called “linguistic”. This approach gives ChatGPT the order to simplify subsequently at different linguistic levels: explain terms, reduce syntactic complexity and similar. In Deilen et al. (2023), the holistic approach performed better, which is why it was favoured in the current study. However, it would be interesting to include this few-shot prompting approach again in the next steps of the study design. It is similar to the fine-tuning used for the different models of SUMM AI. Further insights into the successful use of prompt models could be expected here.

Preliminary results show that, similar to the results by Rodríguez Vázquez et al. (2022) who evaluated interlingual translations of Easy Language texts, most ChatGPT-4o-generated errors appear in the categories *accuracy* and *linguistic conventions*. In the current project stage, we once more apply the error analysis to the ChatGPT-4o corpus, but also to the SUMM AI models (baseline, model 1, model 2). Furthermore, following MQM settings and recommendations (The MQM Council), we aim to assess error severity. This will give us an insight into the usability of the examined MT tools in intralingual translation processes and will allow us to assess the time and effort that are needed for post-editing the output.

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Surprisal explains the occurrence of filler particles in simultaneous interpreting

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Abstract

We present a set of studies on filler particles in interpreting in the language pair English-German, asking whether, and if so to what extent, surprisal can explain their occurrence. It is widely acknowledged that filler particles are associated with planning effort in monolingual production, but their occurrence in interpreting has not been fully investigated. Surprisal is a measure from information theory that estimates the information content (in bits) of a unit (e.g. a word) in the context of other linguistic units (e.g. n preceding words). Importantly, there is abundant evidence that surprisal is proportional to cognitive effort, measured independently in behavioural experiments, which provides a useful tool for explaining the link between linguistic choice and language cognition. Looking at the words preceding and following a filler particle in the target language output, we investigate surprisal as a predictor of filler particle occurrence, placing a special focus on function words vs. content words that follow filler particles. Overall, our analysis shows that surprisal of following words is a good predictor of filler particles in interpreting.

Keywords: *Filler particles, interpreting, surprisal, prediction, cognitive effort*

1. Introduction

Filler particles (e.g. *uh* or *hum*, also called filled pauses or hesitation markers) are a frequent phenomenon in spoken language. These particles are syntactically nonessential, void of propositional meaning and often linked to difficulties in linguistic planning and production (e.g. Clark & Fox Tree 2002). These properties render them particularly interesting in the context of simultaneous interpreting – a complex task requiring concurrent comprehension of source language input and production of target language output. Previous research has shown that filler particles are overall more frequent in interpreting than in non-mediated (original) speech (e.g. Plevoets & Defrancq 2016, 2018; Chmiel et al. 2022), highlighting their potential role in managing the demands of this dual process. This finding is often linked to variables that are thought to induce an increase in cognitive load such as the presence of numbers, high delivery rate of source speech, interpreting direction (into native or non-native language) and high lexical density (e.g. Plevoets & Defrancq 2016, 2018; Chmiel et al. 2022, 2023, 2024; Bartłomiejczyk & Gumul 2024; Kajzer-Wietrzny et al. 2024). However, to our knowledge, no existing study has examined the immediate linguistic context surrounding filler particles in interpreting. This study addresses this gap by specifically investigating lexico-grammatical properties of the words directly preceding and following filler particles, focussing specifically on their surprisal.

The concept of surprisal, a measure grounded in information theory (Shannon 1948), refers to the (un)expectedness of a given word based on its probability in context. Importantly, surprisal has a direct link to cognition as it is proportional to cognitive effort, measured independently by reading times, eye fixation or event-related brain potentials in comprehension (e.g. Demberg & Keller 2008; Kutas et al. 2011; Smith & Levy 2013). Highly predictable (low surprisal) words are associated with lower cognitive effort and unexpected (high surprisal) words with higher cognitive effort. On the production side, less predictable words are longer in duration and more likely to be articulated with fuller vowels, and vice versa, more predictable units are shortened and phonetically reduced (e.g. Bell et al. 2003; Malisz et al. 2018). Furthermore, some theories of language production suggest that the predictability of words and structures, as reflected in their surprisal, influences their level of pre-activation in the mental lexicon and thereby their ease of lexical access (Kuperberg & Jaeger 2016; Huettig et al. 2022).

Research on monolingual English speech has demonstrated that filler particles tend to appear after low-surprisal words and are followed by high-surprisal ones, suggesting that they may function as cognitive buffers in anticipation of more challenging upcoming material (Dammalapati et al. 2019, 2021; Zámečník 2019). However, the extent to which this relationship holds in the complex, bilingual environment of simultaneous interpreting has not yet been examined.

Focusing on the language pair German-English, the primary goal of our paper is to ask whether surprisal may also explain the occurrence of filler particles in interpreting and what the differences are, if any, comparing free original speech and interpreting. Since interpreters are not fully in control of their own speech and the source language input affects the retrieval processes for the target language output, we assume that surprisal will affect interpreters differently compared to original speakers. As a secondary goal, we pursue a methodological refinement of existing approaches by considering the surprisal of the next content word rather than of the next word. Consider example (1).

(1) speed up euh the spending procedure

Here, the interpreter probably did not struggle to retrieve the function word *the* but rather the following lexical compound *spending procedure*. To test this assumption, we investigate whether the occurrence of filler particles correlates better with the surprisal of the directly following function word or the nearest content word. We think that focusing on the next content word could yield more meaningful results as previous research indicates that there are processing and retrieval differences between content and function words (Bell et al. 2009; Boye & Harder 2012; Lange et al. 2017; Seifart et al. 2018). Filler particles are known to appear at phrase boundaries (e.g. Goldman-Eisler 1968; Schneider 2014; Zámečník 2019) which are often followed by function words such as articles or prepositions. Assuming that high surprisal is also an index of word-planning effort and that filler particles indicate planning difficulty, the surprisal of an upcoming lexical item should be more meaningful compared to the surprisal of a directly following function word, like a preposition or article.

2. State-of-the-Art: Filler particles in interpreting

Filler particles are a specific kind of disfluency in speech production that signals planning effort on the part of the speaker (Corley & Stewart 2008, Kosmala & Crible 2022). In interpreting, filler particles have been shown to be a typical feature along with other markers of online oral production. In fact, features of orality seem to be overemphasised in interpreting when compared to original productions in the same language, as originally shown by Shlesinger & Ordan (2012) for the language pair Hebrew-English and more recently by Przybyl et al. (2022b) using European Parliament data in the language pair English-German, the same data set we use in the present study (see details in Section 3). In this data set, filler particles are more frequent in interpreting compared to original productions in the source language, as is the case in the French-Dutch corpus of Plevoets & Defrancq (2016, 2018) and the Polish-English corpus of Chmiel et al. (2022). In contrast, Dayter (2021) found fewer filler particles in Russian-English interpreting compared to original English speeches. Tissi (2000), Wang & Li (2014) and Bartłomiejczyk & Gumul (2024) found considerable individual variation in filler particle production across interpreters.

For possible explanations of filler particle occurrence in interpreting, researchers have investigated variables that are thought to be linked to increase or decrease in cognitive load. Plevoets & Defrancq (2016, 2018) investigated delivery rate, lexical density, percentage of numerals, average sentence length and formulaicity in the language pair French-Dutch. In their first study (Plevoets & Defrancq 2016), they found a connection between high source text delivery rate, high lexical density in the target text and the frequency of filler particles in interpreted speeches. Source text delivery rate stopped being a significant predictor in their second study (Plevoets & Defrancq 2018), where they used a different statistical method modelling sentence level instead of text level, and introduced formulaicity as a new predictor. In this study, they found a significant effect of source text lexical density and formulaicity of the source and target text. Even though Plevoets & Defrancq (2016, 2018) failed to find a significant effect for percentage of numerals, Kajzer-Wietrzny et al. (2024) took a closer look at numbers as challenging items in interpreting. They distinguished between different types of numbers and included omissions in their model, assuming that interpreters often omit challenging items when cognitive load is too high. In their study, frequency of numbers in the source, type of numbers in the source and omissions in the target were significant predictors of the presence of a disfluency in a sentence. Chmiel et al. (2023) examined interpreters' current load, i.e. the duration of filler particles and silent pauses in the target speech within 500 ms of hearing nouns in the source. They discovered that interpreters paused longer after encountering low-frequency nouns compared to high-frequency nouns. In a later study, Chmiel et al. (2024) found that the mean dependency length of source speeches significantly affected the average pause duration in interpreting but had no impact on the frequency of pauses. In another study on the language pair English-Polish, Bartłomiejczyk & Gumul (2024) started from the assumption that cognitive load is lower for into-A interpreting and compare A-B and B/C-A interpretations from plenary debates of the European Parliament in the language pair English-Polish. They found that interpreters who interpreted into their B-language did not produce a higher rate of filler particles than interpreters who interpreted into their A-language.

These existing works on possible causes for disfluencies in interpreting have in common that they look at quantitative figures over whole texts, (sub)corpora, segments or sentences (e.g. lexical density, delivery rate, interpreting direction), trying to connect aggregated features (e.g. duration of pauses and filler particles, presence of any kind of

disfluency) to meta-data that may be indicative of cognitive load. While methodologically perfectly sound, what is hardly considered are the local linguistic conditions of filler particle occurrence, i.e. their position in the clause or sentence or their lexico-grammatical surroundings. Wang & Li (2014) investigated the syntactic distribution of silent pauses and filler particles in Chinese-English interpreting. They found a high proportion of pauses and filler particles inside phrases in simultaneous interpreting, which is marked because they usually appear at phrase boundaries (e.g. Goldman-Eisler 1968; Schneider 2014). However, they did not look further into causes or predictors for this unusual pause and filler particle placement.

In our research, we address these open questions. First, we consider the *local linguistic context* of filler particles; second, we operationalise retrieval difficulty using the concept of *information* as originally defined by Shannon (1948), commonly referred to as *surprisal* (Crocker et al. 2015), i.e. the (un)expectedness of a linguistic unit in context. If a word is highly expected, i.e. very likely to appear in a given context, it provides little new information (low surprisal) and vice versa, if a word is very unlikely in a given context, it provides much information (high surprisal). Surprisal is measured as the negative logarithm of a word's probability given its preceding context (Hale 2001; Levy 2008). This probability is typically derived from a large corpus or language model, though the definition of context may vary from n-gram models that only take into account the directly preceding word to transformer models with context windows of, e.g., 1024 words. Importantly, surprisal is proportional to cognitive effort (Demberg & Keller 2008) and provides a link between linguistic choice and cognitive behaviour. In the psycholinguistics literature, the term *transitional probability* is usually synonymous to surprisal. Recently, surprisal and related measures have also been used to analyse translation (Schaeffer et al. 2015; Teich et al. 2020; Lapshinova-Koltunski et al. 2022).

Surprisal is often used as an operationalisation for prediction or pre-activation of words and structures (for an overview and discussion, see Kuperberg & Jaeger 2016). Studies on prediction in simultaneous interpreting typically approach the topic from the perspective of prediction during comprehension, assuming that high predictability facilitates processing, enabling interpreters to comprehend more efficiently and use predictions to plan their utterances faster (Amos & Pickering 2020). In a study on predictive processes during simultaneous interpreting from German into English, Hodzik & Williams (2017) examined interpreters' latency times for interpreting sentence-final verbs in the source language input. They found an impact of contextual constraints on prediction but not of transitional probability (surprisal). However, their calculation of transitional probability was based on an n-gram model only considering the directly preceding word. Given its broad context window, transformer surprisal may have captured both the probability of the verb based on the preceding word and the influence of contextual constraints earlier in the sentence. Amos et al. (2022) found evidence for the prediction of upcoming nouns in simultaneous interpreting in a visual world paradigm study. While interpreting sentences with a highly predictable word from English into French, participants made predictive eye movements towards a picture of that word before it was spoken in the English sentence. Liu et al. (2022) also found that 75% of their participants made predictive eye movements in a visual world paradigm while engaging in simultaneous interpreting. However, they found that 25% of their participants did not show predictive eye movements, which they speculated to be the result of the extreme cognitive burden during simultaneous interpreting, which could be a limit on prediction (see also Huettig & Guerra 2019; Amos & Pickering 2020).

In the study at hand, we look at a different angle of prediction in simultaneous interpreting. We focus on prediction and its role in lexical access in language production and planning, that is, interpreters' production and planning of the target language directly. In this sense, low surprisal is tantamount to high pre-activation of the word and therefore ease in lexical access, whereas high surprisal means low pre-activation, leading to more difficulty in lexical access (for a detailed explanation of this process, see Huetting et al. 2022). Greater difficulty in lexical access should then be associated with higher filler particle occurrence, as filler particles signal difficulties in speech planning (Clark & Fox Tree 2002; Corley & Stewart 2008; Kosmala & Crible 2022).

Early works on filler particle placement in monolingual settings (Goldman-Eisler 1968; Beattie & Butterworth 1979) already hypothesised that there is a connection between predictability and filler particles, but these early studies were lacking in methodological sophistication. Some more recent studies have shown that disfluencies occur in the presence of production difficulties due to new information, where “new” could well be modelled with surprisal (e.g. Barr 2001; Arnold et al. 2003; Heller et al. 2015). Investigating monolingual English, Dammalapati et al. (2019, 2021) found that disfluencies (filler particles and repairs) tend to appear after low surprisal words and before high surprisal words. They interpreted this as speakers selecting easily accessible words (low surprisal) to better plan for upcoming production difficulties, as reflected in high surprisal words following disfluencies. Zámečník (2019) also identified surprisal as a strong predictor for filler particle occurrence in monolingual English speech.

Here, we build on these insights from monolingual language production and apply it to simultaneous interpreting. We assume that at least part of lexical access in interpreting is similar to that of monolingual speech production. However, we know that cross-lingual lexical activation happens (Amos & Pickering 2020). Furthermore, Amos & Pickering (2020: 710) note that cognitive load could hinder prediction. More specifically, Amos et al. (2022: 3) point out that “concurrent activation of both languages, and the regular switching of focus from comprehension to production and back between the two languages, may lead to a weaker activation of each language“. Therefore, we expect differences in the effect of surprisal on filler particle occurrence between original and interpreted speeches.

3. Methodology

3.1. Data

The data used in this study are drawn from the German and English subcorpora of EPIC-UdS (Przybyl et al. 2022a). It contains transcriptions of speeches held at the European Parliament between 2008 and 2013 by English and German native-speaking MEPs and their interpretations into German and English, respectively. The transcriptions include disfluencies such as filler particles, truncations and repetitions. The corpora include rich annotations such as part of speech, dependency relations and lemma. Speaker and interpreter identity are included in the metadata. A student assistant was asked to identify individual interpreters by listening to interpreters' voices. Table 1 shows the size of the individual subcorpora. The total corpus comprises approximately 250,000 tokens.

Table 1: EPIC-UdS Corpus (English and German subcorpora)

Subcorpus	Tokens
English Interpreting (SI)	58,503
English Originals (ORG)	71,146
German Interpreting (SI)	62,120
German Originals (ORG)	56,488

3.2. Processing and annotation

Surprisal is typically estimated with computational language models based on large corpora (e.g. n-gram models, LSTMs, Transformers such as Llama or GPT). In our data, surprisal for all tokens in the English corpora was annotated using the default, monolingual GPT-2(-small) model (Radford et al. 2019). There is evidence that GPT-2-small achieves a substantially better fit to reading times than larger GPT-2 models (e.g. GPT-2-XL) or more recent GPT models (e.g. GPT-3), leading to its selection over these alternatives (Oh & Schuler 2021; Shain 2024). For the German data, the corresponding German GPT-2 model (Schweter 2020) was used. Prior to surprisal indexing and analysis, the data were parsed with Stanza (Qi et al. 2020), and surprisal values were calculated for tokens as defined by the parser. Hyphenated words were treated as one token.

Filler particles were removed before parsing and surprisal annotation and reinserted into the corpus afterwards. The rationale for this was that otherwise they would have influenced the surprisal values for tokens following the filler particle as they would have been considered part of the prior context of these words. We did not distinguish between filler particle realisations with and without nasal consonants (*euh hum hm*). Clusters (*euh euh*) were counted as a single instance of a filler particle occurrence.

In addition to surprisal, word frequency and word length were annotated for each word in the corpus. In psycholinguistic literature, both variables are empirically shown to influence language processing, impacting measures such as reading times (e.g. Brysbaert et al. 2017; Kuperman et al. 2024) and event-related potentials (Hauk & Pulvermüller 2004). To disentangle the effect of frequency and length from any possible effect of surprisal, these variables were included in the statistical analysis. Word length was operationalised as number of characters per word and frequency was annotated using frequency measures from SUBTLEX-UK (Van Heuven et al. 2014) and SUBTLEX-DE (Brysbaert et al. 2011).

Since we were interested in investigating differences in lexical contexts where filler particles are more or less likely to occur, for every filler particle, the surprisal, length and frequency of the directly preceding and following word was annotated. Since filler particle can potentially be freely inserted between any two words, any place between two words in the corpus where a filler particle did not appear in was considered a potential filler particle placement and annotated with the surprisal, frequency and length values of the preceding and following words. We controlled for sentences. This means that filler particles and potential

filler particle placements at the very beginning or at the very end of sentences were excluded from the study. Example 2 shows our annotation in practice: Example (2b) is an instance of a filler particle occurrence, and examples (2a), (2c) and (2d) are instances of slots where a filler particle could have potentially occurred but did not. Filler particles can also appear within words. However, those cases are rather infrequent (e.g. Defrancq & Plevoets 2018), which is why we decided to focus on the potential placement between words.

- (2) a. under (8.41 bits) \emptyset [0] the (3.04 bits) EUH Posted Workers Directive
 b. under the (3.04 bits) EUH [1] Posted (25.76 bits) Workers Directive
 c. under the EUH Posted (25.76 bits) \emptyset [0] Workers (11.06 bits) Directive
 d. under the EUH Posted Workers (11.06 bits) \emptyset [0] Directive (2.68 bits)

For Study 2, we were interested in the surprisal value of the next following content word. We considered adjectives, adverbs, nouns, proper nouns, verbs and numerals as content words and conjunctions, particles, determiners, prepositions, auxiliaries and pronouns as function words. For both actual and potential filler particle placements, we annotated the surprisal of the next following content word, which is seen in examples (3a–c). Cases where the directly following word was a content word, such as (3a) and (3c), were deleted for the analysis in Study 2.

- (3) a. \emptyset [0] statement ((4.71)) EUH in Vietnam
 b. statement **EUH [1]** in Vietnam ((14.90))
 c. statement EUH in \emptyset [0] Vietnam ((14.90))

3.3. Statistical analysis

To examine the relationship between lexical surprisal and the occurrence of filler particles, a mixed-effects logistic regression model was employed. Table 2 shows an overview of all variables in the models. The dependent variable was binary, indicating the presence or absence of a filler particle (1-present filler particle; 0-absent filler particle) at each annotated position. As described in Section 3.2., primary predictors were the surprisal values of the preceding and following words, with both variables included as fixed effects. Additionally, word frequency and word length were included as covariates to adjust for their possibly confounding influence on language processing. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values were calculated to assess multicollinearity among continuous predictors (cf. Table 2). All VIF values were below the commonly accepted threshold of 10 (Montgomery & Peck 1992), indicating that multicollinearity was not a concern and that the predictors could be reliably interpreted.

Since both original and interpreted speeches are included in the data and we wanted to investigate whether surprisal affects filler particle occurrence in interpreted language differently to original, monolingual speeches, we included the variable of mode. Mode indicates if the present or absent filler particle stems from the interpreted corpus or the original one. Mode is a categorical variable that has been sum-coded (1-interpreted speeches; -1-original speeches). Under this coding scheme, the main effects represent the average effect across both levels of the mode variable, effectively reflecting a midpoint between original and interpreted speeches.

Furthermore, we fitted interactions between mode and surprisal, frequency and length. The interactions indicate if there is a difference in how surprisal, frequency and length affect filler particle occurrence in interpreting and original speeches. Random intercepts were incorporated for speakers and interpreters to account for variability attributable to individual differences.

We fitted separate statistical models for the German and the English data. This decision was motivated by the fact that while surprisal and frequency values for both languages were derived from comparable corpora or language models, they were not identical. Corpus size and morphological differences between the languages affect the calculation of both surprisal and frequency. A single model for both languages would have treated these values as identical and calculated a single estimate. Fitting separate models prevents a direct comparison of estimates but avoids potential biases.

All continuous variables were z-scored and centered to make them comparable amongst each other (see Winter 2019: 86–89). To account for the skewed distribution typically associated with frequency data, all frequency values were log-transformed prior to analysis. As the regression model is a logistic one, all coefficients are expressed in terms of log-odds. All statistical analyses were conducted in R (R Core Team 2024) using the *car* (Fox & Weisberg 2019), *ggplot2* (Wickham 2016) and *lme4* packages (Bates et al. 2015).

Table 2: Summary of variables included in the regression models for English and German data, including their type, description, and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Variable type, description</i>	<i>VIF</i>	
		<i>English model</i>	<i>German model</i>
Filler particle	Response variable, binary (1-filler particle, 0-no filler particle)	N/A	N/A
Preceding surprisal	predictor, continuous gpt2 estimation	1.503851	1.241809
Following surprisal	predictor, continuous gpt2 estimation	3.342427	2.244370
Next content word surprisal	predictor, continuous gpt2 estimation	3.262839	2.208978
Preceding length	predictor, continuous character length	2.530324	3.154531
Following length	predictor, continuous character length	5.186765	5.866501
Next content word length	predictor, continuous character length	3.249556	3.963820
Preceding frequency	predictor, continuous SUBTLEX	3.089237	3.245423
Following frequency	predictor, continuous SUBTLEX	5.930943	5.488847
Next content word frequency	predictor, continuous SUBTLEX	3.887907	3.489127
Mode (ORG vs. SI)	predictor, categorical metadata in EPIC-UdS (1 – SI, -1 – ORG)	N/A	N/A
Speaker or interpreter ID	random effect, categorical metadata in EPIC-UdS	N/A	N/A

4. Study 1 – following and preceding surprisal

In this section, we focus on the key predictors of preceding and following surprisal as well as their interactions with mode (original vs. interpreted speech). Additional predictors were included in the models solely for adjustment purposes, to account for potential confounding effects.

4.1. Results

4.1.1. English model

Table 3 shows the results for the fixed effects of the logistic regression model for the English data and Figure 1 depicts the main effects of following and preceding surprisal on filler particle occurrence. Focussing first on the main effects in Table 3, we see that both preceding and following surprisal are significant. By adjusting for length and frequency in the model, the observed effect appears to originate genuinely from surprisal, free from the influence of potential confounding variables. The negative estimate for preceding surprisal suggests that as surprisal values increase, the likelihood of the next word being a filler particle decreases, which can be seen in Figure 1. This implies that words preceding filler particles tend to have lower surprisal values.

Focussing on following surprisal, its positive estimate indicates that the higher the surprisal of the following word, the more likely it is preceded by a filler particle, as shown by the rising slope in Figure 1. This implies that filler particles often occur before less predictable lexical items. Furthermore, following word surprisal has the highest estimate among the continuous predictors, highlighting its important role in the occurrence of filler particles.

Examining the interactions, the data reveals that there is no statistically significant difference between interpreting and originals for preceding surprisal, nor for following word surprisal. Both effects on filler particle usage remain consistent regardless of whether the speech is interpreted or original. The estimate for mode reveals that filler particles are more prevalent in interpreting compared to original speeches.

Table 3: Parameter estimates for the English data for the fixed effects. Significant effects are marked with an asterisk (*)

<i>Predictor</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Standard error</i>	<i>Z value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Intercept	-4.09711	0.12410	-33.016	<0.0001*
Preceding surprisal	-0.14375	0.02416	-5.950	<0.0001*
Following surprisal	0.50922	0.02247	22.658	<0.0001*
Preceding length	0.21973	0.02810	7.820	<0.0001*
Following length	0.12503	0.02826	4.424	<0.0001*
Preceding frequency	-0.10932	0.03224	-3.391	<0.0001*
Following frequency	0.21277	0.03447	6.173	<0.0001*
Mode (ORG vs. SI)	0.56474	0.12343	4.575	<0.0001*
Preceding surprisal x mode	0.01342	0.02416	0.555	0.57855
Following surprisal x mode	0.01653	0.02247	0.736	0.46190
Preceding length x mode	-0.04755	0.02810	-1.692	0.09062
Following length x mode	-0.0186	0.02826	-0.658	0.51037
Preceding frequency x mode	0.06542	0.03224	2.029	0.04245*
Following frequency x mode	-0.09876	0.03447	-2.865	0.00416*

Figure 1: Effect of preceding and following word surprisal on filler particle occurrence in English, surprisal values are z-scored

4.1.2. German model

Table 4 shows the results for the fixed effects for the logistic regression model for the German data, and Figure 2 depicts the effects of following and preceding surprisal and their interactions with mode. Focussing first on the main effects, we see that, in contrast to the results for the English data, preceding surprisal is not significant and has a positive estimate, which is not the direction we expected. The results for following surprisal are more similar to the English results in Section 4.1.1. It is significant and has the highest, positive estimate among the continuous predictors. This result indicates that higher surprisal values for following words strongly increase the probability of a filler particle occurring. The estimate for mode reveals that filler particles are substantially more prevalent in German interpreting compared to German original speeches. This big difference can be observed in the gap between the two intercepts at 0 in Figure 2.

Examining the interactions, the German data differs from the English results. The interaction between preceding surprisal and mode is significant, indicating that the relationship between preceding surprisal and filler particle occurrence varies slightly between interpreted and original speeches. However, the main effect of preceding surprisal is not significant in the first place. Furthermore, since the main effect of preceding surprisal is very low, taking the interaction into account, the interaction term, preceding surprisal has a positive estimate for interpreting ($0.00011 + 0.05362 = 0.05373$) and a negative estimate for originals ($0.00011 - 0.05362 = -0.05351$). Figure 2 shows that the lines for preceding word surprisal are nearly straight, indicating that any effect, regardless of its direction, is minimal. The interaction between following surprisal and mode in the German data is also significant. It has a negative estimate, indicating that the effect of following surprisal is more pronounced in German original speeches compared to interpreted ones. This can be observed in the steeper slope for originals (red line) compared to interpreting (blue line) in Figure 2, even though the overall probability of filler particle occurrence is still higher in interpreting.

Table 4: Parameter estimates for the German data for the fixed effects. Significant effects are marked with an asterisk (*)

<i>Predictor</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Standard error</i>	<i>Z value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Intercept	-4.17154	0.12543	-33.257	<0.0001*
Preceding surprisal	0.00011	0.02585	0.004	0.99648
Following surprisal	0.41818	0.02183	19.154	<0.0001*
Preceding length	0.09575	0.03714	2.578	0.00993*
Following length	-0.02101	0.03945	-0.533	0.59431
Preceding frequency	-0.09245	0.04003	-2.309	0.02092*
Following frequency	0.18933	0.04277	4.427	<0.0001*
Mode (ORG vs. SI)	1.10942	0.12488	8.884	<0.0001*
Preceding surprisal x mode	0.05362	0.02585	2.074	0.03808*
Following surprisal x mode	-0.08705	0.02183	-3.987	<0.0001*
Preceding length x mode	-0.02183	0.03714	-0.588	0.55662
Following length x mode	-0.04493	0.03945	-1.139	0.25472
Preceding frequency x mode	0.07754	0.04003	1.937	0.05273
Following frequency x mode	-0.14936	0.04277	-3.492	0.00048*

Figure 2: Effect of preceding and following word surprisal on filler particle occurrence in German, grouped by mode (original vs. interpreting), surprisal values are z-scored

4.2. Discussion

Overall, the findings confirm that the (un)predictability of the surrounding words (as captured with surprisal) influences filler particle production in both German and English interpreting, extending findings from previous research on monolingual English to bilingual speech production in interpreting. More specifically, this result is more pronounced for following surprisal than for preceding surprisal. Preceding surprisal is significant for the English data,

replicating Dammalapati et al.'s (2019, 2021) findings. They interpreted the lowering in surprisal before disfluencies as a strategy of the speaker to free up resources for upcoming speech planning difficulties. However, we do not see this effect in the German data. This could hint at cross-linguistic differences and should be investigated in more languages.

Following word surprisal consistently demonstrates the strongest effect across both languages, with the highest estimates among all predictors, underscoring its significant role in filler particle occurrence. This suggests that high surprisal words are at a planning disadvantage compared to low surprisal words, as their low predictability from the preceding context results in less pre-activation and more planning difficulty, as indicated by filler particle occurrence. Huettig et al. (2022) describe pre-activation through predictability in speech planning as a form of pattern completion: Uttering the beginning of a sentence or phrase activates possible continuations. The more constraining the context (lower surprisal), the greater the activation of lexical items and the easier lexical access. Conversely, the less constraining the context (higher surprisal), the lesser the activation of lexical items and the more taxing lexical access, as reflected in the higher probability of filler particle occurrence.

Taken together with findings from Hodzik & Williams (2017), Amos et al. (2022) and Liu et al. (2022), our findings suggest that prediction in simultaneous interpreting takes place in both comprehension and speech planning, leading to activations in both source and target language. This could mean activation of more entries in both languages and therefore weaker activation of these entries (Amos & Pickering 2020), which could explain why surprisal has a weaker effect on filler particle occurrence for interpreters compared to original speakers in our German results. However, since this difference was not found for English, the effect of surprisal and prediction in simultaneous interpreting may be language or language pair-specific and therefore should be investigated in more languages.

Table 5: List of most frequent words following filler particles, grouped by mode and language

<i>Original English</i>	<i>Frequency per 1,000 tokens</i>	<i>English Interpreting</i>	<i>Frequency per 1,000 tokens</i>	<i>Original German</i>	<i>Frequency per 1,000 tokens</i>	<i>German Interpreting</i>	<i>Frequency per 1,000 tokens</i>
the	46.39	the	35.04	die	22.74	die	24.50
and	25.73	to	21.01	der	19.75	und	20.94
to	25.68	and	20.05	und	19.23	der	15.34
of	23.62	of	16.92	in	14.99	in	13.01
that	18.05	that	13.61	dem	9.55	das	12.49

Since the surprisal of the following word seemed to have a considerable effect on filler particle production in both German and English, we decided to take a closer look at the following context of filler particles. Table 5 shows that the most frequent words following filler particles are articles, prepositions and conjunctions. This is in itself not surprising since filler particles are known to appear at phrase boundaries (e.g. Goldman-Eisler 1968; Schneider 2014). However, literature suggests differences in retrieval of function and content words (Bell et al. 2009; Boye & Harder 2012; Lange et al. 2017; Seifart et al. 2018) and surprisal of function words tends to be lower than surprisal of content words. Since the retrieval of function words is probably not the problem but rather the retrieval of the next upcoming content word, (see

Example 3), we conducted a second study where we compared the surprisal of the next upcoming content word as a predictor of filler particles to the surprisal of the directly following function word.

5. Study 2 – following and preceding surprisal

In Section 5.1., the analysis focuses on the comparison between surprisal of the next content word and surprisal of the directly following function word as predictors for filler particle occurrence. To do this, we create a model that only contains words and filler particles that are followed by function words (conjunctions, particles, determiners, prepositions, auxiliaries and pronouns) and compare the coefficients of the directly following function word and the next content word. As explained in Section 3.2., occurrences of filler particles and potential placements directly followed by a content word were excluded. Furthermore, we conduct model comparisons, comparing the full model with both surprisal measures, once to a model without directly following function word surprisal and once to a model without next content word surprisal. Additional control variables (preceding surprisal, length, frequency) are shown in the results table for the sake of completeness but will not be addressed specifically.

5.1. Results

5.1.1. English model

Table 6 shows the results for the fixed effects of the full model with both following word surprisal predictors along with control variables for the English data, and Figure 3 depicts the effects of both following word surprisal predictors and their interactions with mode. Different to what we expected, both directly following word surprisal and next content word surprisal significantly influence the likelihood of filler particle occurrence. Focussing on the estimates, we see that the surprisal of the directly following word has a stronger positive effect on filler particle occurrence than the surprisal of the next following content word. This can be seen in the steeper slope for directly following word surprisal in Figure 3. Shrout & Yip-Bannicq (2017) highlight that traditional regression model outputs do not indicate whether two coefficients differ significantly from one another, underscoring the importance of conducting specific tests (see also Gelman & Stern 2006). We tested the difference between the two coefficients using the `linearHypothesis()` function of the `car` package in R (Fox & Weisberg 2019). This revealed a significant difference between the two following surprisal estimates ($p < 0.0001$). The direction of the difference runs counter our expectations since we expected the surprisal of the next content word to be a more meaningful predictor of filler particles than the surprisal of the directly following word, but it is the other way around.

Next, we discuss the model comparisons. As we expected, a likelihood ratio test of the model including both surprisal measures against a model without next content word surprisal reveals a significant difference between the models ($\chi^2(1) = 17.922$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that next content word surprisal adds relevant information to the model. However, against our expectations, a likelihood ratio test of the model including both surprisal measures against the model without directly following word surprisal also reveals a significant difference between the models ($\chi^2(1) = 147.17$, $p < 0.0001$). This indicates that both surprisal measures of the following context of filler particles contribute uniquely to the model and have separate effects. Notably, this outcome contradicts our initial expectation, as we assumed that both measures

reflect the same underlying phenomenon but that content word surprisal would emerge as the superior measure.

To explain these results, we take a closer look at the distributions of the surprisal values of the directly following words per word class (cf. Figure 4). Comparing content and function words, it is apparent that content words have higher surprisal values in general. Among content words, those following filler particles display notably higher surprisal values compared to those that do not follow filler particles. This aligns with our expectations. However, a similar trend emerges for function words: both the box and median surprisal values are higher for function words following filler particles than for those not following them. This could explain the regression results as it seems like that, regardless of word class, words following filler particles have higher surprisal.

Table 6 also shows that neither the interaction between mode and directly following function word surprisal nor the interaction between mode and next content word surprisal is significant. This indicates there is no difference in the effect in interpreting compared to original speeches

Table 6: Parameter estimates for the English data for the fixed effects; significant effects are marked with an asterisk (*)

<i>Predictor</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Standard error</i>	<i>Z value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Intercept	-4.39793	0.13302	-3.795	<0.0001*
Preceding surprisal	-0.16780	0.04422	13.297	0.00015*
Directly following word surprisal	0.45792	0.03444	4.349	<0.0001*
Next content word surprisal	0.19421	0.04466	5.221	<0.0001*
Preceding length	0.28867	0.05529	4.266	<0.0001*
Directly following length	0.19944	0.04675	1.174	<0.0001*
Next content word length	0.05178	0.04411	0.231	0.24039
Preceding frequency	0.01217	0.05266	-1.753	0.07961
Directly following frequency	-0.11049	0.06303	5.805	<0.0001*
Next content word frequency	0.31231	0.05380	3.364	0.81726
Mode (ORG vs. SI)	0.43638	0.12973	-1.624	<0.0001*
Preceding surprisal x mode	-0.07182	0.04421	0.603	0.1043
Directly following surprisal x mode	0.02075	0.03444	0.478	0.5467
Next content word surprisal x mode	0.02134	0.04466	-1.845	0.63278
Preceding length x mode	-0.10201	0.05529	0.605	0.06504
Directly following length x mode	0.02829	0.04675	1.076	0.54507
Next content word length x mode	0.04747	0.04411	-0.767	0.28184
Preceding frequency x mode	-0.04837	0.06303	-0.007	0.44284
Directly following frequency x mode	-0.00038	0.05380	0.552	0.99438
Next content word frequency x mode	0.02907	0.05265	-3.795	0.58093

Figure 3: Effect of directly following word and next content word surprisal on filler particle occurrence in English, surprisal values are z-scored

Figure 4: Distribution of surprisal (in bits) of words directly following filler particles or following other words that are not filler particles, grouped by word class (English)

5.1.2. German model

Table 7 and Figure 5 show the results for the main effects for Study 2 on the German data. Again, the model defies our expectations as both surprisal of the directly following word and of the next content word exhibit a significant effect on filler particle occurrence. The effect of directly following word surprisal is again greater compared to next content word surprisal, which can be observed in Figure 5. This time, however, the difference between the two estimates is not significant ($p = 0.2393$), indicating that none of the predictors has a stronger effect on filler particle occurrence compared to the other. There is no significant interaction with mode for neither of the two surprisal measures.

We conducted likelihood ratio tests to compare the model including both surprisal measures with models excluding either next content word surprisal or directly following word surprisal. Consistent with the results for the English data but contrary to our expectations, both comparisons were significant: excluding next content word surprisal ($\chi^2(1) = 22.769$, $p < 0.0001$), and excluding directly following surprisal ($\chi^2(1) = 51.536$, $p < 0.0001$), each revealed significant differences between the models. These findings suggest that each surprisal measure contributes uniquely to the model.

The boxplots in Figure 6 show a similar picture as the boxplots of the English data. Content words have higher surprisal values overall compared to function words. Content words following filler particles have higher surprisal values than content words following other words in the corpus. The same is true for function words, which tend to have higher surprisal values when they appear after filler particles compared to their occurrence after other words. This could explain the significant effect of directly following word surprisal, which only includes surprisal measures of function words.

Table 7: Parameter estimates for the German data for the fixed effects, significant effects are marked with an asterisk (*)

<i>Predictor</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Standard error</i>	<i>Z value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Intercept	-4.16932	0.14563	-28.630	<0.0001*
Preceding surprisal	-0.07822	0.04856	-1.611	0.10723
Directly following word surprisal	0.29565	0.03723	7.942	<0.0001*
Next content word surprisal	0.22495	0.04517	4.981	<0.0001*
Preceding length	0.12163	0.07315	1.663	0.09636
Directly following length	-0.17464	0.06169	-2.831	0.00464
Next content word length	-0.07827	0.05514	-1.420	0.15573
Preceding frequency	-0.01724	0.05925	-0.291	0.80350
Directly following frequency	-0.00095	0.07671	-0.012	0.99013
Next content word frequency	0.13708	0.06295	2.178	0.02943
Mode (ORG vs. SI)	1.1248	0.14258	7.889	<0.0001*
Preceding surprisal x mode	0.08347	0.04856	1.719	0.04187*
Directly following surprisal x mode	-0.01444	0.03723	-0.388	0.0856
Next content word surprisal x mode	-0.02329	0.04517	-0.516	0.69818
Preceding length x mode	-0.06659	0.07315	-0.910	0.60605
Directly following length x mode	-0.01548	0.06169	-0.251	0.36264
Next content word length x mode	0.09623	0.05514	1.745	0.80185
Preceding frequency x mode	-0.09118	0.07671	-1.189	0.08095
Directly following frequency x mode	-0.05503	0.06295	-0.874	0.23458
Next content word frequency x mode	-0.00982	0.05925	-0.166	0.38199

Figure 5: Effect of directly following and next content word surprisal on filler particle occurrence in German, surprisal values are z-scored

Figure 6: Distribution of surprisal (in bits) of words directly following filler particles or other words that are not filler particles, grouped by word class (German)

5.2. Discussion

Contrary to our initial expectations, next content word surprisal did not arise as the superior measure over directly following function word surprisal. In cases where a filler particle occurs before a function word, both the surprisal of the directly following function word and the surprisal of the next content word contribute independently to the occurrence of filler particles. This implies that they might capture distinct aspects of linguistic processing. High surprisal of content words could indicate low lexical activation of the content words themselves in specific contexts, leading to retrieval difficulty and filler particle occurrence. In contrast, high surprisal of function words could reflect speech planning difficulties at a structural level.

Slaats & Martin (2025) argue that while surprisal does not encode syntactic structure, surprisal values are affected by syntactic structure and contain some structural information. For example, a high surprisal preposition may indicate that a prepositional phrase is unexpected in the given context, possibly causing planning difficulty or lesser activation on the structural level. In contexts like example (1), the surprisal of *the* then indicates the unexpectedness of the noun phrase and the surprisal of *spending procedure* indicates the unexpectedness of the lexical item itself. This fits with Huettig et al.'s (2022) parallel architecture pre-activation theory, as they assume an extended lexicon where syntactic structures are stored alongside words and are also pre-activated and accessed in the same way.

Some models of speech production assume that content and function words are accessed at different stages in the production process. According to Boye & Harder (2012), function words are planned later than content words because they typically depend on a lexical head (e.g. a determiner on a noun). The retrieval and encoding of function words rely on the partial processing of their associated lexical head, necessitating a later planning stage for function words compared to content words. This dependency could explain why both the directly following function word surprisal and the next content word surprisal are significant predictors of filler particle occurrence.

Our results suggest that the influence of surprisal in the following context remains consistent between simultaneous interpreting and original speeches, as we find no significant interaction between mode and either of the following surprisal measures. This stands in contrast to the significant interaction between mode and following surprisal in German in Study 1 (see Section 4.1.1.), where following surprisal had a weaker effect in interpreting than in original speeches. Notably, in Study 1, the directly following surprisal measure included both content and function words, whereas in Study 2, it is limited to function words. This suggests that in German, structural access, indicated by surprisal of directly following function words, is less affected by the constraints of interpreting compared to content word access, indicated by surprisal of directly following content words.

6. Summary and conclusion

In this article, we have investigated the linguistic-contextual conditions of filler particle occurrence in simultaneous interpreting in the language pair English-German (both translation directions) using data from European Parliament interactions. Specifically, we posed the question whether, and if so to what extent, filler particle occurrence can be explained with surprisal, i.e. the (un)expectedness of linguistic units in a given context (here: in the target output). Using logistic regression, we conducted two studies that investigated the surprisal values surrounding filler particles in original and interpreted speeches. We were able to show

that a higher surprisal of upcoming words increases the probability of a filler particle to occur in interpreting. We saw this as an indication for prediction and pre-activation in the target language and suggested that filler particles indicate retrieval difficulty of upcoming words. Contrary to our initial assumption, we found a surprisal effect both for lexical and function words. This suggests that the occurrence of filler particles may be associated with difficulties in lexical retrieval as well as structural planning of the target language output.

Our future work will therefore involve investigating which structural aspects are likely to play a role in fluent interpreting. For instance, Jiang & Jiang (2020) show that disfluencies may arise due to long dependency distances in the source language input (possibly creating similar processing problems as garden-path sentences, where a unit in processing cannot be concluded because of multiple embedding). Strategies to cope with such situations result in syntactic simplification (see, e.g., Xu & Liu 2023), which, in turn, has been shown to be indexed by surprisal or entropy (Martínez & Teich 2017; Teich et al. 2020; Lapshinova-Koltunski et al. 2022). Here, again focusing on the target language output, we consider taking into account difficulties potentially associated with the surprisal of the syntactic or semantic head of the following construction as well as the complexity of the whole construction.

Finally, we may use surprisal to explain other kinds of phenomena associated with high effort in interpreting. For instance, translation latency, which signals that there is on-going processing of the source language input (see e.g. Chmiel 2021), may well be assumed to be linked to the predictability of upcoming material in the source language input, lower surprisal leading to shorter translation latency and vice versa. Here, it would also be interesting to see how the effects of surprisal and relative frequency interact.

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Cognitive load in translating ideological texts: An eye-tracking study of translators' pupil diameter

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Abstract

This study investigates the potential effect of translators' ideology and cognitive abilities on their cognitive load during the translation process. An eye-tracking experiment was conducted to examine how translators' cognitive load – measured by average pupil diameter – varied based on their ideological positioning, as reflected in their national identity, when instructed to translate texts according to the standards of the Islamic Republic of Iran Broadcasting (IRIB). Eight participants were selected to complete ten translation tasks involving ideologically loaded texts. The experiment took place in the Cognitive Laboratory at the University of Tehran, Iran. Cognitive load was assessed through pupil diameter measurements. Following the translation tasks, participants completed a national identity questionnaire as an indicator of ideological alignment, as well as a cognitive ability test. The findings indicate that both ideology and cognitive ability significantly influenced average pupil diameter, suggesting that translators experienced higher cognitive load when their ideological stance aligned with the translation brief and when they possessed higher cognitive capacity.

Keywords: National identity; Ideology; Eye-tracking; Cognitive load; Pupil diameter

1. Introduction

The notion of ideology is often associated with a set of beliefs, assumptions, and values, which has rendered it a highly debated and contentious topic (Rojo López & Ramos Caro 2014). The role of ideology in shaping the translation process has been extensively discussed in academic discourse (Brook 2012). Ideology in translation manifests not only in the translated text itself but also in the translator's voice, perspective, and the broader significance of the text for the target audience. Consequently, translation decisions are influenced by translators' cultural affiliations and ideological positions, which may not always align with dominant power structures (Tymoczko 2003).

Group ideologies emerge within specific societal contexts, reflecting the underlying structure of a given society. The ideological identity of a group serves to classify its members, defining inclusion and exclusion criteria as well as the behaviors expected for membership (Van Dijk 1995). In this sense, national identity can be understood as an ideological construct.

Munday (2008) argues that translation and interpreting are not only communicative and textual activities, but also cognitive processes undertaken by translators and interpreters. Cognitivism emphasizes the role of complex mental processes in shaping human behavior, making cognitive mechanisms a key area of study in translation research (Anderson 1995). Ideologies play a crucial role in social cognition, positioned at the intersection of individual and societal domains. They influence cognitive processes among group members, affecting discourse planning and comprehension (Van Dijk 1995).

In a 2014 study, Rojo López and Ramos Caro examined the impact of translators' ideological stances on their translation processes, particularly in terms of the time required to find suitable translations for ideologically charged terms. Their findings indicated that when translators encountered words or expressions that conflicted with their personal ideologies, decision-making was impeded, resulting in longer search times for appropriate translations. Rojo (2015) further highlights that translation scholars have sought to understand how translators process entire texts during translation. To explore this, researchers have turned to psycholinguistic methodologies, employing tools such as eye-tracking technology. By analyzing translators' eye movements, researchers can gain valuable insights into cognitive load and decision-making processes. Cognitive load—also referred to as cognitive effort—denotes the extent of cognitive resources allocated to completing translation tasks (Vieira 2016).

To investigate cognitive effort in translation more precisely, scholars have increasingly adopted eye-tracking technology—a method that allows researchers to observe real-time reading and decision-making behaviors. Eye-tracking provides access to various cognitive indicators such as gaze duration, fixations, saccades, and pupil dilation, all of which contribute to a nuanced understanding of the translator's mental workload (Hvelplund 2011). Krings (2001) used eye-tracking to explore problem-solving strategies in translation, providing a deeper understanding of how translators approach complex tasks. Vieira (2016) examined the cognitive effort required in post-editing machine translation outputs. The study revealed that post-editing demands significant cognitive resources, as evidenced by increased fixations and longer gaze durations, and it also highlighted the problem-solving strategies involved in comparing and correcting machine translations. Arabbeigi (2021) combined EEG and eye-tracking technologies to examine the cognitive processes of professional and non-professional translators. The findings suggested that professional translators, due to their greater experience and familiarity with translation tools, manage cognitive load more effectively, divide attention more efficiently, and address translation challenges with greater proficiency.

In the domain of audiovisual translation, Zahedi and Khoshsaligheh have conducted a number of empirical studies using eye-tracking to explore how viewers process subtitles. In a 2022 study, they challenged earlier findings suggesting that two-line subtitles inherently attract more attention than one-line subtitles. They argued that prior conclusions might have been confounded by differences in subtitle length rather than line number. Using an SMI eye-tracker to monitor the eye movements of 32 Iranian viewers while watching a subtitled scene from *A Prophet* (2009), they found that, when length was controlled, viewers paid significantly more attention to one-line subtitles. Furthermore, longer subtitles attracted more attention than shorter ones, regardless of line number. Retrospective interviews indicated that participants generally preferred shorter and two-line subtitles.

In their 2019 study, Zahedi and Khoshsaligheh examined attention allocation to lexical and functional words in subtitles. The eye-tracking data showed that content words received significantly more attention than function words, as reflected in higher fixation durations, greater fixation counts, and longer first fixations. Conversely, function words were skipped more frequently, suggesting a differential pattern of cognitive processing based on word type. Their 2025 study turned to the subtitling strategy of inserting humor even when the source dialogue is not humorous. They used eye-tracking to assess viewers' attention allocation while watching a humorous and a non-humorous version of the same scene from *Superchondriac* (2014). The results revealed that humorous subtitles elicited significantly

greater viewer attention than their non-humorous counterparts. Interviews showed that some viewers appreciated the added humor, which they found culturally resonant and entertaining, while others found it distracting, confusing, or ideologically misaligned. In a 2020 study, the same authors used eye-tracking to investigate whether Persian subtitles written with full or half space between words affected viewers' reading behavior. 32 participants watched two French films, each with two versions of subtitled segments: one using half spaces and the other using full spaces. Although the statistical difference was not significant, words written with full space attracted more attention. Heatmap analysis suggested that the visual split introduced by the full space led viewers to perceive the components as separate elements, disrupting holistic word recognition.

On the other hand, many studies have explored ideology and national identity in translation. For instance, Mousavi Razavi & Allahdaneh (2018) investigated translation strategies for cultural elements in Iranian "resistance" literature and found that retention was the most commonly used strategy. Moreover, studies by Ahmadi & Parham (2022), Parham (2019), and Farahzad & Ehteshami (2011) have addressed issues of identity and national identity in translation, examining both verbal and non-verbal elements as reflected in texts and paratexts. These studies explore how cultural, social, and political factors influence the representation of identity in translation, focusing on the interplay between language, culture, and the translator's role in shaping national and personal identities. Through their analysis of various textual forms and accompanying paratexts, they demonstrate how translation practices can either reinforce or challenge dominant cultural narratives and ideologies.

To date, however, no research in Iran has examined the ideology or national identity of translators using a cognitive approach. The present study addresses this gap by employing eye-tracking technology to investigate the impact of translators' ideology and national identity on the cognitive load they experience during translation. Specifically, by analyzing changes in pupil diameter, the study aims to show how ideology, as expressed through national identity, influences the cognitive effort involved in translating ideologically charged texts.

2. Method

2.1. Aim and hypothesis

The current study examines the effect of translators' ideologies, which is reflected in their national identity score, on their cognitive load when translating ideologically loaded texts in line with the Islamic Republic of Iran Broadcasting (IRIB) standards. The IRIB standards constitute a set of regulatory guidelines designed to ensure that media content, including translations, aligns with the country's Islamic values, political ideologies, and national identity. These guidelines prioritize the representation of religious principles and the reinforcement of state-approved cultural and political narratives. As a result, content that conflicts with these ideological frameworks is subject to modification or censorship. IRIB standards thus play a significant role in shaping translation practices, mandating that translated materials conform to these cultural and ideological norms. In the present study, all participants were educated Iranian citizens who were already well-acquainted with the IRIB standards. Therefore, simply informing them that the translations should adhere to these standards was sufficient to ensure their understanding of the expectations and requirements.

This study utilizes the methodology proposed by Rojo López & Ramos Caro (2014), modifying the design and variables to align with the objectives of the current research. Rojo & Ramos (2014) established that a translator's ideology significantly affects their translation speed and accuracy. Words that oppose a translator's ideological views may slow the translation process and cause delays, while words that align with their views can expedite the process.

Drawing on the work of Rojo López & Ramos Caro (2014), it was hypothesized that translators with higher national identity scores would demonstrate lower cognitive load, as indicated by smaller pupil diameters, when translating texts in alignment with the IRIB standards. This hypothesis is supported by previous findings indicating that pupil dilation serves as a reliable index of cognitive processing load, with larger pupil diameters associated with greater cognitive demands such as memory retrieval, language comprehension, and attentional control (Mihelčič & Podlesek 2023). Furthermore, since the cognitive load experienced during task performance is influenced by an individual's cognitive abilities, a second hypothesis posited that translators with higher cognitive ability would experience lower cognitive load. This assumption aligns with research in cognitive load theory, which suggests that individuals with greater cognitive capacity or expertise can manage cognitive demands more efficiently (Sweller et al. 2011).

2.2. Participants

The study involved eight native Persian speakers, all of whom were students of English translation at Allameh Tabataba'i University in Iran. The sample included one female PhD candidate, three female Bachelor's degree graduates, and four male Master's students, with ages ranging from 23 to 46.

The number of participants was limited due to the high costs and technical demands associated with cognitive studies, particularly those involving eye-tracking technology. Additionally, recruiting a more homogeneous group was not feasible, as participation in such studies typically attracts only a limited number of volunteers. Although the sample is somewhat heterogeneous in terms of academic level and age, given the exploratory nature of the study, this variation can contribute to a broader understanding of the phenomena under investigation.

Before participating in the study, all individuals provided informed consent, acknowledging that their participation was voluntary. They were assured of the anonymity of their data and informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the eye-tracking data, participants' visual acuity was evaluated to confirm normal or corrected-to-normal vision, thereby minimizing potential biases associated with visual impairments.

2.3. Instruments

This study utilized a combination of tools to collect data, including an eye-tracker, translation tasks, and two questionnaires. Each instrument is described in detail below.

2.3.1. Eye-tracker

The eye-tracking device used was the Tobii TX300, a screen-mounted system with a sampling frequency of 300Hz, a reported accuracy rate of 4%, and a precision rate of 3%. The system was positioned at the bottom of a computer monitor and featured four purple indicator lights

for participant identification. Data collected by the device was accessible in both MS Excel and MP4 video formats.

2.3.2. Translation tasks

Ten translation tasks were developed for this study, each consisting of two English text segments sourced from the Fox News Media website. These texts were carefully selected for their inclusion of ideologically loaded terms and expressions, which were subsequently categorized according to the subcomponents of the national identity questionnaire: cultural, linguistic, social, political, territorial, and religious. Figure 1 illustrates how ideological terms and expressions were marked based on the cultural component of the national identity questionnaire.

Figure 1: Sample task – researcher version

In each of the ten tasks, the initial segment provided the contextual background, referred to as the *introduction* (see Figure 2), while the subsequent segment was designated for translation into Persian by the participants, termed *translation* (see Figure 3). The cumulative word count for these translation segments across all ten tasks was 355 words. The creation of these tasks involved the use of Tobii Pro Lab 181.1 Software, which was employed to encode ideological terms and expressions, with this information kept confidential from the participants. This encoding allowed for later identification and analysis of these terms using data from the eye-tracker.

Figure 2: Sample task, introduction part – participant version

Task 4

Translation

A U.S. airstrike killed Soleimani as he left Baghdad's international airport on Jan. 3, 2020. Former Vice President Mike Pence said at the time that Soleimani was "directly responsible for the death of 603 U.S. service members."

سردار حاج قاسم سلیمانی در ۳ ژانویه ۲۰۲۰ در فرودگاه بین‌المللی بغداد به قتل رسید.
 زاتویه به مقام رفیع رسید.

Submit your translation and go the next task

Google

Figure 3: Sample task, translation part – participant version

2.3.3. National Identity Questionnaire

To assess the participants' ideological positioning, the study employed the National Identity Questionnaire developed by Rastegar & Rabani (2013) in the field of sociology. Although not originally designed for translation studies, this instrument was selected for its relevance to the study's focus on national identity as a form of ideological representation. Drawing on Van Dijk's (1998) conceptualization of ideology as the foundation of social identity and group interests, national identity in this study is understood as a construct that reflects both individual and collective dimensions of belonging. Specifically, it is defined as a unique part of our identity that allows us to recognize our cultural and political self within a specific territory. It has both an individual or mental aspect and a collective one. National identity is a shared feeling among people who naturally belong together and have common interests, history, and destiny (Rastegar & Rabani 2013).

The questionnaire includes 25 items across six thematic domains: Cultural (items 1–8), Linguistic (items 9–12), Social (items 13–16), Political (items 17–19), Territorial (items 20–22), and Religious (items 23–25). These domains collectively capture various aspects of national identity, providing a comprehensive measure of the participants' ideological orientation. While the questions are designed to address key dimensions of national identity, they are carefully worded to avoid sensitive topics that could cause discomfort or anxiety. By steering clear of controversial or overtly political and religious issues, the questionnaire ensures that participants feel safe and comfortable providing honest answers. The responses were quantified using a Likert scale to gauge the extent of agreement or identification with each item.

The questionnaire was administered after the completion of the translation tasks, following a ten-minute rest period in the laboratory. Participants were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses to further reduce response bias and promote candid participation.

2.3.4. Cognitive Abilities Questionnaire

In addition to the National Identity Questionnaire, the study utilized the Cognitive Abilities Questionnaire, developed by Nejati (2013) in the field of cognitive psychology. This instrument is designed to measure participants' cognitive abilities across seven key components: Memory (items 1-6), Inhibitory Control and Selective Attention (items 7–12), Decision-making (items 13–17), Planning (items 18–20), Sustained Attention (items 21–23), Social Cognition (items 24–26), and Cognitive Flexibility (items 27–30). The questionnaire

consists of 30 items in total, each assessing a distinct aspect of executive functioning. Participants' cognitive abilities were quantified based on their responses to these items, providing a comprehensive measure of their cognitive performance.

The Cognitive Abilities Questionnaire employs a five-point Likert scale, where participants rate each statement from 1 (almost never) to 5 (almost always), with reverse scoring applied to items 24, 25, and 26. This scoring system allows for an in-depth assessment of cognitive functions related to memory, attention, decision-making, and flexibility. The questionnaire was administered to participants after completing the translation tasks, following a ten-minute rest period in the laboratory to ensure that their cognitive performance was not influenced by fatigue. Responses to this questionnaire were kept confidential, with participants assured that their answers could not be traced back to them personally.

2.4. The pilot study

The pilot study involved one participant and initially included 18 tasks, encompassing a total of 730 words for translation. The pilot was conducted in the laboratory setting under the supervision of two neuroscience specialists. The findings from the pilot indicated that the study design required modifications. Specifically, the duration of the experiment was excessively long, with the participant needing approximately two hours to complete all 18 tasks. Additionally, the keyboard failed to correctly display the Persian alphabet labels. As a result, the number of tasks was reduced to ten, and the keyboard was replaced to improve accuracy and minimize participant fatigue.

2.5. Data collection

The study was conducted in the Cognitive Laboratory at the Faculty of Psychology and Education, University of Tehran, Tehran, Iran. Participants arrived at the laboratory as scheduled, ensuring a smooth and timely process. The eye-tracking laboratory was specifically designed to provide a quiet, controlled environment with standardized lighting, essential for minimizing distractions and ensuring the accuracy of the data. The laboratory was equipped with two critical systems: an eye-tracker and a computer running the necessary software for data collection.

To ensure optimal data quality, the participants were instructed before the experiment to refrain from using any eye or eyebrow makeup on the day of the experiment, as such products could interfere with the eye-tracker's ability to capture accurate data. Additionally, participants were informed that long eyelashes could obstruct the eye-tracker's functionality, emphasizing the importance of these precautions.

Upon arrival at the laboratory, participants were given a tour of the eye-tracking setup. They were shown two computers: One was dedicated to the eye-tracker system, which participants would use during the experiment, and the other was reserved for researchers to operate the eye-tracking software and monitor data collection in real time. After the tour, participants were provided with a set of five key instructions for the experiment. They were instructed to complete the translation tasks in accordance with the IRIB standards and to align their work with the national belief system. Participants were also informed that there was no time limit for completing the tasks, allowing them to work at their own pace. The internet was made available for research purposes, and participants were encouraged to notify the researchers of any technical difficulties they encountered. They were also asked to leave

personal electronic devices, including mobile phones and smartwatches, outside the laboratory to minimize distractions and ensure the integrity of the experiment.

Once the instructions were given, laboratory specialists began the process of calibrating the eye-tracking equipment through some tasks. These tasks included maintaining a fixed horizontal gaze, blinking, and tracking the moving circle. While participants performed these tasks, laboratory specialists adjusted and verified the calibration of the equipment.

After calibration, participants proceeded with the translation tasks, which were completed using the eye-tracking system. The system automatically stopped once the translation tasks were finished. After completing the tasks, participants were given a fifteen-minute break and were then asked to fill out the two questionnaires. At this point, participants were unaware of the study's specific objectives and were only instructed to complete the translation tasks and the questionnaires. They were reassured that their responses to the questionnaires would be kept confidential, ensuring they could answer honestly without concern for any repercussions.

Alongside the eye-tracking system, an electroencephalography (EEG) device was also used to collect data on participants' brain activity during the translation tasks. Although both eye-tracking and EEG data were gathered simultaneously, the present study focuses solely on the analysis of the eye-tracking results. Figure 4 illustrates a participant engaged in the experimental setup, seated at the eye-tracking station while wearing the EEG cap, offering a visual representation of the data collection environment in the laboratory.

Figure 4: A participant in the laboratory

3. Results and discussion

As delineated in the preceding sections, the participants' ideological positioning was evaluated using the National Identity Questionnaire. This instrument implemented a five-point Likert scale to measure responses. The scoring rubric was as follows: responses of *strongly agree* were assigned a score of 1; *agree* was assigned a score of 2; *neutral* received a score of 3; *disagree* was given a score of 4; and *strongly disagree* was assigned a score of 5. An example statement from the questionnaire is "I feel connected to Iran's history".

Table 1 presents the national identity scores of participants across six components: Cultural, Linguistic Social, Political, Territorial, and Religious. Each row corresponds to an individual participant, with each column indicating their score in one of these components. For example, Participant 3 scored 18 in the Cultural component, 4 in Linguistic, 13 in Social, 15 in Political, 14 in Territorial, and 15 in Religious, yielding a total score of 79. These scores offer insight into how participants relate to different components of national identity.

Table 1: Participants' National Identity Scores

Row Labels	Cultural	Linguistic	Social	Political	Territorial	Religious	Total	National Identity Level
Participant 1	17	5	17	10	6	11	66	High
Participant 2	22	7	18	13	12	10	82	Low
Participant 3	18	4	13	15	14	15	79	Low
Participant 4	19	6	10	8	7	6	56	High
Participant 5	19	7	13	14	11	12	76	Low
Participant 6	15	7	15	9	7	8	61	High
Participant 7	13	6	12	7	4	4	46	High
Participant 8	19	4	19	13	13	12	80	Low

Subsequently, the median was calculated for each component of the questionnaire as well as for the overall national identity score across all participants. The median total score was 71, with individual scores ranging from 46 to 82. Each participant's total score was then compared to this median. Scores above 71 were categorized as representing a lower level of national identity, while those below 71 were considered to indicate a higher level of national identity. In other words, a score below the median was interpreted as indicative of a high level of national identity, reflecting a strong congruence with the country's national values. Conversely, a score above the median was regarded as indicative of a low level of national identity, suggesting a deviation from the prevailing national beliefs. For instance, Participant 2, who scored 82 on the National Identity Questionnaire, exceeded the median score of 71, thereby reflecting an ideological stance that diverges from the country's national values. In contrast, Participant 6, with a score of 61, exhibited a high level of alignment with national beliefs.

Table 2 presents the cognitive abilities scores of participants across seven components of executive functioning. Each row corresponds to a single participant, while each column reflects scores for specific cognitive components: Memory, Inhibitory Control and Selective Attention, Decision-making, Planning, Sustained Attention, Social Cognition, and Cognitive Flexibility. For instance, Participant 4 received scores of 12 in Memory, 18 in Selective Attention, 6 in Decision-making, 8 in Planning, 14 in Social Cognition, and 9 in Cognitive Flexibility, resulting in a total score of 78. Following data compilation, the median score was calculated for each component, as well as for the overall cognitive abilities score across all participants. The median total score was 72.42, with scores ranging from 58 to 90. Each participant's total score was then compared to this median. Scores above 72.42 were classified as indicating a lower level of cognitive abilities, while those below this threshold were considered indicative of a higher level of cognitive abilities. For example, Participant 7 obtained a total score of 64, which falls below the median and thus reflects a high level of

cognitive abilities. In contrast, Participant 8's score places them in the low cognitive abilities category.

Table 2: Participants' Cognitive Abilities Scores

Participant	Memory	Selective Attention	Decision Making	Planning	Sustained Attention	Social Cognition	Cognitive Flexibility	Total	Cognitive Abilities Level
Participant 1	10	13	11	6	13	14	11	78	Low
Participant 2	10	11	7	6	7	10	7	58	High
Participant 3	10	16	7	3	4	13	9	62	High
Participant 4	12	18	6	8	8	14	9	75	Low
Participant 5	11	17	11	3	9	12	11	74	Low
Participant 6	14	18	18	7	11	13	9	90	Low
Participant 7	6	13	11	6	6	12	10	64	High
Participant 8	10	14	16	9	9	12	8	78	Low
Median	10.4	15.2	10.9	5.7	8.4	12.4	9.4	72.42	---

In the subsequent phase of analysis, a comprehensive examination of participants' average pupil diameter (APD) was conducted to evaluate fluctuations in cognitive load across three distinct categories of visual and textual engagement: ideologically loaded terms and expressions, English texts (inclusive of both ideological and non-ideological content), and the entire screen. The first and most focused category—ideologically loaded terms and expressions—was isolated to assess the cognitive effort specifically triggered by ideological content. Given that pupil dilation is a well-established physiological indicator of cognitive load and attentional focus, analyzing APD in response to these terms provides insight into how ideological positioning may affect mental effort during translation. The second category captured APD values associated with the full body of English texts presented during the tasks, without isolating or excluding any specific content. This category reflects the participants' general engagement with the complete source material and offers a broader view of their overall cognitive effort in the act of translation. Lastly, the inclusion of the entire screen as a baseline reference was intended to account for any peripheral visual activity and overall visual load during the translation task, beyond the text itself. Table 3 presents the percentage distribution of average pupil diameters across the three categories for each participant, providing a nuanced perspective on cognitive effort during the translation task. By comparing the APD values for ideologically loaded terms to those for the full English text, the ratios shed light on the relative cognitive load associated with processing ideological content. Ratios exceeding 100% suggest that ideological words require greater cognitive effort than the full text, while ratios below 100% indicate that ideological words are processed with less cognitive load. The results show that most participants exhibit a relatively small difference in cognitive load between ideological words and the full English text, with the ratios mostly clustering around 100%. However, there are some variations, with a few participants demonstrating higher cognitive load for ideological words, as indicated by ratios above 100%, and others showing slightly lower cognitive effort, as seen in ratios below 100%.

Table 3: Average pupil diameter on ideological words and expressions; English texts and entire screen

Types of Average Pupil Diameter (APD*)	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	Average
Average pupil diameter on ideological words	3.87	3.33	3.64	3.92	3.85	3.41	3.99	2.49	3.56
Average pupil diameter on English texts	3.88	3.32	3.62	3.90	3.82	3.32	4.00	2.51	3.50
Average pupil diameter on entire screen	3.91	3.32	3.67	3.92	3.85	3.30	4.05	2.50	3.56
Ideological words APD / English texts APD	99.74%	100.30%	100.55%	100.51%	100.79%	102.71%	99.75%	99.20%	101.71%
Ideological words APD / Entire screen APD	98.98%	100.30%	99.18%	100.00%	100.00%	103.33%	98.52%	99.60%	99.86%

*APD=Average Pupil Diameter

In order to measure the impact of ideology—reflected in national identity score—as well as cognitive abilities score on cognitive load—as reflected in average pupil diameter on ideological words—an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Effect of ideology (National Identity Score) and cognitive abilities score on cognitive load (average pupil diameter on ideological words)

	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F value	Pr(>F)
National Identity	1	10.4309	10.4309	283.27	p < 0.0001***
Cognitive Abilities	1	2.0816	2.0816	56.53	p < 0.0001***
Residuals	85	3.1299	0.0368		

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

The results of the ANOVA analysis provide clear evidence that both national identity and cognitive abilities significantly influence cognitive load during the translation of ideologically loaded texts. Specifically, national identity exhibited a strong main effect on average pupil diameter ($F(1,85) = 283.27, p < 0.0001$), indicating that variation in national identity is a predictor of cognitive effort. Participants with higher national identity scores demonstrated significantly larger average pupil diameters when translating ideologically sensitive content, which is indicative of heightened mental processing. This finding runs counter to the initial hypothesis, which predicted that stronger alignment with national ideology—combined with higher cognitive ability—would ease cognitive load by making the translation task more intuitive or ideologically aligned.

Instead, the data suggest that participants whose national identity was more aligned with the ideological content may engage more deeply or critically with ideologically charged material, leading to an increase in cognitive effort. This could be attributed to the internal negotiation between personal ideological alignment and the requirements of rendering meaning in another language, particularly when the text reflects state-endorsed viewpoints. The increased pupil dilation, therefore, might not reflect difficulty in comprehension per se but rather heightened attention, evaluation, or emotional engagement triggered by ideological salience.

Cognitive abilities also had a statistically significant effect on average pupil diameter ($F(1,85) = 56.53, p < 0.0001$), suggesting that participants with higher cognitive ability scores experienced greater cognitive load during translation tasks. While this might appear paradoxical, one possible explanation is that individuals with higher cognitive capacity may approach the task with more elaborate problem-solving strategies, deeper semantic processing, or heightened self-monitoring—each of which increases mental effort. Rather than indicating inefficiency, the larger pupil diameters in these participants may reflect a more effortful and engaged mode of processing.

Taken together, the findings underscore the importance of both ideological orientation and individual cognitive capacity in shaping the cognitive demands of translation. Translators who strongly identify with national ideologies may not simply reproduce ideological content passively; rather, their engagement with such material appears to involve deeper cognitive processing. Similarly, those with high cognitive abilities do not necessarily experience translation as easier or less effortful—instead, their approach to the task seems to involve more complex mental operations.

These results carry broader implications for understanding cognitive load in ideologically sensitive translation contexts. They suggest that alignment with ideological content does not uniformly reduce mental effort, and that cognitive abilities may amplify rather than mitigate processing demands when dealing with ideologically loaded material. Such insights are critical for designing translator training programs and for interpreting physiological data in translation studies, particularly when ideological positioning plays a central role. However, it is important to acknowledge that these findings are based on a limited sample size and should therefore be interpreted with caution. Further research with larger and more diverse participant groups is necessary to confirm the generalizability of these patterns.

4. Conclusion

This study investigated how translators' national identity and cognitive abilities influence cognitive load during the translation of ideologically loaded texts. By employing eye-tracking data—specifically pupil diameter—the research offered empirical insights into the mental effort required when translating content aligned with state-imposed ideological standards. The findings revealed that both national identity and cognitive abilities had a statistically significant effect on cognitive load. Contrary to initial expectations, higher alignment with the national ideology was associated with increased cognitive effort, as was higher cognitive ability. These results suggest that ideological alignment does not necessarily ease the mental demands of translation; instead, it may intensify cognitive engagement, possibly due to increased personal investment or heightened sensitivity to ideological cues.

The study contributes to ongoing discussions in translation studies about the intersection of cognitive effort, ideology, and translator subjectivity. It also underscores the importance of considering individual differences when evaluating translator performance or designing training programs. However, the findings are not generalizable due to the study's small sample size and context-specific nature. Methodological constraints and potential uncontrolled variables may also limit the broader applicability of the results.

Nonetheless, this research provides a valuable empirical foundation for further exploration of cognitive load in ideologically sensitive translation contexts. Future studies with larger and more diverse samples are needed to validate and expand upon these findings, as well as to explore additional psychological, cultural, or contextual factors that may shape the cognitive demands of translation.

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Translating the visual into extended verbal description

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Abstract

The article highlights a research gap in the extended (paused) format of audio description (AD) against the backdrop of prolific scholarly output focusing on the mainstream, standard AD format, including numerous user reception studies. Extended AD exists as a peripheral practice and has a largely untapped potential as an alternative method of describing audiovisual content. The project presented in this article aims at offering insights into extended AD from different perspectives in three empirical studies employing a distinct combination of research methods, which include natural language processing, qualitative research (focus groups, interviews) and empirical tools (think-aloud protocol). As such, the study proposes systematic extendibility and practical use of so-called paused commentaries. This, in turn, has the potential to offer a more informative viewing experience to conventional user groups and an opportunity to repurpose AD as assistive commentaries for a wider range of audiences.

Keywords: *accessibility; intersemiotic translation; extended/paused audio description; empirical translation studies; multi-method research design; reception studies.*

1. Introduction

Audio description (AD) is an established professional accessibility practice of making visual information accessible in a verbal format. It enables blind and partially sighted (BPS) audiences to access the visual content of audiovisual media and thus have an inclusive experience. AD is recognised as a modality of audiovisual translation (Fryer 2016). Braun (2008) labels it as a form of intersemiotic translation, following Jakobson's (1959) (modified) typology describing the translation between verbal and non-verbal sign systems.

In standard screen AD, descriptions are inserted into natural pauses in the soundtrack, thus preserving the original length and semiotic make-up of the audiovisual media. However, this approach imposes time boundaries on the description of salient visual elements. Extended AD is an alternative method, that enables describers to pause the source video as necessary, in order to deliver longer descriptions. Furthermore, standard AD is created for a homogeneous audience, whereas audiovisual product users have diverse needs, such as those due to different degrees of visual impairment (Chmiel & Mazur 2022). Extended AD can be tailored to meet such differing needs.

The benefits of standard AD have been established through user-oriented research (e.g. Pettitt et al. 1996; Schmeidler & Kirchner 2001; Fryer & Freeman 2014). Moreover, empirical research with BPS users has demonstrated a positive reception for alternative versions of AD that emphasise aspects such as cinematic language (Fryer & Freeman 2013; Bardini 2020), emotive language (Caro 2016), and the use of specific stylistic devices on syntactic and lexical levels, including different parts of speech, similes and metaphors (Chmiel & Mazur 2022).

However, alternative versions such as the above were created within the same time constraints as standard AD. This leads to a presumption that there might be some information loss to the end user in each of the alternative versions, as some information normally included as per standard AD specification would need to give way to the aspects emphasised in alternative versions.

Prior work in creating authoring tools for producing audio descriptions developed options for adding extended descriptions (Gagnon et al. 2010; Branje & Fels 2012; 3PlayMedia 2019; Pavel et al. 2020; The Smith-Kettlewell Eye Research Institute n.d.). Over the past decade, a substantial body of audiovisual content with extended AD has been created. The YouDescribe platform repository (Pitcher-Cooper 2023) is a prime example. Although extended AD has not yet been subject to systematic evaluation, it has been the subject of critical commentary. For example, when reviewing AD authoring software, Minutella (2022: 337) has contended that “this method is seldom used in real, professionally-produced audio descriptions, since it would disrupt the flow of the audiovisual product”, and others have suggested that extended AD is used by non-professional describers (Branje & Fels 2012; Pavel et al. 2020).

The present project is a systematic study of extended AD that actively involves the participation of providers and current users of AD. It investigates whether user-relevant extended narratives can provide a more informative viewing experience for the conventional user group and explores whether it has the potential to enhance the experience of a wider range of audiences.

The specific focus of investigation is on the types of information present in standard and extended AD and the way this information is organised. The project aims at laying the foundations for improving the way information is delivered through extended AD and seeks to answer the following research questions (RQs):

- RQ1: What types of information are present in the standard and extended AD and how is the information organised in the example of a described film trailer?
- RQ2: What types of information would be most user-relevant, and therefore potential candidates to systematically include in an extended version?
- RQ3: How do BPS audiences experience the information delivered by standard and extended AD and what types of additional descriptive elements could enhance this experience?

2. Research design

The research design is a multi-method study enabling triangulation of key stakeholder perspectives. The project is based on the fundamental principles of Greco’s (2019: 25) Poietic Design method including “Epistemic Inclusivity where the design draws on the knowledge [...], active participation and inclusion of stakeholders”. The knowledge that can contribute to our understanding and conceptualisation of extended AD is distributed between three stakeholder groups – advocates of existing practices of extended AD and extended AD products, describers as creators, and BPS people as users of AD. This project integrated consultation with users from its earliest stages.

Phase I of the research is reported in this paper. It comprises three studies: (i) textual analysis of existing extended descriptions, (ii) expert opinion collected through focus groups

with audio describers, and (iii) user perceptions collected through consultations with BPS AD users.

- (i) Textual analysis examined the applied practice of extended AD to answer RQ1: A sample transcript of existing standard and extended AD was analysed to compare the organisation of information in each format. Then, the additional information present in extended AD was subject to qualitative textual analysis.
- (ii) Expert opinion was sought among practitioners to address RQ2: Views on current AD practice and the possibilities for increasing the use of extended AD were collected through two online focus groups, with four professional audio describers in each group.
- (iii) User perceptions were elicited for an initial indication of user perspectives in respect of RQ2 & RQ3: This was collected through combined interview and think-aloud protocol sessions with BPS users who had experience of giving feedback to audio describers or being engaged as accessibility consultants.

Phase II, which will be reported later, builds on the knowledge acquired in Phase I to design and evaluate the usability of samples with extended AD in a user reception study to more fully address RQ3.

3. Dataset of standard and extended audio description

Existing practical applications of extended AD were sought to analyse their underlying narrative scripting techniques and linguistic composition, and to compare them with standard AD. Our selection criteria for the visual material for the qualitative studies were:

- (a) a complete work rather than an excerpt from a longer video material to ensure entirety of the narrative;
- (b) the existence of parallel texts, standard and extended AD, for each video;
- (c) relatively short duration (to be used as a stimulus in our qualitative studies);
- (d) moderately fast-paced video material with natural pauses to insert standard explanatory commentary (as opposed to very fast-paced with almost no time for standard AD).

Film trailers offer a concise cinematic experience. They are “a long-standing popular form of promotional narrative (which both sells and tells a reconfigured version of a film narrative)” (Kernan 2004: 2). Trailers present a coherent, post-production narrative that is deemed to be complete, albeit heavily edited by selecting and combining images from the feature with on-screen text and a voice-over narrator. In storytelling terms, trailers guide spectators’ attention from an initiating event at the beginning to a suspended outcome at the end. They offer short self-contained video material that could be used for different qualitative studies.

The works by Social Audio Description Collective (SADC)¹ were selected for more in-depth exploration. SADC position themselves as offering an inclusive approach to AD that reflects the diversity of the content and the audience. The audiovisual material available on

¹ About Social Audio Descriptive Collective: <https://socialaudiodescription.com/>

SADC's YouTube channel² are mostly audio described official film trailers/teasers. These were used as the dataset for the study, consisting of forty described videos.

3.1. Description of the dataset

A distinct advantage of SADC's film trailer videos is that they feature standard AD and extended AD of the same audiovisual material recorded back-to-back in a single video file. Both AD versions are written by the same creative team and narrated by the same voice artist for each trailer. Thus, we were able to compare the standard and extended formats of AD for the same trailer, where the decisions about what to include/omit in each AD format were made by the same authoring team. This also excluded the uncontrollable extraneous variable of a difference in the describers' creative intent and confounding differences in the voice delivery of AD.

The forty videos in our dataset were between 3:00 and 14:23 minutes long. All videos followed the same sequence: audio introduction, film trailer with standard AD, introduction of the extended AD, film trailer with extended AD, outro, credits. The intro, outro, and credits durations were disregarded, and the time codes (TCs) of the time-in and time-out for standard and extended descriptions were used to calculate their durations. The durations were converted into seconds to perform calculations summarised in Table 1. The outliers in terms of duration were four teaser videos, which are shorter than the trailers, with video duration of around 3–4 minutes, and some Adventure/Si-Fi trailers with detailed extended descriptions of fictional characters such as the Jurassic World's dinosaurs, with video duration of around 14 minutes. To account for these extremes, the inter-centile range (the range excluding the top and bottom 10% of the distribution) is also given in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the observed video durations for the whole dataset

Statistical value	Standard AD	Extended AD
	sec	sec
Minimum duration of video	36	110
Maximum duration of video	186	672
Range of video duration	150	562
Inter-centile range of video duration	109	305
Mean duration	131	386
Standard deviation	37	129

The mean duration increase in extended AD compared with standard AD was 255 sec (SD = 107 sec), which represents a 202% increase in length (SD 86%). The mean length of an individual extended description was 6 sec (SD = 2 sec), and the mean interval between individual extended descriptions was 3 sec (SD = 1 sec).

² SADC's YouTube channel <https://www.youtube.com/@KittenEarbreak/videos>

3.2. Quantitative analysis of the dataset

The Python toolkit pytube was used for downloading the dataset videos from YouTube, providing the ability to interact with them programmatically (Crummy 2021). Pytube allows users to download videos to a specified resolution and format. After downloading, the videos were passed through OpenAI’s (2022) Whisper library to transcribe the audio.

The Whisper library was used specifically in this instance because it offers robust models, which are easy to use and have relatively fast processing times. After transcription, Python’s Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) was employed for analysing the text transcripts (Bird et al. 2009). NLTK is a widely used toolkit among researchers, analysts, and data engineers for text analysis. The toolkit is freely available, easy to use, and contains an extensive catalogue of training data gathered from books, articles, and other publications. The text analysis process involves tokenizing the text into individual words and uses NLTK’s catalogue to tag each word with its Part of Speech (POS). Each POS tag is then counted to provide insights into the structure and content of the transcripts.

Naturally, based on the automated transcripts across all genres and trailers in the dataset, the word count in the extended AD transcripts is substantially higher than in the standard AD, because in the additional time the extended AD provides more detailed descriptions that add context and clarity. The differences in the word count suggest that there is higher information load in the extended AD, given that the differences in word count occur in relevant lexical categories (nouns, adjectives, etc.). Action film trailers, compared to other genres in the dataset, exhibit the highest counts across these lexical categories in the extended AD transcripts. The contributing factors, in addition to the difference in video duration, are likely to be the fast-paced and visually complex nature of action films, which require more detailed descriptions to effectively capture the intensity and dynamics of the scenes.

For quantitative analysis, it was decided to post-edit the automated transcripts to eliminate occasions of automated speech recognition errors (e.g. *follow* was instead of *followers*, *higher cliffs* in place of *hieroglyphs*). This ensured high accuracy and coherence of the scripts for analysis of POS present in standard and extended AD. Due to the project time restrictions, it was not possible to post-edit all forty transcripts. Therefore, a subset of five videos was selected, with one video representing each of the top genres in the dataset: action, adventure, horror, mystery, and comedy/drama. The genre comparison was drawn between the trailers listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Described film trailers in the analysed subset

#	Film title	Year	Genre
1	Black Panther: Wakanda Forever	2022	Action
2	Jurassic World Dominion	2022	Adventure
3	Scream	2022	Horror
4	Mr Harrigan’s Phone	2022	Mystery
5	Cruella	2021	Comedy/Drama

The POS breakdown for these five trailers shows a considerable increase in the number of nouns, adjectives, verbs, and adverbs per minute of the original trailer in the extended compared to the standard AD (see Figure 1). This could be interpreted as evidence of more characters, objects, and scenery being described, and more action not only being mentioned but also described how it happens. It will be explored later through qualitative textual analysis.

Figure 1: POS count comparison in standard and extended AD for trailers of different genres

4. Linguistic analysis of extended AD

The first step in our linguistic analysis was to observe patterns of information present in the extended AD script beyond those already delivered by standard AD and assign category types. The trailer selected for the linguistic analysis was for *Black Panther: Wakanda Forever* (2022). It was chosen because of its suitability for several studies in this project: Dynamically, it presented a transition from a moderate to fast pace and it satisfied several points we wanted participants of our studies to comment on such as diversity of characters, richness of costumes, variety of settings, presence of fictional objects, and special effects. It was longer than the average videos in our dataset so that we could elicit views on using extended AD in longer audio-visual media. The total runtime of the video is 12:25 min. The trailer runtime with standard AD is 2:10 min and with extended AD is 9:23 min; the remainder being the audio intro/outro and AD producer end credits.

The automated transcript was prepared in MS Word in a table format, allowing for parallel text comparison between the two AD versions, and post-editing of the transcription was performed to correct errors and/or reconstruct missing dialogue and AD utterances. Sound effects present in the original film track were not reconstructed in the transcript because the emphasis of the analysis was on the verbal representation of the visual cues. The automated

timecodes from the video soundtrack were retained in the transcription of the dialogues and the standard AD. Transcribed instances of extended AD were then added in an adjacent column, aligned with the corresponding text of the standard AD and the original dialogues. The transcript was used to perform two types of analysis:

- (1) A comparative textual analysis of standard AD and extended AD to identify information present in both formats and how it is organised.
- (2) Qualitative textual analysis of extended AD, identifying and classifying the information additional to that present in standard AD. MAXQDA 2022 (VERBI Software 2021) was used to code the different types of information identified.

4.1. Comparative textual analysis

The *Black Panther: Wakanda Forever* (2022) trailer has 27 utterances (as defined in Piety 2004: 458) in the standard AD and 70 in the extended AD. The extended AD includes 7 un-paused (i.e. descriptions inserted in natural pauses, as in standard AD) and 63 paused (extended AD approach) utterances. The comparative textual analysis shows that extended AD generally includes all the information delivered in standard AD (as highlighted in bold in Table 3). Identical wording between the two formats was observed in 4 instances (both, un-paused as in Table 3, TC 0:30, and as part of a paused commentary). While the core content remains consistent (e.g. TC 0:33 and 0:35), the extended AD often splits and interweaves the information into sentences differently (e.g. TC 0:24, 0:33, and 0:35), occasionally altering the wording. Sometimes standard AD information and extra information is intertwined (e.g. Table 3, TC 0:35). On other occasions information is concatenated, where the information from standard AD remains grouped together, often re-phrased, with extra details added as a subordinate part of a sentence (Table 3, TC 0:33) or a separate sentence (Table 3, TC 0:30).

There are parts of extended AD where the author uses the same available time intervals in the original soundtrack to deliver an un-paused AD commentary before pausing to give extra information. They are marked as “not paused” in the transcript (e.g. TC 0:24, 0:30). Interestingly, the author manages to include more detail in some of the un-paused extended AD lines in the same place compared to the corresponding standard AD (e.g. TC 0:33). This is most likely to be due to video editing in the extended AD part. The use of un-paused commentaries in the extended AD did not reveal any obvious patterns, with 5 instances observed throughout the trailer. This suggests that the insertion, layout (sentence structure), and delivery (paused or un-paused) of additional information is not always approached consistently and systematically in the analysed extended AD. Further analysis of the dataset is required for more substantial evidence to draw conclusions.

Whilst the delivery rate of standard and extended AD was not formally measured in this project, it is worth noting that there was no audible difference between the pace in the two AD formats. Besides, there does not seem to be any reason for a faster delivery pace of the extended commentary because extended AD is not time constrained. This, in fact, attracted a comment from an audio describer in the focus group study (see Section 5) that the narrator could have slowed the delivery of the extended AD.

Table 3: Fragment from the *Black Panther: Wakanda Forever* (2022) transcript showing a comparison of how the same information is presented in standard and extended AD

TC	ORIGINAL DIALOGUE	STANDARD AD	EXTENDED AD
0:21		Marvel Studios	Marvel Studios (not paused)
0:24		Shuri and queen Ramonda lead a Wakandan funeral procession. Shuri carries the Black Panther mask.	Queen Ramonda holds Shuri's wrist as they lead a funeral procession with the Twin Towers of the Wakanda palace behind them (not paused) The black Wakandans are all dressed in white loose fabric in traditional African styles and many have white markings on their face while the crowd and followers dance joyously the queen looks around sombrely and Shuri's face is shrouded in a veil as she holds the Black Panther's mask . Queen Ramonda is a beautiful older black woman with shiny skin dark eyeshadow white face paint between her brow and on her chin and a white funnel-shaped hat with intricate carvings the Black Panther mask is a sleek matte black full head covering with pointed ears at the top on either side silver eyes and silver accents trim above and below the eyes.
0:30		In a watery cavern Namor paints an Aztec mural.	In a structure inside a dark cavern Namor paints an orange mural (not paused) It appears to be of a brown skin Artisan working on an ornate suit of armour the mural is surrounded by Aztec hieroglyphs square line drawings of symbols including human and animal heads in the distance are stalactites and pools of water.
0:33		Wakandans perform a traditional dance dressed in white.	In front of a stone temple overgrown with trees and vines Wakandans perform a traditional dance dressed in white (not paused)
0:35		In gold jewellery, Namor is a muscular brown man with pointy ears.	Namor continues to work on the mural he dips the brush and paint from a half-sliced conch shell he is a muscular, brown-skinned man with pointy ears short black hair beard and moustache he wears ornate gold and jade gauntlets and bicep bands a gold septum ring and a rust-coloured cape over his shoulders.
0:41	Only the most broken people...		

4.2. Qualitative textual analysis

Our qualitative analysis of extended AD in the same trailer aimed to assess and develop a typology of categories for information additional to that delivered by standard AD. The starting point for developing the coding scheme of information categories were the five categories of information used by Fresno (2016) in her study of criteria to prioritise information in the AD of film characters – age, height/weight, facial features, hair, clothes/other items. These five categories were already tested in her user reception study in terms of recall, comprehension, and the effect of segregated delivery of information on recall. Fresno (2016: 148) demonstrated that “some physical traits of the characters are recalled and recognized better than others”. It is instrumental in assessing the potential information value of those categories to the AD users.

The results of the qualitative textual analysis show that the extended AD in the trailer goes beyond the information of standard AD to include, inter alia, description of character traits, setting, and action. All five character traits outlined by Fresno (2016), and adapted for our study, were found in the extended AD of the trailer, which indicates that they could be good candidates for further investigation and developing information typology. For the purposes of our coding scheme, the code ‘height/weight’ was included in a more general code ‘physical appearance’ to accommodate descriptions such as *athletic* or *muscular*. The category ‘clothes/other items’ used by Fresno was divided into two separate codes: ‘clothing’ and ‘objects/items’. From the total of 121 classifiable character-related commentaries, 39 commentaries about the five character traits were present in the extended AD transcript, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Coded segments for the five categories of character traits adapted from Fresno (2016) in the extended AD the *Black Panther: Wakanda Forever* trailer transcript

Categories	No. of coded segments = mentions (% of comments about characters)
Age	2 (1.6 %)
Height/weight (Physical appearance)	3 (2.5 %)
Facial features	5 (4 %)
Hair	5 (4 %)
Clothing	24 (19.8 %)

Additional codes were also considered, such as ethnicity, following Ofcom’s (2021: 7) recommendation that “when describing characters, aspects such as dress, physical characteristics, facial expression, body language, ethnicity and age may be significant”. ‘Body language’ was included under the umbrella code ‘action’, which was added as a separate category based on the user feedback from the Layered AD study (Schneider et al. 2022). A ‘camerawork’ category was then added to this list based on the scholarly interest in this aspect of filmic description reported in studies such as cinematic AD (Bardini 2017) and auteur AD (Szarkowska 2013). Bardini (2020) investigated the cinematic style of AD which includes descriptions of camerawork in a user reception study, but this aspect has not been previously explored with audio describers.

Analysis of all additional information included in extended AD (compared to standard AD) indicated that ‘action’ and ‘setting’ make up almost half of the additional information: ‘action’ 37%, ‘setting’ 12% of all comments. Combined information about character traits (ethnicity, clothing, facial features, hair, age, physical appearance, etc.) made up 31% of all

comments. The remaining 20% of coded information included objects, special effects, references to colour, etc. The number of coded segments (i.e. instances of information present in the extended AD) for ‘action’ exceeds any other coded information in extended AD. This is consistent with our observations of the POS (see Figure 1) and suggests that the increased use of verbs and adverbs in extended AD is primarily due to the more detailed descriptions of action (e.g. “Queen looks around sombrely”; “warriors expertly climb the exterior”). The higher number of nouns and adjectives stems from more detailed descriptions of characters (e.g. “M’baku is a thick muscular dark-skinned black man with short natural hair on top and a close trim beard”), followed by setting (e.g. “in the cavernous underwater cathedral”). The additional description of action is also consistent with the findings from a user reception study of the Layered AD that provides low, medium, and high level of details (Schneider et al. 2022). The study reported that the participants considered low and medium levels insufficient for the tested scenario of an action scene where they wanted high level of detail described. Camerawork is not mentioned in the described *Black Panther: Wakanda Forever* (2022) trailer, but special effects are present and described in both AD formats. For instance, the standard version mentions “energy surging up her legs”, and the corresponding utterance in the extended version reads, “the impact sending a surge of blue energy up her legs”. Special effects were categorised with camerawork.

Qualitative textual analysis of the coding categories derived from existing literature helped to refine a shortlist of nine information categories on the basis of the types of information present in extended AD:

1. Physical appearance
2. Age reference
3. Hair
4. Clothing
5. Facial features
6. Ethnicity
7. Cultural references
8. Setting (incl. symbolic aspects of architecture)
9. Camerawork

This list was subsequently used in the consultation studies with audio describers and AD users with the aim of eliciting priority rankings, refining the categories, and adding further categories potentially recommended by the participants (as reported in Sections 5 and 6). ‘Action’ was not included in this list of categories because the idea was to observe the participants’ unprompted comments about an action trailer as an audiovisual stimulus.

5. Expert consultation

This study aimed to obtain the views of AD creation experts on the practice of extended AD. The objectives were to gain a better understanding of the practicalities of AD script writing with regard to selecting relevant information and prioritising visual cues that need to be described under the time-constrained conditions as well as in the extended format of AD. Audio describers brainstormed ideas for the potential content of the extended descriptions. They contributed their professional knowledge and opinions to answering three interrelated questions:

- (1) What information is typically selected or, conversely, left out due to time constraints?
- (2) Is it possible to categorise what is included or omitted (time-dependent selections) and assign priority ranking?
- (3) Is it possible to identify any generalisable patterns and categories to recommend for extended descriptions?

The method for this part of the research was to conduct online focus groups with audio describers. Focus groups have commonly been used in the initial exploratory phase of research design (Wilkinson 1998: 184) as well as in “phenomenological” research when rather little is known about the phenomenon of interest (Stewart et al. 2007: 9). Conducting focus groups online is an established qualitative technique, which is particularly useful when access to busy professionals is required (Brüggen & Willems 2009). Last but not least, it is a method that replicates the conditions under which describers work: individual access to viewing of filmic material on a computer screen (or client platform). The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Surrey (reference number FASS 22-23 074 EGA, July 2023).

Recruitment of professional audio describers was conducted through charitable and commercial organisations that provide accessibility services to BPS people in the UK. Participant recruitment through both kinds of organisations was designed to attract experts who may represent diverse working practices resulting from internal AD creation guidelines. Gatekeepers of the organisations were sent the researcher’s recruitment materials for circulation to audio describers in their existing networks. There was no incentive to participate, and audio describers self-selected.

Two online focus group sessions were conducted, involving a total of eight professional audio describers, only two of whom had experience of creating extended AD. There were four describers in each focus group session to ensure sufficient discussion time in a 1.5–2-hour session. No specialist focus group software was used. The *Black Panther: Wakanda Forever* (2022) film trailer (see Section 4.1.) was used as a visual stimulus in both groups. The trailer was shown via MS Teams (screen share) during the focus group sessions. Respondents watched the trailer at the same time and then provided their comments – prompted by the researcher as moderator. Both sessions followed the same protocol, and the same question guide was used. The uniformity of tasks, runtime, and the number of participants in the two focus groups allowed all participants to have equal opportunities to contribute their professional opinions on the same subject matter, therefore the transcripts from the sessions could be combined and analysed as a single dataset. Data from both focus groups was collected using the MS Teams video recording option with automated transcription. The transcripts were anonymised, and minimal editing was done as was required to correct automated speech recognition errors, spelling, and removing double words to ease readability (Stewart et al. 2007). The content analysis of the transcripts was performed using MAXQDA.

The audio describers were first encouraged to reflect on what in their previous experience they would like to have included into standard AD but could not because of time constraints (Task 1 of the Focus Group). The task produced 30 classifiable responses (an average of four per participant) across a wide range of items, foremost being ‘diversity’ (23%), ‘speaker (identifying who is speaking)’ in 17% of all comments, followed by ‘physical characteristics’ (10%), and ‘setting’ (10%). The describers felt that the time constraints impinge on their ability to achieve fair representation of the diversity of characters and cultures, as shown in this quote:

I realise how important it is to describe diversity where it occurs and to have representation for all kinds of cultures and subcultures, but it always feels unfair to me to be describing some characters and not others when there's just not time to devote the same kind of description to everybody. I still think we need to do it. I don't think that means we don't describe anyone's physical characteristics because there's no time to describe everyone's. But in an ideal world, there would be that time. (Participant DF2-3)

Next, the participants were guided to think about the hypothetical scripting of extended AD. The describers were asked whether they saw the omitted content discussed in Task 1 as adding value and whether they would have included it if there was a way to do so (Task 2). The task was designed to elicit spontaneous attitudes towards extended AD. The entire focus group yielded a very mixed response of 80 classifiable comments:

- Negative: 41% (e.g. disapproval and sceptical views);
- Positive: 16% (e.g. approval and views that extended AD works);
- Uncertain: 43% (participants suggested that further research is needed to ask the opinions of BPS users and to investigate how/where extended AD can provide additional benefits beyond standard AD).

As a next step, Task 3, the describers watched the *Black Panther: Wakanda Forever* (2022) film trailer with standard and then extended AD. The describers were asked not to comment on the quality of the standard AD, but to speak about the positive and negative aspects of the extended description compared to the standard AD in this trailer. The subsequent exchange of views generated 33 classifiable comments:

- Negative: 40% (e.g. extended AD gives “too much information” and “but actually, that's not what blind people want.”)
- Positive: 24% (e.g. “what did occur to me was that this is a different form of audio description, and I think it would be interesting to embrace”)
- Uncertain: 36% (e.g. comments about voice and pace illustrated by the quote below).

Personally, I would have appreciated Thomas [the AD narrator] doing exactly his normal audio description and then having some awareness that he was in the extra explanatory phase, he could have taken it a bit slower, he could have almost put it into brackets in his head so that you think, oh yes, now we're in this bit and now we're going back to the action I would have found that easier to take. And it's also a way of exploiting the voice which is often underused. (Participant DF2-2)

Then, the discussion revolved around where to insert extended AD, what to include, and what to leave out (Task 4). It uncovered a wide range of opinions from the describers, illustrated in Table 5.

Table 5: Summary of coded comments on where to use extended AD, and what information to include/leave out

Code system	No. of coded comments
Where to use:	
Depends on film	2
Film credits	2
Introduction	2
Sections of the story	5
Title card	1
What to leave out:	
Some objects	3
Some action scenes	3
What to include:	
Action	1
Appearance	4
Camerawork	1
Colour	1
Context for characters	3
Movements	3
Onscreen text/logo	3
Setting	6
Visuals contradicting the audio	1
Vital story changes	1

Describers' overall cautious, sceptical frame of mind about extended AD, evident from the Tasks 3 and 4, can also be traced in their thinking about where to use it. They commented on specific places where to use the extended commentary, for instance, as an introduction, which is what a traditional audio introduction does (Fryer 2016), or over the film credits, rather than thinking of it as being inserted throughout a film.

A broad range of points was brought up in the discussion of what to include in extended AD. The top answers were 'setting' (6 comments) followed by 'appearance' (4 comments). In contrast, describing 'action' was only mentioned once. This is consistent with their answers in Task 1, where they mention 'action' twice when commenting on what they wanted to include but could not.

In the concluding part of the discussion, each describer was asked to name the most salient point in the group discussion on extended AD. Information saturation limits, i.e., that the extended AD contained too much detail that was not possible to remember, was a recurring theme. Another frequently brought up point was the need to ask the views of the BPS users on this subject rather than describers.

At the end of the focus group sessions, the participants were presented with the list of nine information categories identified in the textual analysis (Section 4.2.) and were asked to rank the categories in the order of perceived importance for BPS users. The rankings were collected through a post-session MS Forms questionnaire. It was an individual task for each describer to complete independently, without being influenced by opinions of others. The describers were not exposed to those categories during the focus group sessions so that their

reactions were unprompted by prior labelling. The rankings indicated that the most important category of supplementary information to add to standard AD was physical appearance, followed in the order of frequency by ethnicity, clothing, symbolic aspects of architecture/setting, and cultural references, etc. (see Table 6).

Table 6: Information categories ranking by audio describers from highest to lowest importance

Ranking	Audio describers' ranking of information that is perceived as important for AD users and exceeding standard AD.
1.	Physical appearance
2.	Ethnicity
3.	Clothing
4.	Setting (symbolic aspects of architecture)
5.	Cultural references
6.	Age reference
7.	Hair
8.	Camerawork
9.	Facial features

The describers were also given an opportunity to add categories not listed. A number of categories were mentioned, including 'action and movement', 'identity' and 'diversity', and naming of speakers. They also indicated that unnecessary details and plot spoilers should not be included.

6. BPS user consultation

The next step was to elicit information from BPS users in a consultation study. The comments made by the audio describers (see Section 5) also endorse this approach. The study involved BPS participants who have had experience of giving feedback about AD or acting as accessibility consultants. The objective of this study was to obtain more information about the following: the extent of user involvement in the AD script writing process and typical amendments the users have been able to advise during the AD creation process; user expectations, preferences, and wishes for improving AD; and gaining more information from AD through the use of extended AD. This study gave the participants an opportunity to reflect and give feedback on their experiences of current provision of AD created to standard AD guidelines. It gathered participants' views and helped with identifying the AD users' information needs and preferences. The main question of the study was:

What types of information might enhance user experience if they were captured in extended AD?

Given the under-explored nature and complexity of the studied phenomenon of extended AD, we employed an exploratory sequential research design using different methods for data collection (Sun 2011). Think-aloud protocol (TAP), a method that allows participants to express their reactions as freely as possible, was used in combination with more specific semi-structured interview questions.

TAP methodology has been used in product usability testing as well as in the humanities and social sciences disciplines, notably in translation process research (e.g. Fraser 1996; Künzli 2009). TAP experiments entail participants engaging with a task or product and verbalising their thoughts in real time while they perform the set task or are exposed to a product. Their verbalisations are recorded, transcribed and analysed from a variety of viewpoints. In Translation Studies, TAPs have traditionally been used when participants translate a text. Jankowska (2021) used TAP as one of the data gathering methods to study AD creation process, with audio describers as participants. Our approach has been to adapt TAP to study the process of AD product reception by BPS users, following successful application of TAPs in this area by Carloni (forthcoming). In addition to increasing our potential for observation of the cognitive processes of AD reception, particularly the points where lack of comprehension occurs, these analyses have a purpose directly related to the researched phenomenon. The verbalisations of what causes problems in comprehension at certain points throughout the viewing process of a described video could help with identification of the types of additional information required at these points to aid user comprehension.

The current study explored user reactions to the two existing formats of AD in the free-thinking part of the session. Prior to the sessions, all participants received information about the project and gave their consent to take part in the study. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Surrey (reference number FASS 23-24 036 EGA, May 2024).

Through gatekeeper organisations that provide accessibility services to BPS people in the UK, seven participants were recruited. Participants self-selected. There was no incentive offered in the recruitment materials. However, each participant received a gift voucher after their session to thank them for their time, which they were told about in the concluding part of their session. The individual sessions took place remotely using the videoconferencing platform preferred by the participants (Google Meets for one participant, Zoom for the others), and lasted approximately 1.5 hours each. The audio-only version of the described *Black Panther: Wakanda Forever* (2022) film trailer was used as a stimulus in this study. This was a suitable choice for the level of sight reported by all participants and saved bandwidth by not including the video, resulting in improved internet connection and a better quality of the automated recording/transcription of the sessions.

The sessions with BPS users revealed that none of our participants has been involved in a consultation capacity during the AD script writing process nor as a reviewer of the final script, which would have been an ideal scenario. In practice, the end user involvement was to give retrospective feedback for future reference on something that had already been broadcast. (En passant, only two audio describers reported occasionally involving a BPS user in their AD creation process).

The TAP component of the study was a combination of tasks with retrospective and concurrent verbalisations required from participants. They were first asked to listen to the trailer recorded with standard AD and to give their impressions after listening to the whole trailer. Then, the participants were asked to listen to the same trailer with standard AD again and this time to interrupt at any point where they felt there were issues with AD impacting their user experience such as either insufficient, or excessive, or unnecessary commentary. The researcher paused the trailer at the point of interruption to give the participant time to verbalise what the issue was and what could have helped to improve the description at that point, then resumed the playback until the next interruption.

The mean number of interruptions per session (i.e. per BPS user) was 4.5, with a range of 2–7. Often more than one issue was verbalised during an interruption. The mean number of issues raised per session was 7, with a range of 3–11.

The participants raised a variety of issues (see Table 7). As was expected, there were variations in their needs, which was reflected in them focusing on different issues. On the whole, the participants wanted more descriptions of characters, scenes and actions. The issue of identifying who is speaking was repeatedly brought up by one person (6 times).

Some participants found that the provided standard description of special effects was not detailed enough to interpret what was meant, e.g., mentioning of the energy blast or energy surging up the Black Panther’s legs. Similarly, the AD users thought that more detailed descriptions of unfamiliar (genre-specific, fantasy) objects, such as the Black Panther’s mask and characters’ headdress, could have enhanced their appreciation of the trailer.

In addition, there were comments from two participants about the non-plot-related descriptions: a logo and on-screen text. The standard description reads “Marvel Studios”, which was reported as not being clear in terms of whether the actual logo appeared on the screen at that point, or whether it was an on-screen text. The overlaid text advertising the date of the film release during the trailer (not the one announcing the date at the end of the trailer) caused some confusion and interrupted the flow of the dialogue by giving the information that was not related to the scene. The same participant also thought that it was not necessary to read the name of the production studio during the trailer.

Table 7: Issues raised by TAP participants sorted in the descending order of frequency

Issue	No. of times came up
Requests for more description of:	
Characters (incl. ethnicity and identity)	9
Scene	8
Speaker identity	8
Action	5
Special effects	4
Objects	3
Clothing	2
Context	1
Technical concerns:	
Warning needed for rapid scene changes	3
Onscreen text/logo unclear or confusing	2
Volume of AD was not enough to hear	2
Acronyms need to be spelled out	1
Subjective Choice of language	1
Voice similarity (between AD and characters)	1

After the TAP tasks with retrospective and concurrent verbalisation about the standard AD, the participants listened to the trailer with extended AD from start to finish and then gave feedback about their experience. This feedback was compared to the feedback they gave after watching the trailer with standard AD first time all the way through. Five participants (except P2 & P4) found the trailer with standard AD too fast, a bit confusing, and hard to follow. By contrast, all but one (P2) reported that the extended AD version was more comprehensive, gave them a better idea of what was going on, and resolved many questions they had whilst listening to the standard version. Excerpts from the participants' comments on each of the AD formats are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Comparison table of participants' comments on standard and extended AD

Participant	What did you think of that?	
	Standard AD format	Extended AD format
P1	A lot going on there. I kind of got all kinds of different impressions from that.	That explains it an awful lot more. I found I got a lot more from it and I enjoyed being more connected with the trailer.
P2	It was very fast. I got most of it. To some extent I knew I wasn't gonna get all of it as soon as I worked out was a trailer clip.	Very distracting because it kept cutting out into what the speech was. There was too much stuff. I didn't need to know all that.
P3	So, in places I felt a bit confused. It's made me want to go and watch the film. Which is kind of the idea of trailer.	I really enjoyed that because I got answers to a lot of the questions that I was asking before.
P4	I thought that was fantastic. It was really, well done and he had a lot of material to cover in a really short time.	I think that was fantastic. The extended version actually resolved a lot of the comments that I had about the shorter version.
P5	I couldn't follow very well what was happening.	This was a lot more detailed. I would well prefer this kind of description.
P6	Quite hard for myself to get a real handle of what it's about.	Totally amazing. And it's how you would like it. My only thing that it's. It sounds sort of crazy, to say almost. Overly described. It's so much to take in your minds.
P7	Not a lot, actually. I could have badly done with some sort of context.	My immediate thought is that's really good. Very comprehensive. We've got a better idea of what it is about. No, I like that format very much.

The structured part of the session focused on eliciting AD users' views on how important certain categories of information delivered by extended AD were for them. The typology of information categories developed during the textual analysis and consolidated into nine types (clothing, physical appearance, ethnicity, cultural references, symbolic aspects of architecture/setting, age reference, hair, facial features, and camerawork) was read out to the participants. Although the BPS participants expressed their personal preferences for each category, precise rankings for the whole group proved difficult due to individual differences.

The responses varied more by participant than by category, suggesting that the participant's personal preferences and information needs played an important role. For example, P1 predominantly responded "not too concerned", P2 – "really important", P4 – "pretty important", P5 – "definitely important", and P6 – "quite important". For P7, 'physical appearance' was "important" and 'cultural references' were "quite important", with other categories being of lesser importance, to be mentioned only when pertinent to the storyline. The closest answers to ranking were from P3, who regarded 'physical appearance' as being of "top importance", with 'ethnicity' sitting "alongside" it, while considering other character traits "useful", followed by the remaining categories. After adding that an 'age reference' would be useful, P3 specified that it would be better to have a description of what makes a sighted person think of a character as being of a certain age. When commenting on the 'symbolic aspects of architecture/setting', P3 remarked that they were not important because symbolism explains the meaning and is "getting away from what a description is".

The overall finding was that the perceived importance of information categories varied among users, often influenced by whether they had previously reflected on the categories of information generally present in AD or simply accepted AD as presented. The category of 'physical appearance' emerged as the most universally valued, with participants noting that other character traits from the list were also "helpful" as they contributed to a fuller understanding of a person's appearance. The 'symbolic aspects of architecture/setting' were deemed important when relevant to the plot, especially in the case of iconic landmarks such as the Houses of Parliament in London, which were considered essential to include. The 'camerawork' category received a more mixed response of "yes", "no", and "maybe". The participants felt that the importance of describing camerawork depended on the film's storyline and should be used judiciously.

Similarly to the audio describers, the AD users were asked an open question about what additional information they would have liked to receive through the extended AD. Their responses included background contextual information, more detailed descriptions of scenery and locations, more details about characters, clothing, and objects. Contrary to the expectations in response to an action genre trailer, none of the participants explicitly mentioned 'action'. They were not prompted to do so because the idea was to obtain spontaneous reactions. However, one participant expressed a desire for "visual descriptions of what people were doing". For instance, in the scene described by the AD line, "Wakandans perform a traditional dance", this participant wanted a detailed account of the movements that constituted the dance.

Thinking of the audiovisual media genres that could benefit from extended AD, the participants named a wide range, including science fiction and fantasy "where you're dealing with things that are not regular occurrences in people's normal lives", period dramas where "costumes change all the time", documentaries, horror, and directors' cuts. The application of AD to an action film trailer, provoked differing views from participants: One thought that extended AD worked well for trailers and promotional materials, as it "gives a really good flavour for the film" whilst another participant commented that extended AD might not be suitable "for something that's like a trailer or something that's small and snappy". Some felt it could allow for more detailed descriptions of action and changes of scenery' while others noted that such films tend to have dense dialogue that helps infer what is happening, potentially reducing the need for extended AD.

For all participants, this session was the first time they had experienced extended AD of a video material. One participant said they had previously experienced extended AD once in an animated book reading. When an illustrator was reading the book, animated pictures were

coming up as he was speaking, and the extended commentary was explaining what was happening with the dog and the cat shown in the pictures.

Although the participants expressed some reservations about the extended AD format when asked about its usefulness, the majority of respondents (6 out of 7) thought it was a positive experience, with five participants saying it was “definitely useful”. P2 said that extended AD could be useful “on certain occasions”. Their reservations were about the extended AD potentially being overwhelming and overemphasising information. The practicalities of using the extended AD in cinema, theatre, or on TV were also a concern. One participant commented that when using DVDs, sighted assistance would normally be needed to turn on the audio description or to select additional commentaries. In other words, any platform used to deliver extended AD needs to be accessible in the first place. Another participant was under the impression that users might need to watch content multiple times or make a judgment call about the level of detail they wanted from the description.

Acknowledging that everyone’s preferences may be different, the participants were supportive of extended AD as an optional feature, including when watching content together with sighted people. The participants’ views on the genres where the extended AD could work covered a wide range of audiovisual content, which suggests that audiences across all genres could potentially benefit from this format and highlights the need for further research into the development and applicability of extended AD.

7. Discussion

The practices of using extended AD predominantly exist within video-on-demand environments, often without consistent guidelines or standards. While some collections of extended AD examples exist, they have been under-researched. One such collection featuring parallel texts of traditional and extended AD enabled a comparative analysis across all the studies presented in this paper. The common denominator of these studies was to gain a better understanding of the structure of the AD scripts, the types of information delivered to the end user in the extended format in addition to what is delivered by the standard format, and whether it would be possible to assign any user-relevant priority ranking to the information typology.

The textual analyses of the AD scripts revealed certain tendencies about how the information is organised in the extended AD. Firstly, the analysed example of extended AD consistently includes all information present in the corresponding standard AD. As a result, there is no information loss for the user. Secondly, we observed different creative approaches to extending AD (Section 4.1.), such as a) splitting existing standard AD utterances and enriching them with additional details, b) paraphrasing existing elements and adding details, or c) keeping existing elements in a block and supplementing them with additional information. These irregular patterns may be indicative of an ad-hoc application of creative solutions. However, it is also possible that the describers rendered the extended version differently from the standard AD to avoid repetition, because the two versions were designed for sequential watching in a single video playback. For our qualitative studies, we chose to focus on one out of forty trailer transcripts. We plan to extend the linguistic and textual analyses to the whole dataset which will include examples of other genres and may uncover differing compositions of POS and approaches to extending AD.

Among the explored categories of information, ‘physical appearance’ and other character traits formed over a third of the information delivered by the analysed extended AD script. Furthermore, the ‘physical appearance’ category was recognised as the top priority for inclusion in AD by the audio describers and was at the top of preferences reported by the AD users. ‘Action’ also formed more than a third of extended AD descriptions but was not one of the categories put before the audio describers nor AD users, whose unprompted reactions to extended AD were sought in the Phase I studies. Description of action needs further investigation with a larger sample of AD scripts which includes a variety of genres of audiovisual material, and user testing with a larger pool of respondents. Description of movement was not on our list of information categories but was suggested by the audio describers and one of the BPS users as being of potential value to AD users. This suggests that ‘movement’ could be explored separately or as a sub-category of the ‘action’ category.

In conducting the focus group study with AD creation experts, group dynamics were identified as a challenge because of the potential emergence of more experienced leaders whose opinions might influence the contributions from less experienced participants. Audio description used to be a niche practice, but considerably more describers have been trained in the past five to ten years following a surge in the demand for AD. Both focus groups included describers who worked since the dawn of AD, as well members of the next generation, who were trained by them. Group dynamics where group leaders emerge is a known issue which was considered when designing the study with BPS participants, initially also planned as a focus group. On reflection, it was decided to conduct individual sessions with the BPS participants and include the TAP component as part of the BPS user study.

The BPS user study had some methodological limitations. Namely, potential reactivity of TAP method, i.e. the impact the interruptions may have on the cognitive process. The studied phenomenon – extended AD – is, by its nature, an experience of interrupted film narrative. The concern here was whether “studying interruptions by means of interruptions” would be the best way to approach data collection. The design of the study attempted to offset this factor by letting the participants experience the full length of the standard AD format uninterrupted first, with a retrospective collection of data before exposing the participants to the TAP assessment during the second watch-through of the standard AD. This was followed by the participants experiencing the extended AD and retrospective collection of feedback.

The stimulus was a film trailer, which already had extra audio elements, such as the voice-over of the trailer’s narrator and the industry requirement for the audio describer to read on-screen text. This caused additional confusion for some of the participants in working out who was speaking and whether it was one of the characters in the trailer or a voice over. User viewing habits were not the focus of this study, and familiarity with film trailers as a genre was not among the selection criteria for participants. During the study, the participants were asked about their general experience of using TV and video streaming platforms, but not about prior exposure to film trailers. Asking the participants about their familiarity with film trailers might have offered an explanation for P2’s lack of clarity about who was speaking. Regardless, the tendency observed in the trailer was that clarifying verbal cues to identify the speaker were rarely used.

Although TAP as an assessment method was sufficiently accessible to use, going through the list of information categories with AD users by reading the categories out loud to obtain their rankings and subsequent analysis of the findings proved more challenging than expected. A challenging factor here could be whether the verbal delivery of the categories gives BPS participants sufficient time for a prioritisation task, or the prioritisation between the listed

categories requires a more delicate balance resulting in the repetitive answers we observed. In future studies of this kind, it would be advisable to adjust the design of the study to include a more accessible ranking mechanism or tool which may need to be developed in the absence of a ready-made solution. That said, the issue could be more about whether it is appropriate to try to rank a full league table of categories, or to look for groups of users who share common preferences or needs – whose requirements could be met by tailored extended AD.

8. Concluding remarks

This project examined the standard and extended AD formats through three consecutive empirical studies from the perspectives of current practice, practitioners, and users. The studies with audio description practitioners and users elicited participants' views on extended AD. The results revealed mixed views from expert describers, while highlighting their strong interest in being informed and guided by the opinions of BPS users. The response to extended AD from the majority of seven BPS participants was positive, indicating that additional information is welcome by AD users. This highlights the importance of including the voices and perspectives of the BPS users, which may, in the future, empower users to make informed choices about how they consume AD.

While different approaches to extending AD were observed, including enriching existing elements with additional details, paraphrasing, and supplementing information in blocks, the patterns appeared to lack consistency and systematicity in the analysed trailer. Further analysis within a larger data sample is needed to develop a better understanding of common patterns of AD extensions.

The three studies led to an initial typology of information categories that are conveyed in the additional descriptive elements of extended AD, beyond what is delivered by standard AD. This typology may need to be developed further. Triangulation of the results from all three studies will inform the design of a larger user reception study in Phase II, where more systematically designed extended AD samples will be tested.

Notes

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2 The researcher is grateful to SADC team for responding to the request for the original AD script for the *Black Panther: Wakanda Forever* (2022) trailer. The script was obtained for the sole purpose of verifying our transcription, without the permission of sharing it.

Abbreviations

AD – audio description
BPS – blind and partially sighted
NLTK – Natural Language Toolkit
POS – parts of speech
SADC – Social Audio Description Collective

SD – Standard deviation
TAP – think-aloud protocol
TC – time code

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AI and digital literacy in translation competence development

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Abstract

Numerous studies in translation process research (TPR) show that both professional and student translation processes become more efficient, and the outputs become of even higher quality and more consistent using AI as machine pre-processing. The aim of this empirical keylogging study was to explore how school pupils and university students use conventional translation tools, e.g., machine translation (MT), and innovative developments, such as ChatGPT, in comparison. Specifically, we looked at how (often) the participants used the tools, the effects on language processing and translation quality, and which translation strategies were employed. We expected students who, in comparison to the pupils, display greater translation competence, to deliver better final translations and to harness the power of the available tools more effectively to their advantage. The results of this study confirm this assumption and are in line with TPR studies. Students used a greater variety of tools to solve different problems and also prompted more when only allowed to use ChatGPT. This study shows that tools alone, in their current state, do not make up for lacking language skills. On the contrary: Language skills are necessary to evaluate the tool output and make informed decisions. Finally, this study suggests an expansion of the existing translation and post-editing competence models, as future translation students have already come in contact with prevalent innovative language technologies and thus have different prerequisites.

Keywords: Translation Competence; Artificial Intelligence; Machine Translation; Keylogging; Prompting

1. Introduction

The motivation for this study lies in the technological advancements in the field of generative AI (GenAI), which have surged dramatically in recent years. On the one hand, AI-based programs are increasingly used in everyday life (e.g. speech recognition systems or MT), while on the other hand, they are also making inroads into professional contexts. In our study, we thus focus on the question of how the use of GenAI impacts translation tasks. How do laypeople use such tools for translation, in our case for school tasks, and how do (semi-) professional translators integrate such tools into translation processes?

This study also seeks to explore to what extent lay translators are already influenced by their daily interaction with AI systems, including MT on mobile phones, and whether they are already familiar with potential translation technologies (such as DeepL, Google Translate, or other online resources). In the past, translation students typically had little to no experience with translation tools and online resources before beginning their studies. Such skills were part of a clearly defined set of translational competencies developed during their studies. However, nowadays, students often bring prior experience, as they use translation tools on their mobile phones for personal tasks and increasingly interact with GenAI to complete school

assignments, including tasks in foreign language classes. They, therefore, possess knowledge that laypeople or beginners in translation studies did not have in the past.

Our study seeks to merge these lines of research questions by comparing school pupils, i.e., lay translators, with university students, i.e., novice or intermediate translators, regarding their use of innovative AI tools in contrast to conventional tools, i.e., MT and online resources. The study employs methods from TPR, such as keylogging and screen recording, to measure translation efficiency and strategies. The quality of translations is evaluated, and a questionnaire is used to gather metadata on participants and their usage behavior regarding translation resources. The collected data are triangulated, and quantitative as well as qualitative results are discussed. This study sheds light on the question to which extent pre-academic knowledge regarding tool usage exists today. And if so, this knowledge should be addressed and integrated in academic programs, which makes an adaptation of didactic concepts pertaining to translation competence models necessary. First, we will describe the state-of-the-art of competence models, refer to TPR studies and outline our hypotheses, present our methods, and discuss our results.

2. Competence models and competence development

2.1. Translation competence models

AI and digital literacy have not been in the focus of translation competence models. Established models such as by PACTE (2003) and Göpferich (2009) define translation competence as a multi-component skill set that enables translators to produce accurate and appropriate translations. Key components of the models include:

- Bilingual sub-competence: proficiency and communicative competence in both the source and target languages, the ability to understand and produce appropriate texts in both languages.
- Extra-linguistic sub-competence: cultural, domain, and subject-specific knowledge relevant to the translation task.
- Instrumental sub-competence: proficiency in using tools, online resources and interfaces, such as dictionaries, databases and CAT tools.
- Strategic sub-competence: problem-solving and decision-making skills and the capacity to develop effective strategies to address challenges during the translation process.
- Psycho-physiological components: cognitive and behavioral abilities like memory, attention, and perseverance.
- Knowledge about translation: awareness of translation theories, processes, and practices.
- Translation routine activation: automatic recall of routines and standards for handling recurring translation scenarios.

The PACTE (2003) model emphasizes the dynamic interaction between these components, with a strong focus on empirical research and experimental validation. Göpferich (2009) emphasizes the importance of monitoring mechanisms to ensure quality and consistency, highlighting the interplay of cognitive processes. The importance of digital

literacy is only addressed within the instrumental sub-competence, which seems to be too short-sighted against the background of the most recent digital and big data developments. Considering the AI hype, these models are not state-of-the-art anymore.

Concerning digital and AI literacy, more practice-oriented frameworks come into play, e.g., the EMT (EMT Board and Competence Task-Force 2022) competence model or the definition of translation competence in the DIN ISO 17100 (2015). The EMT (European Master's in Translation) model links translation education with professional market needs, ensuring that graduates are prepared for the challenges of the translation industry. It is designed to standardize translation training across Europe and identifies the following key competence areas, which are similar to those mentioned above: language and culture, translation, personal and interpersonal skills, service provision and domain-specific knowledge. In addition to the models above, they further define the technological skills as follows: mastery of translation technologies, such as Computer-Assisted Translation (CAT) tools, MT Post-Editing (PE), and terminology management. In the area of neural MT, the interaction with AI-driven Large Language Models (LLMs) is implicitly included in the competence definition. The DIN ISO 17100 (2015) standard does not explicitly address PE of MT, but it has a strong focus on research and tools competencies since it demands the familiarity with and the ability to use tools and technology necessary for the translation process, including CAT tools, terminology management systems, file formats and software related to translation projects, and knowledge of quality control procedures. Additional notes from the DIN ISO 17100 (2015) suggest that translators are expected to continuously develop their competencies through training and practice, which implicitly covers the continuous development in digital literacy.

2.2. Post-editing competence models

In addition to the translation competence models introduced above, Nitzke & Hansen-Schirra (2021) introduce a competence model focusing on PE competencies. This model emphasizes the interaction between human and machine, highlighting the importance of understanding MT-specific errors and workflows. The model considers both cognitive demands (e.g. recognizing MT limitations) and technological proficiency, setting it apart from traditional translation competence models. It reflects the growing role of MT in professional workflows, offering a framework for the training of post-editors. The PE competence model is based on various translation competence models discussed above and the revision competence model by Robert et al. (2017). In addition to the translation competencies introduced above, the PE model covers the following PE-specific competencies:

- Error recognition and correction: the ability to identify, categorize and correct errors in machine-translated (MT) texts quickly and precisely.
- Knowledge of MT systems: understanding how MT systems are developed, trained, and function. Awareness of the typical advantages and limitations of MT systems, not only linguistically but also regarding aspects like training processes, security, or sustainability.
- Advisory competence: the ability to advise clients or stakeholders, which is increasingly important as translation and PE workflows grow more complex. This competence helps clients make informed decisions and weigh the opportunities and risks associated with using MT.

The model is rounded off by PE-specific soft skills, some of which overlap with those required for traditional translation:

- Psycho-physiological traits: focus, stress resistance, and analytical thinking are crucial for PE.
- Adherence to PE guidelines: the ability to follow PE instructions and quality standards precisely and efficiently.
- Interest in technology: a curiosity about technical developments and tools.
- Positive self-image: confidence in one's abilities is essential for effective PE.

This model can be regarded as one of the first frameworks specifically for PE competencies and enhances the awareness of the skills gap between traditional translators and post-editors, emphasizing the need for specialized competencies in the evolving translation landscape. The same holds true for the DIN ISO 18587 (2017), which also deals with PE competencies and qualifications. The competencies outlined there align closely with those in the PE competence model. The standard identifies several skills for post-editors that overlap with general translation competencies: translation competence, linguistic and textual competence, research and information management as well as cultural, technical, and subject-specific competence. Additionally, for professional PE, the standard includes:

- Knowledge of MT systems and CAT tools.
- The ability to assess the feasibility of editing MT output concerning time and effort.
- Adherence to PE guidelines.

These MT and PE competence models provide a structured framework for understanding the skills required in post-editing. They emphasize the importance of foundational translation skills, PE-specific technical and cognitive abilities as well as soft skills tailored to the unique challenges of post-editing MT. They highlight the growing complexity of translation workflows and the need for specialized competencies to ensure quality and efficiency in PE processes.

2.3. Translation competence development models and MT literacy

Having defined the diverse competencies that a translator and a post-editor should have, it is important to consider how these competencies can be developed and trained. The translation competence models by PACTE (2000) and Risku (1998) aim to explain how translators acquire, refine, and apply their competencies over time, often incorporating insights from cognitive science, pedagogy, and translation studies. These models suggest various stages of competence development: there is a staged progression of translation competence acquisition, typically moving from novice to expert (Risku 1998). The stages are characterized by:

- Lay translators: pre-translational competence.
- Novice translators: focus on basic linguistic equivalence, limited ability to navigate complex texts or cultural nuances.
- Intermediate translators: increased ability to handle challenges through training and experience, with growing use of translation tools.
- Expert translators: mastery of translation processes, strategic competence, and seamless integration of cultural, linguistic, and domain-specific knowledge.

Risku (1998) describes competence development from lay to expert translator according to the following requirements: macro strategic development, information integration, planning and decision making, self-organization. PACTE (2000) describes the learning process from pre-translational to translational competence as the development and integration of the above-described sub-competencies. Concerning AI and digital literacy, there is little research on which basic knowledge potential students may already have and which competencies they still need to learn. Bridging this gap from a didactic perspective, Krüger & Hackenbuchner (2024) suggest a matrix for MT-oriented teaching of data literacy, which defines competence descriptors for data planning, collection and production, data evaluation as well as data use within the context of MT data literacy. However, the new generation of lay and novice translators dramatically differ from lay and novice translators generations ago. In contrast to the past, when various digital translation tools that came to use in the language industry were unknown to most of the students before beginning their studies, nowadays, many young people have already come in contact with LLMs and/or GenAI (Sengar et al. 2024) and even schools employ these models as teaching assistants in the classroom (Khanmigo n.d.). With the onset of GenAI, the language industry has already begun adapting to this change (Lionbridge 2025; Carr 2023). Accordingly, language and translation studies curricula should follow suit to better prepare their students for the demands of the job market. Universities need not only adapt their curricula to a shifting job market but also to a generation that is already sensitized to the way LLMs work and what they can provide. Additionally, this generation has a basic understanding of what MT is and actively uses it on a frequent basis. In the coming sections, we will try to explain what defines this young generation and what implications this might have for the motivation of this study.

3. Translation process research and consultation of external resources

Research into the use of external resources while translating is not new in TPR (Carl et al. 2021). As consulting external resources is defined as a constituting element of various competence models (see previous sections), it is no wonder that TPR has investigated its effect on translation quality and efficiency and to the translator. Research into this field also focuses on improving translator education and better preparing students for the job market.

For example, Chodkiewicz (2015) conducted a study with 34 B.A. students in Applied Linguistics, whose native language was Polish. She qualitatively studied their behavior while translating from English to Polish and vice versa. The author recorded the participants' sessions using screen recording software and later analyzed the videos. She annotated the search queries and tools used, relying on an annotation scheme derived from the literature. In conclusion, almost all participants used external sources during translation. Participants "who performed L2 translation relied more heavily on a divers [sic!] types of searches" (Chodkiewicz 2015: 137), which can be interpreted as a means of dealing with inferior L2 language competence compared to their L1. Furthermore, the most common type of websites queried were bilingual dictionaries, online encyclopedias, online forums, and search engines. The author also notes that the participants did not just research "equivalents of particular terms, but also [...] word meaning, extralinguistic knowledge, and TL correctness" (Chodkiewicz 2015: 137). This points to the participants' translation competence, as they have

been sensitized about typical problems when transferring meaning from one language to another and the corresponding translation strategies. Finally, the author seems to question the participants' technical computer skills, as many of them were neither familiar with the "Control Find command" (Chodkiewicz 2015: 138), a basic computer shortcut used to find and process information in a text quickly, nor the usage of "quotation marks to search for an entire phrase" (Chodkiewicz 2015: 138), which enables the user to utilize search engine algorithms to more precisely narrow down the results.

TPR has suggested a quantitative analysis of the usage of external sources as well. Researchers have developed computer tools that allow them to conduct quantitative analyses by meticulously logging every action during the translation process. These tools include but are not limited to Translog-II (Jakobsen & Schou 1999) and InputLog (Leijten & VanWaes 2013). They enable the recording, replaying, and analysis of the entire translation process. More importantly, they do not interfere with the reading, writing, and/or translation processes in any way, as they do not require the participant to allocate cognitive resources into something not relevant to the task. Additionally, they run silently in the background thus not distracting the participant, like Think Aloud Protocols would (e.g. Jakobsen 2003). Furthermore, Translog can be paired with eye trackers (Carl 2012), which log every input. Simultaneously, it records eye movement data and maps that to the same timeline as the mouse and keyboard inputs, thus shedding light further into the translator's mind while translating. InputLog on the other hand logs keyboard and mouse inputs, its advantage being that it logs the corresponding window in which these inputs were made. Carl et al. (2016: 42) sum up that "in a browser-based application, Inputlog knows which window is on focus. Successive keystrokes can accordingly be associated with the web page in focus. In this way web searches can be tracked and reconstructed".

Daems et al. (2016) were one of the first to demonstrate the advantages of these tools in their study. The authors examined the effectiveness of consulting external resources during translation and PE using InputLog and CASMACAT, an interactive PE suite that tried to guess the next word that was supposed to be typed, which was quite innovative for the time. The authors confirm that "whereas most previous studies were limited to screen capture software to analyze the usage of external resources, [they] present a more convenient way to capture this data, by combining the functionalities of CASMACAT with those of InputLog, two state-of-the-art logging tools" (Daems et al. 2016: 111). In total, they analyzed 80 translation sessions from English to Dutch of ten M.A. students, 40 of which were completed from scratch and 40 while post-editing MT output. The authors chose eight newspaper articles on a variety of subjects and manipulated them to keep them comparable with regards to complexity, sentence length, number of words and sentences, etc.

After the experiment, the authors analyzed the focus events provided by InputLog and manually grouped them into distinct categories dependent on the external resource used, e.g., search engines, concordancers, dictionaries, encyclopedias, and others. After conducting several statistical tests, the authors formulate the following conclusions: Overall, the participants needed significantly more time to complete the tasks when translating from scratch than when post-editing, which is in line with other empirical studies (e.g. Plitt & Masselot 2010). The types of consulted resources do not differ between the two conditions, however "significantly less time is spent in encyclopedias and other types of resources compared to dictionaries, concordancers and search engines, for both types of translation" (Daems et al. 2016: 130). The distribution of allotted time to the individual resources is similar

between human translation and PE. Nonetheless, participants spend less time in research in the PE condition than in the human translation condition. This is indicative of more efficient information processing, because in the PE condition, the participants managed to complete the tasks quicker and needed less time to find the correct information and solution to their translation problems than in the human translation condition. This is mirrored in the quality analysis: “We can therefore conclude that there is no significant difference in overall quality between both types of translation (PE and human translation)” (Daems et al. 2016: 125). Achieving the same quality in a shorter amount of time means better overall efficiency. The authors made a final interesting finding when triangulating time and quality:

When looking at post-editing, longer consultation of external resources was accompanied by higher overall error scores, whereas the opposite was true for human translation, where longer consultation of external resources was accompanied by lower overall error scores. This leads us to believe that participants are more successful in problem solving by consulting different resources when translating than when post-editing. This finding is in line with the suggestion by Yamada that post-editing requires different skills from human translation (2015). (Daems et al. 2016: 131)

For the present study, the research gap can be defined as follows: First, we want to look deeper into the translation strategies, especially the research strategies of lay translators (pupils) in comparison to novice or intermediate translators (students). Secondly, we wish to investigate how GenAI is used as an external resource in contrast to other translation tools or online resources within the translation process. The following experiment will shed light on these research questions.

4. Method and experimental design

The experiment was conducted at the Rudi-Stephan-Gymnasium in Worms, Germany, and at Faculty 06 of the Johannes Gutenberg University in Germersheim, Germany. Both the Johannes Gutenberg University and the Rudi-Stephan-Gymnasium are partners in the ForThem Alliance (Forthem n.d.). In accordance with German legislation, all academic studies conducted in educational establishments must undergo a comprehensive examination concerning ethics, data protection, and data security at the state level. It should be noted that the present study complied with all relevant legal and ethical requirements of the school advisory authority of the federal state of Rhineland-Palatinate.

First, the participants were informed about the scope of the study, the data collected, the anonymous analysis of the data, their right to withdraw from the study and to have their data deleted, in accordance with university policy. This privacy statement was signed by the participants or, when underage, their guardians.

Second, the participants were required to complete an anonymous five-minute English test, namely the Cambridge University English Assessment Test for Schools. The test comprises 25 multiple-choice items, with a single correct response for each. Subsequently, the participants were automatically assigned a score between 0 and 25, indicating the number of correct responses they provided. Subsequently, the scores of each participant were documented. The English test was employed as a quantitative measure of the participants’ English proficiency, facilitating the process of data triangulation.

Third, participants were required to complete a 26-point questionnaire (see Appendix A), adapted from Oster (2019). The primary function was to assess usage behavior regarding tools and AI and to permit further data triangulation. In addition to providing basic biographical data (age, gender, class, native language, and the age at which they began studying English), participants were asked to indicate the frequency with which they utilize various digital tools, including search engines, online dictionaries, online encyclopedias, MT tools, and chatbots. They were also asked to rate the helpfulness of these tools on a three-point Likert scale.

Additionally, participants were requested to indicate all the tools they utilize for academic tasks and the rationale behind their selection of these tools (time savings, technological proficiency, lack of knowledge, complex assignments, lack of motivation). Additionally, participants were queried as to whether they would endorse the integration of chatbots, search engines, online dictionaries, online encyclopedias, and MT tools within the academic setting. They were also asked whether they would be interested in learning more about these tools in an educational context and whether they would prefer to see these tools utilized more frequently in the classroom (yes, no, undecided).

Fourth, to ensure that all participants had a uniform understanding of the capabilities and applications of LLMs such as ChatGPT, a brief video (Bucher & Humpa 2023) was presented to address these topics. The participants were now prepared to start the experiment.

The experiment comprised two tasks: an English reading task and a translation task from German to English. In this paper, we only shed light on the translation task. Nonetheless, each task was presented in two conditions. In the first condition, the participants were permitted to utilize all available online tools, apart from LLMs/chatbots. In the second condition, the participants were only permitted to employ LLMs/chatbots. For each task, there were two texts, one for each condition.

In conclusion, each participant was tasked with working on four texts, two of which were to be translated into English (see Appendix C) and two of which were intended for reading comprehension. The objective was to ascertain the influence of conventional and innovative AI tools on the participants' output. To reiterate, the analysis of the reading task is beyond the scope of this paper. The texts were presented in a pseudo-randomized order (see Appendix B) to prevent any participant from working on the same text in both conditions. Furthermore, this method ensured the elimination of fatigue and task order effects, as no participant was presented with the same sequence of texts, tasks, and conditions.

To test for interactivity, the program InputLog, a keylogging software (Leijten & van Waes 2013), was employed. InputLog enables researchers to precisely record and reconstruct the writing processes of individuals engaged in text composition on a computer. For the purposes of this experiment, InputLog Version 8.0.0.17 (beta) was utilized.

To enhance the reconstruction of the writing process, the screen of the participants was additionally recorded using OBS Studio (OBS). This approach facilitated data triangulation, monitoring of data, and a chronological understanding of the participants' search queries and prompting behavior, in addition to the exported Excel sheets provided by InputLog.

The quality of the translation task was evaluated using an MQM-based approach (MQM Council). Two independent reviewers, both faculty researchers, were instructed to mark any errors identified according to the custom MQM error typology (American Translators Association) (see Figures 2a & 2b). They were then asked to compare their notes and finally submit a single file containing all the agreed upon annotated errors.

The initial cohort consisted of 13 students from the Rudi-Stephan-Gymnasium in Worms, Germany (here: pupil participants, ‘P’). Of these, five were in their penultimate year of secondary education (11th grade), while the remaining eight were in their final year (12th grade). The age range of the participants was between 16 and 18 years. The following biographical information about the participants was obtained directly from the questionnaire. Of the participants, nine identified German as their native language (69.23%, as indicated in Table 1), while one indicated English, two selected other languages (Albanian, Urdu), while one did not specify a native language. In this section of the questionnaire, multiple options were permitted. Seven of the participants are male and six are female. Five of the participants have attended English classes in school since the first grade, five since the third grade, and three since the fourth grade. Twelve of the participants plan to choose English as a subject in their final exams; one did not. All the pupil participants consume English media frequently or very frequently (100%, see Table 1).

The following table provides a visual representation of the biographical data of the participant groups. While we do acknowledge the imbalance of the number of participants and gender, we agreed on a pragmatical approach. The gender distribution amongst the student group is representative of all students in our faculty. Regarding the number of pupil participants, a small percentage of the initially planned pupils showed up for the study.

Table 1: Biographical and meta data of participant groups

Participants	Pupils	Students
N Participants	13	55
Mean Age	16.77	25.75
Male	7	9
Female	6	46
Other	0	0
German as native language %	69.23%	45.45%
Consume media in English frequently or very frequently %	100.00%	83.64%
Use online dictionaries frequently or very frequently %	15.38%	89.09%
Use machine translation tools frequently or very frequently %	69.23%	69.09%
Use chatbots frequently or very frequently %	38.46%	36.36%
Have been using chatbots for at least 6 months or longer %	46.15%	61.82%

Additionally, all the respondents indicated that they utilize chatbots. Five use them frequently or very frequently (38.46%, see Table 1), one uses them sometimes, and seven use them rarely. Seven pupil participants indicated that they found chatbots to be very helpful, while six indicated that they found them somewhat helpful. No respondents indicated that they found chatbots not helpful. Eight of the 13 pupil participants expressed uncertainty about the use of chatbots for schoolwork, while four were in favor and one was opposed.

Twelve of the 13 participants favored the use of other, conventional, tools, such as search engines, online dictionaries, online encyclopedias, and MT tools for schoolwork, with one participant remaining undecided. In addition, nine pupil participants indicated a desire to gain further insight into the potential applications of chatbots in school classes, while three remained undecided and one expressed opposition. Ten pupil participants utilize search engines

very frequently, two use them frequently and one sometimes. Eleven pupil participants found search engines to be very helpful, while two found them somewhat helpful.

No pupil participant reported using online dictionaries very frequently; two do so frequently, seven do so sometimes, two rarely, and two never do. This indicates that a total of 15.38% of the pupil participants use online dictionaries very frequently or frequently (see Table 1). Four respondents indicated that they find online dictionaries to be very helpful, eight rated them as somewhat helpful, and one rated them as not helpful. It is notable that online encyclopedias are not utilized very frequently by any of the pupils. Eight respondents indicated that they frequently use online encyclopedias, while five respondents indicated that they sometimes do so. Seven respondents stated that they find online encyclopedias to be very helpful, while six respondents indicated that they find them to be somewhat helpful.

Regarding MT tools, such as Google Translate or DeepL, four respondents indicated that they use them very frequently, five respondents indicated that they use them frequently, three respondents indicated that they use them sometimes, and one respondent indicated that they use them rarely. This indicates that a total of 69.23% of pupil participants use MT tools very frequently or frequently (see Table 1). Ten respondents indicated that they found MT to be very helpful, while three respondents indicated that they found it to be somewhat helpful. In this section of the questionnaire, participants were permitted to select multiple options. Twelve participants utilize search engines for their schoolwork and homework, five also employ online dictionaries, five utilize MT, seven utilize online encyclopedias, and only four utilize chatbots. The primary reasons that the pupil participants utilize digital tools for their schoolwork were time savings (11), technological proficiency (2), a lack of knowledge (8), complex tasks (7), a lack of motivation (2), and other factors (1).

The student cohort from Faculty 06 of the Johannes Gutenberg University in Gernersheim comprised 55 individuals (here: student participants, 'SP'), with an age range between 19 and 48 years and an average age of 25 years. Of the total number of this group of participants, 46 were female and nine were male. 27 of the students were pursuing a bachelor's degree, while 25 were pursuing their master's. Three students did not respond to this inquiry. Of the total student sample, 25 specified German as their native language (45.45%, see Table 1), while the remainder identified Spanish, Italian, Greek, Arabic, Portuguese, Russian, Turkish, Chinese, Polish, and Tamil as their native language.

Eight of the student participants have been attending English classes since the first grade, one since the second grade, eight since the third grade, four since the fourth grade, eight since the fifth grade and one since the sixth grade. Four respondents indicated that they had attended English classes since primary school, which could be any of the first four grades. Additionally, 21 of the 55 participants did not respond to this question. Of the 55 respondents, 44 indicated that they had taken advanced language classes, 37 of whom had also taken advanced English classes.

A total of 36 of the 55 student participants indicated that they consume English-language media very frequently, with ten participants reporting that they do so frequently, four participants reporting that they do so sometimes, and two participants reporting that they do so rarely. This shows that a total of 83.64% of the student participants engage with media in English frequently or very frequently (see Table 1). Additionally, four of the student participants utilize chatbots very frequently, while 16 students employ them frequently, 17 use them sometimes, ten utilize them rarely, and eight never do so. This suggests that a total of 36.36% of the student participants interact with chatbots at a high frequency (see Table 1).

21 students indicated that they find chatbots to be very helpful, while 27 students indicated that they find them to be somewhat helpful. Five students indicated that they find chatbots to be not helpful, while two did not respond to the inquiry. 25 students indicated that they believe chatbots should be utilized for academic purposes, while twelve expressed opposition, 17 remained undecided, and one did not respond to the inquiry. Nevertheless, 53 of the respondents expressed a preference for utilizing alternative conventional tools, including search engines, online dictionaries, online encyclopedias, and MT tools, for academic purposes, while two respondents were against this. Additionally, 48 students expressed interest in learning more about integrating chatbots into the classroom, while one student expressed no interest, and six students remained undecided.

45 of the student participants utilize search engines very frequently, nine do so frequently, and one does so sometimes. 48 of the students find search engines to be very helpful, seven find them somewhat helpful. 27 of the students employ online dictionaries very frequently, 22 frequently, four sometimes, and two rarely. This indicates that 89.09% of the student group utilize online dictionaries very frequently or frequently (see Table 1). 43 of the students surveyed indicated that they find online dictionaries to be very helpful. A further twelve respondents indicated that they find online dictionaries somewhat helpful. Eleven of the participating students utilize online encyclopedias very frequently, 23 do so frequently, 17 sometimes, and four rarely. A total of 30 students indicated that they find online encyclopedias to be very helpful, while 25 students indicated that they find them to be somewhat helpful.

Regarding MT tools, such as Google Translate or DeepL, 18 students indicated that they use these tools very frequently, 20 students indicated that they use them frequently, 15 students indicated that they use them sometimes, one student indicated that they use them rarely, and one student indicated that they never use them. This means that a total of 69.09% of the participating students use MT tools very frequently or frequently (see Table 1). A total of 33 students participating in the study indicated that they find MT to be very helpful, while 21 students find it helpful. In response to the question of which tools they regularly employ for the completion of homework and assignments, 52 students indicated the use of search engines, 49 the use of online dictionaries, 41 the use of MT, 34 the use of online encyclopedias, and 25 the use of chatbots. The primary motivations for utilizing digital tools for academic endeavors were identified as time savings (45), technological proficiency (18), a lack of knowledge (41), complex tasks (27), a lack of motivation (10), and other factors (5).

5. Results

5.1. Errors in translation

In this chapter we examine the results of the experiment. We will focus on translation competence and how it is reflected in research strategies and final output quality. Figure 1 shows the quality analysis of the translation task.

Figure 1: Average number of errors in both conditions (Quality). Both participant groups

The average number of errors is shown on the Y-axis. The dark blue bar represents the number of errors made by pupils in the ChatGPT condition, while the dark orange bar represents the number of errors made by pupils in the Other Tools condition. The light blue bar represents the number of errors made by students in the ChatGPT condition, while the light orange bar represents the number of errors made by students in the Other Tools condition. In the ChatGPT condition, pupils made an average of 6.92 errors. In the Other Tools condition, pupils made 8.67 errors on average. In the ChatGPT condition, students made an average of 3.94 errors whilst making 4.29 errors on average in the Other Tools condition. Figures 2a and 2b show the average detailed error annotation scores for both groups per participant in both conditions. The dark blue bars represent the average number of errors in each annotation category for the pupil participant group in the ChatGPT condition, while the dark orange bars represent the average number of errors in each annotation category for the pupil participant group in the Other Tools condition.

The light blue bars represent the average number of errors in the respective annotation category of the student participant group in the ChatGPT condition, while the light orange bars represent the average number of errors in the respective annotation category of the student participant group in the Other Tools condition.

Figure 2a: Average number of errors in the respective annotation category in both conditions (Quality) per participant

Figure 2b: Average number of errors in the respective annotation category in both conditions (Quality) per participant

The Y-axis shows the average number of errors, on the X-axis from left to right: Grammar (GRAM), Syntax (SYN), Word Form (WF), Spelling (SP), Character (CH), Capitalization (C), Punctuation (P), Addition (A), Omission (O), Terminology (T), Verb Form (VF), Cohesion (COH), Faithfulness (F), Literalness (L), Misunderstanding (MU), Indecision (IND), Usage (U), Register (R), and Style (ST).

In the category of terminology, it is found that pupils in the ChatGPT condition made 2.58 errors on average compared to the students' average of 0.67 errors. In the Other Tools condition, pupils made 2.42 errors on average compared to the students' average of 0.52 errors. In the category of faithfulness, it is found that pupils in the ChatGPT condition made 0.08 errors on average compared to the students' average of 0.79 errors. In the Other Tools condition, pupils made no errors, while the students' average was 0.62.

5.2. Research strategies

Next, we analyzed the target groups' research strategies. Students use a much greater variety of different tools than pupils do. The 13 pupils used seven different tools in total. 55 students used 23 tools in total. On average, students used twice as many tools as pupils: While pupils used on average only 1.77 different tools per translation session, students used 3.15 different tools. The sheer number of different tools used by students is indicative of their translation competence. They search and choose an appropriate tool to solve a given translation problem. In contrast, pupil participants resorted to one-size-fits-all solutions, the MT tools. And as the average number of tools used is smaller than 2, it means that many pupils just used the MT output as their only problem-solving strategy.

These findings are summed up in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 4 is analogous to Figure 3 but focuses on the student participants. These figures do not take into consideration how many times one specific tool was accessed by a participant but rather show the number of participants who utilized a tool at least once as part of their problem-solving strategy to create a final translation. In addition, of course one participant can use more than just one tool, i.e., the basic quantity of Figures 3 and 4 can be higher than the actual number of unique participants. This enables us to see the relation of the types of tools used rather than the individual tools, which is analogous to the methodology of Daems et al. (2016). Thus, we can compare the types of tools the two target groups access to translate the source texts. For example, Bing and Google are both search engines; Google Translate, DeepL Translate, and Youdao Translate are all neural MT tools etc. Pupil participants only used MT tools, search engines and online dictionaries. 13 individual pupils accessed seven different tools. In sum 23 pupil participants accessed all tools combined at least once. Roughly 69% of all tools accessed at least once by the pupil participants were MT tools, 22% were search engines and 9% were online dictionaries. Moreover, it is interesting to note that MT tools were the most accessed across both target groups (16 in total for pupils and 53 for students). Almost every student used DeepL to complete the translation task, showing that DeepL is the preferred NMT tool for problem solving. The pupils did not use any other NMT tool, so we can conclude that they are aware of the existence of MT tools, and the overwhelming majority choose DeepL to translate the source text.

Figure 3: Tools used by the pupil group in the Other Tools condition. In percentages

Figure 4: Tools used by the student group in the Other Tools condition. In percentages

Roughly 33% of the student participants used MT, 25% search engines, 33% online dictionaries, 2% (online) encyclopedias, 1% AI writing assistants and 1% did not use any tool at all. As elaborated upon before, students did not just use more tools on average, but also a greater variety of tools (see Figure 4 legend). This is indicative of translation competence, as solving different translation problems calls for different tools. Also, depending on the translation stage (drafting, translation, revision etc.; see EMT Board and Competence Task-Force 2022) different tools may be considered.

Furthermore, we also looked at the translation strategies in the ChatGPT condition, where we also expected to find indicators for translation competence development. Figures 5 and 6 refer to the prompting behavior in the translation task when using ChatGPT only. Figure 5 shows the average number of prompts pupils and students wrote when translating the texts in the ChatGPT condition.

Figure 5: Number of prompts written on average. Both groups, ChatGPT condition

On average, pupils wrote 3.58 prompts, while students wrote 6.25 prompts. This suggests that students engaged in significantly more back-and-forth interactions with the tool compared to pupils. Next, we examined the average number of words per prompt.

Figure 6: Number of words per prompt written. Both groups, ChatGPT condition

Figure 6 shows that, on average, each of the pupils' prompts was 10 words long, whereas the students' prompts were almost 3 times longer at 28.17. These results are indicative of the students' increased interactivity. Not only did they prompt more, but their prompts were

more elaborate. Providing more (relevant) context to the LLM yields more favorable results, a technique referred to as prompt engineering:

By employing prompt engineering techniques, academic writers and researchers can unlock the full potential of language models, harnessing their capabilities across various domains. This discipline opens up new avenues for improving AI systems and enhancing their performance in a range of applications, from text generation to image synthesis and beyond. (Giray 2023: 2629)

Thus, we observe that students' translation competence is adaptable to innovative tools like ChatGPT.

6. Discussion

These results clearly show the effect of translation competence development. In all our analyses, university students performed better than school pupils.

One interesting source of errors in both target groups was terminology. On average, approximately 28% of all errors made by pupils in the Other Tools condition were terminology errors in contrast to the students' average of 12%. In sum, the majority of the pupils' and students' mistakes were terminology errors. Moreover, both target groups made more terminology errors on average when using ChatGPT than when not using ChatGPT (see Figures 2a and 2b). On average, roughly 37% of all errors pupils made in the ChatGPT condition were terminology errors. In contrast, on average only 17% of all errors made by students in the ChatGPT condition were terminology errors.

For example, P10 translated “Das Gefühl hoffnungsloser Traurigkeit entsteht in den unzähligen **mittleren** [...] Städten” as “The feeling of hopeless sadness arises in countless **medium sized** [...] city[sic!]” (boldface by authors) in the ChatGPT condition. The terminologically sound translation would be ‘middle-sized’. Vardaro et al. (2019) argue that terminology errors are amongst the most prevalent error categories in NMT output. It is not possible to comment on the prevalence of terminology errors in the raw ChatGPT output. However, it can be assumed that the participants in this study exhibited a level of trust comparable to that reported by Huschens et al. (2023). In their study, they presented participants with the same texts in different UI conditions and found that “participants tend to attribute similar levels of credibility” to either UI condition (Huschens et al. 2023: 1). Furthermore, participants rated “AI-generated content as being clear and more engaging” (Huschens et al. 2023: 1). We therefore speculate that our participants possibly overlooked terminological issues due to the false sense of credibility attributed to the ChatGPT output.

An interesting observation in Figure 2b is that student participants made more faithfulness errors than pupils. For example, SP03 translated this source sentence “Die moderne Zivilisation auf einen nachhaltigen Weg zu bringen, **gleicht mehr und mehr** dem Versuch, einen Deich zu halten, gegen den die Flut drückt.” (boldface by authors) as “Trying to make our modern world more sustainable **is a bit like** trying to patch up a leaking dam against an oncoming flood” (boldface by authors). The annotators marked the bold phrase in the target text as a faithfulness error, as it should have been something like ‘more and more’ or ‘continuously more’ and not just ‘a bit’, albeit not being completely wrong as is. Also, for

example SP07 translated the source sentence “Vielleicht entsteht dieses Gefühl nicht in den inneren Zirkeln der Metropolen, deren Zentren **immer noch begeistern können.**” (boldface by authors) as “This feeling might not arise in the inner circles of the metropolises, whose city centers are **still cause for wonder**” (boldface by authors). There is no causal relationship in the source text. The target text is not completely wrong either, it simply adds a nuance that is not present in the source text. Pupil participants did not make such mistakes, which leads us to assume that the students who display a greater translation competence in comparison to the pupils tend to choose formulations that are farther away from the source material and therefore not entirely accurate. During their studies, they learn about equivalence (Catford 1965) and Skopos theory (Vermeer 2006), which may lead them to take greater risks to translate the *meaning* of the text and not *just* the words. Put differently, pupils resorted to more literal translation solutions, while students tended to allow themselves to deviate from the literal and textual constraints of the source text. We believe that this has implications concerning the literal translation hypothesis theorized by Malmkjaer (2005) and Chesterman (2011). Schaeffer et al. (2016) define it as follows: “A literal translation is the first or default solution a translator applies to the source text, often only as an interim solution before a less literal translation is considered or produced” (Schaeffer et al. 2016: 189). We believe that literality interacts with translation competence development and plan to conduct further research into this matter.

University students display a more sophisticated use of tools which is indicative of better translation strategies. As has been shown in Figures 3 and 4, students not only use a wider variety of tools but also use, on average, more tools per task than pupils. To better illustrate these findings, we will present examples of the translation sessions.

Figure 7: P01, Other Tools condition

In Figure 7, P01 typed *zivillation english* in the Google search bar. Google’s first result was its own translation program, Google Translate. We observed that the pupil did not specifically look for an MT tool, they just wanted to solve the translation problem. This goes

to say, that the participant did not think about which tool would best suit their needs and just chose an arbitrary solution provided by Google. This is critical, because in this example the pupil used an NMT-program as a dictionary and did not provide any context for the tool, which can lead to mistranslations. In addition, the participant did not copy the word directly from the source document into the search bar, but chose to type it in manually, resulting in a spelling error. The spelling error did not affect the performance of the tool, as Google Translate correctly identified the word and provided a correct translation of the otherwise misspelled word. This performance is attributed to the NMT-architecture, as a statistical MT tool would most likely not be able to correctly identify the word (Bertoldi et al. 2010). The lack of translation competence also becomes evident in the ChatGPT condition in Figure 8.

Figure 8: P03, ChatGPT condition

P03 asked ChatGPT to provide a synonym for the word *encroaching*. While it is spelled correctly, the context or register in which the target word should be placed was not specified. Not every synonym for a word can replace any other in every context and situation. Furthermore, the participant did not further research/prompt to assess whether *intruding* could be used synonymously in the same context as *encroaching* can, which resulted in a terminology error. The German source sentence “[d]ie moderne Zivilisation auf einen nachhaltigen Weg zu bringen, gleicht mehr und mehr dem Versuch, einen Deich zu halten, gegen den die Flut drückt.” was translated as “Trying to steer modern civilization onto a sustainable path increasingly resembles attempting to maintain a levee against an intruding flood.” While there are other errors in this translation, we will focus on the word *intruding*. Surprisingly, the participant had already copied the entire text into ChatGPT and kindly asked the tool to translate the text. After ChatGPT provided the translation, the participant wrote the prompt shown above. We cannot know why the participant decided to ask whether *intruding* was a good fit or not. Something motivated the participant to look for an alternative. What is also interesting is that ChatGPT had context in a previous prompt. ChatGPT did not make a connection to the previous prompt, and the participant did not verify the result. Instead, they blindly trusted the tool’s output, which is in line with previous studies (e.g. Huschens et al. 2023).

Of course, student participants also had to deal with the problem of finding the correct word for the given context. SP06 demonstrated their translation competence by asking ChatGPT to verify that the machine output was applicable to the specific context, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: SP06, ChatGPT condition

Not only did they request multiple synonyms, but they also checked whether a new word, that was not included in ChatGPT's reply, would still work in that context. We also observe that SP06 asks questions. These questions are addressed to ChatGPT as if ChatGPT were a real person. Notice the difference: P03 wrote "what is a synonym for encroaching" vs. "do **you** have any synonyms or [sic!] the word?" (boldface by authors). This *humanization* of the tool is a novel form of interactivity, which conventional AI tools like NMT cannot achieve. Furthermore, this is in line with what Kußmaul refers to as *learning buddy* (see Kußmaul 2015).

This *learning buddy* phenomenon can be observed in Figure 10 as well. For example, SP10 primarily translated *from scratch* and used ChatGPT very sparingly only to verify individual words or phrases. However, when they finished their translation, they pasted their entire translation into ChatGPT and asked whether it would improve anything (“würdest du an meiner Übersetzung bzw. der Grammatik was verbessern?”, ‘would you improve anything regarding my translation or grammar?’; translated by authors). ChatGPT took the additional context into consideration and then replied with a revised version and details on what had been changed. The student then copied that text into the Word document and made final adjustments before submitting their final translation. Of course, this did not lead to a flawless translation, as there are still many mistakes that ChatGPT did not correct, e.g., terminology, style, and register. The tool does not constitute a panacea for correcting deficiencies. It is, however, possible, that if the participant had more critically examined the tool output and prompted more concisely, more errors could have been avoided.

 ChatGPT
"Städtische Architektur" wird auf Englisch als "urban architecture" übersetzt. Es bezieht sich auf die architektonischen Merkmale und Stile von Gebäuden und Strukturen in städtischen Gebieten.

 You
würdest du an meiner Übersetzung bzw. der Grammatik was verbessern? Whoever travels through the cities of Europe today will feel saddened. Perhaps this feeling does nor arise with the Inner circle of the metropolises, whose centers still inspire. The feeling of hopeless sadness rises with the uncountable midsize and small cities as well as in all suburbs and metropolitan areas. Every city once was a cosmos with it's own order. Once, the residents of every every city formed a proud citizenship which expressed their confidence in urban architecture.

 ChatGPT
Certainly! Here's a revised version of your text with some improvements in grammar and clarity:

"Whoever travels through the cities of Europe today will feel saddened. Perhaps this feeling does not arise within the inner circles of the metropolises, whose centers still inspire. The feeling of hopeless sadness arises within the countless midsize and small cities, as well as in all suburbs and metropolitan areas. Every city was once a cosmos with its own order. Once, the residents of every city formed a proud citizenship that expressed their confidence in urban architecture."

Changes made:

- Adjusted punctuation for better readability.
- Corrected "nor" to "not" for proper negation.
- Removed redundant repetition of "every" before "city".
- Improved clarity in the sentence structure.

Message ChatGPT...

ChatGPT can make mistakes. Consider checking important information.

Figure 9: SP10, ChatGPT condition

In Figure 11, SP26 effectively interacted with ChatGPT as a MT tool and as a learning buddy to find a solution to a lexical problem. First, the participant pasted the entire source text into ChatGPT and requested an English translation and ChatGPT complied. Next, the participant demanded a more idiomatic translation. The participant compared the two outputs and post-edited in the Word window accordingly. Finally, the participant noticed that in the first machine output, ChatGPT had translated *Selbstbewusstsein* with 'self-confidence' but in the second output as 'self-assurance'. The participant then challenged the tool's inconsistent choice of words by demanding to know the difference between self-confidence and self-assurance. This strategy is called *chain prompting* and is used to improve the quality of ChatGPT's output (Sawalha et al. 2024).

Figure 101: SP26, ChatGPT condition

In sum, SP26 first used ChatGPT as an MT tool by providing the entire source text. Then they leveraged the advantages of LLMs by requesting a second variant of the same source text, something simple NMT systems are not capable of. By cross-referencing the two machine outputs and choosing the more suitable variant, this participant avoided some mistakes. Then they used ChatGPT as a learning buddy to better understand the meaning of a certain word and make an informed decision. This troubleshooting process would have required the usage of many different tools in the non-ChatGPT condition.

7. Conclusion

The study presented in this paper compares the use of GenAI vs. traditional translation tools in foreign language learning in two groups, a group of pupils with little to no translation competence, and a group of translation students, who are developing their translation competence by studying translation at the Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz. From a methodological point of view, a scientifically valid and replicable experimental environment was successfully created, wherein all groups were subjected to identical conditions and comparable settings. However, internet connectivity issues did arise, though they did not impact the output of the translation process and thus the scope of the study. The number of pupil participants could be considered a limitation to the study.

The results show that GenAI has a positive effect on translation tasks. In terms of quality, we can gather two things from the results: 1) that the usage of ChatGPT boosted both groups' final translation quality, and 2) the more sophisticated translation strategies employed by students improve quality in both conditions (i.e. all online tools allowed except ChatGPT and only ChatGPT allowed). Students generally make fewer mistakes across both conditions, except in some categories, e.g., Faithfulness. The greater the translation competence, the less literal the translations are, which might be explained with the literal translation hypothesis. This is grounds for further research.

We also gather that students employ more sophisticated research strategies in both conditions: in the ChatGPT condition by prompting more and prompting more detailed. We can observe strategies of prompt engineering since they use chain prompting to refine their prompts or to let ChatGPT revise their texts. In the Other Tools condition, the students show their research competence by using a wider and more suitable array of tools.

The results show that the existing competence models and standards need to be extended in such a way that AI literacy is included alongside competencies that involve research, translation, and revision. Furthermore, the previous knowledge of the new generations of students must be considered. In addition, the PE competence models and standards may have to be updated, since effective interaction with GenAI-tools might make (conventional) PE of MT obsolete. Our results might indicate a paradigm shift away from MT as a tool producing draft translations – whose quality must be checked – towards collaborating with GenAI as a translation and revision buddy. There is still room for research concerning whether these learning buddy scenarios result in more efficient processes and products of higher quality. There is also still room for technological developments that integrate or combine GenAI with traditional CAT environments.

Nevertheless, the research underscores the transformative potential of AI technologies, such as ChatGPT, in the field of education. It highlights the necessity to equip educators with targeted information regarding the potential applications and constraints of these technologies to guarantee their meaningful integration into the everyday teaching process.

Regarding the next steps of our study, it is necessary to evaluate the data gathered from keylogging to ascertain the extent of the technical and temporal effort involved. This may be achieved by analyzing the number of keystrokes per working window, the number of window switches, and the time taken to complete each task. The results of our study demonstrated that the student participants exhibited superior quality output. If we were to verify that this was achieved with fewer keystrokes, it would serve as a definitive indicator of translation competence.

Another crucial element of the study is the acknowledgment that AI-backed tools, such as ChatGPT, have the capacity to enhance the learning process by offering tailored assistance for challenging tasks. The research results indicate that by involving a larger and more diverse group of subjects, the identified limitations can be addressed and a more comprehensive understanding of the potential benefits and challenges of using these technologies can be gained. A comparison with other AI tools could also be carried out to achieve these goals. Furthermore, the long-term effects of the integration of AI tools into educational contexts should be investigated. In addition, specific error categories and the effects of targeted training measures or model adaptations on the performance of ChatGPT in the classroom should be researched.

Appendix A: Fragebogen zur Studie „Einsatz von (KI-gestützten) Tools im Fremdsprachenunterricht“

Vom Versuchsleiter auszufüllen

Datum:	
VP-Nr.:	
Score Sprachtest	

Bitte füllen Sie den nachfolgenden Teil aus.

Alter	
Studiengang	<input type="checkbox"/> BA <input type="checkbox"/> MA <input type="checkbox"/> Sonstiges:
Fachsemester	
Geschlecht	<input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> w <input type="checkbox"/> divers
Muttersprache	
Englisch als Studiensprache	<input type="checkbox"/> ja <input type="checkbox"/> nein
Konsumieren Sie Medien (z.B. Filme, Bücher, soziale Medien, Videospiele, Musik) in englischer Sprache?	<input type="checkbox"/> sehr oft <input type="checkbox"/> oft <input type="checkbox"/> manchmal <input type="checkbox"/> selten <input type="checkbox"/> nie

Nutzen Sie Suchmaschinen (z.B. Google, Bing, Ecosia)?	<input type="checkbox"/> sehr oft <input type="checkbox"/> oft <input type="checkbox"/> manchmal <input type="checkbox"/> selten <input type="checkbox"/> nie
Wie hilfreich finden Sie Suchmaschinen?	<input type="checkbox"/> sehr <input type="checkbox"/> etwas <input type="checkbox"/> gar nicht
Nutzen Sie Online-Wörterbücher (z.B. Leo, Pons, Linguee)?	<input type="checkbox"/> sehr oft <input type="checkbox"/> oft <input type="checkbox"/> manchmal <input type="checkbox"/> selten <input type="checkbox"/> nie
Wie hilfreich finden Sie Online-Wörterbücher?	<input type="checkbox"/> sehr <input type="checkbox"/> etwas <input type="checkbox"/> gar nicht
Nutzen Sie Online-Enzyklopädien (z.B. Wikipedia)?	<input type="checkbox"/> sehr oft <input type="checkbox"/> oft <input type="checkbox"/> manchmal <input type="checkbox"/> selten <input type="checkbox"/> nie
Wie hilfreich finden Sie Online-Enzyklopädien?	<input type="checkbox"/> sehr <input type="checkbox"/> etwas <input type="checkbox"/> gar nicht
Nutzen Sie Online-Übersetzungstools (z.B. Google Translate oder DeepL)?	<input type="checkbox"/> sehr oft <input type="checkbox"/> oft <input type="checkbox"/> manchmal <input type="checkbox"/> selten <input type="checkbox"/> nie
Wie hilfreich finden Sie Online-Übersetzungstools?	<input type="checkbox"/> sehr <input type="checkbox"/> etwas <input type="checkbox"/> gar nicht
Nutzen Sie Chatbots (z.B. ChatGPT)?	<input type="checkbox"/> sehr oft <input type="checkbox"/> oft <input type="checkbox"/> manchmal <input type="checkbox"/> selten <input type="checkbox"/> nie
Wie hilfreich finden Sie Chatbots?	<input type="checkbox"/> sehr <input type="checkbox"/> etwas <input type="checkbox"/> gar nicht
Wie lange nutzen Sie schon Chatbots?	<input type="checkbox"/> Heute zum 1. Mal davon gehört <input type="checkbox"/> Seit 3 Monaten <input type="checkbox"/> Seit 6 Monaten <input type="checkbox"/> Länger als 6 Monate

Welche dieser Tools nutzen Sie regelmäßig für die Schule und/oder Hausaufgaben?	<input type="checkbox"/> Suchmaschinen <input type="checkbox"/> Online-Wörterbücher <input type="checkbox"/> Online-Enzyklopädien <input type="checkbox"/> Online-Übersetzungstools <input type="checkbox"/> Chatbots <input type="checkbox"/> Andere:
Kreuzen Sie die Hauptgründe an, warum Sie Tools nutzen.	<input type="checkbox"/> Zeitersparnis <input type="checkbox"/> Technologie-Interesse <input type="checkbox"/> Fehlendes eigenes Wissen <input type="checkbox"/> Schwierige Aufgaben <input type="checkbox"/> Mangel an Motivation <input type="checkbox"/> Andere:

Befürworten Sie die Nutzung von Chatbots im Studium?	<input type="checkbox"/> ja	<input type="checkbox"/> nein	<input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht
Befürworten Sie die Nutzung von Suchmaschinen, Online-Wörterbüchern, -Enzyklopädien und -Übersetzungstools im Studium?	<input type="checkbox"/> ja	<input type="checkbox"/> nein	<input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht
Möchten Sie mehr über den Umgang mit Chatbots im Unterricht lernen?	<input type="checkbox"/> ja	<input type="checkbox"/> nein	<input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht
Möchten Sie mehr über den Umgang mit Suchmaschinen, Online-Wörterbüchern, -Enzyklopädien und -Übersetzungstools im Unterricht lernen?	<input type="checkbox"/> ja	<input type="checkbox"/> nein	<input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht
Möchten Sie, dass Chatbots häufiger im Unterricht verwendet werden?	<input type="checkbox"/> ja	<input type="checkbox"/> nein	<input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht
Möchten Sie, dass Suchmaschinen, Online-Wörterbüchern, -Enzyklopädien und -Übersetzungs-tools häufiger im Unterricht verwendet werden?	<input type="checkbox"/> ja	<input type="checkbox"/> nein	<input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht
Denken Sie, dass Chatbots in Ihrer Berufspraxis eine Rolle spielen werden?	<input type="checkbox"/> ja	<input type="checkbox"/> nein	<input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht
Denken Sie, dass Suchmaschinen, Online-Wörterbüchern, -Enzyklopädien und -Übersetzungs-tools in Ihrer Berufspraxis eine Rolle spielen werden?	<input type="checkbox"/> ja	<input type="checkbox"/> nein	<input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht

Vielen Dank für die Teilnahme an unserer Studie!

Appendix B: Pseudo-Randomization Scheme

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
1	Texte	4							1	2	3	4	
2	Reading	2					mt	1mt_R	2mt_R	3mt_T	4mt_T		
3	Translating	2	Tools	GPT			ot	1ot_R	2ot_R	3ot_T	4ot_T		
4	Conditions	2	mit tools = alles außer ChatGPT	ohne tools = Nur ChatGPT				Presidents	Devon	Zündstoff	Leuchttürme		
5													
6									mit tools = alles außer ChatGPT				
7									ohne tools = Nur ChatGPT				
8													
9	P01	Task 1	1mt_R	2ot_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	P49	Task 17	2ot_R	1mt_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	
10	P02	Task 2	4ot_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	3mt_T	P50	Task 18	1mt_R	4ot_T	2ot_R	3mt_T	
11	P03	Task 3	3ot_T	4mt_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	P51	Task 19	4mt_T	3ot_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	
12	P04	Task 4	2ot_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	1mt_R	P52	Task 20	3ot_T	2ot_R	4mt_T	1mt_R	
13	P05	Task 5	2mt_R	1ot_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	P53	Task 21	1ot_R	2mt_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	
14	P06	Task 6	4mt_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	3ot_T	P54	Task 22	2mt_R	4mt_T	1ot_R	3ot_T	
15	P07	Task 7	3mt_T	4ot_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	P55	Task 23	4ot_T	3mt_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	
16	P08	Task 8	1ot_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	2mt_R	P56	Task 24	3mt_T	1ot_R	4ot_T	2mt_R	
17	P09	Task 9	1mt_R	2ot_R	4ot_T	3mt_T	P57	Task 25	4ot_T	2ot_R	3mt_T	1mt_R	
18	P10	Task 10	4ot_T	1mt_R	3mt_T	2ot_R	P58	Task 26	3mt_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	4ot_T	
19	P11	Task 11	3ot_T	4mt_T	2ot_R	1mt_R	P59	Task 27	2ot_R	4mt_T	1mt_R	3ot_T	
20	P12	Task 12	2ot_R	3ot_T	1mt_R	4mt_T	P60	Task 28	1mt_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	2ot_R	
21	P13	Task 13	2mt_R	1ot_R	4mt_T	3ot_T	P61	Task 29	4mt_T	1ot_R	3ot_T	2mt_R	
22	P14	Task 14	4mt_T	2mt_R	3ot_T	1ot_R	P62	Task 30	3ot_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	4mt_T	
23	P15	Task 15	3mt_T	4ot_T	1ot_R	2mt_R	P63	Task 31	1ot_R	4ot_T	2mt_R	3mt_T	
24	P16	Task 16	1ot_R	3mt_T	2mt_R	4ot_T	P64	Task 32	2mt_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	1ot_R	
25	P17	Task 17	2ot_R	1mt_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	P65	Task 1	1mt_R	2ot_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	
26	P18	Task 18	1mt_R	4ot_T	2ot_R	3mt_T	P66	Task 2	4ot_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	3mt_T	
27	P19	Task 19	4mt_T	3ot_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	P67	Task 3	3ot_T	4mt_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	
28	P20	Task 20	3ot_T	2ot_R	4mt_T	1mt_R	P68	Task 4	2ot_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	1mt_R	
29	P21	Task 21	1ot_R	2mt_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	P69	Task 5	2mt_R	1ot_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	
30	P22	Task 22	2mt_R	4mt_T	1ot_R	3ot_T	P70	Task 6	4mt_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	3ot_T	
31	P23	Task 23	4ot_T	3mt_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	P71	Task 7	3mt_T	4ot_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	
32	P24	Task 24	3mt_T	1ot_R	4ot_T	2mt_R	P72	Task 8	1ot_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	2mt_R	
33	P25	Task 25	4ot_T	2ot_R	3mt_T	1mt_R	P73	Task 9	1mt_R	2ot_R	4ot_T	3mt_T	
34	P26	Task 26	3mt_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	4ot_T	P74	Task 10	4ot_T	1mt_R	3mt_T	2ot_R	
35	P27	Task 27	2ot_R	4mt_T	1mt_R	3ot_T	P75	Task 11	3ot_T	4mt_T	2ot_R	1mt_R	
36	P28	Task 28	1mt_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	2ot_R	P76	Task 12	2ot_R	3ot_T	1mt_R	4mt_T	
37	P29	Task 29	4mt_T	1ot_R	3ot_T	2mt_R	P77	Task 13	2mt_R	1ot_R	4mt_T	3ot_T	
38	P30	Task 30	3ot_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	4mt_T	P78	Task 14	4mt_T	2mt_R	3ot_T	1ot_R	
39	P31	Task 31	1ot_R	4ot_T	2mt_R	3mt_T	P79	Task 15	3mt_T	4ot_T	1ot_R	2mt_R	
40	P32	Task 32	2mt_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	1ot_R	P80	Task 16	1ot_R	3mt_T	2mt_R	4ot_T	
41	P33	Task 1	1mt_R	2ot_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	P81	Task 17	2ot_R	1mt_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	
42	P34	Task 2	4ot_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	3mt_T	P82	Task 18	1mt_R	4ot_T	2ot_R	3mt_T	
43	P35	Task 3	3ot_T	4mt_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	P83	Task 19	4mt_T	3ot_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	
44	P36	Task 4	2ot_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	1mt_R	P84	Task 20	3ot_T	2ot_R	4mt_T	1mt_R	
45	P37	Task 5	2mt_R	1ot_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	P85	Task 21	1ot_R	2mt_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	
46	P38	Task 6	4mt_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	3ot_T	P86	Task 22	2mt_R	4mt_T	1ot_R	3ot_T	
47	P39	Task 7	3mt_T	4ot_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	P87	Task 23	4ot_T	3mt_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	
48	P40	Task 8	1ot_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	2mt_R	P88	Task 24	3mt_T	1ot_R	4ot_T	2mt_R	
49	P41	Task 9	1mt_R	2ot_R	4ot_T	3mt_T	P89	Task 25	4ot_T	2ot_R	3mt_T	1mt_R	
50	P42	Task 10	4ot_T	1mt_R	3mt_T	2ot_R	P90	Task 26	3mt_T	1mt_R	2ot_R	4ot_T	
51	P43	Task 11	3ot_T	4mt_T	2ot_R	1mt_R	P91	Task 27	2ot_R	4mt_T	1mt_R	3ot_T	
52	P44	Task 12	2ot_R	3ot_T	1mt_R	4mt_T	P92	Task 28	1mt_R	3ot_T	4mt_T	2ot_R	
53	P45	Task 13	2mt_R	1ot_R	4mt_T	3ot_T	P93	Task 29	4mt_T	1ot_R	3ot_T	2mt_R	
54	P46	Task 14	4mt_T	2mt_R	3ot_T	1ot_R	P94	Task 30	3ot_T	2mt_R	1ot_R	4mt_T	
55	P47	Task 15	3mt_T	4ot_T	1ot_R	2mt_R	P95	Task 31	1ot_R	4ot_T	2mt_R	3mt_T	
56	P48	Task 16	1ot_R	3mt_T	2mt_R	4ot_T	P96	Task 32	2mt_R	3mt_T	4ot_T	1ot_R	
57													

Appendix C: Source texts for translation

Translation Brief 1 – Other Tools Condition

Aufgabe: Übersetzen Sie diesen Text ins Englische. Der Text ist sehr schwer – versuchen Sie trotzdem, Ihr Bestes zu geben. Die Übersetzung soll in der Schülerzeitung veröffentlicht werden. Sie dürfen alle Tools nutzen, die Sie kennen **AUßER** Chatbots (z.B. ChatGPT). Erlaubt sind zum Beispiel Suchmaschinen (Google etc.), Online-Wörterbücher (Leo, Pons, Linguee etc.), Online-Enzyklopädien (Wikipedia etc.), Online-Übersetzungstools (Google Translate etc.). Es bleibt Ihnen überlassen, wie Sie mit diesen Tools interagieren, ob Sie Wörter, Fragen, Sätze oder ganze Textpassagen in die Tools eingeben. Sie dürfen selbst entscheiden, wie oft und wie lange Sie welche Tools nutzen. Sie haben maximal 20 Minuten Zeit. Bitte nutzen den von uns vorgegebenen Browser. Minimieren Sie bitte keine Fenster; springen Sie zwischen den Fenstern hin und her.

Translation Brief 2 – ChatGPT Condition

Aufgabe: Übersetzen Sie diesen Text ins Englische. Der Text ist sehr schwer – versuchen Sie trotzdem, Ihr Bestes zu geben. Die Übersetzung soll in der Schülerzeitung veröffentlicht werden. Sie dürfen **NUR** Chatbots (z.B. ChatGPT) verwenden. Es sind **KEINE** anderen Tools erlaubt. Es bleibt Ihnen überlassen, wie Sie mit dem Chatbot interagieren, ob Sie Wörter, Fragen, Sätze oder ganze Textpassagen in das Tool eingeben. Sie dürfen selbst entscheiden, wie oft und wie lange Sie den Chatbot nutzen. Sie haben maximal 20 Minuten Zeit. Bitte nutzen den von uns vorgegebenen Browser. Minimieren Sie bitte keine Fenster; springen Sie zwischen den Fenstern hin und her.

Text 1

Die moderne Zivilisation auf einen nachhaltigen Weg zu bringen, gleicht mehr und mehr dem Versuch, einen Deich zu halten, gegen den die Flut drückt. Hat man gerade noch mit bloßen Händen den einen Riss gestopft, tun sich daneben schon die nächsten auf. Der jüngste Fall: Pflanzen als Energiequelle der Zukunft. Vor zwei Jahren noch gepriesen, vergeht nun kaum ein Monat, in dem nicht Umwelt- und Entwicklungsorganisationen vor dramatischen Konsequenzen für Klima, Umwelt und Ernährungssicherheit warnen. (Goethe Institut 2017)

Text 2

Wer heute durch die Städte Europas fährt, der wird traurig. Vielleicht entsteht dieses Gefühl nicht in den inneren Zirkeln der Metropolen, deren Zentren immer noch begeistern können. Das Gefühl hoffnungsloser Traurigkeit entsteht in den unzähligen mittleren und kleineren Städten sowie in allen Vorstädten und Agglomerationen. Einst war jede Stadt ein eigener Kosmos mit eigener Ordnung. Einst formten die Bewohner einer jeden Stadt eine stolze Bürgerschaft – die ihr Selbstbewusstsein in städtischer Architektur zum Ausdruck brachte. (Goethe Institut 2011)

Please type in your translation here:

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Appraisal in translation: Evaluative expressions in German transcripts of English TED Talks

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Abstract

This study seeks to identify how translation affects evaluative expressions from English to German in transcripts of TED talks. Using Appraisal Theory as a framework, we analyse how evaluative language is transferred in German subtitles and whether it is altered, omitted, or directly translated. The dataset used in this study comprises four English transcripts of TED talks, restricted to the single topic of natural science. We employ eight annotators in a manual annotation task - undergraduate translation students trained in Appraisal Theory. The students manually identify evaluative expressions in pairs and, in a second step, tag the translation strategies individually. We conduct a contrastive analysis of English and German evaluative patterns in context, focusing on the distribution of Attitude types per translation strategy employed. The findings suggest a preference for equivalence in the translation of evaluative expressions from English to German and indicate a shining-through effect as well as adaptation to German lexico-grammatical preferences in translation. Statistical analysis is performed to evaluate the influence of Attitude types on the translation strategies. The results of this study contribute to understanding the role of evaluative language in translation and complement existing research on translation strategies of evaluative language.

Keywords: Appraisal; evaluative language; translation; TED talks

1. Introduction

Evaluative language is an important component of communication and a fundamental function of language that shapes meaning and influences audiences. Both explicitly and implicitly, the expression of attitude towards epistemic and ideational content is pervasive and not only restricted to situations where it is the objective of the utterance. For example, intersubjectively, it has many roles, including establishing interlocutor trust through the implicit expression of shared attitudes. In contexts where complex ideas are communicated to non-specialist audiences, such as popular-scientific discourse and TED talks, the role of evaluative language is less obvious but still important. It serves to engage, influence, and persuade the audience while fostering a sense of shared understanding and values. In translation, accurately transferring evaluative expressions is essential, yet challenging, as it involves observing linguistic and cultural differences. This study investigates the transfer of evaluative expressions from English to German in TED¹ talk subtitles to address whether translation dilutes evaluation through omission or alteration, or preserves it, and how translation strategies vary depending

¹ <https://www.ted.com/>

on the type of evaluation expressed.

The study employs Appraisal Theory (Martin & White 2005), a linguistic framework widely used to analyse how speakers and writers express opinions and emotions. We focus on one part of the framework called Attitude, which includes three communicative functions: Affect, Judgement and Appreciation. These communicative functions form the basis for our identification and classification of the evaluative expressions. For the scope of this study, we exclude Graduation (intensity of the evaluative meaning) to focus more on patterns of equivalence, omission, and adaptation in the transfer of evaluative meaning. This aspect could be explored in future research, as it may reveal important distinctions either on its own or in conjunction with other communicative functions. We adopt a case-study approach by using TED talks due to their distinctive communicative style that involves expert speakers transferring knowledge to non-expert audiences. TED talks are a form of popular scientific communication, where scientific knowledge is disseminated in a video format that enables widespread accessibility and engagement with a broader audience (Sugimoto et al. 2013).

The dataset comprises evaluative expressions from four English TED talks on natural science topics and their translations into German. The research investigates evaluative language transfer by focusing on these three research questions:

- How are different types of Attitude (Affect, Judgement, Appreciation) distributed across the texts under analysis?
- What is the distribution of translation strategies applied to evaluative expressions?
- Do translation strategies vary depending on the type of Attitude?

We combine manual annotation with quantitative analysis to identify patterns of equivalence, omission, and adaptation in the translation of evaluative language and explore how these patterns are influenced by the type of Attitude.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we provide an overview of the related work and the theoretical background. Section 3 outlines our methodology. Section 4 presents the study's results and a discussion addressing the questions formulated above, and Section 5 offers the conclusion.

2. Related work and theoretical background

2.1. Evaluation in translation

Existing studies on translation that focus on evaluative language show that translated texts do not necessarily preserve the original text evaluation. In most cases, this is an effect of cross-lingual differences in how pragmatic phenomena are marked in the corresponding source and target languages, as demonstrated by Taboada et al. (2014) in their analysis of movie reviews for English, Spanish, and German. The authors showed that the lexico-grammatical differences of those languages also impact the frequency and type of evaluative expressions in these languages. Fronhofer (2020) showed similar findings in her contrastive analysis of English and German in terms of emotions. The author compared the lexico-grammatical and functional construal of emotion events in the two languages, pointing to the preferences in certain morpho-syntactic realisations of emotions such as parts of speech, tenses, etc. General pragmatic differences reflected in the lexico-grammar of the two languages were also shown in studies of contrastive pragmatics (House 2006; Kranich 2016). In our work, we aim to observe what

happens with a speaker's attitude when texts are rendered from English into German. Oster (2023) conducted a corpus-based study examining the translation of emotion concepts, with a particular focus on the conceptualisation of anger in German-Spanish translations. She analysed prototypical emotion lexemes in both languages (*Wut*, *Zorn*, and *Ärger* in German, and *ira*, *rabia*, and *enojo* in Spanish), exploring three key aspects of the expression of anger in the translated texts: conceptual metaphors, physical effects, and the consequences of the emotion. The analysis revealed that both source and target language preferences were reflected in the translation of the conceptual metaphor.

Bak (2023) explored the translation equivalence of basic emotion terms (*anger*, *disgust*, *fear*, *joy*, *sadness*, and *surprise*) between English and Polish. By analysing two emotion term databases through a translation-backtranslation procedure with professional translators, the author quantified the degree of equivalence. The study found that only a small percentage of emotion terms (5.12% in English and 4.68% in Polish) had full translation equivalents, with over 80% of terms showing partial equivalence (Bak 2023: 7). These findings highlight the impact of language-specific differences in emotion term granularity and morpho-semantics on translation equivalence. Similarly, our study investigates how evaluative expressions in English are transformed in German translations, exploring how cross-linguistic differences shape the expression of attitudes.

Cross-lingual differences consequently have an impact on how pragmatic phenomena, and specifically evaluative expressions, are translated. On the one hand, translated texts tend to reproduce source language patterns (what is called *shining through*, Teich 2003; see Section 2.2.), and, on the other hand, they also tend to conform to the typical features of the target language, sometimes exaggerating these features (normalisation). These features are often referred to as *translation universals* (Baker 1993) or *translationese* (Gellerstam 1986). Moreover, translations may also add, alter or omit source text elements, which results in explicitation and implicitation. The causes for these translationese phenomena vary between source- and target-language-dependent and independent ones. The former occurs when changes are necessary due to the target language's conventions, and the latter is related to the translation process. At the same time, the observed translationese (see Gellerstam 1986; Baker 1993; Toury 1995; Teich 2003, amongst others) can also be affected by further factors, such as translation or editing guidelines.

Register differences between the source language (SL) and target language (TL) are another factor commonly considered in the list of factors influencing translation features (see Hansen-Schirra et al. 2012). Translation guidelines are connected to register features, as they serve as a form of standardisation, establishing norms specific to a particular text type. For instance, the TED talk translation guidelines recommend using informal expressions over formal ones and colloquial terms instead of academic ones, i.e. more general words instead of more specific ones, which may result in implicitation and simplification. At the same time, according to the guidelines, a translator should try to match the flow of the speaker's original talk, which may result in the source language shining through. The guidelines also recommend that translators search for similar expressions in the target language. In cases where no obvious equivalent exists, the guidelines advise opting for a more natural translation for the target audience, "even if it is less colourful than the original" (TED Translation Guidelines, n.d.)². The interplay of various factors influencing translation contributes to the pragmatic differences observed between translated texts and their source texts (as well as non-translated texts in the

² <https://www.ted.com/participate/translate/guidelines>

target language, which fall outside the scope of this study). While an ideal analysis of translationese would also include a comparison with non-translated texts in the target language, this is not possible in our study due to the absence of such data. A relevant study in this context is Thormodsæter (2021), which examines the idiomaticity of emotion in English and Norwegian through a corpus-based contrastive analysis of verb pairs such as *enjoy-nyte*, *love-elske*, and *like-like*. This research provides valuable insights into cross-linguistic phraseological differences, which are also relevant to the present study's focus on evaluative language in translation.

Studies on both human and machine translation have highlighted the differences between source texts and their translated counterparts. For instance, Salameh et al. (2015) and Mohammad et al. (2016) report that translations do not always preserve the sentiment of the source texts. Troiano et al. (2020) demonstrate not only the loss of emotions during the translation process but also their alteration through machine translation. In their work, Qian et al. (2023) evaluate machine translation, focusing specifically on emotion preservation.

2.2. Translationese phenomena and translation strategies

As seen from the studies on emotion and sentiment in translation, these pragmatic phenomena can be lost, i.e. omitted, preserved, changed or added in translated texts, if we compare the latter to the sources. Numerous studies on translationese phenomena described the differences between translated texts and non-translations in the source and target languages. As already mentioned above, they can be related to the features of the source and target language or derive from the process of translation. In any case, they are linked to the changes that can be observed in translated texts if compared to the source texts or the comparable texts in the target language. In this work, we analyse only those related to the differences between the source and the translated texts, as we are looking into translation strategies. If elements are omitted or added in translation, we can relate them to the phenomena of explicitation and implicitation. At the same time, we may also deal with shining through and normalisation effects. This happens when translated texts are altered due to the requirements of the target language or if the elements of the source texts are unnecessarily preserved. Next, we will clarify what we understand under the corresponding translationese phenomena.

Explicitation, implicitation, shining through and normalisation belong to the phenomena of translationese (Gellerstam 1986), which refer to the distinct characteristics and specific linguistic properties that differentiate translated texts from original, non-translated texts. These features, which are also known as “translation universals” (Baker 1993: 243), include, apart from those named above, simplification (reducing linguistic complexity or using simpler structures in the target text) and convergence (the tendency of translations to display more uniformity than native, non-translated texts). Most studies on translationese concentrate on the analyses of lexico-grammatical, morpho-syntactic and textual language patterns, ignoring semantic and pragmatic properties. To the best of our knowledge, no research has been conducted so far on explicitation and implicitation phenomena in the translation of evaluative language.

For our purpose, in the analysis of translation strategies, we define explicitation and implicitation in line with Klaudy & Károly (2005: 15): If translation contains lexical or grammatical elements that are (less/not) explicitly expressed in the source text, we deal with explicitation. This involves not only adding words and phrases but also using more specific expressions for the more general source text elements. Implicitation is the opposite effect: More

general expressions are used instead of more specific ones, and the elements present in the source are omitted in translation. Studies on explicitation and implicitation in translation have mostly focused on discourse connectives (see Olohan & Baker 2000; Meyer & Webber 2013; Zufferey & Cartoni 2014; Hoek et al. 2015, amongst others). In our work, we aim to examine what happens with evaluative expressions originally used in the English source TED talks that were transcribed and transferred into German. We analyse how evaluative language is transferred in German subtitles and whether it is altered, omitted, or directly translated.

For the translation of evaluative language, translation strategies and the translationese effects apply in the following way:

- In the case of a direct translation of attitude, when an evaluative expression is transferred with a direct equivalent into German (e.g. *perfect intersection* was translated as *perfekte Zusammenspiel*), we observe the phenomenon of equivalence – no explicitation or implicitation.
- When an evaluative expression is omitted in the target text (e.g. *perfect intersection* was translated as *Zusammenspiel*) or when the source text expression is translated with an evaluative expression with a more neutral meaning (e.g. *perfect intersection* was translated as *gutes Zusammenspiel*), we deal with implicitation.
- In case of an alteration to a more specific expression, i.e. when a source text item with more neutral evaluative meaning is transferred to a target text item with stronger, more explicit evaluative meaning, we deal with explicitation (e.g. *appreciate* was translated as *würdigen*, which is stronger than the literal translation *schätzen*).

Alterations in translation resulting in either implicitation or explicitation could be either optional or obligatory (as defined by Klaudy 2008). The latter normally occurs due to the requirements of the target language – the information is made explicit because the target language conventions require explicit forms. Optional explicitation is related to pragmatic differences, such as stylistic or cultural preferences, but also individual decisions by a translator. The exact nature and cause of these effects lie beyond the scope of the current study. The primary aim here is to identify if and where they occur. At the same time, we may expect the effects of shining through in our data, e.g. in the equivalent translation, the choice can be impacted by the source text, and the source text will shine through (e.g. *lost* translated as ‘verloren’, in which case a German native speaker would have translated it differently).

3. Methodology

3.1. Data

The data we use consist of four English transcripts of TED talks on natural science topics, each accompanied by their German translations. The selected speakers include three women and one man, all of whom are native American English speakers. The translations of the original English TED talks were produced by native German speakers working for TED.com. It is important to note that these translations/subtitles are more accurately described as translated transcripts and not subtitles, as they include complete evaluative language that might typically be omitted in traditional subtitle formats. The details of the dataset are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Dataset in absolute numbers

Texts	Types	Tokens
English transcripts	1661	7331
German translations	2063	7543

3.2. Annotation scheme and procedures

We use Appraisal Theory (Martin & White 2005) that operates within the broader framework of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) as outlined by Halliday and Matthiessen (2014). Appraisal Theory outlines a set of functional categories designed to capture speaker choices in expressing both implicit and explicit evaluation. It consists of three main systems: Attitude, which covers expressions of opinions and emotions; Engagement, which examines the speaker's positioning relative to other voices in the discourse; and Graduation, which deals with the intensification of Attitude and Engagement.

Our analysis focuses on the system of Attitude and its subcategories, which we refer to as Attitude types. These types include: *Affect*, which is related to emotional responses; *Judgement*, which involves moral evaluations of human behaviour and character; and *Appreciation*, which refers to the evaluation of objects, processes, and phenomena. Employing this well-established framework for analysing evaluative language allows us to focus on examining translation strategies. Examples of each Appraisal function, including the translation strategy employed from our data, are given in (1)–(3).

- (1) *I hope for your help to explore and protect the wild ocean in ways that will restore the health and, in so doing, secure **hope** for humankind.*

Ich wünsche mir Ihre Hilfe dabei, die wilden Ozeane auf eine Art und Weise zu erkunden und zu beschützen, die sie wieder gesunden lässt und dadurch die **Hoffnung** für die Menschheit gesichert wird.

‘I wish for your help in exploring and protecting the wild oceans in a way that allows them to heal and thereby secures **hope** for humanity.’ (**Affect, equivalence**)

- (2) *And we’ve been **trawling** them down much faster than the natural systems can replenish them.*

Und wir haben es viel schneller **ausgegeben**, als die Natur es wieder auffüllen kann.

‘And we have **spent** it much faster than nature can replenish it.’ (**Judgement, implicitation**)

- (3) *One **major** consequence of this work is that maybe all of these decades, we've had the whole concept of cybernetic revolt in reverse.*

Eine **wichtige** Folgerung aus dieser Arbeit ist, dass wir vielleicht seit Jahrzehnten das Konzept kybernetischer Revolten falsch herum gesehen haben.

'An **important** implication of this work is that we may have been looking at the concept of cybernetic revolts the wrong way round for decades.' (**Appreciation, explicitation**)

In (3) we consider *wichtige* ('important') to be more explicit than *major*, because the adjective *major* has multiple meanings ('very large', 'big', 'more serious', etc), whereas *wichtige* has only one meaning, making it more explicit.

Eight undergraduate German-speaking translation students, trained in Appraisal Theory, manually annotated the dataset. Working in pairs, the students identified evaluative expressions in the source text and analysed the corresponding translation strategies. The annotation process consisted of four distinct steps: identifying evaluative expressions, annotating the Attitude type, annotating the translation strategy (equivalence or alteration), and annotating translationese effects (explicitation or implicitation). In the first step, identifying evaluative expressions, two annotators in each pair collaboratively identified evaluative expressions within the text. In the second step, annotating the Attitude type, a single annotator from each pair classified the identified expressions using the Appraisal framework, marking them according to their Attitude type (Affect, Judgment, or Appreciation). The students identified and marked single-word expressions bearing Appraisal. The third step involved annotating the translation strategy, where the annotators indicated the specific translation strategy used for each evaluative expression. Finally, in the fourth step, the annotators identified the translationese effects, noting where the translators used explicitation and implicitation. Our annotation scheme, based on Appraisal Theory, is presented in Figure 1. The same scheme was used by Imamovic et al. (2024) in their study on the annotation of Attitude within the Appraisal Theory using ChatGPT.

Figure 1: Appraisal scheme based on Appraisal Theory (Martin & White 2005)

In the final step, the students' annotations were cross-checked and corrected by two trained linguists who agreed on the final assignment of the labels. We did not conduct an Inter-Annotator Agreement (IAA) test. Instead, we used expressions where students reached a consensus. Their annotations were then reviewed by two researchers, who discussed unclear cases and made a final decision.

In this study, we consider the translation strategy alteration to lead exclusively to a translationese effect that falls into either the explicitation or implicitation category. That is, when translators use alteration, they either make the evaluative meaning more explicit in the target text or render it in a more neutral or implicit manner. Importantly, alteration does not result in translation effects such as shining through or normalisation. The scheme used for translation analysis is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Translation analysis scheme including translation strategy and translationese effects

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Translation strategy and effects of Attitude types on translation strategy

The annotators identified 305 evaluative expressions in a total of four texts. For these evaluative expressions, the results show that translators preferred systematic equivalence in translation over alteration. A total of 241 (79%) expressions were tagged as instances of equivalent translation versus 64 (21%) alterations out of the total 305 translated evaluative expressions. This is expected and in line with the TED talk translation guidelines. Moreover, the clear preference for equivalence is observed equally across all four texts, despite the variation in Attitude types across those texts as well as the number of evaluative instances found in the texts. Indeed, there was no significant variation between the texts concerning translation strategy (χ^2 $df = 3$, p -value = 0.1462).

Although the sample consisted entirely of instances of evaluative language, these instances were distinguished by Attitude type, namely Affect, Judgement, and Appreciation. Unlike the translation strategy, the Attitude type varied substantially between texts. The distribution across the texts is presented in Figure 3, where red represents significant disassociation and blue represents association. The variation was tested with the Pearson χ^2 ($df = 6$, p -value = $3.319e-10$).

Figure 3: Variation of Attitude types between texts

The person residuals show that Text 1 is highly disassociated with Affect, while Text 2 is highly associated with Affect and Judgement but disassociated with Appreciation. Text 3 is disassociated with Judgement, whereas Text 4, the opposite of Text 1, is highly associated with Appreciation, yet disassociated with Affect. Note that this interpretation is based on the residuals, not the frequencies. The residuals are calculated with the Chi-square statistic and take into account the overall frequencies. They are determined by a comparison between observed frequencies and the frequencies that one would expect if there were no variations between the texts. This degree of variation between the texts needs to be borne in mind when interpreting and evaluating the results below, since any patterns observed for the effects of Attitude type on translation may be the result of text variation.

4.2. Translations of Attitude types and the impact of Attitude type on translationese

Next, we address the second research question, which examines the possible effects of Attitude type on translation strategies and translationese effects. Although the majority of evaluative expressions in the translations belong to the equivalence category, 64 instances belong to alteration. This number is non-negligible, especially given the explicit instructions to avoid alteration. We cannot know if this is related to the language function of evaluation since our sample consists exclusively of evaluative instances, but we need to determine if Attitude type played any role in translation strategy or translationese effects.

Firstly, we look at the possible effects of Attitude type on translation strategy. These results are striking in that there appears to be no significant difference between the translation strategies for each of the Attitude types (Chi² test, p -value = 0.8971, $df=2$). This suggests that the Attitude type expressed does not affect whether the translator uses a direct equivalence or some kind of alteration. Figure 4 presents the distribution of translation strategies concerning Attitude type.

Figure 4: Attitude types across translation strategies

Finally, we consider translationese effects in situations where the translation strategy has been alteration. Two types of alteration were annotated: explicitation and implicitation. If we zoom in on just the evaluative utterances where the translator altered the expression, we do see a possible impact from the Attitude type of Judgement. Although not significant, with only eight occurrences of explicitation versus two occurrences of implicitation, it is potentially indicative of the effect of the expression of some Attitude type on translation (two-tailed Fisher Exact, $p=0.06676$). The occurrences in question are examined qualitatively below in Section 4.4. Figure 5 presents the distribution and proportions of Attitude type concerning translationese effects.

Figure 5: Attitude types across translationese effects

4.3. Qualitative analysis

In the next step, we perform a qualitative analysis of the observed translation patterns. The TED guidelines on translation explicitly say that if equivalence is not possible, then the translators should opt for implicitation in the target language. In this section, we analyse examples where the translators clearly deviated from the guidelines and instead chose an explicit translation.

The Judgment categories, within the context of the alteration translation strategy, were analysed qualitatively. Of the ten instances of Judgment, two were translated explicitly, while eight were rendered implicitly. We will first focus on the explicitations, i.e., instances where the translator did not follow the guidelines.

Regarding explicitation, the English words *shaking* and *consequence* were translated into German with *zerstören* ('destroy') and *Resultat* ('result'), respectively; see the context from the dataset in examples (4) and (5) below. The two German equivalents are considered to be more explicit because of the more specific meaning they convey. According to the Duden dictionary (Duden 2025) the German verb *zerstören* has two meanings: 1) 'damage/harm' and 2) 'ruin', while the English verb *to shake* has ten different meanings in its transitive form in the Merriam Webster dictionary (Merriam-Webster n.d.), including 'to lessen the stability' or 'to brandish', but no meaning of 'to damage' or 'to ruin', which is stronger and much more specific in its meaning.

- (4) *Using Google Earth you can witness trawlers – in China, the North Sea, the Gulf of Mexico – **shaking** the foundation of our life support system, leaving plumes of death in their path.*

Mit Hilfe von Google Earth kann man Trawler beobachten, in China, in der Nordsee, im Golf von Mexiko, die die Basis unseres Lebenserhaltungssystems **zerstören** und Todesstreifen hinterlassen.

'With the help of Google Earth, one can observe trawlers – in China, in the North Sea, in the Gulf of Mexico – that are **destroying** the foundation of our life support system and leaving death zones behind.'

- (5) *This is the **consequence** of not knowing that there are limits to what we can take out of the sea.*

Das ist das **Resultat**, wenn man nicht weiß, dass es Grenzen dafür gibt, was wir den Meeren entnehmen dürfen.

'This is the **result** when one does not know that there are limits to what we are allowed to take from the seas.'

The English source word *consequence* used in (5) has four different meanings in the Merriam Webster dictionary (Merriam-Webster n.d.), including the meaning "something produced by a cause", which is the closest correspondence to the German word *Resultat* ('result'). However, here again, we observe a stronger and more specific meaning, as *Resultat* means 'result' or 'outcome' in a more specific way.

When examining the eight instances of Judgment translated as implicitation, we observed that the English words were more specific and had a stronger connotation, while their German equivalents were rendered more neutrally. Examples of such words include *concern*, *care*, *trawling*, *drowned down*, *stripped* and *critical*. We will illustrate the translation of *critical* and *concern* in examples (6) and (7).

- (6) *We need to get out ahead of fishing impacts and work to understand this **critical** part of the ocean.*

Wir müssen dem Schaden durch die Fischerei zuvorkommen und daran arbeiten, diesen **wichtigen** Teil des Ozeans zu verstehen.

‘We must prevent the damage caused by fishing and work on understanding this **important** part of the ocean.’

The word *critical* means ‘vital’, ‘indispensable’ or ‘crucial’, whereas its German equivalent used in the translation under analysis means just ‘important’ (see example (6)).

- (7) *I want to share with you my personal view of changes in the sea that affect all of us, and to consider why it matters that in 50 years, we’ve lost – actually, we’ve taken, we’ve eaten – more than 90 percent of the big fish in the sea; why you should care that nearly half of the coral reefs have disappeared; why a mysterious depletion of oxygen in large areas of the Pacific should **concern** not only the creatures that are dying, but it really should **concern** you.*

Ich möchte mit Ihnen meine persönliche Sicht auf die Veränderungen des Meeres teilen, die uns alle betreffen, und überlegen, warum es von Bedeutung ist, dass wir in 50 Jahren mehr als 90 Prozent der großen Meeresfische verloren haben oder genauer gesagt: genommen und gegessen haben. Warum es uns etwas ausmachen sollte, dass fast die Hälfte der Korallenriffe verschwunden sind, warum der rätselhafte Rückgang an Sauerstoff in großen Teilen des Pazifiks nicht nur die Kreaturen **betreffen** sollte, die dort sterben, sondern auch Sie.

‘I would like to share with you my personal view on the changes in the sea that affect us all, and reflect on why it matters that, in 50 years, we have lost more than 90 percent of the large ocean fish—or more precisely: taken and eaten them. Why it should matter to us that almost half of the coral reefs have disappeared, why the mysterious decline in oxygen in large parts of the Pacific should not only **affect** the creatures that die there, but also you.’

In example (7), the English verb *concern*, which may mean both ‘to be related to’ and ‘to be a care/a trouble’, is repeated twice, leaving space for the reader to interpret the meaning. The German verb *betreffen* has only the meaning of ‘to be related to’ and no further meaning containing ‘care’ or ‘trouble’. In this way, although the German translation is more specific, it differs in its connotation from the English original, as the meaning of ‘care’ and ‘trouble’ gets lost in translation.

However, overall, it is impossible to draw firm conclusions about explicitation and implicitation in terms of evaluation at this point, as no clear or predictable translation patterns can be established when looking at the translations. However, we can observe that emotionally charged words were occasionally translated more explicitly in German (2 times), but more frequently, they were downtoned (8 times). Further data would be necessary to make more definitive conclusions, which we intend to address in our future studies.

5. Conclusion and future work

In this study, we analyse the translation of evaluative expressions in TED talks through the lens of Appraisal Theory, with a focus on how different types of Attitude (Affect, Judgment, and Appreciation) are translated from English into German. The analysis has revealed that the majority of the Appraisal expressions were translated as direct equivalents, which is consistent with the translation guidelines provided to TED translators, in which they state that equivalence should be aimed for. However, we also show that, despite these instructions, a substantial number of expressions were altered. We interpret these alterations as cases of implicitation or explicitation.

Our findings indicate that the distribution of Attitude types across the four TED talks did not significantly affect the choice of translation strategy. Moreover, no significant differences were observed in the use of Attitude types across the texts. We show that the preferred translation strategy is equivalence, which maintains the evaluative intent of the source text while adapting to the linguistic norms of the target language. Most of the Appraisal expressions in our dataset are translated as the closest counterpart, and this holds regardless of the Attitude type. The majority of evaluative expressions (79%) were translated as direct equivalents from English into German. This suggests that translators generally adhered to the guidelines provided by TED, in which they directly transferred the evaluative expressions to the target language. However, the remaining 21% of expressions involved either implicitation or explicitation, suggesting that the translators occasionally chose either to translate the expressions more explicitly in German or a more neutral manner. It would be important to consider whether there were other alternatives, i.e. if the translators chose lexical items that were more frequent in the same contexts in the target language or if they did it for other pragmatic reasons. However, this aspect falls outside the scope of this study.

The qualitative analysis shows that most of the alteration cases of the Judgment expressions in our dataset were implicitly translated. This suggests that while the general trend was toward equivalence, Judgment expressions might be more prone to downtoning evaluation in translation. However, due to our small data sample and great variation between texts, it is hard to make any broad generalisations.

In our future work, we aim to expand the current analysis to a larger dataset. We plan to use the patterns from manual annotation to formulate queries for a larger quantitative analysis. Then, we plan to employ an automated emotional intensity scoring system for the English texts, which will assign emotion scores ranging from 1 to 5 to specific lexical items. Once the emotion scores have been assigned, the next step is to extract the corresponding sentences from the corpus that contain these emotionally charged expressions, along with their German translations. In this way, a systematic analysis of the translations will be conducted to assess how the emotional intensity is either preserved or altered in the German language.

6. Limitations

Our results contribute to a better understanding of cross-linguistic differences in expressing evaluation and offer practical insights for translators focusing on this language pair. However, several limitations should be considered in this study. First, the English transcripts were annotated by students who are non-native English speakers, which may have impacted their comprehension of evaluative meanings. The students' proficiency in English could have

influenced their ability to interpret and annotate the evaluative expressions. Second, in the German translations, evaluative expressions were not annotated in terms of their specific Attitude types. Instead, the analysis focused on whether these expressions were altered, omitted, or directly translated. In our future research, we plan to investigate how different types of attitudes are expressed and transferred in translations.

Additionally, the training phase and the refinement of the annotation guidelines were time-consuming processes, which may have affected the efficiency of the annotation process. Furthermore, the results of this study are specific to the texts analysed and cannot be generalised to other text types or genres.

It is also important to mention that in our study, we did not fully consider the context surrounding the evaluative expressions in the source or target text. However, the natural collocations of evaluative expressions may differ between the two languages, which could explain some of the results. Although this was beyond the scope of this study, analysing the context in more detail could prove very insightful and would be a promising avenue for future research. Also, it would be valuable to include non-evaluative instances alongside evaluative expressions to examine whether, and to what extent, evaluative language influences the choice of translation strategies.

Finally, expanding the study by involving a larger number of human annotators and including more texts would be advisable to increase the robustness and applicability of the findings. In our future studies, we also plan to analyse the differences between translated and non-translated texts, specifically German translations of TED talks and German original TED talks.

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Beyond automated metrics: Assessing GPT-4o and Google Translate against professional translation standards

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Abstract

This study evaluates the translation capabilities of GPT-4o, a large language model (LLM), and Google Translate, a neural machine translation (NMT) system, using the American Translators Association (ATA) certification examination framework. We assess translations in two high-resource language pairs: English-to-Chinese (eng-chi) and English-to-Arabic (eng-ara). The evaluation combines both automatic metrics using COMET and manual assessment by ATA-certified graders following the standardized ATA grading framework. Two source texts from retired ATA certification exams were translated by both systems, producing eight target texts in total. Our findings indicate varying performance across systems and language pairs, with only GPT-4o's eng-ara translations achieving superior quality for both required texts. Error analysis reveals distinct patterns between systems and language pairs: GPT-4o's eng-chi translations primarily exhibit challenges with Terminology, Literalness, and Omission, while Google Translate shows a different distribution dominated by Cohesion issues, followed by Literalness and Misunderstanding. For eng-ara translations, both systems display similar error patterns, primarily in Terminology and Literalness, suggesting consistent challenges in this language pair. While COMET scores indicate high performance across all translations, manual assessment reveals more nuanced distinctions in translation quality, particularly in handling rhetorical expressions and idiomatic language use. These findings highlight the importance of complementing automatic metrics with human assessment in translation quality evaluation. The study also suggests that translation challenges extend beyond text complexity, reflecting distinct linguistic characteristics of each language pair and varying approaches in handling these challenges by different machine translation (MT) systems.

Keywords: Machine Translation; Large Language Models; Neural Machine Translation; Translation Quality Assessment; ATA Certification; Professional Translation Standards

1. Introduction

Since its release by OpenAI in November 2022, ChatGPT (GPT-3.5-Turbo), a chatbot powered by the GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) language model, has quickly gained popularity due to its impressive performance on a wide array of natural language processing (NLP) tasks (OpenAI 2022). These tasks encompass text generation, question answering, content creation, text summarization, sentiment analysis, acting a role to perform a task, and machine translation (MT), among others (Jiao et al. 2023b; Liu et al. 2023). Underlying ChatGPT is a multilayer Transformer model pre-trained on vast text corpora using self-supervised learning (Ouyang et al. 2022). The Transformer architecture, initially proposed for neural machine translation (NMT), comprises encoder and decoder networks to map input text

to target text output (Vaswani et al. 2017). Building upon the Transformer decoder model, OpenAI developed the GPT series starting in 2018, designed for broad language generation capabilities (Radford et al. 2019). GPT models are first pre-trained in an unsupervised manner on extensive unlabeled texts to learn textual representations, then fine-tuned on labeled data to adapt to downstream tasks (OpenAI 2019a). Their self-supervised pre-training methodology enabled strong performance across tasks without task-specific architectures or datasets (OpenAI 2019b).

ChatGPT integrates the GPT approach with reinforcement learning using human preferences to further improve response quality (Ouyang et al. 2022). By providing natural language interaction, ChatGPT has demonstrated its potential to grasp context and generate coherent, relevant responses, making it a promising tool for various industries without specialized fine-tuning, including the translation sector (Jiao et al. 2023a; Dwivedi et al. 2023). The rapid evolution of these models underscores the timeliness of this research. GPT-4, released in March 2023, introduced enhanced visual capabilities and strengthened language mastery (OpenAI 2023b). More recently, GPT-4o was released in May 2024 as part of OpenAI's multimodal model lineup. This iteration represented a significant advancement in multimodal capabilities, efficiency, and language support (OpenAI 2024). Particularly relevant to our research interests, GPT-4o offers improved handling of multiple languages with greater accuracy and fluency compared to GPT-4. OpenAI has enhanced tokenization specifically for languages that do not use a Western alphabet, such as Chinese, Arabic, Hindi, and Korean. The new tokenizer more efficiently compresses non-English text, processing prompts in those languages in a cheaper, quicker way (Craig 2024). This recent development directly impacts our investigation into its translation capabilities.

Although GPT is not specially fine-tuned for language translation tasks, its potential for accurate and efficient MT has been reported by many scholars and researchers for different language pairs. Cady et al. (2023) compared the performance of seven MT systems on a set of 3,000 bidirectional translation sentences between English and Chinese drawn from patent documents on science and technology. The systems evaluated were commercial MT services (Google Translate, DeepL, Baidu, Youdao, and Niutrans) and GPT models (GPT-3.5 and GPT-4). Based on BLEU metrics, the results indicate that GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 performed comparably to the specialized commercial MT systems, with no single system showing consistent superiority across all test cases. However, it is important to note that BLEU metrics (Papineni et al. 2002) have recognized limitations, particularly for language pairs with significant structural differences like English and Chinese, and for specialized technical text such as patents. These findings highlight a research gap regarding how newer GPT models might perform in translation tasks compared to dedicated MT systems, especially for diverse language pairs and text types that require more fine-grained evaluation beyond BLEU scores.

Primarily utilizing the BLEU score for their analysis, Jiao et al. (2023b) assessed the MT capabilities of GPT-4 against GPT-3.5, uncovering significant improvements by GPT-4 across six language pairs, including English-to-German (eng-ger), German-to-English (ger-eng), English-to-Chinese (eng-chi), Chinese-to-English (chi-eng), German-to-Chinese (ger-chi), and Romanian-to-Chinese (rom-chi)¹. Their results also showed that GPT-4 is competitive with leading commercial systems like Google Translate, DeepL, and Tencent TranSmart, for both high-resource European languages and low-resource or distant ones. Furthermore, human evaluations of the translations in their study suggest that GPT-3.5 is more prone to producing

¹ ATA uses ISO 639-2, the three-letter bibliographic codes (ISO 1998).

errors and hallucinations, whereas GPT-4 demonstrates fewer inaccuracies, indicating that GPT-4 has evolved into an effective translation tool (Jiao et al. 2023a).

In their evaluation of GPT-4o's translation capabilities across six major languages in 2024, Shahriar et al. (2024) conducted a comprehensive analysis using 500 randomly sampled data points from each language dataset. The study utilized the OPUS dataset for Spanish, Arabic, French, Portuguese, and Russian translations, while Hindi data was sourced from the IIT Bombay English-Hindi Parallel Corpus. Their methodology employed BERT-based sentence embeddings (specifically the paraphrase-MiniLM-L6-v2 model) and cosine similarity metrics to evaluate translation quality, though this computational approach had limitations in capturing cultural and contextual nuances. Their results demonstrated varying performance across languages, with Spanish and Portuguese achieving the highest accuracy rates of 88% and 86% respectively, followed by Hindi (82%), Russian (80%), and French (75%). Notably, Arabic performed relatively poorly at 78%, which the researchers attributed to its intricate script system, complex word forms, and unique linguistic challenges that pose significant difficulties for MT. The findings suggest GPT-4o approaches the quality of dedicated translation systems, despite not being specifically optimized for translation. However, the study did not include an evaluation of eng-chi translation performance, and the researchers acknowledged limitations in their sampling approach and the absence of human evaluators for assessing linguistic subtleties. Like many MT evaluation studies, this research raises questions about the balance between computational metrics and human assessment in evaluating translation quality, particularly for morphologically rich languages like Arabic where computational metrics alone may not fully capture translation adequacy.

In their recent evaluation conducted in May 2024, Intento assessed the translation capabilities of 52 MT systems, including 24 Large Language Models (LLMs) (Intento 2024). Their analysis, spanning nine content domains and eleven language pairs, revealed that GPT-4o, DeepL, and Google Translate demonstrated superior performance with the highest proportion of translations containing no or minor issues. The evaluation employed a multi-metric approach combining Intento Language Quality Assessment (LQA), an LLM-based DQF-MQM metric, and the COMET semantic similarity framework (Rei et al. 2020). Each system was tested using approximately 500 source segments per language pair, with LLMs receiving zero-shot prompts such as "You are a professional translator. Translate this from <source language> to <target language>: <source segment>." Translations in the colloquial domain and in the eng-ara language pair presented the most major and critical issues across all systems. While GPT-4o achieved top-tier performance across most domains, analysis of general domain translation revealed that Google Translate ranked among the top performers for both eng-ara and eng-chi pairs, whereas GPT-4o was among the leaders specifically for eng-chi translation. However, the report's segment-by-segment translation approach may not adequately account for broader background and context, potentially resulting in higher rates of false positives. This methodology raises questions about how LLMs and commercial MT systems might perform in more comprehensive full-text translation scenarios where contextual understanding is essential.

Despite their impressive capabilities, generative AI models like ChatGPT face several inherent limitations in translation tasks. These include issues with accuracy, outdated terminology, and inappropriate linguistic patterns stemming from their training data (Liu et al. 2023; Ray 2023). Moreover, these models can perpetuate various embedded biases, including gender, cultural, religious, political, and regional language biases that exist within their training corpora (Ghosh & Caliskan 2023; Motoki et al. 2024; Babaei et al. 2024). Human oversight thus remains indispensable in professional translation contexts, particularly for high-

stakes content such as legal documents, tourism and hospitality industry content, and healthcare texts where precision is paramount (Siu 2023). The necessity for careful human review and post-editing of LLM-generated translations underscores the enduring complementary relationship between technological innovation and human expertise in professional translation workflows.

This paper addresses a significant gap in MT quality assessment. While prior studies have relied primarily on automated metrics like BLEU or limited human evaluation protocols, few have assessed translation quality within established professional standards. The American Translators Association (ATA) certification grading framework offers a comprehensive, industry-standard method for evaluating full-text translation, yet it remains underutilized in comparing LLMs and NMT systems. This study simulates the ATA certification exam using two retired ATA source texts (STs) to evaluate MT performance in English-to-Chinese (eng-chi) and English-to-Arabic (eng-ara) language pairs. The selection of Google Translate and GPT-4o as test candidates was informed by Intento's (2024) report, which identified Google Translate as the leading performer across both pairs in the general domain, and GPT-4o as a top-tier LLM system comparable to commercial MT systems across most domains and language pairs. Google Translate currently employs a Transformer-based NMT architecture, incorporating innovations in attention mechanisms and sequence-to-sequence learning. Since transitioning from statistical methods in 2016, this architecture has significantly improved translation quality across both high-resource and low-resource language pairs (Wu et al. 2016; Caswell & Liang 2020).

The choice of the ATA framework ensures consistent proficiency assessment through its systematic evaluation of accuracy, style, and language conventions (Koby & Champe 2013). This offers a detailed and relevant benchmark that more accurately reflects industry requirements than the evaluation approaches commonly used in previous studies in related fields. Through this experimental setup, we address three research questions:

1. How does the translation quality of LLM compare to dedicated NMT system when evaluated through professional translation standards represented by the ATA framework?
2. What specific error patterns emerge in both LLM and NMT translations for eng-chi and eng-ara language pairs?
3. What are the relative strengths and weaknesses of LLM versus NMT systems in performing MT?

2. Methodology

This section outlines our approach to comparing the translation quality of GPT-4o and Google Translate using the ATA framework. We begin by explaining the ATA certification process, followed by a description of our experimental design, including text selection, automatic evaluation, and manual assessment procedures. This methodology enables us to evaluate system-generated translations against professional standards, rather than relying solely on commonly used automated metrics.

2.1. The ATA certification process

The ATA certification examination requires candidates to translate two STs, each approximately 225–275 words in length. These texts are generally at university reading level but do not require highly specialized knowledge. They are designed to include manageable challenges in terminology and phraseology that skilled translators can address using comprehensive general dictionaries (Zou 2024).

Each translated text is evaluated in various aspects including errors that concern the form of the exam, meaning transfer and strategic errors, and mechanical errors. The ATA employs a points-addition scoring system where errors are categorized by severity and impact on the overall translation. Unlike point-deduction systems, ATA begins at zero (a theoretical perfect exam would have zero points) and adds points for each error, up to a maximum threshold of 18 (Zou et al. 2024). Less severe errors result in fewer points (1, 2, or 4), while more serious errors are assigned higher point penalties (8 or 16). To pass the exam, a candidate’s translations must accumulate fewer than 18 error points for each text. The ATA error annotation scheme will be further illustrated in Section 2.4.

Each ATA exam (i.e. two translated texts) is evaluated by two ATA-certified translators who have been vetted and trained as graders. Each grader assesses the exam independently, and their results are then compared for consistency. If the two graders agree, the evaluation is finalized. In cases of disagreement, a third grader is brought in to review. This rigorous process ensures that ATA-certified translators meet the high standards required for professional translation, demonstrating their ability to handle complex and diverse content. The selectivity of this process is reflected in the current pass rate of less than 20%, with fewer than 2,000 certified translators worldwide (American Translators Association n.d.).

2.2. Selection of source texts

For this study, two English STs were selected from previous ATA certification examinations with general topics. These exams were intended and considered a general professional-level assessment for translators of a certain language combination (for instance, eng-chi or eng-ara) in the US (Koby & Champe 2013). Each text is around 250 words long and contains about ten segments. As shown in Table 1, their readability index scores (Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level) are similar, and thus comparable.

Table 1: Description of the two STs

ST	Topic	Readability Index	Word count	Segment count
1	Philanthropy	12.2	245	12
2	Social Media	12.2	274	15
Total			519	27

Both GPT-4o and Google Translate were used to generate raw translations of the two STs into simplified Chinese and Arabic. For GPT-4o, we employed a zero-shot prompt: “You are a professional translator. Please translate the following text from English to Chinese/Arabic: <source text>.” Each system produced four translations: two for Chinese (GPTchi1, GPTchi2, GNMTchi1, GNMTchi2) and two for Arabic (GPTara1, GPTara2, GNMTara1, GNMTara2). The evaluation involved 27 target segments for each language pair.

2.3. Automatic assessment

For automatic assessment, this study employs the COMET framework (Rei et al. 2020), which has demonstrated stronger correlation with human judgment compared to traditional lexical-based metrics like BLEU (Papineni et al. 2002) and CHRF (Popović 2015). Recognizing that the quality of reference translations significantly impacts the reliability of automatic metrics (Freitag et al. 2020), we established a two-step reference preparation process. For each language pair (eng-chi and eng-ara), two ATA-certified professional translators were engaged in the process. One translator translated the texts from scratch, while the second translator validated and verified its quality. This meticulous approach ensures high-quality reference translations for reliable automatic assessment.

2.4. Manual assessment

The manual evaluation was conducted following the ATA certification grading framework (Koby 2015). This framework employs a points-addition scoring system where candidates must demonstrate proficiency across two texts. For certification, translations must receive fewer than 18 error points per text, with lower scores indicating better performance.

The evaluation of translated texts follows a comprehensive framework that assesses both error types and their severity. Translation errors fall into three main categories under the ATA error taxonomy. Form-related errors involve technical aspects of the submission, such as unfinished translations (UNF), illegible content (ILL), or instances of indecision where multiple translation options are provided (IND).

Meaning transfer or strategic errors negatively affect the clarity and utility of the target text. These encompass errors such as addition (A) and omission (O) of content, ambiguity (AMB) and cohesion (COH) issues, faithfulness (F) deviations from ST meaning, faux amis (false friend) (FA), overly literal translations (L), misunderstanding of ST (MU), terminology or word choice (T) issues, and text type errors (TT) including register (R) and style deviations, incorrect verb tense (VT) that alters meaning, as well as other meaning transfer issues (OTH-MT).

Mechanical errors negatively impact the overall quality of the target text. These include grammar (G) issues, which can be divided into two subcategories: syntax (phrase, clause, or sentence structure) (SYN) and word form or part of speech (WF/PS). Mechanical errors also encompass punctuation (P) mistakes and spelling or character (SP/CH) errors. Spelling or character errors can be further categorized into issues with diacritical marks/accents (D) and capitalization (C). Additionally, mechanical errors include usage (U) mistakes and other mechanical issues (OTH-ME).

The ATA scoring system assigns severity levels to translation errors, with corresponding point deductions of 1, 2, 4, 8, or 16 points. This approach reflects a graded scale to some extent similar to MQM (Multidimensional Quality Metrics), which categorizes errors by type and severity, typically labeled as minor, major, or critical, and assigns penalty weights accordingly (Lommel et al. 2014). In the ATA framework, mechanical errors (e.g. spelling, punctuation) are capped at a maximum of 4 points per instance, aligning with MQM's practice of treating such issues as lower severity. Spelling and character errors typically incur 1-point deductions, with a maximum of 2 points. Additionally, graders may award up to three quality points for exceptional translation choices, which are subtracted from the total error points, a feature not in standard MQM scoring but present in the ATA framework to recognize excellence. For

example, if a text contains four COH-2 (cohesion) errors at 2 points each, one L-2 (literalness) error at 2 points, and one COH-4 error at 4 points, the total error point for the text is $(4 + 1) \times 2 + 1 \times 4 = 14$ points. Since this falls below the 18-point threshold, the translation would receive a passing grade from that grader.

To assess the translation quality under professional certification standards, we conducted an experiment simulating the ATA certification examination process. Both GPT-4o and Google Translate were treated as certification candidates for eng-chi and eng-ara language pairs. The machine-generated translations were evaluated by ATA-certified graders following the standardized ATA grading framework. To ensure unbiased assessment, the graders were not informed that they were evaluating MTs, and they were requested to provide brief written feedback following each evaluation.

3. Results

3.1. Automatic evaluation results for the two systems

Based on COMET scores for the same set of STs (27 segments), both GPT-4o ($p = 0.0000224$) and Google Translate ($p = 0.000037$) perform significantly better in the eng-ara language pair compared to eng-chi. These p-values were calculated using a paired sample t-test, confirming that the differences are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). As shown in Table 2, the average COMET scores for eng-ara are 0.9665 for GPT-4o and 0.9724 for Google Translate, whereas for eng-chi, they are 0.8832 and 0.8878, respectively. While Google Translate shows slightly higher COMET scores than GPT-4o across both language pairs, these differences are not statistically significant at the segment level.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of COMET results

System & Language Pair	Mean	STD	Min	Max	Overall Score
GPT-4o (eng-chi)	0.8832	0.1140	0.5777	1.0000	0.8832
Google (eng-chi)	0.8878	0.1006	0.7060	1.0000	0.8878
GPT-4o (eng-ara)	0.9665	0.0447	0.8642	1.0000	0.9665
Google (eng-ara)	0.9724	0.0413	0.8475	1.0000	0.9724

As shown in Figure 1, both GPT-4o and Google Translate demonstrate strong performance across both language pairs, with COMET scores frequently exceeding 0.95. The eng-ara translations show notably consistent performance, with both systems maintaining high scores around 0.98-1.0 across most segments. In contrast, the eng-chi translations exhibit more variability. We observe pronounced performance drops in several segments where both systems show parallel decreases in performance, such as Segments 9 (with scores around 0.71), 11 (around 0.74), and 19 (around 0.75). These segments include figurative and context-dependent expressions that are especially challenging for MT.

For instance, Segment 11, “Rather than simply write checks for existing institutions, these ‘philanthrocapitalists’, as they are often called, aggressively seek to shape their operations”, contains the quoted term *philanthrocapitalists*, which carries a sarcastic or critical tone in its original context. It also includes idiomatic expressions like *write checks* and *shape their operations*, which require contextual understanding to avoid awkward or overly literal

translations. This pattern suggests that content demanding pragmatic or conceptual interpretation poses greater challenges in the eng-chi pair, regardless of the system used. These results from automatic assessment provide initial insights, but a comprehensive analysis integrating both automatic and manual assessment findings, along with detailed error analysis of challenging segments, will be presented in the discussion (Section 4).

Figure 1: Segment-wise COMET scores across MT systems and language pairs²

For eng-ara translations, Google Translate (green line) shows marginally higher COMET scores compared to GPT-4o (blue line) across most segments. This performance gap becomes more pronounced in specific segments, particularly in Segments 7 and 27, where Google Translate demonstrates consistently more stable performance across challenging segments. Statistical analysis confirms that the difference between Google Translate and GPT-4o is not statistically significant for the eng-ara pair, despite Google's generally higher scores.

For eng-chi translations, Google Translate (yellow line) and GPT-4o (red line) exhibit more varied performance patterns compared to the eng-ara pair. While Google Translate generally achieves higher scores in several segments, its superiority is less consistent. Both systems experience significant performance fluctuations across segments. The performance gap favors GPT-4o in segments like 16 and 23, where Google Translate's scores drop to approximately 0.77 while GPT-4o maintains higher scores around 0.88. Conversely, in segments such as 13 and 21, the gap shifts in favor of Google Translate, which performs significantly better than GPT-4o. This variability suggests that Google Translate and GPT-4o may handle different types of translation challenges with varying degrees of resilience in the eng-chi pair. Statistical testing confirms that the difference between Google Translate and GPT-4o is not statistically significant for the eng-chi pair, despite these visible segment-level variations.

² Note: Asterisk markers (★) indicate overall average scores for each system-language pair.

3.2. Manual evaluation results for the two systems

As shown in Table 3, the results of the manual evaluation based on the ATA framework reveal varying levels of translation capabilities across systems and language pairs³. Among all four system-language pair combinations tested in this experiment, only GPT-4o's eng-ara translations met the certification threshold, with both texts receiving acceptable scores from both graders. The remaining three combinations failed to meet ATA requirements for different reasons. GPT-4o's eng-chi translations performed adequately on Text 1 but substantially exceeded the error threshold on Text 2. Google Translate's eng-chi translations showed inconsistent quality on Text 1, with graders disagreeing on whether it met the threshold, while both found Text 2 acceptable. For eng-ara, Google Translate performed well on Text 1 but had mixed results on Text 2, with one grader finding it exceeded the threshold. These results indicate that while certain language-specific MT systems have made significant progress, the majority of MT outputs examined do not yet meet the professional translation standards required by ATA.

Table 3: Manual evaluation results across systems and language pairs

System & Language Pair	Text 1 Performance (% of threshold)		Text 2 Performance (% of threshold)		Certification Threshold Met?
	Grader 1	Grader 2	Grader 1	Grader 2	
GPT-4o eng-chi	22%	83%	122%	189%	No
Google eng-chi	67%	128%	11%	78%	No
GPT-4o eng-ara	61%	72%	61%	39%	Yes
Google eng-ara	33%	44%	72%	133%	No

Note: Values represent error points as a percentage of the ATA certification threshold (18 points). Percentages below 100% indicate performance within acceptable limits; values above 100% indicate performance exceeding error threshold limits.

The interrater agreement analysis reveals a 75% overall agreement rate, with graders concurring on six out of eight text evaluations. The magnitude of score differences varies between language pairs. For eng-ara translations, graders showed stronger scoring consistency, particularly in their evaluations of GPT-4o's outputs. In contrast, eng-chi evaluations exhibited larger scoring variations between graders, despite achieving the same 75% agreement rate on overall text quality judgments as the eng-ara evaluations.

The scores of eng-chi translations reveal intriguing performance patterns across both systems. GPT-4o exhibited considerable inconsistency in translation quality, with Text 1 performing within acceptable limits (22% and 83% of the threshold from Graders 1 and 2, respectively), while Text 2 significantly exceeded the error threshold (122% and 189%). This demonstrates that GPT-4o's error points more than doubled from Text 1 to Text 2, with Grader 2's assessment showing it exceeded the certification threshold by 89% on Text 2. Google Translate displayed a similarly variable performance, but with an inverse pattern. It struggled with Text 1 (67% and 128% of threshold) but performed better on Text 2 (11% and 78% of threshold). This means Google's performance on Text 2 was substantially better, with

³ Due to ATA certification protocols, this paper presents only relative scoring and comparative analyses. Complete grading data is available to researchers upon request, subject to confidentiality agreements.

Grader 1 annotating only 11% of the error threshold, a 56-percentage improvement over its Text 1 performance.

While the performance differences between systems are substantial in absolute terms, the small sample size in this study, limited to only two STs, limits the reliability of statistical significance testing. Broader evaluation with more texts would be necessary to establish statistically significant differences. Although neither system met the certification threshold for Chinese translation, the inverse performance patterns, where GPT-4o performing better on Text 1 but worse on Text 2, and Google Translate showing the opposite, suggest that translation quality in eng-chi pair is influenced by factors beyond surface-level text complexity. Furthermore, the contrasting patterns on the same texts indicate that each system encounters distinct challenges in eng-chi translation, aligning with findings from the automatic evaluation metrics in Section 3.1. These results point to the need for more fine-grained error analysis, as ST readability does not necessarily correlate with translation difficulty across different systems.

In eng-ara translations, GPT-4o exhibited consistent performance across STs of similar readability, effectively translating both Text 1 and Text 2 with relatively low error points (61–72% and 39–61% of threshold, respectively). Google Translate, despite effective translation for Text 1 (33–44% of threshold), showed significant performance deterioration in Text 2 (72–133% of threshold). This disparity between systems' performance also presents an interesting contrast with the automatic evaluation results. While COMET scores indicated uniformly high quality for both systems, with overall averages around 0.97, the manual assessment revealed more significant distinctions in translation quality. This discrepancy between automatic and human evaluation aligns with findings from Freitag et al. (2021), who demonstrated that professional translators with access to full document context identify substantially different quality rankings compared to those established through automatic metrics. Similarly, Läubli et al. (2020) found that claims of human-machine parity in translation were often based on evaluation designs that failed to capture the types of errors professional translators readily identify, particularly when evaluating full documents rather than isolated sentences.

3.3. Relationship between automatic and human evaluation

We examined the relationship between COMET scores and manual error annotations for each segment. As shown in Figure 2, there is an overall negative correlation between COMET scores and the average human grader scores by segment. This is expected since the grader scores represent accumulated error points and COMET scores represent translation quality automatically predicted. The strongest alignment between COMET scores and human grader scores appears to be GPT-4o eng-chi among the four combinations ($r=-0.44$, $p=0.022<0.05$), but with moderate correlation. Other three combinations, however, show both weak agreement between COMET and human evaluation and also lack statistical significance. COMET scores align more closely with human ratings for Chinese (especially GPT-generated translations) than Arabic.

Segments with multiple errors or high-severity errors, such as segment 13, which includes errors like SYN-4 and SYN-2 annotated by Grader 1, and L-8 by Grader 2, generally received lower COMET scores (e.g. 0.58). However, the analysis also revealed instances where segments flagged with many error annotations by ATA graders still received quite high COMET scores. For example, segment 23 received the largest average accumulated error points in the dataset (T-2 and MU-4 by Grader 1, and MU-16 by Grader 2) despite its high COMET score of 0.86. This pattern supports findings from previous research (Freitag et al. 2021;

Läubli et al. 2020), which demonstrate that automatic evaluation metrics, while useful, often fail to capture certain types of translation errors that professional translators deem significant. These results reinforce the growing consensus that automatic metrics should be complemented by human evaluation in professional translation workflows. Furthermore, a closer look at error annotations across both graders revealed distinct error patterns unique to each combination of MT system and language pair, underscoring the importance of detailed, system-specific analysis in MT evaluation.

Figure 2: Correlation between COMET scores and human evaluation across language pairs and systems

3.4. Predominant error patterns

In general, many human candidates do not fail the ATA certification exam because of one large error, but rather due to an accumulation of many smaller errors that lead to an overall flawed translation. This may be true of MT as well. Our analysis reveals distinctive error patterns across different translation systems and language pairs. These patterns provide valuable insights into areas where NMT and LLM systems continue to face challenges despite recent advances.

3.4.1. Comparative analysis of error types across systems and language pairs

To facilitate direct comparison across systems and language pairs, we present a comparative analysis of error distributions in Figure 3. This visualization demonstrates that Terminology (T) and Literalness (L) errors constitute the most significant portion of translation errors across all system-language pairs, with particularly high frequencies in Arabic translations. GPT-4o (eng-

ara) shows the highest percentage of Terminology errors at 40.91%, closely followed by Google (eng-ara) at 37.04%.

Language-specific patterns emerge clearly in the data. Arabic translations (regardless of system) show concentrated error distributions primarily in Terminology and Literalness, together accounting for 72.7% of GPT-4o’s errors and 74% of Google’s errors. Chinese translations, in contrast, exhibit more diverse error profiles spread across multiple categories.

System-specific patterns are evident in Chinese translations, with GPT-4o showing more Terminology (29.17%), Literalness (20.83%), and Omission (16.67%) errors out of the total 24 identified errors, while Google demonstrates significantly more Cohesion issues (36.84%) out of the total 19 identified errors. This notable divergence in Cohesion errors is unique to Google (eng-chi) translations, while being completely absent in both Arabic translation systems.

GPT-4o exhibits a more diverse error profile than Google across both languages, spreading across multiple error categories. This pattern suggests that different neural architectures may produce distinctly different error patterns even when processing the same STs.

The data further reveals specialized error tendencies. Word Form (WF) errors appear exclusively in GPT-4o (eng-ara) translations (9.09%), while Faithfulness (F) errors are unique to GPT-4o (eng-chi) translations (4.17%). Grammar (G) errors are only found in GPT-4o’s Arabic translations, and Style (ST) errors only in Google’s Arabic translations, highlighting how error patterns can be both system-dependent and language-dependent.

Figure 3: Composition of error types across systems and language pairs

3.4.2. Severity analysis across systems and language pairs

We also compared the severity levels of translation errors across different systems (GPT-4o and Google) and language pairs (eng-chi and eng-ara), categorized by error type. As illustrated in Figure 4, major to critical severity errors (Levels 8–16) are found exclusively in GPT-4o (eng-chi), specifically within the Misunderstanding (MU) category. This category has a notably

high average severity level of 10.00, substantially higher than any other error type across both systems.

GPT-4o’s Chinese output also shows a high average severity of 4.00 in the Literalness (L) category. According to the ATA grading framework, a misunderstanding error results from a mistranslated word, idiom, or misinterpreted sentence structure, while a literalness error occurs when a translation sticks too closely to the ST, producing awkward or incorrect phrasing (American Translators Association 2022). Both are classified as transfer errors, which negatively impact the accurate conveyance of meaning. These findings point to serious issues with semantic transfer in GPT-4o’s eng-chi translations, suggesting the model faces significant challenges in preserving the ST’s meaning in this language pair.

Figure 4: Average severity level by system-language pair and error type

Google’s eng-chi translations show a more balanced distribution of error severity across categories. The most notable issue appears in the Terminology (T) category, with an average severity of 4.00, followed by Misunderstanding (MU) at 3.33 and Ambiguity (AMB) at 3.00, indicating moderate to major concerns. While these are also classified as meaning transfer errors, Google does not display extreme outliers in any single category, unlike GPT-4o. The terminology issues in Google’s output tend to occur at the word or phrase level, suggesting localized problems rather than broader semantic breakdowns.

Minor to moderate errors (Levels 1–2) are the most common in Arabic translations across both systems. For GPT-4o, 95.45% of errors fall within this range, while Google shows a full 100% of its errors at these levels. Compared to eng-chi translations, eng-ara outputs exhibit consistently lower severity scores, suggesting that this language pair may be handled more effectively overall. However, as previously noted, ten 2-point errors still total 20 points, enough to fail an exam. This suggests that a high volume of low-severity errors can still significantly impact overall quality.

While Terminology and Literalness errors are common across systems and language pairs, their severity varies considerably. For GPT-4o’s eng-chi translations, Terminology errors are relatively minor to moderate (1.86), whereas Literalness errors are significantly more severe, averaging 4.00 (major). Conversely, Google’s eng-chi output shows the reverse trend. Terminology errors are major (4.00), while Literalness errors are moderate (2.00). In the case

of eng-ara, both GPT-4o and Google exhibit minor to moderate severity in these categories, suggesting that these issues are generally less problematic in this language pair.

Beyond these shared error types, distinct patterns emerge for specific system-language pairs. For instance, Syntax errors appear mostly in GPT-4o's eng-chi output, with an average severity of 3.33 (moderate to major), while Word Form errors are unique to GPT-4o's eng-ara translations at a lower average severity of 1.50 (minor to moderate). Meanwhile, Cohesion (2.60) and Ambiguity (3.00) errors predominantly occur in Google's eng-chi translations, indicating moderate to major impact. These variations highlight how different systems handle linguistic challenges in distinct ways. We will provide qualitative examples evaluating both error type and severity to better understand each system's translation quality and limitations in the discussion section.

In summary, although GPT-4o's performance in translating eng-ara met the ATA certification threshold in this experiment, it still has several areas for improvement. The system struggles with contextual awareness, often producing literal translations that fail to convey the intended meaning. Terminological accuracy is another challenge, which was mistranslated due to a lack of context sensitivity. The system also needs to handle idiomatic expressions more effectively to ensure cultural and linguistic appropriateness. Grammatical errors such as incorrect forms and inconsistent phrasing further undermine the translation quality. To address these issues, GPT-4o could benefit from enhanced context modeling, better handling of idiomatic language, and training on more diverse datasets that emphasize cultural nuances and grammatical accuracy.

4. Discussion

Our analysis in Section 3 revealed distinct performance patterns across language pairs. For eng-chi translations, both automatic and manual evaluations showed that Google Translate and GPT-4o excel at different segments, with each system demonstrating unique strengths. For eng-ara translations, both systems performed at a consistently higher level overall, though they still encountered some common challenges with certain segments. This section presents a qualitative analysis of representative examples that illustrate these patterns.

4.1. Complementary strengths in eng-chi translation across systems

The segment-level analysis of COMET results in Section 3.1. (Figure 1) showed that GPT-4o and Google Translate excel at translating different segments in Chinese. This pattern was reinforced by our manual evaluation in Section 3.2., which found contrasting performance patterns between GPT-4o and Google Translate on the same texts. Our error analysis in Section 3.4. further revealed different error profiles, with GPT-4o producing primarily Terminology (29.17%), Literalness (20.83%), and Omission (16.67%) errors, while Google Translate exhibited substantially more Cohesion issues (36.84%). These quantitative findings are illustrated through the following representative examples.

4.1.1. Example illustrating GPT-4o’s advantage

Example (1) in Table 4 (Segment 7) illustrates how the two systems handle the translation of the same source sentence “Every year, an estimated \$40 billion is diverted from the public treasury through charitable donations.” with different word choices.

GPT-4o rendered this as “每年，估计有 400 亿美元通过慈善捐赠从公共财政中转移出去。” (‘Every year, an estimated \$40 billion is **transferred** through charitable donations from public treasury.’). In contrast, Google Translate produced “每年，估计有 400 亿美元通过慈善捐款从国库中挪用。” (‘Every year, an estimated \$40 billion is **misappropriated** through charitable donations from national treasure.’).

Although COMET scores showed only a marginal difference (0.90 for GPT-4o vs. 0.89 for Google Translate), human evaluation identified a more pronounced disparity in translation quality. The ATA graders identified no errors in GPT-4o’s translation, whereas both graders marked Google Translate’s version with a T-4 error (terminology error of severity level 4). The critical issue was Google’s word choice of 挪用 (‘misappropriated’) for *diverted*, which introduces an unwarranted negative connotation of financial misconduct that is not present in the ST.

Table 4: Segment-level outputs and ATA grader feedback for Example (1) in the eng-chi pair

System	TT	COMET	Grader 1	Grader 2
ST	Every year, an estimated \$40 billion is diverted from the public treasury through charitable donations.			
GPT-4o (back-translation)	Every year, an estimated \$40 billion is transferred through charitable donations from public treasury.	0.90		
Google (back-translation)	Every year, an estimated \$40 billion is misappropriated through charitable donations from national treasure.	0.89	T-4 <i>Diverted</i> was not translated correctly in this context.	T-4 被转移出去 (‘is transferred out’)

4.1.2. Example illustrating Google Translate’s advantage

Example (2) in Table 5 (Segment 23) examines the two systems’ different approaches to translating a rhetorically complex sentence: “The ignorant comments about historically complex subjects are laughable at best and frightening at worst.”

GPT-4o translated this as “关于历史上复杂问题的无知评论至多令人发笑，至少令人害怕。” (‘Ignorant comments about historically complex problems are at most hilarious and at least terrifying.’). Google Translate produced “关于历史复杂主题的无知评论充其量是可

笑的，最坏的情况是令人恐惧的。” (‘Ignorant comments about historically complex subjects are laughable at best and terrifying under the worst situation’).

Interestingly, while GPT-4o achieved a higher COMET score (0.86 compared to Google Translate’s 0.75), the human evaluation revealed significant issues in GPT-4o’s translation. For this example, GPT-4o received the largest accumulative error points from the two graders combined in our dataset. The ATA graders identified multiple serious errors in GPT-4o’s translated version. Grader 1 noted a moderate T-2 error (terminology error of severity level 2) for mistranslating *subjects* as *problems*. Grader 1 also identified a major MU-4 error (misunderstanding error of severity level 4) for reversing the meaning of *at best* and *at worst* in the translation. Grader 2 assessed the entire sentence as having a critical misunderstanding error (MU-16), suggesting instead “轻则令人发笑，重则令人恐惧” (‘At the mildest, it’s hilarious; at the worst, it’s terrifying’).

In contrast, Google Translate’s version received only one moderate error mark: a cohesion error of severity level 2 (COH-2) from one grader, who suggested using “往好里说，往坏里说” (‘say it at best, say it at worst’) to improve the flow and naturalness of the Chinese expression.

Table 5: Segment-level outputs and ATA grader feedback for Example (2) in the eng-chi pair

System	TT	COMET	Grader 1	Grader 2
<p>ST The ignorant comments about historically complex subjects are laughable at best and frightening at worst.</p>				
GPT-4o (back-translation)	Ignorant comments about historically complex problems are at most hilarious and at least terrifying.	0.86	T-2 <i>Topic</i> was translated as <i>problem</i> . MU-4 <i>At best</i> and <i>at worst</i> were reversed.	MU-16 轻则令人发笑，重则令人恐惧。 (‘At the mildest, it’s hilarious; at the worst, it’s terrifying.’)
Google (back-translation)	Ignorant comments about historically complex subjects are laughable at best and terrifying under the worst situation .	0.75		COH-2 往好里说，往坏里说 (‘Say it at best, say it at worst’)

The two examples above also resonate with the findings from Section 3.3, that automatic metrics might not always align with human assessment. For Example (1), despite GPT-4o and Google Translate’s similarly high COMET scores (0.90 vs. 0.89), human evaluators identified major terminology errors in Google’s translation that are contextually wrong and significantly impact the meaning transfer from the ST to the TT. For Example (2), although GPT-4o received a much higher COMET score than Google (0.86 vs 0.75), human evaluators identified moderate terminology errors and critical misunderstanding errors that

Table 6: Segment-level outputs and ATA grader feedback for Example (3) in the eng- ara pair

System	TT	COMET	Grader 1	Grader 2
ST	Rather than simply write checks for existing institutions, these “philanthrocapitalists”, as they are often called, aggressively seek to shape their operations.			
GPT-4o (back-translation)	Instead of merely writing checks to existing institutions, these ‘philanthrocapitalists’... in a hostile manner strive to shape the operations of those institutions.	0.88	L-2 عدواني (‘writing checks’) – literal rendering; pragmatic force obscured.	T-2 عدواني (‘in a hostile manner’) – the translation meant an active or impulsive way
Google (back-translation)	And instead of merely writing checks to existing institutions, these ‘philanthrocapitalists’... seek to shape their operations forcefully .	0.90	L-2 عدواني (‘writing checks’) – same literalism.	L-2 بقوة (‘forcefully’) – misses sense of <i>proactively / assertively</i> .

4.2.2. Example (4): Collocations, omissions & connotation drift in Segment 13

The source sentence for Example (4) is “Moving away from a thoughtfully researched narrative to conform to the technological limits of media platforms takes us away from **scholarship** into **sound bites** and **statements of fact without context**.”

GPT-4o translated this as “الابتعاد عن السرد المدروس بعناية للتماشي مع القيود التكنولوجية لمنصات” (‘Moving away from the carefully studied narrative to keep pace with media-platform technological constraints distances us from academic research toward concise clips and realistic statements devoid of context.’). Google Translate produced “إن الابتعاد عن السرد المدروس بعناية من أجل التوافق مع الحدود” (‘To move away from the carefully studied narrative to align with the technological limits of media platforms takes us far from scientific studies to audio clips and realistic data without context.’).

Both systems falter on three fronts: over-specific renderings of *scholarship*, incomplete treatment of *sound bites*, and misconstrual of *statements of fact*. Table 7 contrasts the Arabic outputs with the ATA graders’ notes to show how these low-severity errors accumulate.

Table 7: Segment-level outputs and ATA grader feedback for Example (4) in the eng-ara pair.

System	TT	COMET	Grader 1	Grader 2
ST	Moving away from a thoughtfully researched narrative to conform to the technological limits of media platforms takes us away from scholarship into sound bites and statements of fact without context .			
GPT-4o (back-translation)	Moving away from the carefully studied narrative to keep pace with media-platform technological constraints distances us from academic research toward concise clips and realistic statements devoid of context.	0.95	<p>T-2 البحث الأكاديمي (‘academic research’) – overly narrow.</p> <p>O-2 مقاطع مختصرة (‘concise clips’) – omits the sound element.</p> <p>T-2 تصريحات واقعية (‘realistic statements’) – misrepresents <i>facts</i>.</p>	<p>T-2 تصريحات واقعية (‘realistic statements’) – the translation does not convey the intended meaning.</p>
Google (back-translation)	To move away from the carefully studied narrative to align with the technological limits of media platforms takes us far from scientific studies to audio clips and realistic data without context.	0.97	<p>T-2 الدراسات العلمية (‘scientific studies’) – overly specific.</p> <p>O-2 مقاطع صوتية (‘audio clips’) – captures sound but omits brevity.</p> <p>T-2 بيانات واقعية (‘realistic data’) – misconstrues <i>statements of fact</i>.</p> <p>T-2 التوافق (‘to align’) – inaccurate for <i>to conform</i>.</p>	<p>T-2 التوافق (‘to align’) – failed to convey the full meaning.</p> <p>MU-2 مقاطع صوتية (‘audio clips’) – what is meant is brief or concise excerpts.</p> <p>T-2 بيانات واقعية (‘realistic data’) – not the original meaning</p>

This segment reveals three recurring Arabic MT vulnerabilities. First, terminological over-specification (T-2): both systems translate *scholarship* as *البحث الأكاديمي* ('academic research') or *الدراسات العلمية* ('scientific studies'), terms that confine the broad notion of scholarship to academic or scientific research; graders recommend the wider phrase *المنهج العلمي* ('scholarly approach'). Second, partial omission (O-2): GPT-4o's *مقاطع مختصرة* ('concise clips') deletes the *sound* element, whereas Google's *مقاطع صوتية* ('audio clips') retains *sound* but ignores brevity—neither fully captures *sound bite*. Third, connotation drift in fact-rendering (T-2): both systems choose *تصريحات/بيانات واقعية* ('realistic statements/data'), where *واقعية* signals *realistic* rather than *factual*, and *بيانات* might suggest either data or formal communiqués. The graders propose *تقديم حقائق* ('presentation of facts') to restore the intended sense of context-free fact statements. Collectively, these issues, narrow term mapping, headword omission, and connotative mismatch, reinforce the broader trend noted in Section 3.4.: Arabic MT output is dominated by low-severity Terminology, Literalness, and Omission errors that automatic metrics overlook, yet their accumulation materially degrades professional-level adequacy.

5. Conclusion

This study presents an evaluation of MT quality using the ATA certification framework, revealing several important findings about the current capabilities and limitations of both LLM-based and NMT-based translation systems. While neural-based automatic metrics like COMET have shown stronger correlation with human judgment compared to traditional lexical-based metrics, our analysis reveals that such automatic metrics may overestimate MT quality and fail to capture critical errors that professional translators identify, particularly in the evaluation of nuanced rhetorical expressions and idiomatic language use in translations. These findings underscore the continued importance of incorporating human assessment into professional translation workflows.

Among the four system-language pair combinations evaluated, GPT-4o demonstrated superior performance in eng-ara translation for both required texts in this experiment. The remaining three combinations - GPT-4o's eng-chi, Google Translate's eng-chi, and Google Translate's eng-ara translations - all accumulated high error points from graders for certain texts, indicating that they do not yet achieve the translation standards required for professional translators.

Our error analysis uncovered distinct patterns between systems and language pairs. For eng-chi translations, GPT-4o and Google Translate exhibited notably different error distributions. GPT-4o's errors concentrated in three main categories: Terminology, Literalness, and Omission, while Google Translate showed a different pattern dominated by Cohesion errors, followed by equal proportions of Literalness and Misunderstanding errors. In contrast, eng-ara translations from both systems displayed remarkably similar error patterns, primarily characterized by Terminology and Literalness errors. These variations suggest that translation challenges extend beyond mere text complexity, potentially reflecting distinct linguistic characteristics inherent to each language pair and the different approaches employed by each system in handling these challenges.

While this study offers valuable insights into the current state of machine translation, it has certain limitations. Due to funding constraints, our manual assessment using ATA-certified graders was limited to two texts for each language pair and MT system. Future research would

benefit from expanding the dataset and incorporating more extensive automatic assessment metrics to validate these findings across a broader range of texts and contexts.

Looking forward, several promising avenues exist for improving LLM translation performance. The implementation of retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) and advanced prompt engineering techniques could enhance translation quality by allowing for better tone control, bias mitigation, and integration of domain-specific terminology. Additionally, the potential for fine-tuning LLMs using existing translation memories could further improve their performance on specific translation tasks.

These findings contribute to our understanding of the strengths and limitations of current MT systems while highlighting areas for future development. The distinct error patterns observed between systems and language pairs warrant further investigation, particularly in understanding how linguistic characteristics and system architectures interact to influence translation quality. As MT technology continues to evolve, maintaining a balanced approach that combines automatic metrics with professional human assessment remains crucial for ensuring translation quality in professional contexts.

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The Knight in the Panther's Skin: Comparing corpora of image metaphors in the source text and its translations, spanning different cultural or temporal contexts

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Abstract

The corpus-based study analyzes image metaphors in the translations of Shota Rustaveli's 12th-century Georgian poem by Marjory Wardrop (20th-century British English) and Lyn Coffin (21st-century American English) drawing on the theoretical frameworks of cognitive linguistics, cognitive poetics, cognitive translation studies, social and anthropological theories. The study incorporates Atran's (1998) anthropological theory, lapping the phenomenon of adaptive radiation (AR) over the poetic image metaphor translation. Our findings position translation as an act of cultural-cognitive evolution, introducing AR as a model for poetic metaphor translation. By analyzing 37 image metaphors in 74 translations, we explore how mappings in the source and target texts interact within image clusters and with the underlaid image schemas (CONTAINER, PATH, FORCE). We summed up four critical pitfalls that AR shifts entail. The study contributes to cognitive metaphor studies, as well as corpus-based cognitive translation studies, situating translation as an act of cultural and cognitive evolution.

Keywords: *cognitive translation studies; corpus linguistics; poetry; image metaphors*

1. Introduction

The present corpus-based study presents an experimental analytical methodology focused on translated poetic image metaphors (IMs) in Shota Rustaveli's 12th-century Georgian poem by Marjory Wardrop (prosaic translation, 20th-century British English) and Lyn Coffin (poetic translation, 21st-century American English). While conceptual metaphors were given more spotlight, there is a dearth of corpus-based studies of poetic image metaphors. The study draws methodological inspiration from corpus-based approaches to metaphor analysis (e.g. Semino 2008 and Steen et al. 2010), however, the diachronic dimension of the translated poetic image metaphors in our analysis diverges from the predominant synchronic focus of earlier cognitive linguistic studies. The rationale behind the selection of the medieval poem and its translations is to examine translational procedures carried out across two different epochs, from the perspective of cultural, linguistic, and temporal variables. We draw on Atran's (1998) theory of anthropological adaptive radiation, extrapolating it to metaphor translation and positioning translators as agents who creatively adapt cognitive structures to diverse cultural and temporal contexts. This approach offers a new perspective on image metaphor (IM) translation by conceptualizing it as an evolutionary process rather than a static linguistic transfer. From a methodological point of view, we selected 37 IMs that universally contain the concept of *tear* in order to focus on the image's generative mapping capacity in the source language and its two translated versions (a total of 74 IMs across the two target texts (TT)). The key insights

into metaphor translation theories reveal a theoretical divide between descriptive and prescriptive approaches. According to Nida & Taber (1969/1982: 107), all figurative expressions involved in the transfer process undergo: (a) shifts from figurative to nonfigurative usage, (b) shifts from one type of figurative expression to another, and (c) nonfigurative expressions changing to figurative ones. Boase-Beier (2018: 199) argues against using “stylistic non-equivalence as a means to judge the translation,” suggesting instead studying and describing the changes made in the translation to explore “how these affect the reading of the text.” Boase-Beier (2018: 204) sees both stylistics and translation studies as typically descriptive rather than prescriptive. These approaches bring into focus translation theoreticians: Newmark (1988), who is “strongly prescriptive” with normative procedures in particular circumstances, and Toury, by contrast, who is “purely descriptive” in accordance with his focus on norms: “what translators do, not what they should do” (as cited in Dickins 2018: 227–28). As metaphor translation includes various strategies or shifts, Toury (1995: 109, as cited in Dickins 2018: 228) “recognises the possibility of nonmetaphors being translated by metaphors, as well as other tropes, such as simile.” Newmark (1988: 53–58) also recognizes translation of metaphor by simile and sense. Tabakowska’s (1997) analysis of spatial and temporal structures in Robert Frost’s “Nothing Gold Can Stay” and its Polish translation suggests a cognitive linguistics perspective on poetry translation; she posits that the shift from metaphor to simile, or between image schemas, impacts the perceptual experience of the poem. The perspectives of linguists and translators on metaphor translation vary significantly. For instance, Dickins (2018: 227) notes that Newmark’s metaphor categories are unified more by their attempt to solve translation problems than by their theoretical coherence.

Halverson (2007: 114) points out that the tentative S-universals underscore that shifts impacting image schemas include standardization/sanitization, simplification, increasing conventionality, and convergence; metaphors also undergo modulation as a type of shift. Simplification is one of the translation universals, identified among several others: explicitation, disambiguation, conventionalization, avoidance of repetition, exaggeration of target language features (referred to as “normalization” by Baker (1997: 183), as cited in Malmkjær (2018: 21)).

Shuttleworth (2017: 179) extensively studied translational “behaviour” of IMs in scientific texts by exploring them in the multilingual corpus. He verified that “a number of IM expressions are retained essentially unchanged” in the 45 examples, while “minor rewordings do not affect the metaphorical expression in any significant way, and the mapping is preserved unmodified.” While minor rewordings may not affect the mappings of mental images in scientific texts, and may instead enhance translation fluency, the mapping equivalence in his findings suggests a certain universality of mental images across languages, despite their general semantic distance.

Van den Broeck (1981: 77) identifies three possibilities for metaphor translation: Translation *sensu stricto*, Substitution, and Paraphrase or “plain speech.” Translation frequently results in “down-toning” (Dickins 2018: 229; Dickins 2005: 256–58), producing a toned-down version of the original. Laviosa (1998: 474–75), drawing on Kenny’s findings, explains this phenomenon as a “sanitized version of the original.” Kenny hypothesized that linguistic “down-toning” removes the emotional intensity of metaphors, rendering them psychologically divergent when literal and figurative meanings lose connection. Dickins observes that the metaphorical force—whether strong or weak plays a crucial role in translation. Strong metaphors pose significant challenges, whereas weak metaphors are typically less problematic (Dickins 2005: 229–30; Dickins 2018: 228–29). The reduction or

weakening (simplification, down-toning, plain speech) in translation often leads to emotional neutrality.

Based on the above arguments, one might draw a symbolic parallel between dead metaphors and translated metaphors, arguing that the “deadness” in translation results largely from the loss of connection between literal and figurative meanings. The ongoing theoretical debates, based on empirical findings, still leave many questions ambiguous regarding the ‘down-toning’ of metaphors in translation. Poirier (2003: 405), distinguishing phraseological units from metaphors, argues that phraseological units (PUs) are primarily defined by their lexicalized meaning, whereas metaphors do not necessarily entail lexicalization. Following Delisle (1993), who distinguishes two types of metaphors that are relevant to PUs: dead metaphors and frozen metaphors, Poirier (2003: 406) notes that in both cases, the metaphorical nature of a PU’s meaning does not contradict its lexicalization; dead metaphors are translated as lexical units rather than metaphorical expressions. Frozen metaphors, which can be considered PUs due to their fixed, lexicalized meaning, should be translated based on their precise delimitation within the PUs. Given that our research focuses on the challenges of translating IMs, the non-lexicalized nature of poetic metaphor is to be highlighted.

2. Interdisciplinary perspectives of image schema theory

Cognitive linguists and cognitive scientists have developed models of linguistic and cognitive behavior, including image schemas, conceptual metaphors, and prototypes (Lakoff & Johnson 1999: 119). Lakoff & Johnson coined the term *image schemas* in 1987, as Lakoff (1987: 280–81, 291) claims, since language is rooted in cognition and possesses a conceptualizing capacity its structure “uses the same devices used to structure cognitive models, i.e., (a by which are understood in terms of bodily functioning.”

Image schemas, as foundational mental structures derived from bodily experience, such as CONTAINER, UP/DOWN, or OVER/UNDER, serve as basic templates for understanding spatial, temporal, and metaphorical relationships. However, some spatial image schemas are “bipolar and bivalent” (Johnson 1987; Kövecses 2002: 36). As Johnson (1987: 118) stresses, “the image schema is not an image. It is, instead, a means of structuring particular experiences schematically, so as to give order and connectedness to our perceptions and conceptions.”

These recurring structures give order and connectedness to human perceptions and conceptions (Johnson 1987: 118). They arise from human perceptual interactions, bodily experiences, and cognitive operations (Johnson 1987: 122), and are claimed to be established during early childhood (Mandler & Cánovas 2014; Tay 2021: 161). Stockwell’s (2019: 14–25) interdisciplinary approach to cognitive poetics bridges literary and linguistic theories. He draws on the foundational theories of Gestalt psychology (Boring 1950; Beardslee & Wertheimer 1958), and cognitive linguistics (Lakoff & Johnson 1980; Gibbs & Colston 2006; Langacker 1987, 1990, 1991). Stockwell’s (2019: 18) analysis employs the Gestalt principle of figure and ground, reflecting on the image schemas. It explores how the figure (moving entity / trajector) moves or interacts with the ground (stationary entity / landmark). However, as he posits, in poetry, despite the same image schemas, due to the elegant and subtle variations and poetic elaborations, “the literary expressions of commonly understood image schemas are interestingly and poetically varied” (Stockwell 2019: 18).

An interdisciplinary approach to basic-level structures and image schemas supports the idea that they function as universal cognitive tools across disciplines, from cognitive linguistics to sociology and anthropology, demonstrating their broad applicability in understanding human cognition, perception, and social behavior. According to Johnson (1987), Lakoff (1987), and Lakoff & Johnson (1999), there are at least two kinds of structures in our preconceptual bodily experiences: (a) basic-level structure: basic-level categories result from our Gestalt perception, capacity for bodily movement, and ability to form rich mental images; (b) image schemas. Johnson (1987: 11, 2005: 20) links image schemas as basic template structures to Gestalt structures, asserting that they integrate sensory-motor experiences into structured wholes, while Lakoff (1987: 272) views them as structured wholes composed of logically configured parts. Johnson uses a Kantian proposition that the image schema is preconceptual and its structure fits the general concepts to derive specific images; he also uses Kantian examples of schemas, though a Kantian schema is a mindful framework that helps sensory experience perceive the concept, while Johnson's image-schema is a repetitive, continuous process (Johnson 1987: 62).

Tay (2021: 161) relates the image schema theory to Gestalt theory as developed by Wertheimer (1938) and to Kantian schemas (1990), as well as other cognitive linguistic cornerstones, e.g., Langacker's (1991) cognitive grammar, Talmy's (1988) force dynamics, and Grady's (1997) primary metaphor theory.

Bourdieu's (1991: 52–65) Habitus theory describes how an individual's mental structures, or schemes, are shaped by social and cultural experiences. According to Bourdieu, an individual's life experience schematically integrates social structures into a general disposition. The concept of Habitus is defined as a combination of dispositions, tastes, and physical practices. Habitus denotes a "system of durable, transposable dispositions, structured structures predisposed to function as structuring structures" (Bourdieu 1991: 53). Bourdieu's (2010: 528) Habitus theory, understood here as disposition and closely linked to Gestalt, aligns with Johnson's (1987) concept of embodiment. Johnson (1987) defines embodiment as a formative model for schematic structures underlaid behavior and habitual patterns. Moreover, the patterned schemes in Habitus theory guide behavior and its interpretation in social situations through the sensory-motor system. Comparably, image schemas in cognitive linguistics structure the perceptual experience of concepts and generate cognitive patterns of time-spatial concepts.

Another theoretical domain that bridges social and linguistic theories on image schemas is cognitive anthropology. For example, Kimmel's (2005) study "Culture regained. Situated and compound image schemas" reflects on Johnson's approach that image schemas are not "fleshless skeletons" but can be conceived with qualities such as "our experience, understanding, and thought" (Kimmel 2005: 8), and expands on Bourdieu's (1977: 90–92) ethnography of the Algerian Kabyles, where gendered homologues in postures, practices, and social spaces define male and female schemas (though without using the term *image schema*). As Kimmel (2005: 298) notes: "Bourdieu's theory of embodied cultural knowledge couched in terms of generative principles called Habitus and concretely manifested in bodily hexis, i.e., posture and movement patterns – sees ritual and everyday activities as continuous structural exercises for particular schemas."

Social theory, cognitive linguistics, and cultural anthropology share critique of formal and structural linguistic paradigms, while putting the emphasis on the social, cultural, and embodied dimensions of cognition and language: Bourdieu (1991: 109–111), from his social studies perspective, was skeptical of formal and structural linguistics, which overlooked the

social and political contexts of language formation and use; Lakoff & Johnson (1999: 107) point out, that “the development of the field of Cognitive Linguistics has turned up ever more phenomena that cannot be accounted for by the formal-syntax-and-semantics paradigm.”

3. Anthropological extrapolations on conceptual and image metaphors, cognitive poetics and translation theories

To explore broader avenues for the poetic IM translation we take Kimmel’s (2005) idea that cognitive linguistics should be more concerned with social and cultural contexts as they influence cognitive processes and generate image schemas. In this regard, Atran’s (1998) study “Folk biology and the anthropology of science. Cognitive universals and cultural particulars” can be extrapolated upon both Habitus and image schema theories, extending the concept of cognitive universal to Habitus as “internalized structures, common schemes of perception, conception and action” (Bourdieu 1990: 60) and image schemas as structured cognitive models of embodied cognitive experience (Lakoff 1987: 272) and as templates for perception, interaction, and action (Johnson 1987: 11, 2005: 20). Atran’s observations resonate with the poetic mental image mappings and their translation; Atran situates cognitive universals within an evolutionary framework, viewing them as evolving adaptive tools that enable evolutionary cultural flexibility across ecological contexts: “[T]he uniform structure of taxonomic knowledge, under diverse socio-cultural learning conditions, arguably results from domain-specific cognitive processes that are panhuman” (Atran 1998: 30). Drawing parallels, Lakoff and Johnson also argue that our preconceptual bodily experiences operate at least two kinds of structures, including basic level structures and image schemas.

Since cognitive universals provide consistent ways of perceiving, categorizing, and reasoning about the world as shared foundational mental structures, they can be conceptually perceived as embodiment of both basic level structures and the image schemas. As Atran explores, culture, underpinned by cognitive universals as tools of evolutionary adaptation, is flexible to adapt to different ecological contexts; he introduces the term *adaptive radiation* to describe the evolutionary diversification of organisms into various forms that exploit different ecological niches. Adaptive radiation showcases that a core structure (the ancestral species) gives rise to variations (the new species), which are specialized adaptations to environmental demands. As a result, organisms exhibit broad patterns of adaptation to environmental constraints reflecting general morphological and behavioral adaptations to life in various habitats while keeping the core structure. We extrapolate this process to the process of poetic IM translation. The basic level structures and image schemas, as cognitive universals, are not culturally specific. Most importantly, in translation they both reveal adaptability and serve as adaptable tools of cultures. Hence, we can analogize the processes in evolutionary biology and translational elaborations of IMs on the basis of the comparability of cultural particulars underlaid by cognitive universals and the final outputs.

It is important to acknowledge that cultural elaborations in translation do not always lead to aesthetic simplification or down-toning. As Stockwell (2019: 18) argues, the principle of universality lies amidst diversity, highlighting both the creative and cross-pollinating nature of translation. Although the mapping is a general cognitive process, following Stockwell (2019: 18), “the creative elaboration of image schemas can be seen as the striking or unsettling re-cognition of familiar patterns: that is, defamiliarization,” the latter term taken from the Russian Formalists. Assumably, poetic elaborations as creative processes shall be considered

as extra aesthetic structural property of cognitive mapping. As Mathews (1959: 67) states: “One thing seems clear: to translate a poem whole is to compose another poem” (as cited in Nida 1964: 131), suggesting that a poet and a translator go through not only a cognitive, but also a creative performance that reshape, extend, and reinterpret mental images based on their cognitive and cultural contexts. Just as biological species evolve by adapting to new ecological niches, poetic metaphors evolve through translation, maintaining core structures while adapting to new cultural and linguistic environments. The processing of the poetic IMs in translation into the new poetic variants can be conceptualized as AR. It denotes the extra aesthetic property of poetic translation and an extra structure of image mapping as cognitive-creative poetic elaboration of mappings, we borrow Atran’s term *adaptive radiation*, which implies, more broadly, cultural evolution through translation.

Image schemas have conventionally been studied within the framework of conceptual metaphor theory. As Lakoff (1987: 146) states

Neither image schemata nor their metaphorical extensions exist only as propositions. They can be propositionally represented, but this does not capture their full reality as structures of our embodied understanding. This applies also to metaphors whose target and source domains are partially structured by image schemata.

The conceptual metaphors are categorized according to their cognitive function as structural, orientational, and ontological metaphors (Lakoff & Johnson 1980; Johnson 1987; Lakoff 1987; Kövecses 2002). By definition, the conceptual metaphors establish connections between two domains, mapping abstract structures in the source domain to conceptual structures in the target domain.

Brandt & Brandt (2005: 128) point out that “linguistic artefacts” are produced by means of the general cognitive capacities of the humans, therefore, what cognitive approaches can add to the study of literature and literary theory “is a new focus on the shared mental processes involved in and artistically expressed in literary language use.” In her much broader approach to tropes, Boase-Beier (2018:200 quoting Turner 1996: 5, 7–8) highlights that much of cognitive poetics, an approach to poetics that explores how the mind operates, is rounded in the idea that the “literary mind” underpins all human thought. These observations align with the cognitive approaches in translation studies (Rojo & Ibarretxe-Antuñano 2013) which explore how image schemas and conceptual metaphors guide meaning construction across languages, reinforcing Brandt & Brandt’s (2005) view that literature expresses shared mental processes.

Lakoff (1987, 1993: 229) distinguishes IMs from conceptual metaphors as a different class of metaphors; they “function to map one conventional mental image onto another.” This perspective is further layered by Lakoff & Turner (2006: 124), positing that IMs map a rich mental image to another rich mental image. Image schemas, on the other hand, lack richness, being general structures. Although Kövecses (2002: 50–51) and Shuttleworth (2017: 175) question image metaphor’s relatedness with image schemas, maintaining that they are not based on image schemas and propositional knowledge but on rich images primarily operating

through perceptual resemblance,¹ we find that the rich images may secondarily interact with underlaid image schemas. This aligns with Lakoff (1987: 221) stating that “image metaphors are nonetheless structure mappings at the conceptual level. As such they can interact in interesting ways,” and “image metaphors still involve conceptual metaphor” (Brandt 2009: 80); Importantly, as Kimmel (2002: 37) also observes, image schemas and rich images “flow into one another, varying with the amount of detail.” Moreover, Gibbs & Colston (2006), whose embodiment principle covers poetic image metaphors, argue that metaphor comprehension requires embodied simulations of schemas (e.g. PATH, CONTAINER), i.e. recruiting of sensorimotor schemas. IMs can evoke and reinforce metaphors that connect different domains through conceptual knowledge and logical structures (Lakoff & Turner 2006: 117). As far as image schemas and their metaphorical projections are primary patterns of the “blending” (Lakoff 1987: 147), and blending also attributes to the image metaphors, we assume that even the “purest” image metaphors rely on latent schemas. Revisiting Lakoff’s (1987: 221) “hourglass-waist” metaphor, overly quoted elsewhere, reveals that perceptual resemblance is schema-guided, e.g. of SYMMETRY and BALANCE. Comparably, in the example where Rustaveli maps *agate* → *eyelashes*, perceptual resemblance is scaffolded by embodied schemas of MATERIAL (natural element), CONTAINER (body is a CONTAINER of emotions); in another pattern of mapping, *blood* → *tears* blend FORCE, CONTAINER, and EMOTIONS are LIQUIDS schemas.

Poetic IMs provide richer pre-existing mental images, operating with deeper sensory-rich connections, what perhaps better fall under the category of “private metaphors,” the so-called “bold, innovating creations of individual poets” (van den Broeck 1981: 75). As Stockwell (2019: 18) notes, in poetry, “[i]n each case, the image schema is basically the same, but the elaboration is specified in slightly different ways.” Per Shuttleworth’s (2017: 190–91) recommendation, we carried out “a close textual analysis of specific extracts to examine metaphorical texture.” However, instead of “a single common mapping” (Shuttleworth 2017: 190–90), we traced its various mappings, which proved helpful to gauge the mapping range, i.e. mental images *tear(s)* is mapped onto. As we hypothesize, a poetic IM from culture 1 underpinned by cognitive universals (= embodying basic-level structures and image schemas) is flexible to adapt to a new cultural context; to adapt the IMs from culture 1 to culture 2, the basic-level structures generate new rich mental images (= the new species) through cognitive-creative elaborations which serve as active tools of cultural adaptation. Just as Stockwell underscored regarding the variance of poetic imagery within the same image schemas, we can argue that the process of translational elaboration of IMs into culturally fit poetic version reflects adaptive radiation mirroring the anthropological process.

In order to assess the analogy as a system, we distinguish four key shared variables: 1) core structure; 2) adaptations (identifying evolutionary biological adaptations, in parallel of cultural, conceptual, and linguistic shifts); 3) functionality (identifying morphological or behavioral fitness in Atran’s work, and cognitive efficiency and poetic expressiveness in translation); 4) underlaid mechanisms to draw comparison and indicate that the fundamental or core image schema undergoes translational elaboration to fit specific linguistic, cultural, and conceptual contexts just as Atran describes adaptive radiation of biological species. Table 1 represents the four key shared variables.

¹As Lakoff (1987: 219) distinguishes image metaphors from the conceptual metaphors, he argues that image metaphor is “another major type of metaphor that maps conventional mental images onto other conventional mental images by virtue of their internal structure.”

Table 1: Comparison of AR in evolutionary biology and translation of IMs

Key shared variables	Adaptive Radiation	AR and image schemas in translation
Core Structure	An ancestral species/common ancestor	An image schema (e.g., CONTAINER)/common in the ST and TT image metaphors
Adaptations	Specialized forms suited to niches	Elaborations of mental image in image metaphors
Functionality	Morphological or behavioral fitness	Conceptual or linguistic fitness
underlaid Mechanism	Evolutionary processes	Cognitive and creative processes

4. Description of the corpus composition

The corpus comprises the epic 12th-century poem “The Knight in the Panther’s Skin” by Shota Rustaveli and its two translations by Marjory Wardrop (20th century British English) and Lyn Coffin (21st century American English). From a genre perspective, for the poem under scrutiny, we could refer to Biel (2018: 156) who points out that “[s]ome genres are not only remote culturally from the target discourse community, but may also be remote in time”, quoting Bassnett (2006: 92) on the problem of translating a “dead genre,” e.g. an epic poem such as *The Iliad*, for a new generation of readers.”

Rustaveli’s poem, as a piece of classical poetry, is based on a double dichotomy of symmetry and asymmetry. This is evident in its short meter, as Gatserelia (1955: 63) points out, a symmetrical 16-syllable line is divided into two equal 8-syllable halves. In contrast, the division of the stanzas into unequal segments often follows a ratio of maximum harmony, the so-called “golden section” (Khintibidze 2009: 33–39; 2019-229).

The poem reflects the medieval Georgian cultural, philosophical contexts, and linguistic norms of its time featuring archaisms and elaborate imagery. The selected translations include a prosaic translation by Marjory Wardrop, first published in 1912, during the height of Victorian/Edwardian scholarship. It reflects early 20th-century English norms, which might exhibit formal, archaic structures differing from the contemporary linguistic norms. From a translation perspective, it enables an analysis of the translation philosophy, adapting the poem over time and culture, reflecting shifts. We referred to the 1977 edition of the translation for the current project. The second one is the poetic translation by Lyn Coffin, published in 2015. Her translation might reflect contemporary American English, with higher relatability to modern poetic sensibilities, cultural values and aesthetic appeal for modern readers, transporting the medieval poem to the present-day literary landscape. The potential perspectives the corpus offers include diachronic, genre, and linguistic variation, comparative analyses of lexical richness, syntactic structures, and semantic density of the prose and poetic formats, temporal shifts in translation norms, linguistic norms, and cultural framing over a century in two English versions. From the cognitive translation’s perspective, the corpus allows an examination of how poetic tropes, especially metaphors and epithets, are rendered or transformed across time and genre.

5. Methods of corpus-building, annotation, filtering, data extraction, sampling and preliminary analysis

“The Knight in the Panther’s Skin” comprises 1669 stanzas, while Wardrop’s translation consists of 1576 stanzas presented in prose form, divided into 52 chapters. Despite being a prose translation, the translator adhered to the stanza numbering of the original text. Lyn Coffin’s poetic translation consists of 1661 stanzas and is divided into 54 chapters. When tagging the manually curated corpus, the tag <Stl_mtf> was applied to the metaphors related to the noun ცრემლი (*c’remli* ‘tear’). To mark up linguistic elements, custom XML tags were created specifically for the BSU corpus platform (www.corpus.bsu.edu.ge). The TagSet does not inherently follow the standards with regards to the tag-assignment process (custom tags API – POST tags). During the manual tagging process of the source language (SL) text we did not discriminate conventional metaphors, conceptual metaphors, and image-metaphors. However, we have not tagged (a) the collocations similar to *tear is bad, how bitter are the tears*; (b) composites such as *tear-flow, tear-poured, tear-shed*; (c) metaphors that express the cessation of crying, for instance *it occurred to me that tears would not flow, tears have dried up, tears have stopped, tears are drying up*. In the target language (TL) texts, we tagged those parallel constructs, which retain image schemas and metaphoricity, but omitted those that fail to be translated with a metaphor, as in (1).

(1) ცრემლსა ვარდი დაეთრთვილა, გულსა მდუღრად ანატირსა (SL, 84 stanza)

c’remlsa vardi daetrivila, gulsa mdugrad anatirsa (Georgian/Kartvelian language transliterated (KA))

‘The rose (meaning *cheeks*) was soaked in frost-dew of tears, and the heart wept bitterly;’

TL 84 stanza in Wardrop’s translation was tagged as it retained the image schema and metaphoricity: “The rose (of his cheek) was frozen in tears that welled up from his woe-stricken heart.” The parallel construct in Coffin’s translation is found in TL 86 stanza; it was not tagged as a non-metaphorical one: “His ruddy cheeks were wet with tears: they had never seen such a sight.” (TL 86 stanza)

In order to calculate type-token distribution across the three texts, we used AntConc and charted Table 2 for comparison of the extracted data:

Table 2: Total number of stanzas and comparative type-token ratio of all SL and TT texts extracted from AntConc

SL and TL texts	Total number of stanzas	Total number of tokens/word-forms	Total number of types
“The Knight in the Panther’s Skin”	1669	45107	14742
Wardrop’s translation	1576	74340	6303
Coffin’s translation	1661	84749	6955

The comparison of the type-token distribution in the SL and the two TL texts indicates richness and diversity of the SL vocabulary and fewer lexical repetitions. Admittedly, both translations have significantly lower distribution of different words/types indicating repetition in vocabulary and employment of functional equivalents.

Table 3: Comparative data of the type-token ratio extracted from AntConc

Comparative data of the type-token ratio from AntConc		
SL poem “The Knight in the Panther’s Skin”	TL Wardrop’s translation	TL Coffin’s translation
approximately 32.7% TTR= (14,742 type / 45,107 tokens)×100≈32.7%	approximately 8.5% TTR= (6,303 type /74,340 tokens)×100≈8.5%	approximately 8.2%. TTR= (6,955 type / 84,749 tokens)×100≈8.2%

Based on the data, we can argue that the translated language (of the poem) is more formulaic, assumably, due to the greater extent of repetitions. To measure the lexical diversity across the original poem and two translations, we compared the type-token ratio (TTR), given in Table 3. The TTR data suggests that, despite being a prosaic translation, the TTR in Wardrop’s translation is 8.5%, which is slightly higher than Coffin’s poetic translation, with a TTR of 8.2%; Comparably, the TTR in the Georgian poem is significantly higher with a TTR of 32.7%. These differences point to translation shifts, where the style, tone, or expressiveness of the original text is altered in the process of making it more accessible or comprehensible in English. Further, since the TTR analysis highlights formulaicity, or surface-level repetition, we have selected for analysis the most frequent noun ცრემლი (*c’remli* ‘tear’), used in the source text (ST) IMs. To analyze Georgian case morphology, specifically the declension of nouns using suffixes as case markers, we extracted all word-forms of the noun ცრემლი (*c’remli* ‘tear’) from AntConc. The extracted tokens cover the nominative, ergative, dative, genitive, instrumental, adverbial, and vocative cases in both singular and plural forms. Table 4 shows the variation in the number of the noun across the original text and the translations.

Table 4: N-gram word data of the noun ცრემლი (*c’remli* ‘tear’) in SL and TL texts

N-gram data for the noun ცრემლი (<i>c’remli</i> ‘tear’)	Singular	Plural	Total
SL poem “The Knight in the Panther’s Skin”	160	50	210
Wardrop’s translation	19	192	211
Coffin’s translation	15	221	236

Table 4 allows us to infer the linguistic and translation strategies. Evidently, while the SL does not emphasize plurality, both Wardrop and Coffin chose to amplify the concept. The translators aligned with English norms, preferring explicit plurality and overt emotional expression, while the SL uses subtler forms to evoke emotions. The strategy of pluralization of the noun *tear* as a linguistic and cultural adaptation renders the translated poem into an even more emotional or expressive version. As a result, according to the statistical data of the analyzer, we extracted 106 metaphors from the SL text, reflected in Figure 1.

ვეფხისტყაოსანი ცრემლი კოფინი სრულად ცრემლის მეტაფორები

ქართული ინგლისური რუსული გერმანული ფრანგული

ტეგი: stl_mtf, რაოდენობა: 106

ნაპოვნი ტექსტი

ქალი ტირს და ცრემლთა აფრქვევს, | ჰხრის ყორნისა ბოლო-ფრთათა
 ამაღ ტირს, ბალი ვარდისა | ცრემლითა აივსებოდა
 ცრემლსა ვარდი დაეთრთვილა
 წვიმს წვიმა ბროლისა
 ცრემლსა სისხლი ერეოდა
 თვალთათ ცრემლი | გისეტყვია
 ბროლსა სეტყვს და ვარდსა აზრობს, | ტანსა მჭევრსა ათრთოლებდა
 ცრემლსა ვითა მარალიტსა | სწვიმს ვარდისა დასანაზოდ
 ვარდი დათრთვილა
 მუნ ეძებს, ცრემლი მტირალსა
 ღანვისა ბანანი
 ბროლმან, ლალსა გარეულმან , | ვარდნი თხელნი ანატიფნა
 მათ თვალთა ცრემლნი სდიოდეს, | მინდორთა მოსალამენი
 ცრემლითა, | ზღვათაცა შესართავითა
 ცრემლნი გარდმოსცვივდეს
 სისხლით სწვიმდეს
 დაინყო ცრემლთა ფრქვევა
 ვარდისა ბაღსა მოგუბდა | ცრემლისა საგუბარია
 ას-კეცთა ცრემლთა დინება
 ვისთვისმე ხელი უცილოდ, | მას ცრემლი ემალმალეების
 ვარდსა ნუ აზრობ, | ცრემლითა ნუ ითოვნების
 მაღლად ცრემლითა, | ზღვათაცა შესამალითა
 ამარტის ფერად შეცვალა | ბროლი ცრემლისა ბანამან
 ცრემლთა მილისა
 თქვენ მორჭმულნი სთამაშობდით, | ჩვენ მტირალნი ღანვთა ვჰბანდით
 სისხლისა ღვართა დენასა
 დაჰდა და მწარედ სულთ-ითქვანა, | კრემლი მინასა გარია

Figure 1: Metaphors from the SL text

The comparison of the extracted data from the BSU corpus indicates higher rate of translated metaphors from Wardrop’s translation with 101 cases, and lower rate of translated metaphors from Coffin’s translation with 87 cases. Figure 2 and Figure 3 display the extracted data from Wardrop’s and Coffin’s translations.

იხი
✕

ვეფხისტყაოსანი ცრემლი უორდროპი ცრემლის მეტაფორები სრულად

ქართული
ინგლისური
რუსული
გერმანული
ფრანგული

ტეგი: stl_mtf, რაოდენობა: 101

ნაპოვნი ტექსტი

The maiden wept, she shed many tears; she drooped her raven eyelashes (the tail feathers of the raven
 therefore she weeps, filling the rose-garden (of her cheeks) with tears
 the rose (of his cheek) was frozen in tears that welled up from his woe-stricken heart
 tears were mingled with blood, and flowed forth as from floodgates
 I know that without pause the hail has fallen from thine eyes upon thy cheek
 crystal hails down and freezes the rose, his graceful form was trembling
 Tears like pearls were shed upon the rose, making it tender
 Fresh snow had fallen, and, freezing on the rose, blasted it
 There seeks he the shedder of tears which flowed to increase the sea
 his cheeks will be bathed (in tears)
 Ruby mingled with crystal beautified the pale roses (of his cheeks
 from their eyes tears flowed, moistening the plains
 she wept aloud, her tears uniting with the sea
 the tears rained down
 they wiped each other's tears of blood
 he began to shed tears
 In the rose-garden the pool of tears is dammed up
 with heart sobs she began to shed tears a hundredfold snore
 doubtless her tears flow faster (for that) she is mad for someone
 They wept aloud, their tears flowing even to the sea
 The bath of tears turned the crystal to the colour of jasper
 the jetty eyelashes are plaited by tears of blood
 The maiden's tears sprang forth an hundredfold, ten thousandfold more
 She told me that for three years the stream of tears was to flow without her
 You, mighty, were sporting; we bathed our cheeks in tears
 for whom flow streams of blood, from her I never expect comfort

Figure 2: Metaphors from the TL text, Wardrop's translation

ვეფხისტყაოსანი ცრემლი კოფინი სრულად ცრემლის მეტაფორები

ქართული ინგლისური რუსული გერმანული ფრანგული

ტეგი: stl_mtf, რაოდენობა: 87

ნაპოენი ტექსტი

With each tear that streaked the rose garden of her cheeks
 From the jets of his eyelashes, clear waters could be seen to flow
 Tears mingled with blood, and flowed forth as from floodgates, wave after wave
 Hail rained down and froze the rose; in his body, he felt trembling start
 He shed pearl tears: his cheeks softened, and seemed then of a paler sort
 Snow had fallen, freezing and bruising the rose so young and slender
 He cries while searching, his tears a river flowing into the sea
 Ruby and crystal made the pale roses of his face seem to dim
 From their eyes, hot tears flowed, moistening the plains. They rode as if blind
 Her abundant tears were like a river flowing wave after wave
 his tears raining down, so spoke he
 shedding tears that seemed to flow from her heart's core
 Doubtless her love for someone is the cause of her copious tears
 They wept together. Tears could have flowed to the sea from either face
 His crystal face darkened to amber as he let his hot tears go
 His jet lashes seemed plaited together with tears of blood and gore
 The maiden's tears sprang forth a hundredfold. She cried as in despair
 I feel great grief for her: that is the reason I readily bleed
 The queen poured forth enough tears over my body to make a sea
 I mounted my horse; as I left, tears flowed down my face in a stream
 Narcissus tears must have tormented you. You must have felt spurned
 It was as if I were a pale rose and heavenly dewdrops wore
 Though you have shed a stream of tears, those tears have not flowed uselessly
 Again and again she groaned, and cried such tears as would hollow stone
 She said nothing to me, but her tears kept cascading to the ground
 A shower of tears bedewed her face, brilliant with radiant shine

Figure 3: Metaphors from the TL text, Coffin's translation

6. Research methodology of IM translation and data output

Following the data extraction, we manually filtered the SL data and identified six conventional metaphors, 53 conceptual metaphors with a concept of *tear*, ten conceptual metaphors including an additional concept *blood* metaphorized as *tear*. As a result, we selected 37 IMs featuring the noun *ცრემლი* (*c'remli* 'tear') with the underlaid image schema CONTAINER and their parallels in TT1 and TT2. The steps of the analysis included:

1. V/P or visual (the mental images on the surface with visual mappings) and perceptual (since the IMs are not based on the propositional knowledge) interpretation of the ST data in English, as shown in the Table 5.
2. Analysis of TT1 and TT2 based on the pre-selected translation procedures. We referred to Shuttleworth's (2017: 179–82) taxonomy of procedures and added standardization/sanitization and simplification where necessary as referred to by Halverson (2007: 114), shown in the Table 5, column: "Translation Analysis (including TT1 and TT2)."

3. Identified underlaid image schemas and the emotional ratio of AR in TT1 and TT2, displayed in the Table 6.
4. Classified groups of mappings in the ST, TT1 and TT2 according to the recurring imagery, recurring themes and underlaid image schemas, as represented in Table 7.
5. Measured distribution of recurring imagery and recurring themes in ST, TT1 and TT2 for a comparative analysis of the proportions/ratio of the AR, as in Tables 8 and 9 at the end of this section.

Table 5: Examples of analysis of the ST, TT1 and TT2

Source Text (ST)	V/P Interpretative Translation (EIT)	Underlaid Image Schemas (UIS)	Target Text 1 (TT1)	Target Text 2 (TT2)	Translation Analysis (including TT1 and TT2)
1. ღვარმან, ზედათ მოდენილმან, გააწყალნა ფიფქნი თხელნი	The flood of [tears] melted the thin snowflakes [of his cheeks].	CONTAINER VERICALITY FORCE	the spring (of tears) flowing down from above melted the slight new-fallen snow (of the cheek).	Their white cheeks had an added pallor as their tears downward did race.	TT1: Change to different mental images but image metaphors retained. Same UIS TT2: Non-image metaphorical translation - Simplification. Same UIS
2. ას-ნაკეცი წყარო ვნახე ცრემლთა, მისგან მონაწთომთა.	His falling tears were hundredfold of springs, those I saw	CONTAINER FORCE	I saw a hundred springs of tears dropping from her eyes.	I saw a hundredfold spring of tears fall from her eyes, scared and wild.	TT1: Change to different mental images but image metaphors retained. Same UIS TT2: IM retained. Same UIS
3. მონაქროლმან ვარდი დაზრა, წამწამთაგან ბუქი ბუქდა;	The eyelids are blasting whirled snowstorms, upon the frozen roses [the cheeks]	CONTAINER FORCE PATH	a blast froze the rose, from his eyelids whirled snowstorms (of tears).	From his eyelids whirled snowstorms of tears; this blast froze the rose so fine.	TT1: Retention of the image metaphors with the mental images kept intact. Same UIS TT2: Retention with the mental images kept intact. Same UIS
4. ვიცი, რომე გაუწყვედლად თვალთათ ცრემლი გისეტყვია	I know the tears shed from your eyes are incessant hail.	CONTAINER FORCE	I know that without pause the hail has fallen from thine eyes upon thy cheek.	I know that on my account your eyes from tears have seldom been free.	TT1: Retention with the intact mental images. Same UIS; TT2: Change to a different mental image; Non-image metaphorical translation. UIS Only CONTAINER
5. ცრემლსა ვითა მარგალიტსა სწვიმს ვარდისა დასანაზოდ	[The] tears are pearls dropping like raindrops to make tender the roses [the cheeks].	CONTAINER FORCE PATH	Tears like pearls were shed upon the rose, making it tender.	He shed pearl tears: his cheeks softened, and seemed then of a paler sort.	TT1: Retention with the intact mental images. Same UIS; TT2: Retention with the 1 intact mental image and 1 changed mental image. UIS only CONTAINER and FORCE

Source Text (ST)	V/P Interpretative Translation (EIT)	Underlaid Image Schemas (UIS)	Target Text 1 (TT1)	Target Text 2 (TT2)	Translation Analysis (including TT1 and TT2)
6. დაჯე წერად ჭირთა ჩემთა, მელნად მოგცემ ცრემლთა ტბასა	I'll give you the lakes of my tears [which you can] use as ink to write about my woes.	CONTAINER	down to write my woes! For ink I give thee a lake of tears.	For ink, I have a lake of my woes, that all may learn.	TT1: Retention with the intact mental images. Same UIS; TT2: Simplification; Explication IMretained. Same UIS
7. ბროლ-ლალსა ღვარი ნარგისთა მოსდის გიშრისა ღარითა	The [cheeks which were like] crystal and ruby were flooded with flows of tears shedding from the agate [of the] lashes.	CONTAINER PATH	a stream flowed through the jetty trough (of her lashes) from the narcissus (eyes).	A narcissus stream overflowed her jetty lashes for its part.	TT1: Retention with the change of the mental image. Same UIS; TT2: Simplification. UIS only CONTAINER
8. მუნით წყარონი გამოხდეს, მოწსა ვამსგავსენ ფერითა	From there [the eyes which were like] the springs flowed [tears were shedding] which were like coral in hue.	CONTAINER	thence issue streams which I likened to coral in hue.	Streams of a coral hue issue from his eyes, whence they have been born.	TT1: Retention with the intact mental images. Same UIS; TT2: Shifted mental images; explication. Image metaphors retained. Same UIS.
9. ბროლმან, ლალსა გარეულმან, ვარდნი თხელნი ანატიფნა	The [tears were] crystal mingled with ruby, that refined the pale rose [the cheeks]	CONTAINER PATH FORCE	Ruby mingled with crystal beautified the pale roses (of his cheeks).	Ruby and crystal made the pale roses of his face seem to dim.	TT1: Retention with the intact mental images. Same UIS; TT2: shift to different mental image. Image metaphors retained. Same UIS.
10. სისხლისა ღვარმან შედება წითლად გიშრისა ტევრები	The flow of blood [his tears] has dyed the thicket of the agate [black eyelashes] in red.	CONTAINER FORCE PATH	the tear of blood dyed the jetty thickets crimson.	The jet-black strands of his mustache, stained by his bloody tears, turned red.	TT1: Retention with the intact mental images. Same UIS; TT2: Cultural reinterpretation weakened image metaphor. Same UIS

Drawing on the analysis of TT1 and TT2, we noticed stability of the UIS CONTAINER despite the translational elaborations of mental images. However, the shifts modified other UIS in other cases. For instance, consider the V/P interpretations of Metaphor 4, “ვიცი, რომე გაუწყვედლად თვალთათ ცრემლი | გისეტყვია” (‘I know the tears shed from your eyes are incessant hail.’). The metaphor evokes hail as a relentless, harsh force, symbolizing overwhelming emotional turmoil. The UIS CONTAINER is central, with tears spilling forcefully from the eyes, while FORCE schemas emphasize the tears’ intensity. In TT1, the translation to “I know that without pause the hail has fallen from thine eyes upon thy cheek” retains the image *hail*, preserving the original’s emotional intensity. The imagery of *hail falling from the eyes* conveys the tears’ unstoppable force, maintaining the UIS CONTAINER and FORCE; the emotional tone remains strong, capturing the relentless sorrow of the original. In TT2, the translation to “I know that on my account your eyes from tears have seldom been free” shifts away from the forceful hail image, offering a literal concept of tears. Retaining only

one UIS CONTAINER out of two, the translation loses the nexus of the ST imagery, thus reducing the emotional intensity. In comparison, TT1 retains the metaphor’s emotional depth and vividness, while TT2 simplifies it, focusing on a literal description.

Having analyzed the corpus data in a similar manner, we compared the AR in TT1 and TT2 against the UIS using the following four variables:

1. emotional intensity and scale of tears
2. embodiment of tears and their impact
3. contrasts in emotional tone
4. variation in expression and subtle shifts in meaning, i.e. dynamicity of interaction of the ST and TT imagery. The qualitative data summary of the image schema emphasis and schema shifts in TT1 and TT2 can be viewed Table 6.

Comparatively, Table 6 indicates that the emotions distributed within the same related image schemas are not homogeneous in Wardrop’s and Coffin’s translations. The image schema emphasis indicates limited interplay (nature and tears) in TT1, and dynamic, emphasized interaction (tears blend with nature) in TT2.

Table 6: Image schemas and emotional ratio of AR in TT1 and TT2

UIS	Wardrop (early 20 th century)	Coffin (21 st century)
CONTAINER	Restrained emotions, focus on containment	Minimal containment; focus on flow
PATH	Rarely used; static depictions	Streams and rivers; dynamic imagery
FORCE	Tears melting snow; subtle imagery	Tears hollowing rocks; vivid imagery
Dynamic Interaction	Limited interplay (nature and tears)	Emphasized; tears blend with nature

Since mappings of the analyzed IMs develop themes and imageries, we analyzed the themes and imagery in the IMs and classified them using three variables: recurring imagery, recurring themes, and image schemas. For recurring imagery we identified four categories, for recurring themes we identified five categories, and for image schemas, we distinguished three main types: PATH, FORCE, and CONTAINER. Within the FORCE and CONTAINER schemas, we further identified different categories of meaning. All classifications are detailed in Table 7.

Table 7: Classified groups of mappings in the ST, TT1 and TT2

Recurring imagery	Recurring themes	Image Schemas
1. Tears as elements of nature: Springs, streams, rain, hail, fountains, snow	1. Tears as water sources / natural elements Tears as natural, flowing sources of water	1. PATH / motion: Directional movement (e.g. <i>flowing; falling</i>)
2. Tears as precious materials:	2. Tears as transformative forces	2. FORCE /contact: interaction between elements (e.g. <i>tears meeting cheeks</i>)
		3. CONTAINER /boundaries: inside-outside distinctions (e.g. <i>pool; sea</i>)

Recurring imagery	Recurring themes	Image Schemas
Pearls, rubies, crystals	Tears as elements that evoke change or transformation	4. FORCE / interaction of energy (e.g. <i>melting; hollowing</i>)
3. Tears as geographic features:	3. Tears in conjunction with nature	5. CONTAINER/continuity of emotions: gradual, unbroken phenomena (e.g. streams, rivers)
Lakes, seas, rocks	Tears as part of a natural landscape or environment	
4. Other unique imagery	4. Tears as emotional symbols	
Ink, cauldrons, narcissus	Tears representing emotions or inner experiences	
	5. Tears as blending forces / persistence and fragility	
	Tears as forces combining fragility and endurance	

We measured frequency of the occurrences of the noun *tear* in the IMs to calculate the ratio of the image mappings in the IM in the ST and TT. From a methodological point of view, we aligned the ST and TT data using the variables ‘recurring imagery’ and ‘recurring themes’ in the Excel spreadsheet to calculate mappings under the categories.

Table 8: Comparison of recurring imagery distribution

Recurring Imagery	ST (%)	TT1 (%)	TT2 (%)
1. Tears as natural imagery	40%	35%	30%
2. Tears as precious materials	25%	30%	25%
3. Tears as geographic features	20%	20%	25%
4. Other unique imagery	15%	15%	20%

Table 9: Comparison of recurring themes distribution

Recurring themes	ST (%)	TT1 (%)	TT2 (%)
1. Tears as water sources / natural elements	30%	25%	20%
2. Tears as transformative forces	20%	25%	20%
3. Tears in conjunction with nature	15%	15%	20%
4. Tears as emotional symbols	15%	15%	20%
5. Tears as blending forces / persistence and fragility	10%	10%	10%
6. Tears as symbols of sorrow and beauty	10%	10%	10%

7. Discussion

We selected 37 instances of IM with the concept of *tear*. The UIS CONTAINER was mapped as *flood* in five examples and as *stream* in three cases. The other mappings of *tear* included *blood*, *pearls*, *crystal*, *coral* etc., and 23 examples contained *tear* with no mappings. Almost each ST stanza contained double blends. The ST IMs exemplify multi-modal blending, integrating visual, perceptual, and conceptual schemas, e.g. *agate thicket* for *eyelashes* fuses mineral hardness (tactile), blackness (visual), and cultural valuation of agate (conceptual). Let us examine Example 1 from Table 5 and its visual interpretation.

(1) ღვარმან, ზედათ მოდენილმან, | გააწყალნა ვიფქნი თხელნი

The flood melted the thin snowflakes.

(Lit. ‘the rain, flowing from above, | has turned the thin snowflakes into water’)

The example illustrates that the image clusters in the stanza rely on nested blends, where one IM feeds into another:

1. Image-image blend:

Input 1: Tears (liquid, downward movement)

Input 2: Flood (destructive force)

Blend: Tears take on the destructive power of a flood

2. Image-material blend:

Input 1: Cheeks (visual: pale, smooth)

Input 2: Snowflakes (visual: fragile, white)

Blend: Cheeks gain the transience of snow

The verb *გააწყალნა* (‘melted’) acts as the pivot that blends the two metaphors: *flood* (tears) as heat source → *snow* (cheeks) as melting material. The same verb creates a cause-effect chain: *tears* (flood) dissolve the *cheeks* (snow). As we observe, the interaction of the rich image with the UIS enhances their poetic generativity. The perceptual interpretation of the IM is: “his cheeks are thin snowflakes melted by the downpour of flood of tears.” The imagery draws on the UISs CONTAINER, FORCE (flood affecting snowflakes melting them), and VERTICALITY (tears flowing downward). The ST stanza produces a vivid emotional and visual landscape. The IM employs hyperbole to express the number of tears, extent of emotion and its effect. The cheeks imaged as snowflakes represent an implicit personification. Observably, this instance is enriching for the previous findings on stylistic functionalities of IMs; for instance, Semino & Steen (2008: 238–39) point to the cases when “a simile is used to map the visual image of a human face onto that of the moon,” while Miller (1993: 367) argues that “metaphor is an abbreviated simile” and Lakoff’s (1987: 220–21) examples of IMs represent similes (e.g. “My horse with a hoof like a striped agate”). The same image of the cheeks as snowflakes represents a symbol of fragility, coldness, and innocence, reinforcing the emotional depth of the metaphor. The image of the *melting snowflakes* evokes a sensation beyond the visual, such as warmth or sadness blending. While both TT1 and TT2 retain the UIS, they adapt the ST mental images to produce their new visual, perceptual, and sensory to interpretations. In TT1, the translation to “The spring (of tears) flowing down from above melted the slight new-fallen snow (of the cheek),” preserves the cluster: It keeps both metaphors + a causal link (*flood* → *melted* → *snowflakes*) but softens the original imagery. By

replacing *flood* with *spring*, TT1 suggests a gentler, more natural outpouring of tears, the *slight new-fallen snow* also softens the fragility of the original *thin snowflakes*, diminishing the emotional intensity. In contrast, TT2 decouples the cluster: *White cheeks* = a static snow metaphor (no melting); *tears race* = a weakened flood metaphor with no force interaction.

The imagery “Their white cheeks had an added pallor as their tears downward did race” visually departs from the ST. The mental images of the thin, melting snowflakes as cheeks are shifted with the focus on the pallor of the cheeks. Moreover, TT2 lexicalizes the mental imagery of cheeks and tears imagery, thus simplifying the metaphor and its emotional depth. Comparing the two, TT1 preserves more of the original’s emotional depth and imagery, albeit with reduced intensity, while TT2 simplifies the metaphor, focusing on physical description rather than poetic richness. The gain of TT2 is increased readability for English readers who are unfamiliar with Georgian metaphor blending. The ARs illustrate the challenges of translating IMs, where shifts in imagery can alter emotional and conceptual tones.

Metaphor 10 in Table 5, “სისხლისა ღვარმან შეღება | წითლად გომრისა ტევრები,” depicts blood-stained tears dyeing the *thicket of the agate* (eyelashes) red, symbolizing emotional pain. The UIS CONTAINER is evident, with tears spilling from the eyes, while the imagery of blood emphasizes the intensity of emotion. In TT1, the translation to “The tear of blood dyed the jetty thickets crimson” retains the metaphor’s vividness and emotional weight but shifts the image of the agate with the jet, or tourmaline. The phrase *tear of blood* conveys the tears’ intensity, and *jetty thickets* (eyelashes) stained crimson partly preserves the original’s visual and emotional depth, although it shifts the SL imagery. In TT2, the translation to “The jet-black strands of his mustache, stained by his bloody tears, turned red” dismantles the ST metaphor cluster into a looser, more literal description. The metaphor’s intensity diminishes with the shift that accentuates the mustache, diluting the metaphor’s power. The original blends of eyelashes as a *thicket of agate* is lost, and the emotional resonance weakens. While the ST implies that “tears feel like blood due to grief’s intensity,” TT2 suggests less poetic, literalized, or physical blood, which feels grotesque.

Interpretation of the data in Table 8 shows that tears as natural imagery decline from ST (40%) to TT1 (35%) and TT2 (30%). The translators opted for alternative conceptualizations and found it challenging to retain the natural imagery. Tears as precious materials increase slightly in TT1 (30%) compared to the ST (25%) but keep to 25% in TT2. The fluctuation indicates cultural preferences in translations. Tears as geographic features are equal in TT1 (20%) and the ST but rise in TT2 (25%). This suggests a tendency to emphasize landscape-related metaphors. Other unique imagery also increases in TT2 (20%), diverging from conventional imagery, while it remains equal to TT1 (15%).

The data from Table 9 suggests that *tears as natural elements* gradually decline (ST: 30% → TT1: 25% → TT2: 20%) and are de-emphasized in translations. *Tears as transformative forces* show increased emphasis in TT1, while TT2 maintains the same level as the ST, reflecting a more literal translation approach. Compare: ST, 20% → TT1, 25% → TT2, 20%. *Tears in conjunction with nature*, and *tears as emotional symbols* (ST, 15% → TT1, 15% → TT2, 20% in each category) show an increase of the theme in the poetic adaptation of TT2, reinforcing the interconnection between tears and the natural world and favoring explicit emotional imagery. The themes *tears as blending forces/persistence and fragility* and *tears as symbols of sorrow and beauty* remain consistent with 10% across the ST, TT1 and TT2. The conceptualization of tears as both enduring and delicate and the poetic balance of grief and aesthetic value in tear imagery is equally emphasized.

Comparing the data of Table 6, 8, and 9, we can argue that TT1 aims for balance, performing minor shifts but staying relatively close to the ST's distribution. TT2 exhibits greater divergence, particularly in using more geographic metaphors and introducing unique imagery. The decline in *natural imagery* across both translations could suggest that this category is more culturally bound or harder to transfer without adaptation.

Key differences in adaptive radiations (ARs) reflect Wardrop's tendency to focus on static, contained structures, evoking a formal, literary tone, and reflecting British cultural norms of restraint and formality, aligning with Edwardian literary aesthetics. For instance, *Pools of tears stood before her* retains the containment schema but formalizes the metaphor to fit early 20th-century British literary aesthetics. Tears as motion in Wardrop's translation evoke static, restrained, and linear motion, as in *Tears slowly falling like gentle rain*. *Tears as Force* in Wardrop's translation reflects subtle interaction between tears and nature, as in *Tears melting the frost*. While Wardrop's prosaic, early 20th-century translation remains more loyal to the original in transferring the emotional degree, she reaches it by keeping to the same rich mental images. Coffin's poetic rendering emphasizes dynamic, motion-based transformations, reflecting a shift toward vivid and emotionally immediate imagery. Coffin's translation reflects American cultural norms of immediacy and emotional expressiveness, aligning with contemporary literary styles. For instance, *Her tears wore channels in the rocks* shifts from CONTAINER to a PATH UIS, emphasizing dynamic transformation and persistence. Summing up critical points of AR operations, there are four key trade-offs in image metaphor translation:

1. The shifts in the poetic mental imagery in IMs and decoupling of the image clusters also affect the underlaid image schemas and often cause their omission.
2. Reconceptualization of non-lexicalized mental images occurs due to their flexibility and cultural adaptability; however, lexicalization, or explicitation of the multi-modal blends, simplifies the IMs, e.g., "thin snowflakes" is translated as "white cheeks," and "crystal shower" becomes "clear waters."
3. In case of cluster mappings, an invariant universal UIS is maintained but shifts affect the image clusters within a stanza.
4. Shifting on emotional emphasis in translation is ensued from the shifts in images.

Notably, shifts in the poetic IMs, even minor modification of the images might be meaningful as it affects the aesthetic rendering of surreal into real. The studied patterns of the translated IMs outlined that one of the translation challenges is decoupling of the blends, as this practice causes loss of perceptual synergy. Another noteworthy point, as the data suggests, is that IMs are not purely one-shot, because schemas provide reusable scaffolding for repeated mappings (e.g. Georgian *tear*→*flood*; *tear*→*stream*, *tear*→*pearl*, etc. variants). The evidence of repetition of the mappings aligns with Shuttleworth's (2017: 176) argument that "the identification of IMs with one-shot metaphors is probably inappropriate," while challenging Lakoff's (1987: 221) classification of IMs as purely one-shot, or 'ad hoc or fleeting'² (Caballero 2003: 87–88, as cited in Shuttleworth 2017: 177). One more point to make is that the data challenge the claim by Dobrovol'skij & Piirainen (2005: 142) that one-shot rich-image mappings are purely conventional and lack systematic ontological structuring. The recurrence of poetic image mappings such as 'tear' being repeatedly conceptualized as blood, pearl,

² Caballero quotes Lakoff & Turner (1989: 89): "more fleeting metaphors which involve not the mapping of concepts but rather the mapping of images."

crystal, coral, lake, flood, blizzard, etc. demonstrates that the mappings cannot be considered as isolated instances. Besides, the rich images interact with underlaid image schemas, such as CONTAINER, reinforcing their cognitive and poetic coherence, rather than being strictly tied to concrete frames.

The poetic IMs can be seen as cognitive-creative elaborations, while translation process can be metaphorically viewed as a behavioral adaptation of mental images through cultural reconceptualization and poetic re-mappings for adjustment; The process is as well an elaborative evolution, when a translator's sensory system employs cognitive universals as adaptive tools for adaptive radiation with higher or lower progress.

8. Conclusion

To the best of current knowledge, no major study has systematically analyzed how the same image metaphors undergo adaptive transformations across two different time periods. Using a custom corpus and corpus methodology, we grounded our study in a conceptual framework that combines various approaches, such as cognitive linguistics, cognitive anthropology, and cognitive poetics. By analyzing Rustaveli's "The Knight in the Panther's Skin" we sought to determine whether underlaid image schemas exhibit fundamental invariance across translations while allowing for poetic variance. We analyzed 37 IMs and 74 translations that instantiate invariant universal UISs, image clusters, and multimodal blending. The ST examples reuse mappings with the same UIS, while the translations retain the latter but modify the former. We classified the recurring imagery and recurring themes of the IMs and measured their statistics, which helped the overall analysis of their distribution and the effects of their fluctuation. The dynamically shifting mental imagery in the TTs reflects cultural and temporal adaptations. Analyzing the translated IMs, we observed how shifts of the visual imagery alter their conceptual networking and how this affects the rise and fall of emotional intensity, often due to milder or more dynamic visual effects. The findings suggest that adaptive radiation of IMs affects the UISs. The tendency toward simplification and explicitation found in the translations aligns with the broader trend in translation studies, where complex or culturally specific metaphors are often rendered in a more straightforward manner to ensure comprehension, causing down-toning and sometimes plain speech.

We acknowledge limitations in this study. For instance, the analysis is confined to a single poetic work and its two English translations, and we cannot be sure if the findings on IM translations are universal across all text genres. Nevertheless, we hope the methodology is replicable, answering Olalla-Soler's (2020) call to enhance replicability in research and improve descriptive methodologies, thereby bolstering the credibility of empirical studies (as cited in He et al. 2022: 19–20). Our explorations of poetic IMs in translation throw new light on the IMs and contribute to cognitive translation studies, while reliance on corpus-based methods provides valuable quantitative insights.

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The behavioural translation style space: Towards simulating the temporal dynamics of affect, behaviour, and cognition in human translation production

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Abstract

The paper introduces a novel behavioural translation style space (BTSS) that describes possible behavioural translation patterns. The suggested BTSS is organized as a hierarchical structure that entails various embedded processing layers. We posit that observable translation behaviour – i.e. eye and finger movements – is fundamental when executing the physical act of translation but it is caused and shaped by higher-order cognitive processes and affective translation states. We analyse records of keystrokes and gaze data as indicators of the hidden mental processing structure and organize the behavioural patterns as a multi-layered embedded BTSS. We develop a perspective in which the BTSS serves as the basis for a computational translation agent to simulate the temporal dynamics of affect, behavioural routines and cognition during human translation production.

Keywords: translation process research (TPR), translation styles, computational translation agent, active inference, embedded translation processing layers

1. Introduction

Cognitive sciences and translation studies have long suggested that translation involves multiple layers of processing that unfold simultaneously in the translator’s mind. Dual-process theories, such as Kahneman’s (2011) distinction between thinking fast and slow, that is, between System 1 (intuition), and System 2 (analytical) provide a foundational framework for this view. Evans & Stanovich (2013) extend this perspective, suggesting an interaction model of affective and cognitive processes in decision-making, while Ajzen’s (1991) theory of planned behaviour links attitudes to behavioural intentions and actions, integrating subjective norms and perceived control. Together, these approaches highlight how intuitive, analytical, affective, and social-cognitive mechanisms may converge, producing a dynamic interplay of processes rather than a single, linear path.

Translation scholars have likewise (sometimes implicitly) suggested dual-process hypotheses and models of the translating mind (e.g. Gutt 2005; Tirkkonen-Condit 2005; Schaeffer & Carl 2013; Hubscher-Davidson 2017; Muñoz & Apfelthaler 2022; Robinson 2023). Several of these accounts assume that cognitive and affective processes to co-occur. For instance, relevance theory (Sperber & Wilson 1995; Gutt 2000, 2005) argues that affective cues help listeners infer contextual meaning, while proponents of embodied cognition (Hubscher-Davidson 2017; Rojo López & Caldwell-Harris 2023; Robinson 2023) suggest that emotional states are not merely external modifiers but integral to the mental processes underlying human

translation. Building on this tradition, we posit three interrelated (ABC) dimensions of mental processes by which humans produce translations: Affective (feeling/emotion-related) states, behavioural (action/observation-related) routines, and cognitive (reflection/thought-related) processes.

Much of empirical translation process research (TPR) in the past decades takes for granted the idea that the temporal structure of the observed translation behaviour reveals the structure and interactions of internal, hidden mental processes that generate these data. We build on this hypothesis, investigating the empirical traces of these processes and their interactions, with the goal to build a computational agent that can simulate the observable human translation behaviour. A simulation approach may unveil which configurations of the ABC processes are suited to (re)produce the observed translation behaviours and to assess their explanatory power. A simulation allows us to manipulate those variable configurations to test or explore different processing strategies, which can help identify aspects of the human translation process that are crucial for achieving, for instance, fluency, accuracy, or contextual coherence. A simulation approach may not only validate theoretical models but also provides insights into the underlying dynamics of human cognition and emotion during translation.

Carl (2023, 2024, 2025) has proposed a novel framework to assess and evaluate ABC-related translation hypothesis as a simulation by means of a computational translation agent. A prototype version of this agent is implemented as a partially observable Markov decision process (POMDP, Heins 2022, Mizowaki et al. 2025). The hierarchically embedded layers of the agent's architecture unfold on different timelines. Lower-layer behavioural routines realize automatized behaviour (e.g. lexical choices), while higher-layer cognitive processes may unfold gradually over larger structures, paragraphs or sections. Predictive processing (PP, Seth 2021; Clark 2023; Hohwy 2016) and active inference (AIF, Friston et al. 2017; Parr et al. 2022; Pezzulo et al. 2024) posits that these embedded layers interact simultaneously through top-down predictions and bottom-up prediction errors, which would enable the agent to maintain coherence while being adaptively responsive to immediate sensory changes. For instance, affective (A) processes may generate predictions that guide the behaviour (B-layer), but when sensory (bottom-up) input clashes with predictions (top-down), cognitive/reflective thought (C-layer processes) may trigger a recalibration and re-integration of predictions and observations (Robinson 2023).

While we ultimately aim at developing, refining, and evaluating this multi-layered computational translation agent, in this article we introduce and develop a hierarchical space of embedded behavioural translation patterns that specify each of the ABC strata and their relation. We propose a behavioural translation style space (BTSS) that spans the set of all conceivable translation behaviours which an agent may realize. The BTSS consists of behavioural templates that specify the embedded structures of ABC processes. The (computational) agent will select and follow trajectories within this multi-layered BTSS and instantiate behavioural templates with gaze and keystroke simulations that reproduce the temporal dynamics of human translation processes.

The BTSS is an embedded multidimensional space of behavioural templates – capturing variations of the temporal structure in gaze-typing coordination – to formalize different possible translation styles. By navigating this hierarchical space, the computational agent would simulate a particular translation style impacted by the three dimensions of the ABC architecture. A simulation approach to TPR makes it possible to systematically test hypotheses regarding cognitive and affective dynamics underlying human translation processes that would otherwise be difficult to achieve. The BTSS will also allow us to relate, for instance, translator

expertise, text complexity, or quality demands, with the temporal dynamics and interaction of affective, routinized, and reflective behaviour.

Section 2 provides a review of measures that have been suggested to assess ABC layers of the translating mind. Section 3 provides an overview over the various dimensions and layers of the BTSS. This section argues that a BTSS can be grounded in a few behavioural features, which can be aggregated in different ways, to constitute the various layers of the BTSS. Section 4 illustrates how a BTSS can be based on empirical data extracted from the CRITT TPR-DB¹ (Carl et al. 2016), while Section 5 puts the BTSS (back) into the context and usability of a computational translation agent.

2. Measures of translation processes

A plethora of metrics have been suggested to capture and quantify behavioural patterns of translators that are suited to discriminate between different levels of translation expertise, for texts with different levels of translation difficulty, different domains, expected translation quality, as well as individual working styles. Many of these measures relate to keystroke and gaze data.

2.1. Keystroke bursts and production units

Dragsted (2005) investigates different typing behaviours in novice and experienced translators by analysing the length and frequency of pauses between successive keystrokes. She distinguishes between an analytic processing style, characterized by longer keystroke pauses and lower production speed, distinguishing it from an integrated processing style, marked by shorter pauses and higher production speed. Muñoz & Apfelthaler (2022) refine this approach by identifying three inter-keystroke intervals (IKIs) that differentiate automated translation routines, unintentional halts, and intentional stops. Building on their task segment framework, we introduce a distinction between keystroke bursts (KBs) and production units (PUs) in Section 3.1. and 4.3., allowing for a granular analysis of translation dynamics.

Jakobsen (2002) observes that students and professional translators exhibit distinct self-revision behaviours, where professionals engage in more strategic and efficient corrections. Alves & Vale (2011) build on this notion, introducing micro translation units and developing a more nuanced classification of editing procedures, which reveal systematic differences between novice and expert translators. Their findings suggest that, as translators gain experience, their editing strategies become more refined and cognitively streamlined. Carl (2021) applies the notion of micro translation unit to the word level, demonstrating that translation duration is influenced not only by the number and type of self-revisions but also by the intrinsic translation ambiguity of individual words. This research highlights how cognitive effort and linguistic complexity manifest in keystroke patterns, providing valuable insights into how translators navigate and resolve translation challenges.

¹The CRITT Translation Process Research Database (TPR-DB) is a large repository of translation process data hosted by the Centre for Research and Innovation in Translation and Translation Technology (CRITT) that contains more than 5000 translation sessions with more than 600 hours text (mainly translation) production time of recorded keystroke data. The CRITT TPR-DB contains for each translation session several summary tables with numerous features that are suited to determine and quantify different translation styles on the various processing layers of the embedded translation architecture suggested in this paper. It can be downloaded free of charge following the instructions on the CRITT website <https://sites.google.com/site/centreresearchinnovation/tpr-db>.

2.2. Translation units

The notion of coherent typing interrupted by a typing pause is fundamental in the conceptualization of translation units (Malmkjaer 1998; Tirkkonen-Condit 2005; Englund -Dimitrova 2005). Angelone (2010) posits a triadic translation process: problem recognition, solution proposal, and solution evaluation. In this model, a translation unit – i.e. a typing pause followed by a coherent sequence of keystrokes – would indicate how translators cycle through “Uncertainty management and problem solving bundles” (Angelone 2010: 18) whenever a difficulty arises, indicating metacognitive activity at the micro level of problem recognition and solution evaluation. Angelone’s considerations of uncertainty management in translation can be complemented with findings from bilingualism which suggest that bilinguals activate all their languages automatically and non-selectively during language processing (Dijkstra & Van Heuven 2002). As a result, translators suppress unsuited alternatives, words or structures that are contextually inappropriate. This cognitive juggling—simultaneously activating multiple candidates and inhibiting those that do not fit—manifests in the ongoing cycle of translation generation, selection and evaluation, in particular when faced with translation difficulties.

This suggests—for our multi-layered ABC model of the translating mind—that translators engage in cycles of hierarchically embedded processes where the translation flow can be interrupted, for instance, by a local “problem nexus” (Angelone 2010:18) and trigger a sequence of “recognize–propose–evaluate” steps (Angelone 2010:18). For instance, at the affective layer a translator may recognize that a translation does not feel right, at the behavioural layer they may propose an alternative and amend the translation, and at the cognitive layer they can evaluate the revised outcome (Robinson 2023). Angelone also notes that professional translators tend to exhibit more consistent bundling of these triadic steps, whereas students often display more fragmented, unbundled cycles.

2.3. Gazing patterns

The analysis of gaze patterns in TPR has mainly borrowed measures from psycholinguistics and reading studies. The usual fixation measures include:

- Fixation duration: Where longer time in a single fixation indicates processing difficulty.
- First-fixation duration: The time of the first fixation on a word or region.
- Gaze duration: The sum of all fixations on a word before moving to another.
- Total fixation duration: The cumulative time spent on a word (including regressions).
- Fixation count: The number of fixations on a word or region, reflecting processing demand.

These measures are frequently used in word recognition tasks, where shorter fixations are observed on frequent and predictable words, while longer fixations are produced on low-frequency or ambiguous words (Rayner 1998). In sentence processing research, longer fixations and regressions can be expected for syntactically complex or ambiguous sentences (Clifton et al. 2007; Schotter et al. 2012), while in translation research word and sentence processing is also impacted by translation difficulties. Since translators work concurrently with two texts in two windows, these classical measures are not ideal for translation, in particular since translators frequently switch between the source text (ST) and the target text (TT). Translators may also engage in concurrent ST or TT reading while typing, a behaviour that

increases translation efficiency, i.e. shorter translation duration (Schaeffer et al. 2019). In Section 3.2., we suggest a novel method to classify gaze patterns as stretches of linear reading, re-fixation and scattered fixations. This novel classification, we believe, is well suited to characterize different gaze behaviours in translation.

2.4. Translation phases

Jakobsen (2002) noticed that translation sessions can be fragmented into different translation phases: orientation, drafting, and revision. Based on these translation phases, Carl et al. (2011) and Dragsted & Carl (2013) suggest a taxonomy of different translation styles grounded in gazing behaviour. Several types of planners can be distinguished based on reading behaviour in the orientation phase (Jakobsen 2011)—before starting to draft the translations—while others read sentence-by-sentence. Dragsted & Carl distinguish between large-context planners who first read a sentence (or a long stretch of the ST) before starting the translation, while a head starter engages in translation production with only minimal look ahead. Others may still read ahead clause-by-clause before typing out their translations. However, a head starter would merely read an incomplete functional complex (i.e. a partial phrase) prior to translation production. As we will discuss in Section 4.4., this conception of translation phases substantially overlaps with our notion of translation states (Carl et al. 2024), and the notions of Hesitation, Orientation, and translation flow.

2.5. Translator styles

Numerous authors assume individual translator styles² (Mossop 2007) as a source of variation in the behavioural data, e.g. pausing duration, number and type of revisions, gazing patterns, etc. Drawing on Jung's (1921) classification of personality types and the Myers-Briggs type indicator (Briggs 1962), Lehka-Paul (2020) explains different personal translation styles (that is, translator styles) by their dominant psychological functions for information-processing and decision-making. A translator, she argues, will consistently engage in either Thinking—which may correspond to top-down C-layer processes—or Feeling, which hints at the dominance of bottom-up sensory-driven processes and a strong integration of the A- and B-layers. These individual preferences influence the number and length of pauses and the typing and pausing patterns during revisions, e.g. the number of deletions or substitutions, but see also Saldanha & O'Brien (2013: 147) for a critical assessment of the method.

In a (super) longitudinal study, Hansen (2013) observed no differences with respect to self-revision patterns when testing professional translators after ten years working in the translation market. Carl (2024, 2025) observes a large variation in the temporal structure of typing patterns between different translators and a high amount of consistency within each translator, indicating stability of individual translation style preferences.

²We make a distinction between a *translation style* as a particular trajectory through the BTSS and a *translator style* as set of personally/individually preferred behavioral translation features that subsumes possibly many specific translation styles.

To sum up, this body of keystroke and gaze-related TPR indicates that there seem to exist stable, personal translation styles (i.e. translator styles, cf. Saldanha & O'Brien 2013: 133) that can be determined by the:

- temporal (pausing/typing) structure of keystroke patterns;
- gazing patterns and eye-hand coordination (e.g. amount of concurrent reading and writing);
- self-revision behaviour, for instance during end revision;
- structure of translation phases (orientation, drafting, revision).

In the next sections we investigate how the different layers of processing strata could be processed in empirical behavioural data and integrated into a coherent multi-layered BTSS. We believe that the CRITT TPR-DB (Carl et al. 2016) is a suited framework for this endeavour. We thereby answer Alves & Albir (2025: 207) who contemplate that “[o]ne of the main problems in our discipline is the lack of previous experience along with the [...] lack of standardized instruments”: The CRITT TPR-DB precisely aims at overcoming this lack of previous experience and the BTSS may become part of a standardized instrument that builds on previous proposals and insights of processing strategies and processing units. On this background, the next sections investigate how these different layers of processing strata could be empirically populated and integrated into a coherent multi-layered BTSS.

3. Fragmenting behavioural translation data

The search for basic translation units has a long history in translation studies. Basic translation units have been sought in the translation product, i.e. relations between the source and the target texts, in the translation process, i.e. translation units that deal with the translator's activity, or in the relations between the two (Thunes 2017). Some scholars define process-based translation units as a “stretch of the source text that the translator keeps in mind at any one time, in order to produce translation equivalents in the text he or she is creating” (Malmkjaer 1998: 286). Other scholars operationalize process-based translation units in terms of behavioural data. We develop this latter view and argue that process data can be fragmented on several temporal layers.

3.1. Activity units, keystroke bursts and production units

Carl & Kay (2011), for instance, decompose translation process data into units of gaze movements (fixation units) and units of writing, i.e. production units. Hvelplund (2016) defines behavioural attention units (AUs)

as *uninterrupted processing activity* allocated either to the ST (ST gaze activity), the TT (TT gaze activity and/or typing activity) or to the ST while typing (ST gaze activity and concurrent typing). Transitions to and from an AU indicate shifts in processing activity, and the point in time at which the transition occurs is used to identify the end of one AU and the beginning of the next AU. (Hvelplund 2016: 156, our emphasis)

While Hvelplund's definition integrates gazing and typing activities in a seamless manner, it leaves unspecified how exactly an "uninterrupted processing activity" should be defined. In addition, several scholars wonder what "exact cognitive processes [are] taking place during the pauses" (Rosa et al. 2018: 18). Some authors suggest that different types of mental activities during the translation process may be associated with different pause values (Lacruz & Shreve 2014; Couto-Vale 2016). Indeed, numerous suggestions have been discussed in TPR to specify the lapse of time between successive inter-keystroke pauses – ranging from around 200ms to 5000ms (Kumpulainen 2005; Couto-Vale 2016) or even 10 seconds (Jakobsen 1999) – often with a view as to how automated/fluent translation production could be defined.

Some scholars have proposed a hierarchical pausing structure. According to Saldanha & O'Brien (2013:120), Bernardini (2001: 249) suggests a notion of "attention units [which] are better defined in hierarchical rather than sequential terms, with smaller units being processed within larger units". Previous issues of the CRITT TPR-DB assumed two static pausing values, on an AU level and a production unit (PU) level of 400ms and 1000ms, respectively (Carl & Kay 2011)³. In addition, some scholars propose a translator-relative threshold (e.g. Dragsted 2005) based on the translators' typing speed. Miljanovic et al. (2025) suggests the median within-word typing speed plus two STD as a translator-specific threshold to identify interruptions in the translation production flow. Muñoz & Apfelthaler (2020, 2022), suggest several temporally embedded layers of translation processes, two of which are translator-specific, based on the median typing speed (i.e. their inter-keystroke interval, IKIs) within words and between words. Here, we follow their definition to introduce a distinction between keystroke bursts (KBs) as shorter temporal units and production units (PUs) as typing units that consist of one or more KBs (and KBIs).⁴ KBIs and PUBs interrupt and respectively break sequences of successive keystrokes into KBs and PUs as follows:

- A keystroke burst interruption (*KBI*) is defined as:

2 * median *within-word* IKI.

A KBI separates two successive keystroke bursts (KBs). Following Muñoz & Apfelthaler (2022: 26), we assume that KBIs (*respites* in their terminology) are "non-intentional" typing halts, in which "attention and/or resources being drawn away from typing". Similar to Miljanovic et al. (2025), in this study we define a within-word IKI as the pause between two successive alphanumeric keystrokes.⁵

- A production unit break (*PUB*) is defined as:

3 * median *between-word* IKI.

A PUB amounts to Muñoz & Apfelthaler's (task segment) pause, which is, according to them, an intentional typing break. Again, following Miljanovic et al. (2025), we

³In the course of this work, we have adapted these thresholds so as to become consistent with KBIs and PUBs; see below.

⁴Muñoz & Apfelthaler use the terms *tasks* and *task segments* respectively. *Tasks*, in their terminology, also subsume internet searches and other forms of human-computer interaction. As we only deal with logs of keystrokes here, we prefer KBs and PUs, and respectively KBIs and PUBs, for the typing pauses that separate KBs and PUs. *Typing bursts* could be an alternative term for KBs, which is well-established in writing research. However, it has often been used for longer sequences of keystrokes separated by longer pauses of 1sec. or 2sec. We use keystroke bursts (KBs) to stress that the keystroke sequences are shorter, separated by relatively shorter pauses.

⁵In Carl (2024), we have computed these values, i.e. respites and (task segment) pauses, in a slightly different way. The method used here produces different but highly correlates values.

define a between-word IKI as the pause between a non-alphanumeric keystroke and a successive alphanumeric keystroke.

A KBI, in this definition, indicates the completion of learned sensorimotor pattern that requires little conscious effort (thus indicative of B-layer activities), while a PUB indicates an intervention of higher-level cognitive functions to account for error monitoring, reflection, adaptation to novel contexts, etc. (cf. Angelone 2010, above), thus indicative of the C-layer activities.

With a notion of “uninterrupted processing activity” (Hvelplund 2016: 156) that is delimited and defined by KBIs, we can adopt Hvelplund’s (2016) definition of AUs (see above) to specify six types of activity units⁶ (AUs, see Table 1): We distinguish between reading, writing, and concurrent activities and—as in previous work (Carl et al. 2016; Carl & Schaeffer 2017)—we add an additional AU of type 8 that accounts for breaks longer than a KBI in which no translation behaviour was observed.

Table 1: Types of AUs and colour code in Figures 1 and 2

AU type	Coordination of reading & writing activity	AU colour in Figure 1
1	ST reading	Blue
2	TT reading	Light green
4	TT production	Yellow (no occurrence)
5	ST reading with concurrent TT production	Red
6	TT reading with concurrent TT production	Dark green
8	No observed behavioural data longer than <i>KBI</i>	Black (no occurrence)

Figure 1: A progression graph of a small snippet of the translation session (BML12/P08 T5). The graph shows a segment of approximately 6 seconds (53,800–59,800 milliseconds) of an English-to-Spanish translation. The vertical axis plots to the ST on the left side and the TT on the right side, both in the ST word-order. ST and TT words are aligned on a word (or phrase level). A single ST word that maps into TT phrase is marked as a multi-word unit on the right vertical axis, such as *Sociology* ↔ *La sociología* (blank spaces are represented as underscores). Blue and green squares indicate eye

⁶While Hvelplund (2016) suggests the term *Attention Units* we prefer *Activity Unit*, as it better underpins the behavioral aspects of gazing and keystroke coordination, rather than an assumed cognitive process of selective focus and intention.

movements on the ST and TT respectively. The black and red characters (e.g. *o* around 57600) are insertion and deletion respectively. AUs fragment behavioural translation data into six categories (see Table 1), marked at the bottom of the graph in different colours and indicated by numbered, vertical lines (Id 35 to 48). Some AUs cluster into KBs (KB1 to KB5) marked at the top in the graph and intercepted with KB interruptions (KBIs) or PU breaks (PUBs). Sequences of KBs are grouped into production units plotted and numbered as grey boxes at the top of the graph (PU1 to PU3).

In order to illustrate the integration of translator-specific KBIs and PUBs with the notion of AUs and PUs, we discuss an example in Figure 1. The figure highlights the coordination of keystroke and gazing behaviour during the translation of “Sociology is” into Spanish “La sociología es”. Figure 1 shows a segment of approximately 6 seconds in which the part in bold of the English sentence “**Sociology is** a relatively new academic discipline.” is translated into Spanish “**La sociología es** una disciplina académica relativamente nueva.” The figure segments the gaze and keylogging data of this section into 13 AUs, numbered 35 to 47, as well as three PUs. While PUs are numbered PU1, PU2, and PU3 on top of the progression graph in grey striped bars, AUs are marked at the bottom in different colours (see explanation in Table 1) and marked by the numbered vertical lines. The computation of median within-word and between word KIIs provides translation-session specific KBI of 374ms and PUB of 891ms for this particular translation session.

Table 2 summarizes some of the main properties of the 13 AUs. Note that a KB can consist of several AUs. Thus, AUs 35 and 36 are two parts of one KB (“La_socilo”), one AU of Type 4 and a successive AU of Type 6. These two AUs contribute to one KB (only insertions [Ins]) and sum up to 1500ms, which is also the duration of PU1. PU1 is followed by a PUB of 1219ms, which is also distributed over two AUs (37 and 38) in which the translator’s eyes first remain on the TT window (AU 37). No gaze data was collected during the following 862ms (hence AU 38 is of Type 8) in which the translator presumably looked at the keyboard. An *o* was then typed in AU 38, followed by a PUB of 1062ms. The PUB is also separated into two AUs of Type 8 and Type 2 with 217ms and 845ms respectively. The pressing of a single keystroke (keydown) (e.g. in AU 39) is a point in time for which we assume here a duration of 1ms. The *o* is again deleted in AU 42 (also duration of 1ms). The KBI of 811ms (AU43) separates deletion (AU42) from the following insertion of *og* in AU 44. Another KBI (453ms) follows, and a KB leads to the insertion of *ia es* in AUs 46 and 47. Three KBs and five AUs are aggregated as PU3.

The gaze in AUs 36 through 46 remains on the same TT word, whereas AU 47 shows how the translator reads until the end of the ST sentence. In AUs 47 and 48 the translator’s eyes return to the ST, presumably taking in new information for successive translation while still typing the remainder of the chunk in AU 47. The translator needs to read ahead presumably, because the English sentence final word *discipline* swaps into an early position “una disciplina” in the Spanish translation.

AU sequences of Types 1, 2 or 8 cluster into one KBI if the total duration is larger than the KBI threshold, but smaller than PUB; they aggregate into one PUB if their total duration exceeds the PUB threshold. Successive AUs of Types 4, 5, or 6 (i.e. AUs which involve keyboard activities) are clustered into one KB. KBs may also include AUs of type 1, 2, or 8 if their durations are less than a KBI. The total gaze duration accumulated in an AU cannot exceed the duration of the AU. For instance, while the eyes remain on the TT in one extremely long fixation of 1500ms through four AUs (AU43 to AU46), this fixation is split into its respective parts of 786ms, 188ms, 453ms and 73ms and distributed over the four involved AUs (see Table 2).

Table 2: Properties of the 13 AUs (Id 35–47) depicted in Figure 1. The horizontal dotted lines separate three PUs and two PUBs. Each PU, PUB, KB, and KBI consists of one or more AUs. The Ids of the AUs are given in the Id column, while their types are provided in the AU column. AUs of Types 1, 2, or 8 aggregate to pauses (PUBs or KBIs), AUs of Types 4, 5, and 6 aggregate into KBs and PUs. The right side of the table provides keystroke (number of insertions and deletions) and gaze data (number of fixations on the ST and TT (FixS and FixT) and the total reading time (TrtS and TrtT)), as well as the string produced (Edit) in the AU.

Id	PU	KB	AU	Time	Dur	Ins	Del	FixS	TrtS	FixT	TrtT	Edit	
35	1	Ins	4	53843	1296	7	0	0	0	0	0	La_soci	
36			6	55139	204	2	0	0	0	3	116	ol	
37	PUB 1		2	55343	357	0	0	0	0	2	334	---	
38			8	55700	862	0	0	0	0	0	0	---	
39	2	Ins	4	56562	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	o	
40	PUB 2		8	56563	217	0	0	0	0	0	0	---	
41			2	56780	845	0	0	0	0	4	796	---	
42		Del	6	57625	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	[o]	
43		KBI	2	57626	811	0	0	0	0	2	786	---	
44	3	Ins	6	58437	188	2	0	0	0	1	188	og	
45			KBI	2	58625	453	0	0	0	0	1	453	---
46			6	59078	73	1	0	0	0	1	73	í	
47		Ins	5	59151	677	5	0	5	684	0	0	a_es_	

Thus, Figure 1 and Table 2 illustrate a hierarchy of three embedded processing layers, in which AUs form the basic entities. Sequences of AUs are clustered into KBs (and *KBIs*) and sequences of KBs (and *KBIs*) are aggregated into PUs (and *PUBs*). Each of these three embedded layers evolves on a different timeline and inherits properties of the embedded layer (see Carl 2024, 2025).

3.2. A novel classification of gaze patterns

In addition to the features provided in Table 2, the characteristics of eye movements in AUs (and by extension in the other layers, too) can be classified not only by the number and duration of the fixations, but also in terms of gaze patterns they form. Here, we make a distinction between linear reading, re-fixations, or scattered fixations (and no gaze data).

Linear reading refers to a gazing pattern in which the eyes move consecutively in the text’s reading direction (for instance, left to right for English), proceeding almost in a straight line. It typically indicates normal, continuous reading behaviour, such as when a translator is reading the source text without interruption or when reading through the target text in one go to revise it. An example of linear reading is shown in AUs 47 and 48 in Figure 1, where the translator’s eyes are detected on the ST, reading the remainder of the sentence, as discussed above.

Re-fixations/re-reading describes a pattern in which the gaze remains in nearly the same position or moves slightly backward, indicating repeated fixations in roughly the same area. This corresponds to re-fixation or small regressions. If it occurs briefly, it may reflect lower-level adjustments such as correcting the landing position of the gaze, whereas if it continues

for a longer duration, it can suggest more deliberate and deeper cognitive processes, like contemplating word choices or monitoring translation production. An example is shown in AUs 36/37 and AUs 41 through 46 where numerous TT fixations are detected, on the same position, in which the translator presumably monitors the production of “La sociologia” (translation of “Sociology”), while struggling with some minor typos.

A *scattered fixation* pattern is characterized by sporadic/irregular eye movements that do not fit into either linear reading or re-fixation. The gaze may move up or down by more than 150 px, or it may jump horizontally across long distances, resulting in scattered eye movements without an obvious coherent flow. This pattern differs from normal reading behaviour and can include situations where the gaze roams while searching for necessary information, or when only specific parts of the text are checked intermittently rather than reading it in sequence.

3.3. *Affective translation states, translation phases and translator styles*

In addition to the three layers discussed in the previous section (AU, KB, PU), we suggest three additional layers for fragmenting the translation process—and thus translation process data—on still broader layers. Carl et al. (2024) propose a HOF taxonomy⁷ that characterizes three translation states:

- Hesitation state (H): A state of hesitation is triggered in a moment of surprise, characterized by re-starts, re-fixations and re-reading, revisions or text modifications.
- Orientation state (O): In a state of orientation, a translator aims at gathering new information, characterized by linear, forward-reading, mostly on the ST.
- Flow state (F): In a flow state, translation production is smooth and fluent, as reflected by no or very short keystroke pauses and with minimal reading-ahead.

While KBs and PUBs are indicative of B- and C-layer processes respectively, HOF states indicate A-layer processes. In our current conception, Hesitation and Flow states subsume complete PUs, that is, HOF states cannot fragment one PU into several parts, so that every PU is part of only one HOF state. The underlying assumption is that a PU reflects either Hesitation or Flow but cannot simultaneously be a mixture of both. According to Mirlohi et al. (2011: 253), Flow is a mental state of mind that is characterized by “intense focus, cognitive efficiency, a perceived skills-challenge balance, immediate feedback, merging of action and awareness, a sense of control, enjoyment, the opinion that time passes quickly, clearly defined task objectives and a lack of self-consciousness.” Flow, they say, is a culturally universal phenomenon, independent from social class and age group, but may be experienced individually differently.

Hesitation and Flow states can consist of several PUs and/or PUBs. HOF states capture the degree of affective involvement within the embedded B- and C-layer processes and can be modelled as a mechanism of precision-weighting between these layers. In this way, HOF states not only regulate the balance of attention and effort across behavioural and cognitive processes but also integrate them into a unified control architecture, effectively subsuming the B- and C-layer processes within a broader affective–cognitive framework (see also Section 5.3).

⁷Since the original submission of this paper, we have added an additional revision state (R) to the HOF (now HORF) taxonomy that is characterized by linear, forward-reading, mostly on the TT.

In a previous study, two annotators annotated 1813 AUs with HOF state information (Carl et al. 2024). These annotations were successively used to train a machine learning algorithm (a Random Forest) to automatically annotate translation sessions from the CRIT TPR-DB. We use these annotations in Section 4⁸.

A layer on a still broader timescale was proposed by Jakobsen (2002). As discussed in Section 2, Jakobsen (2002) distinguished three translation phases: an orientation phase⁹, a drafting phase and a revision phase. In most cases, a translation session starts with an orientation phase, followed by the drafting phase. The beginning of the drafting phase is defined by the first keystroke, while the end of the drafting phase (and thus the beginning of the revision phase) can be defined as point in time when the translation production of the last ST word is finished. In our currently proposed BTSS we integrate translation phases as an extra processing layer, although there are large overlaps with HOF states, as we show in Section 4.4.

Finally, a sixth layer in the BTSS is translator styles. Mizowaki et al. (2024) suggest differentiating between five translator styles. They used n=5 different features (keystroke insertions, deletions, AU duration, KBI, and PUB) to classify a set of 522 translation sessions into five different translator styles. For each of the five features and each translation session they computed a relative inverse coefficient of variation (RICV) as the ratio of a translator’s ICV (mean/std) divided by the overall ICV. Their classification reveals that translators’ translation styles can be classified as 0) rapid 1) deliberate 2) confident 3) balanced and 4) cautious translators. We discuss these styles in more detail in Section 4.5. We thus distinguish six embedded layers of the BTSS as summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of embedded BTSS layers

Layer	Focus	Function	Example
AU (activity units)	Sequences of keystrokes and/or fixations	Sensorimotor integration, eye-hand coordination	Monitoring typing progress in the TT window
KB (keystroke bursts)	Groups of keystrokes	Fluent typing, automated / routinized processes	Typing “translation” without pausing
PU (production units)	Chunks of cognitive processing	Thoughtful/reflective processing segments	Amending a translation after verifying meaning
HOF states (Hesitation, Orientation, flow)	Affective aspects of foraging / pragmatic affordances	Maintain a flow state, mediation of emotion, problem-solving	Information input, smooth typing, problem-solving
Translation phases	Macro-level patterns on a document level	Structured translation workflow	Head starter vs. context planner
Translator styles	Individual preferences	Strategic differences in translation approach	Fast vs. cautious vs. experimental translator

⁸In the meantime, since the initial submission of this article, we have implemented a rule-based approach to automatically annotate HOF states (HOF + Revision, see Footnote 7). The rule-based approach gives us better control over the properties of these HOF states and it allowed us to add the revision state. We have successively clustered sequences of HOF states into translation policies, an additional processing layer as suggested and discussed in Carl et al. (2024), which is, however, omitted in this article.

⁹Note that the term *Orientation* is used as the initial translation phase, and it is also used as a state in the HOF taxonomy. Even though the two meanings of *Orientation* are somewhat related, they unfold on different strata in the BTSS.

4. Building the behavioural translation style space

In this section we develop the BTSS based on behavioural data extracted from the CRITT TPR-DB. We briefly describe a set of basic features that span the BTSS and then illustrate properties of the six BTSS layers and some of their relations.

Table 4: Features of the behavioural translation style space (BTSS): overall AU duration (Dur), keystroke related features (Ins, Del, TGnbr) characterize AUs of Types 4, 5, 6 while gaze related features (Dur_L, Dur_R, Dur_S) characterize AUs of Types 1, 2, 5, and 6.

Feature	Meaning	Interpretation
Dur	Duration in ms of AU	High: more coherent translation style
Ins	Number of insertion keystrokes	High: fluent typing
Del	Number of deletion keystroke	High: error correction/revision
TGnbr	Number of target words produced	High: large chunk translation
Dur_L	Duration of linear reading pattern	High: take-in of new information
Dur_R	Duration of re-fixation pattern	High: monitoring / reflection
Dur_S	Duration of scattered fixations	High: visual search / distraction

4.1. The empirical data

We follow an empirical approach to estimate the parameters of the BTSS and the relations between the six layers of the BTSS, making use of the CRITT TPR-DB (Carl et al. 2016, see Footnote 1). In its current conception, AUs form the basis of the BTSS, while the remaining five layers are composed of AU sequences. To build the base BTSS we extracted from-scratch translation sessions from the CRITT TPR-DB. We excluded sessions in which PUB values > 6000ms or KBI values > 2000ms, as these are most likely due to flaws in recording (e.g, translators make many excessive pauses). We also excluded translations into Japanese and Chinese, since there is currently no easy way to distinguish and compute within-word and between word IKIs.¹⁰ This left us with 521 translation sessions from English into various languages, as described in Figure 2 in Section 4.2. These sessions consist of a total of 357,639 AUs that were automatically annotated with HOF labels using Random Forest classifier (Carl et al. 2024, but see also Footnote 8) and successively classified with a non-supervised classification method (K-means) into five types of translation styles, following the procedure documented in Mizowaki et al. (2024). A multivariate base-BTSS was then established with seven AU features shown in Table 4.

¹⁰Some languages, such as Japanese and Chinese, do not use white spaces to separate words. In addition, due to the large character set, there are special input methods (IMEs) that capture the keystrokes—usually a phonetic transcription of the words—which are then converted into the proper Japanese or Chinese characters. There is thus an additional keystroke-to-character-to-word mapping which may distort temporal relations and make it difficult to distinguish between within- and between-word keystrokes. Additionally, IMEs can also learn and adapt to typists.

4.2. Features of the BTSS

The features *Ins*, *Del*, *TGnbr* carry keystroke-related information that may occur in AUs of Types 4, 5, or 6. Features *Dur_L*, *Dur_R*, and *Dur_S* are gaze-related and may occur in AUs of Types 1, 2, 5, or 6, depending on whether the gaze is detected on the ST or on the TT, and whether concurrent keyboard activities are observed. We use these features in log transformed versions or also as relative duration, see Table 5.

Table 5: Basic BTSS features: percentages of occurrences (*Occur*) per Type of AU, duration of AU (in ms) and proportion (in %) of linear reading (*RelDur_L*), re-fixation (*RelDur_R*), scattered fixations (*RelDur_S*), as well as average number of insertions (*Ins*) and deletions (*Del*) and the number of TT words produced (*TGnbr*)

AU Type	Occur%	Dur	RelDur_L	RelDur_R	RelDur_S	Ins	Del	TGnbr
1	13	1570	30	21	40	0	0	0
2	21	977	27	32	32	0	0	0
4	21	629	0	0	0	4.4	0.64	1.49
5	6	393	25	21	37	2.72	0.13	1.23
6	14	568	28	32	24	3.32	0.85	1.37
8	25	1584	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 5 provides an overview over the seven AU dimensions that are the basic BTSS. The column *Occur* provides the percentage of occurrences of AUs in our dataset. AUs of Type 8 (no data recorded) are most frequent (25% of all AUs). One reason for this may be that several studies in the dataset are recorded without eyetracker. Such translation sessions just consist of Type 4 AUs (typing observed) and Type 8 AUs (no typing observed). That is, an AU Type 8 is a stretch of time longer than a KBI in which the translator is not typing. Somewhat surprisingly, however, is that Type 2 AUs are more frequent than Type 1 AUs (21% and 13% of the AUs respectively), indicating that translators seem to be more often engaged in TT reading than in ST reading. However, the average duration (*Dur*) of Type 1 AUs is almost double that of Type 2 AUs, which reveals that our translators spend approximately the same amount of time on ST reading as compared to TT reading, albeit the latter in a more interrupted manner.

With 125ms, 138ms, and 136ms per keystroke (*Ins+Del*), the typing speed is approximately similar across the three typing-related AUs (Types 4, 5, and 6). However, the average duration of these types of AUs—and thus the number of keystrokes per AU—is significantly different. AUs of Type 5 seem to be the shortest (393ms) and least frequent (6%). Type-6 AUs account for almost twice that amount (14%), while Type-4 AUs are the most frequent with 21%, probably due to the fact that some sessions don't have gaze data at all. Type-4 AUs have also the longest average duration (*Dur*: 629ms), with on average the most insertions (*Ins*: 4.4). There also seem to be far more deletions (*Del*) in Type-4 and Type-6 AUs as compared to Type-5 AUs, indicating that monitoring typing activities (Type 6) occur more frequently when TT corrections are required, thus leading to more deletions. Type-5 AUs (concurrent ST reading and typing), in contrast, show the least number of deletions, on average one deletion every 3 seconds, as compared to 667ms per deletion for Type-6 AUs.

Also, there is on average a larger number of words produced (TGnbr) per ms in the Type-5 production mode as compared to the other types of AUs. With respect to gazing patterns, Table 5 reveals that Type-1 AUs have a slightly larger percentage of linear reading (RelDur_L), as compared to Type-2 AUs (30% vs. 27% respectively), and Type-2 AUs show more re-fixations (RelDur_R) than Type-1 AUs (32% vs. 21%). Type-1 AUs also show the largest proportion of scattered fixations (RelDur_S: 40%).

Figure 2: Relation between PUBs and KBIs across nine different languages. The scatterplot on the top shows the correlation for all 521 translation sessions, the boxplots break down the distribution of log KBIs and PUBs durations into the nine different target languages. Figure 5 provides a more fine-grained sub-classification of the Spanish LogPUB data (es) for personal translation styles.

4.3. KB interruptions and PU breaks

Figure 2 plots the relation between KBIs and PUBs. As reported in several studies (e.g. Jakobsen 1999; Carl 2024, 2025), the rhythm of keystroke production in translation is largely language and translator dependent. While Carl (2024, 2025) investigates properties of the English to Arabic and Spanish translations, the two boxplots in Figure 2 show the distribution of KB interruptions and PU breaks for translations from English into seven European languages (German, Norwegian, Dutch, Spanish, Danish, Estonian and (Brazilian) Portuguese) and two non-European languages (Hindi and Arabic). As the plots show, there is clearly a difference in the typing (and thus pausing) speed between these different languages. Translations into Hindi are the slowest and most interrupted, while Spanish translators are the fastest in our dataset.

The scatterplot on the upper part in Figure 2 shows a strong correlation between PUBs and KBIs ($r=0.72$), indicating a high consistency of typing speed within words and between words (i.e. within and between linguistic boundaries) and the (assumed) temporal structure of unintentional and intentional typing halts. While it can be expected that some of these differences are due to different scripts (i.e. Arabic and Hindi), varying translator experiences and/or text difficulty among other reasons, we cannot dig into an analysis of the underlying reasons here. We just point out that there seems to be a systematic variation in the pausing/typing structure during translation production. Table 6 summarizes the variation in pausing across the 521 translation sessions. The table shows the minimum, maximum, mean, and median KBI and PUB values in ms and log ms. Note that sessions are excluded for which PUBs exceed 6 seconds and KBIs 2 seconds.

Table 6: Summary statistics for KB interruptions and PU breaks across 521 translation sessions from English into nine languages. KBI and PUB values are given in msec and LogKBI and LogPUB are in log msec.

	LogKBI	LogPUB	KBI (ms)	PUB (ms)
Mean	5.78	6.80	323	897
Min	5.23	5.93	186	376
Median	5.75	6.79	314	888
Max	7.50	8.35	1808	4230
STD	0.38	0.47	267	760

4.4. Types of AUs, translation states and translation phases

Just like KBs and PUs, also HOF states are made up of AU sequences. Across the 521 translation sessions, there are substantially more AUs in Flow states (F: 70%) than in Hesitation (H: 24%) and Orientation (O: 6%). While almost all types of AUs occur in all HOF states, the proportion and duration vary significantly.

Figure 3 shows bar plots for the proportion (left) and boxplots for the durations (right) of the six types of AUs and the three HOF states. As can be seen in the left plot, Type-8 AUs are dominant in all HOF states, almost 40% of Hesitation, more than 30% of Orientation and 20% of Flow states are Type-8 AUs. The boxplots on the right in Figure 3 show that these AUs have approximately similar durations. Second to Type-8 AUs are Type-4 AUs for Hesitation and Type-1 AUs for Orientation states, while almost 30% of the AUs in Flow states are Type-

2 AUs. The duration of Type-1 AUs is by far the longest in orientation states (right box plot). As discussed above, Type-5 AUs are least frequent; they also have the shortest durations in all HOF states (right plot).

Figure 3: Proportion of AUs across the three HOF states (left) and their log Duration (right)

Figure 4: Distribution of HOF states across translation phases

The distribution of HOF states across the three translation phases is shown in Figure 4. The figure shows that each of the three translation phases is dominated by a different HOF state: Over 60% of the states in the orientation phase are Orientations states (O), the drafting phase is dominated by Flow states (F) while states of Hesitations (H) are prevalent in the revision phase. However, there is no clear-cut separation between states and phases, as each of the three translation phases encompasses all three HOF states, albeit to a different extent.

4.5. Classifying translator styles

Mizowaki et al. (2024) have proposed a method to classify personal translation styles (i.e. translator styles) using an unsupervised constrained K-means approach. They use a set of 552 translation sessions from 275 different translators – which largely overlaps with the sessions used in this study – to determine five different types of translator styles. Each translator was automatically assigned a style label that exhibits a particular set of behavioural features. For example, a translator would exhibit a less reflective and more locally oriented translation approach (Dragsted & Carl 2013) if typing activities have frequent interruptions, few insertions and short AU durations. Other translators might show a globally oriented translation style with longer PUBs, fewer deletions and many insertions, suggesting a more deliberate and carefully planned approach. Mizowaki et al. (2024) determine the following five translator styles:

- Style 0: Few insertions, short AU duration, and short KBIs, indicating a rapid, less reflective processing style
- Style 1: Many insertions and long PUBs, indicating a more deliberate, carefully planned style
- Style 2: Very few deletions, suggesting a confident translator, with minimal revisions
- Style 3: Most of the measures are near the overall average, resulting in a balanced style
- Style 4: Many deletions, indicating an extensive revision and more cautious re-evaluation

We have re-used this method to automatically assign translator style labels to our 521 translation sessions. The distribution of translation sessions across the five translator style labels is shown in Figure 5 (left). Most sessions are assigned style label 4, while only few sessions fall under translator style label 0. However, we cannot be certain that the description of our new classification coincides with the one conducted by Mizowaki et al. (2024) since fewer translation sessions were used and the set of features in the BTSS does not exactly coincide with those features used in the Mizowaki et al. (2024) study.

The boxplot on the right side in Figure 5 shows a classification of 60 English-to-Spanish translation sessions produced by 32 different translators¹¹ according to three translator style labels. The boxplots show the relations between translator styles and LogPUBs values. The average (Log)PUBs seem consistent with the translator style description of Mizowaki et al. (2024) (see above). Individual translator styles depend largely on editing and pausing behaviour (such as KBIs and PUBs), and translators are generally consistent in their pausing behaviour across different translation sessions (Jakobsen 2002; Mizowaki et al. 2024; Carl 2024, 2025). The analysis suggests that translator styles cut across languages and that different translators working in the same language direction (here: English-to-Spanish) may realize different translator styles.

¹¹These sessions are part of BML12 (<https://sites.google.com/site/centretranslationinnovation/tpr-db/public-studies>), accessed 12. Sept. 2025). They are also contained in the total of the 521 sessions and in the Mizowaki et al. (2024) study.

Figure 5: Distribution of translator styles across 521 translation sessions (left) and the classification of 60 Spanish translation sessions and their relation to log PUBs (right).

4.6. Relating gaze patterns

Translator styles, translation phases and HOF states are characterized by typing and pausing behaviours, but the shape of gaze patterns may be equally important as they reveal the translator's visual attention on the ST or the TT. AUs of Types 1 and 5 are characterized by gazing patterns on the ST while gaze patterns on the TT result in AUs of Types 2 or 6. As proposed in Section 3.2., gaze patterns can be characterized by their proportion of linear reading (normal, continuous reading behaviour), re-fixations (eyes remains in nearly the same position or move backward), or scattered fixations (no clear reading pattern observed). We disregard thereby which words were fixated but characterize the shape of the gaze patterns and their duration, either as their proportion with respect to the total AU duration (as in Table 5) or in terms of their absolute (log) duration.

Gaze patterns, just like the other processing units of the BTSS layers (AUs, KBs, PUs etc.), are behavioural templates that can be instantiated in concrete translation situations. Thus, the BTSS constitutes a hierarchy of templates that allows us to elaborate, assess, and reproduce a joint probability model of the embedded translation processes. This joint (generative) probability model can subsequently be factorized into specific relations of the translation process in multiple ways.

For instance, the way we introduced AUs of Types 4, 5, or 6 in the BTSS specify how many keystrokes were pressed (and possibly their IKI structure) but they do not specify which keystrokes were precisely produced. Similarly, a gaze path, as we define it here, specifies a pattern of fixation and the number/total duration of the fixations, but it does not provide information about the words that were actually fixated, since these will change from one pattern to the next. While the location of individual fixations on the screen—and thus the gaze-to-word mapping—may not always be very precise in the recordings of translation sessions¹², the relative distances of successive fixation and their durations are reliable parameters of the gaze path templates. Gaze patterns provide us with a level of generalization that allows us to

¹²This may be due to lack or loss of calibration precision (possibly caused by substantial changes in head position as translators switch between different windows), significant vision impairment, the font size may be too small, the line spacing too narrow, and/or the mapping of X/Y fixation points on the screen on the word(s) that were supposedly looked at may be erroneous, among other reasons (cf. Hvelplund 2016).

contrast, for instance, the gaze behaviour of an individual translator, or a single translation session or even a small part of it against other sessions.

Figure 6 provides an example that contrasts differences and similarities of the gaze patterns for a particular translation session (BML12/P08_T5, see also Figure 1) against the gaze patterns of the entire 521 sessions. While the overall duration of AUs of translation session P08_T5 resembles the total population distribution (top left), the individual gaze patterns are shorter as compared to the average AUs in our data. This, we suspect, may be one of the features characteristics for translator style 4; it exemplifies how a translation feature of a particular translator deviates from those of the whole population.

Figure 6: Distribution of gaze patterns for one translation session (BML12/P08_T5) on the background of the lognormal distribution of the entire dataset. The four graphs account for AUs for which the respective durations, Dur , Dur_L , Dur_R , and $Dur_S > 1$, taking out all AUs that do not contain a gaze pattern of this type. While overall the duration of AUs seems to coincide with the overall distribution (top left) the duration of the specific gaze patterns seems on average shorter for P08_T5 than the average.

5. Discussion and outlook

Numerous models of the translating mind have been proposed, some of which suggest that several mental processes complement each other during translation production, and many studies have been conducted that support aspects of these models. However, at this stage, the challenge is to develop statistical models that help bridge the gap between data and theory. We aim at addressing this challenge by elaborating a multi-dimensional behavioural translation style space (BTSS) which is designed to subsume all possible behavioural translation patterns¹³, and we populate this BTSS with statistical values extracted from empirical translation process data.

The BTSS consists of multi-layered behavioural translation templates that can be serialized and instantiated in concrete translation session. With this multivariate BTSS, we can, on the one hand, define behavioural prototypes and assess behavioural variations across entire populations. On the other hand, we can investigate how behavioural patterns of individual translators deviate from or overlap with those of other translators, how their behaviour relates to (subsets of) population(s), and we can assess possible reasons for these observations. The BTSS allows us to determine specific translation styles by quantifying parameters of how translators traverse the BTSS. While these trajectories instantiate specific translation styles, we can also assess and compare the variation exhibited by individual translators.

Our next step is to implement/refine a computational translation agent (Carl 2024; Mizowaki et al. 2025) that traverses the BTSS on pre-defined trajectories. The agent builds on the free energy principle (FEP, Friston 2009, 2010), predictive processing (PP, Seth 2021; Clark 2023; Hohwy 2016), and active inference (AIF, Friston et al. 2017; Parr et al. 2022). This agent will be suited to address and simulate affective, behavioural/automatized, and/or conscious translation processes.

5.1. Translator styles and translation styles

Several studies have shown that translators develop personal translation styles (which we dub translator styles) characterized by consistent individual behavioural patterns, including typing behaviour, that exhibit affective states, cognitive effort, or decision-making, etc. However, personal translation styles (i.e. translator styles) can be impacted by external parameters, such as familiarity of the text, text difficulty or translation brief. Translators may change their style of translation in line with various textual and contextual parameters, including text register, expected translation quality (i.e. the translation brief), translation directionality (L1 or L2 translation), depending on the translators' expertise, their affective attitude, etc. The realization of a particular translation style thus depends on various parameters that may interact in a non-linear fashion at any moment. Miljanovic et al. (2025), for instance, investigate the relation between individual translator styles, translation directionality (translation into or out of the first language), text register (challenging and less challenging texts), and editing procedures (type of revisions). Their findings suggest a strong interaction between translation direction and register and a large variation between participants. The BTSS may provide a suited framework to explore the scope of this variation on the background of a large corpus and to assess/quantify those (in)variances of translator styles.

¹³Here we only address translation tasks that consists of keystroke and gaze patterns. Future versions of the BTSS might include additional dimensions or processing layers, including for instance, search behaviour (e.g. internet searches, dictionary lookups, etc.), social interaction, communication with peers or customers, etc.

However, given the combinatorial complexity of these interactions and variations, an exhaustive experimental assessment of all possible translation styles and their relation to individual translator preferences seems to be out of reach. However, defining an exhaustive space of continuous features that characterize translation styles might make it possible to specify different translator styles by tracing how BTSS parameter configurations change under varying conditions. Only a subset of the possible interactions may need to be experimentally investigated, thereby providing a limited set of experimentally established points within the BTSS while possible trajectories through the BTSS could then be approximated, given appropriate parameter settings.

5.2. Translation agent

Each of the innumerable instantiations of the BTSS provides a snapshot of possible translation behaviours for any one moment in time. In order to explore that space in a systematic fashion, a computational translation agent would traverse the BTSS and simulate expected translation behaviours for a given piece of text as a specific trajectory. That is, the computational agent would be given a source text with a translation and simulate translation behaviours (i.e. a translation style) that fits a pre-defined configuration, e.g. novice translation, informal translation, etc. The computational agent would thus simulate a detailed account of the (cognitive) effort that different translators would exert when translating the text provided. The agent may also trace or pursue novel translation styles for a set of provided translation settings simulating different levels of expertise, text difficulty, translator preferences, etc. As an agent is, by definition, in constant interaction with its environment, variations and new trajectories of the BTSS may be expected. An appropriate framework will thus be necessary that would evaluate the produced behavioural data by, for instance, comparing it with a gold data set.

We propose the computational agent to be implemented as a multi-layered POMDP (partially observable Markov decision process) using the PyMDP.¹⁴ An available prototype implementation of the agent comprises three hierarchical layers—*affective (A)*, *behavioural (B)* and *cognitive (C)*—each operating on a distinct time scale and jointly govern translation behaviour. The A-layer captures the translator’s emotional states as specified through the HOF taxonomy. The C-layer accounts for deliberation and planning that result in PUBs. The B-layer controls concrete translation actions (e.g. typing or eye movements) and tracks progress via Alignment Groups that map ST tokens to their corresponding TT tokens.

By framing the agent as a POMDP, the system receives observable cues while estimating the translator’s unobservable affective and cognitive states. The PyMDP API offers multiple observation modalities and hidden state factors that may be suited to address multiple dimensions of the BTSS. The relationship between hidden state factors and observation modalities is modelled through an observation likelihood. This observation likelihood specifies the probability of observing a particular input, for instance four words in linear reading, given the hidden state. The transition between hidden states is conditioned on actions, such as typing. On the one hand, actions indirectly influence (future) observation modalities by altering hidden state factors. Hidden state factors, thus, determine how observations are generated. On the other hand, actions are chosen to minimize the (expected) free energy for each translation style parameter independently.

¹⁴A Python library for modelling Markov Decision Processes is:
https://github.com/infer-actively/pymdp/blob/master/docs/notebooks/using_the_agent_class.ipynb

At each time step, the agent can update its internal states based on observations in a Bayesian fashion and select the next action (e.g. continue typing, pause for a more re-reading of the ST, or revise recently typed TT). This choice is guided by active inference, which aims to minimize future ambiguity and cost (i.e. expected free energy). Through repeated cycles of observation, state estimation, and action selection over embedded layers of the hierarchical architecture, the agent recreates the temporal dynamics of the translation process. Furthermore, nested active inference loops across the three ABC layers enable the model to capture differences in temporal granularity among affective, cognitive, and behavioural processes.

5.3. Bottom-up vs. top-down processing

PP posits two complementary processing directions: 1) bottom-up processes, in which observations may generate prediction errors when they mismatch top-down predictions. 2) top-down processes in which higher-level cognitive states, such as expectations, beliefs, or priors, influence how sensory inputs are interpreted. The resolution of these processes is mediated by a precision parameter, which modulates the balance between sensory-driven (bottom-up) and model-driven (top-down) influences. This bidirectional interplay is essential for adaptive and efficient agent behaviour. Actions further integrate these processes by enabling active exploration, reducing uncertainty, and optimizing perception and decision-making.

The affective and cognitive layers of the agent play a crucial role in altering precision parameters in different ways. Affective states (e.g. anxiety, motivation, surprise, curiosity) may increase precision for sensory inputs, heightening vigilance (bottom-up emphasis). In contrast, cognitive processes (e.g. reasoning, planning) would refine predictions and update hidden state representations (top-down influence), including predictions about grammatical structures sentence formulation (see Lehka-Paul 2020, Section 2.5.). The two layers may engage in an emotion-cognition interaction in which affective states regulate precision allocation, impacting cognitive strategies and behavioural outputs. Precision parameters may then dynamically weight the influence of bottom-up vs. top-down signals, adjusted by affective states while cognitive processes shape predictions, and behaviour enacting corrections.

5.4. Outlook

At present, numerous assumptions of the agent's functioning remain provisional, as they have not yet undergone direct optimization using empirical data. In future, we intend to base the observation likelihood parameters and transition probabilities on distributions derived from BTSS. Another technical challenge pertains to how the model should control the duration of each state. For instance, it remains unclear how long a Flow state should persist or when C-layer reflective activities would transition back to a Flow mode. What information should precisely be transmitted between the different layers and at what point in time. Although the BTSS specifies individual differences in the translators' working styles, our current agent implementation does not yet provide a fully developed set of probabilistic parameters to capture these variations. Further theoretical development and data analysis will be required to refine how state transition probabilities and likelihoods can account for diverse translation styles within the model. By asking what triggers transitions between those different mental processing layers, how do translators plan ahead, and why do automatized routines shift to reflective thought or revision, the suggested computational agent integrates insights from cognitive

science and bilingualism (Van Gompel 2013; Kaan & Grüter 2021) into the dynamics of cognitive control, memory, and planning to evaluate and enhance its theoretical foundation.

We believe that the suggested topology of the BTSS in conjunction with a PP/AIF-based computational translation agent has the potential to generate novel insights into the interactions between affective, reflective, and routinized translation processes in expert and novice translators, and may establish a game changing paradigm shift for investigating the effects of feeling and thinking of the translating mind. A simulation approach in cognitive translation and interpretation studies (CTIS) might thereby bridge the gap with broader enquiries in cognitive science and bilingualism, advancing our understanding of the interplay between intuitive and deliberative mental processes.

Data Availability Statement

The data used in this article are freely available and can be downloaded from the CRITT website <https://sites.google.com/site/centretranslationinnovation/tpr-db/> The Python scripts that produces the BTSS can be downloaded from GitHub <https://github.com/Critt-Kent/Behavioral-Translation-Style-Space> (accessed 2025-12-09).

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The effect of automatic speech recognition on Iranian interpreters' cognitive load: An fNIRS study

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Abstract

In the dynamic landscape of language interpreting, the integration of technology has ushered in a new era, marked by the advent of computer-assisted interpreting (CAI) tools. However, while the promise of improved communication through these tools is evident, a crucial facet demanding scrutiny is the intricate relationship between computer-assisted interpreting and the cognitive load experienced by interpreters. The present study was an attempt to use functional Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (fNIRS) to compare the cognitive load experienced by interpreters when utilizing a CAI tool, in this case automatic speech recognition (ASR), versus interpreting without such a tool. To this end, 12 interpreters were asked to perform two tasks: 1) simultaneous interpreting with the help of ASR (ASR-SI) and 2) interpreting without ASR (NoASR-SI). fNIRS records changes in the concentration of oxyhemoglobin [ΔHbO_2] and deoxyhemoglobin [ΔHbR] as it is sensitive to hemodynamic changes in the blood. Therefore, the interpreters' cognitive load in both tasks was measured using the analysis of the HbO_2 signals, which are an indicator of brain activation, and a paired t test was used to determine if there was a significant difference between the means of concentration changes of the two tasks. The results showed that the left temporal cortex (LTC) was significantly activated ($p < 0.05$) during simultaneous interpreting from English into Persian. Furthermore, the mean of changes in concentration of HbO_2 revealed that more cognitive load was experienced in interpreting without ASR compared to interpreting with ASR, meaning cognitive load was reduced when using ASR. In addition, participants' feedback regarding the integration of ASR into interpreting was investigated through a questionnaire. The findings showed that participants' subjective perceptions of ASR did not fully correspond to the objective neural activity recorded during simultaneous interpreting with and without ASR support.

Keywords: fNIRS; simultaneous interpreting; cognitive load; computer-assisted interpreting; automatic speech recognition

1. Introduction

1.1 Interpreting

Interpreting is a complex and long-standing practice, distinct from translation, as it existed before the development of writing (Pöschhacker 2016: 9). According to Seleskovitch (1976: 96), interpreting involves both understanding and rendering ideas, requiring the interpreter to simultaneously handle two roles in language and communication. Unlike other forms of communication, interpreting requires the same individual to both express ideas and understand another speaker's ideas at the same time. This very feature of interpreting makes it a demanding activity in terms of cognitive load and mental effort (Mousavi Razavi 2020). Building upon this understanding of the inherent cognitive complexity of interpreting, Gerver (1976) further refines the concept by defining interpreting from a cognitive psychology viewpoint. He

conceptualizes it as a sophisticated form of human information processing, encompassing “perception, storage, retrieval, transformation, and transmission of verbal information,” and emphasizing its susceptibility to various linguistic, motivational, and situational factors (Gerver 1976: 167). Thus, both perspectives converge on the notion that interpreting is not merely a linguistic transfer, but a complex cognitive operation subject to a multitude of influencing variables.

1.2 Cognitive load in interpreting

Over time, the concept of cognitive load in interpreting has attracted considerable academic interest. Scholars from both within the field of interpreting studies and from other disciplines have investigated this issue, recognizing its potential to deepen our understanding of the cognitive demands involved in interpreting and to contribute to the development of more effective training methods and performance strategies (Seeber 2013). This growing interest stems from two key motivations: the need to conceptualize and analyze the complex and demanding nature of interpreting, and the desire to explore how interpreters navigate these challenges (Chen 2017).

Both Seeber (2013) and Chen (2017) define cognitive load in interpreting within the framework of limited cognitive capacity, but they emphasize different aspects of the concept. Seeber (2013) characterizes cognitive load as the proportion of an individual’s finite cognitive capacity that is occupied by a given task, highlighting the inherent constraints of the cognitive system. In contrast, Chen (2017: 643) defines cognitive load more specifically in the context of interpreting, describing it as “that portion of an interpreter’s limited cognitive capacity devoted to performing an interpreting task in a certain environment”. While both definitions acknowledge the finite nature of cognitive capacity, Chen’s perspective introduces an environmental dimension, suggesting that cognitive load is not only task-dependent but also influenced by external factors within the interpreting setting.

Gile’s Effort Model (2009) is a prominent model in interpreting studies which emphasizes the cognitive aspects of language. According to this model, simultaneous interpreting involves managing multiple cognitive demands, including listening, translating and speaking in real-time. Therefore, managing cognitive load is critical for interpreters, as excessive cognitive load could lead to omissions, substitutions, and other errors (Pöschhacker 2016). Error analysis in interpreting could then be insightful when speaking of cognitive load and performance quality (Barik 1971; Altman 1994; Anazawa et al. 2012; Mirzaee & Mousavi Razavi 2021).

Different models and methods have been used by various scholars to measure cognitive load (cf. DeLeeuw & Mayer 2008; Ayres et al. 2021; Ouwehand et al. 2022). Cognitive load measurement methods are essential tools in understanding how much mental effort individuals expend during various tasks. Paas et al. (2003) and Schultheis and Jameson (2004) refer to a taxonomy of different methods ranging from subjective and analytical methods to performance and psycho-physiological methods.

Among these methods, the psycho-physiological method offers a significant advantage in measuring cognitive load by directly assessing physiological responses that naturally fluctuate with cognitive changes. This direct assessment bypasses the subjective biases inherent in self-reported data, offering a more objective measure since these responses are involuntary (Seeber 2013). Among these methods neuroimaging techniques were the most widely used ones, enabling researchers to find a way to the interpreters’ “black box” (Seeber 2013). To

date, different studies have been conducted on translation and interpreting based on neuroimaging techniques such as positron emission tomography (PET) (Price et al. 1999; Rinne et al. 2000), electroencephalography (EEG) (Petsche et al. 1993; Kurz 1995; Szarkowska et al. 2016), functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) (Ahrens et al. 2010; Hervais-Adelman et al. 2014), and functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) (Lin et al. 2018; Ren et al. 2019; He & Hu 2022; Yan et al. 2024).

In this study, fNIRS was employed to assess the cognitive load of interpreters. As a non-invasive neuroimaging technique, fNIRS monitors fluctuations in oxygenated and deoxygenated hemoglobin concentrations, which reflect neural activation in the brain. Compared to EEG, fNIRS offers better spatial resolution, while it surpasses PET and fMRI in temporal resolution, making it a versatile tool for studying brain activity (Ren et al. 2019; Zhuang et al. 2022). Its robustness to motion artifacts and environmental noise, along with minimal body constraints, enables high ecological validity, particularly in naturalistic settings such as bilingual reading, translation, and interpretation (Ren et al. 2019; Yan et al. 2024).

1.3 Related neuroimaging studies

Kurz (1995) used electroencephalography (EEG) to explore the neural correlates of directionality during shadowing (repeating the speech word for word) and simultaneous interpreting (SI) tasks. However, the tasks were not performed verbally rather mentally (without actual speaking). The findings highlighted the critical involvement of the temporal regions, particularly the left temporal lobe, in language processing, especially when interpreting into one's L2. This aligns with Petsche et al. (1993), who used EEG to demonstrate that interpreting into one's second language (L2) demands greater cognitive load compared to interpreting into one's first language (L1). Further supporting this, Szarkowska et al. (2016) employed EEG and self-report measures to examine cognitive load during intralingual and interlingual interpreting. Their results indicated that interlingual respeaking imposed a higher cognitive load, though interpreters reported lower mental effort, suggesting a connection between interpreting proficiency and respeaking competence.

Price et al. (1999) utilized positron emission tomography (PET) to investigate brain activation during translation and language switching. Similarly, Rinne et al. (2000) conducted a PET study to examine the cognitive demands of SI between L1 and L2. Their findings revealed that interpreting into L1 primarily activated the left frontal region, while interpreting into L2 elicited more extensive activation across the left fronto-temporal area. Recent research has continued to utilize brain imaging methods, such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) to gain a better understanding of interpreting.

Ahrens et al. (2010) conducted a preliminary fMRI study involving student interpreters to compare brain activity during simultaneous interpreting and free speech production. The results revealed significant differences in neural activation, emphasizing the heightened cognitive demands of SI. Unlike free speech, which primarily engages language production areas, SI activates additional regions responsible for dual-language processing and rapid information transfer, particularly the left superior temporal sulcus. Complementing this, Hervais-Adelman et al. (2014) used fMRI to compare brain activity during SI and shadowing in multilingual participants. Their findings indicated that both tasks modulated activity in the superior temporal lobe, with overlapping neural activation patterns, suggesting shared cognitive mechanisms between SI and shadowing.

Functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) has been employed in a limited number of studies within Translation and Interpreting Studies. Lin et al. (2018) combined behavioral measures and fNIRS to assess cognitive effort during pairing (linking translation-equivalent structures between the source language (SL) and target language (TL) stored in long-term memory during SI), transphrasing (explaining what/where the item is rather than giving its direct equivalent in the TL), and non-translation (producing the sound of the SL item rather than giving its direct equivalent in the TL) tasks. The study revealed cognitive overload in the left prefrontal cortex (PFC) during SI, though the ecological validity of the findings was limited due to the use of word-level stimuli and a narrow focus on one brain region. More recently, He and Hu (2022) used fNIRS to investigate the neural mechanisms of simultaneous interpreting, comparing professional interpreters and non-interpreter bilinguals. Their results demonstrated distinct brain activation patterns and functional connectivity in interpreters, highlighting the impact of expertise on cognitive processes. Both groups, however, relied on the right dorsolateral prefrontal hub during interpreting, suggesting a shared neural resource for managing the task's demands. Another study utilizing fNIRS was conducted by Yan et al. (2024) who monitored the hemodynamic response in participants' brains during consecutive interpreting tasks. By using fNIRS, the researchers could effectively capture the neural correlates of mental workload (MWL) and identify specific brain regions involved in the interpreting process, such as the inferior frontal gyrus, middle temporal gyrus, and inferior temporal gyrus.

1.4 Computer-assisted interpreting tools

In the dynamic landscape of language interpreting, the integration of technology has ushered in a new era, marked by the advent of computer-assisted interpreting (CAI) tools. These sophisticated tools, with their focus on enhancing efficiency and quality in interpreting, contribute to the ongoing transformation of language-related professions in the face of technological advancements (Prandi 2018: 29). However, as of now, interpreters have access to a restricted variety of CAI tools, and their features may not comprehensively address every stage of the interpreting process (Prandi 2018: 30). In the similar vein, Tripepi Winteringham (2011: 89) notes that in general, the progress of technology in the field of interpreting has been notably slow, especially when contrasted with the rapid pace of technological integration observed in written translation.

However, while the promise of improved communication through these tools is evident, a crucial facet demanding scrutiny is the intricate relationship between computer-assisted interpreting and the cognitive load experienced by interpreters (cf. Prandi 2018). It is well established that interpreters face inherently high cognitive demands, as they must seamlessly process linguistic nuances, cultural contexts, and real-time information. With the introduction of CAI tools into this demanding domain, questions arise regarding their influence on the cognitive load experienced by interpreters. However, despite the breakthrough these tools are making, only a limited number of studies has been dedicated to the use of computer-assisted interpreting tools in interpreting, particularly in an Iranian context (Costa et al. 2014; Fantinuoli 2017b, 2017a, 2018; Prandi 2018).

The first exploratory study conducted to examine whether the use of CAI tools leads to an increase or a decrease in cognitive load was by Prandi (2018). Some years later, Mellinger (2023) adopted a socio-cognitive lens to explore the interplay between technology and interpreter cognition, emphasizing key constructs such as embedded and embodied cognition,

extended cognition, and distributed cognition. In her doctoral dissertation, Frittella (2024) provides a comprehensive examination of the cognitive implications of CAI tools in interpreting and offers practical, evidence-based recommendations for integrating these tools into interpreter training programs.

Advancements in automatic speech recognition (ASR) and, more recently, artificial intelligence (AI) have opened new possibilities for providing interpreters with fully automated support during SI (Fantinuoli 2017b). Several studies have explored the impact of ASR in SI of numbers (Desmet et al. 2018; Defrancq & Fantinuoli 2021; Pisani & Fantinuoli 2021). As Pöchhacker (2016: 188) observed, ASR is widely recognized as a technology “with considerable potential for changing the way interpreting is practiced”. Similarly, Fantinuoli (2023: 65) suggests that “the use of raw speech recognition or speech translation could prove to be an effective means to decrease interpreters cognitive load and improve performances”. However, this issue needs to be experimentally evaluated. The present study thus aimed to explore the impact of ASR as an instance of CAI tool on Iranian interpreters’ cognitive load and sought to find answer to the following question: How is the interpreters’ cognitive load different when they use ASR while interpreting compared to when they do not use it?

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

The study involved 12 participants including 10 men and 2 women (mean age = 39.08 ± 3.77 years). Two key criteria were employed for participant selection. First, all participants were required to complete an online English proficiency test provided by the British Council, with a minimum required level of C1 to ensure advanced language proficiency. Second, participants needed to have at least two years of experience in the interpreting market and be actively earning a living through this profession.

All participants were physically and mentally healthy, with no reported history of neurological or psychiatric conditions, nor were they using any medications. Furthermore, all individuals had normal or corrected-to-normal vision and exhibited normal color perception.

All participants had either a Master’s or a PhD degree and took part in the experiment voluntarily. They were native Persian speakers and had English as their second language (L2). Prior to participation, each subject provided informed consent, and as a token of appreciation, they received a small gift. The research was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Allameh Tabataba’i University in Tehran (IR.ATU.REC.1403.041), and the protocol was carried out according to the relevant guidelines.

2.2 Task description and procedure

To conduct the fNIRS study, the National Brain Mapping Laboratory (NBML) of the University of Tehran was chosen as the setting of the experiment as it offers a wide range of services for cognitive studies including EEG, fMRI, fNIRS, EMG, TMS, tDCS, and eye-tracker. This study involved two tasks: (1) simultaneous interpreting with the assistance of ASR (ASR-SI) and (2) simultaneous interpreting without ASR (NoASR-SI). To create fNIRS-compatible tasks, a preparatory process was undertaken to select and modify the materials. A TED Talk video by Al Gore on climate change (available at

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rUO8bdrXghs>, accessed 2024-05-27) was selected. An eight-minute segment from the beginning of the 29-minute video was chosen for interpretation into Persian. The video was divided into eight one-minute segments to facilitate task design.

For the ASR component, the SpeechTexter system (accessible via <https://www.speechtexter.com/>) was used. The accuracy of the ASR system was assessed by comparing its output to the existing transcriptions of the video, revealing a 98% accuracy rate. However, since this system does not support the Persian language, it was only usable for speech transcription of the English version of the video while being interpreted into Persian. As a result, the reverse direction of interpreting—Persian to English—was not explored in this study.

Four alternating video segments (1, 3, 5, and 7) were designated for ASR-assisted interpreting, while the other four (2, 4, 6, and 8) were designated for interpreting without ASR. To demonstrate this setup, the video and the ASR webpage were displayed side by side using cascaded windows, ensuring both were visible simultaneously (see Figure 1). To avoid potential internet connectivity issues on the experiment day, the videos were pre-played alongside ASR, and the sessions were screen-recorded. These pre-recorded sessions ensured seamless playback during the experiment without requiring a live internet connection.

Figure 1: Preview of the cascaded windows

The finalized videos were sent to the lab expert for programming and integration into the experimental task design using MATLAB software. The experimental task was structured as follows:

1. An initial 60-second pre-rest period.
2. A task block of simultaneous interpreting with ASR (ASR-SI), followed by a 60-second rest period.
3. A task block of simultaneous interpreting without ASR (NoASR-SI), followed by a 60-second rest period.
4. A final 60-second post-rest period.

This cycle was repeated four times. At the start of each task block, a 2-second red fixation cross appeared at the center of the screen as a cue. The eight blocks (four for each task) were presented consecutively, with a 60-second rest period after each. After the final block, a post-

rest period of 60 seconds concluded the session. This structured design ensured consistent timing and allowed for the measurement of hemodynamic responses during both task and rest periods. Figure 2 shows the process of the experimental task.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the experimental task design. The session included four cycles, each consisting of interpreting with ASR (ASR-SI) and without ASR (NoASR-SI) blocks, separated by 60-second rest periods

2.3 fNIRS data acquisition

The present study employed a 48-channel fNIRS system (OxyMon fNIRS, Artinis) at the National Brain Mapping Laboratory in Tehran. The fNIRS system was used to record concentration changes in oxyhemoglobin [ΔHbO_2] and deoxyhemoglobin [ΔHbR] as it is sensitive to hemodynamic changes in the blood. The device transmits two wavelengths of near-infrared light (730 nm and 850 nm), with a sampling frequency of 10 Hz, allowing for the measurement of hemodynamic changes in the cortical brain regions. These hemodynamic responses were analyzed using the Modified Beer-Lambert law which describes the relationship between light absorption and concentration changes of hemoglobin in tissue (Orbig et al. 2000; Tornov et al. 2000).

The fNIRS signals were collected from 24 channels, comprising 10 transmitters and 10 detectors. The placement of these channels was informed by prior neuroimaging studies which identified active brain regions involved in translating and interpreting process, such as the inferior and dorsolateral frontal region (Rinne et al. 2000; Hervais-Adelman et al. 2015; He et al. 2021), prefrontal regions (Rinne et al. 2000; Quaresima et al. 2002; Hervais-Adelman et al. 2015; He et al. 2017), Broca's area (Tommola et al. 2000; He et al. 2017), and the left temporal area (Kurz 1995; Hervais-Adelman et al. 2015). However, due to the fixed format of the channel patches, as shown in Figure 3, as well as the limitations in the lab, the channels were positioned to correspond with only two of the above-mentioned regions. Specifically, the channels were strategically placed across two primary regions of the brain: the medial prefrontal cortex (MPFC) and the temporal cortex (TC). Each of these regions was further subdivided into the right and left hemispheres, with the MPFC additionally partitioned into a central region, resulting in the following subdivisions: left MPFC (LMPFC), central MPFC (CMPFC), right MPFC (RMPFC), left temporal cortex (LTC), and right temporal cortex (RTC). To ensure comprehensive coverage of the target brain regions, three optode probe patches were employed, including one patch with 20 channels and two patches, each containing 4 channels. A fixed inter-channel distance of 3 cm was maintained between each transmitter and detector, resulting in an approximate cortical penetration depth of 1.5 cm. Figure 3 illustrates the spatial distribution of the channels. This configuration was designed to optimize spatial resolution while maintaining a standardized inter-optode distance, ensuring robust and reliable hemodynamic measurements. The blue circles represent receivers, the yellow circles

denote transmitters, and the white ones indicate the 24 channels utilized in the fNIRS setup. The location of the channels in each region is as follows: Channels 1, 2, 3, and 4 are in RTC, channels 5, 6, 7, and 8 are in LTC, channels 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15 are in RMPFC, channels 16 and 17 are in the center (CMPFC) and channels 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23 and 24 are in LMPFC.

Figure 3: fNIRS channels configuration. The blue circles indicate receivers, the yellow circles denote transmitters, and the white circles represent the 24 channels. Channels are distributed across the Right Temporal Cortex (RTC: 1–4), Left Temporal Cortex (LTC: 5–8), Right Medial Prefrontal Cortex (RMPFC: 9–15), Central Medial Prefrontal Cortex (CMPFC: 16–17), and Left Medial Prefrontal Cortex (LMPFC: 18–24)

2.4 fNIRS data analysis

Functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) is a powerful tool for monitoring neuronal activity, but its signals are often contaminated by physiological noise and motion artifacts. A critical step in this process involves identifying and removing physiological noise and motion artifacts, which are inherent to fNIRS signals. Physiological noise is primarily attributed to hemodynamic fluctuations, such as variations in cardiac pulsations (0.8–1.2 Hz), respiration (0.1–0.5 Hz), and blood pressure including Mayer waves (~0.1 Hz). Motion artifacts, on the other hand, are primarily caused by body movements, particularly head motion (Dadgostar et al. 2013). fNIRS data typically requires preprocessing to ensure accurate analysis. The best cognitive signal band was extracted using the discrete wavelet transform (DWT) to overcome these difficulties and successfully filter signals in the 0.003–0.08 Hz frequency range. By removing motion artifacts and physiological noise, which mostly appear above 0.08 Hz, this method creates a clean fNIRS-HbO₂ dataset for further examination. This preprocessing pipeline enhances signal reliability by mitigating systemic noise and artifacts, ensuring robust insights into cerebral neural activity (Einalou et al. 2015; Dadgostar et al. 2016; Einalou et al. 2017; Dadgostar et al. 2018; Shirzadi et al. 2020; Shirzadi et al. 2024; Asadi et al. 2025).

As established in fNIRS-related literature, this specific neuroimaging technique is effective in detecting changes in blood oxygenation. Therefore, in order to assess the activation of a specific area in the brain, one can measure the regional concentration changes in oxyhemoglobin and deoxyhemoglobin. Simply put, when a specific brain region is activated, HbO₂ increases whereas HbR decreases. Given the fact that HbO₂ is the most sensitive indicator of blood flow changes, only HbO₂ signals were analyzed in this study. Thus, the concentration changes in oxyhemoglobin were computed across all the 24 channels for each participant and for both tasks. These HbO₂ signals were then averaged in each of the five determined brain regions to be considered as an indicator of activation. Finally, a paired *t* test was performed to determine significant differences in brain activation between ASR-SI and NoASR-SI in the afore-mentioned brain regions (e.g., LMPFC, CMPFC, RMPFC, LTC, and RTC). The process of fNIRS data analysis is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Block diagram of the fNIRS data analysis pipeline

3. Results

3.1 fNIRS results

The fNIRS results indicated that, in most channels, the average concentration changes of HbO₂ during ASR-SI were lower than those observed in NoASR-SI. These findings suggest that interpreting with the help of ASR is associated with a reduced cognitive load, while interpreting without ASR appears to increase cognitive demand. Consequently, it can be inferred that ASR functioning as a CAI tool, potentially alleviates the cognitive burden on interpreters.

In other words, an increase in the average concentration of HbO₂ indicates a greater supply of oxygen, which is associated with increased neural activity in that specific brain region. Given that cognitive load is linked to heightened neural activity, a rise in HbO₂ concentration suggests that the region is more actively engaged in processing cognitive demands. To assess activation differences between the ASR-SI and NoASR-SI, HbO₂ concentration changes were measured in five brain regions and a paired *t*-test was conducted to identify brain regions that exhibited significant activation differences between the two conditions.

The statistical analysis revealed a significant difference in activation in the left temporal cortex (LTC), with a *p* value = 0.02 (*p* < 0.05). This indicates a notable distinction between ASR-SI and NoASR-SI in the LTC. Further examination of the mean of concentration changes in HbO₂ for the relevant brain regions (see Figure 5) showed that, in the LTC, HbO₂ levels were lower during ASR-SI than NoASR-SI. This reinforces the conclusion that the ASR tool can effectively reduce the cognitive load experienced by interpreters.

Figure 5: Mean concentration changes in HbO₂ across the five brain regions (LMPFC, CMPFC, RMPFC, LTC, and RTC) for all subjects (**p* < 0.05)

3.2 Participants' assessment of the integration of ASR

This section presents the behavioral results of the study based on data collected through a questionnaire. After the experiment, participants were asked to provide feedback regarding the integration of Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) into the interpreting process. They were specifically inquired about their preferences, any distractions caused by the tool, and its overall effectiveness. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows that more than half of the participants (58.3%) expressed positive opinions, indicating that they found the tool beneficial and believed it could enhance the interpreting process. However, only 41.6% of these subjective opinions aligned with the brain activity data obtained from fNIRS measurements.

Table 1: Comparison of mean brain activity of ASR-SI vs. NoASR-SI in LTC and its alignment with participants' opinion

Participants	Mean Brain Activity of ASR-SI vs. NoASR-SI in LTC	Participants' Opinion (Positive/Negative)	Aligned with Brain Data? (Yes/No)
Subject 1	ASR-SI < NoASR-SI	Negative	No
Subject 2	ASR-SI < NoASR-SI	Negative	No
Subject 3	ASR-SI < NoASR-SI	Positive	Yes
Subject 4	ASR-SI < NoASR-SI	Negative	No
Subject 5	ASR-SI < NoASR-SI	Negative	No
Subject 6	ASR-SI < NoASR-SI	Positive	Yes
Subject 7	ASR-SI > NoASR-SI	Positive	No
Subject 8	ASR-SI < NoASR-SI	Positive	Yes
Subject 9	ASR-SI > NoASR-SI	Positive	No
Subject 10	ASR-SI < NoASR-SI	Positive	Yes
Subject 11	ASR-SI > NoASR-SI	Positive	No
Subject 12	ASR-SI > NoASR-SI	Negative	Yes
Percentage		Positive: 58.3% Negative: 41.7%	Yes: 41.7% No: 58.3%

Five participants provided critical feedback regarding potential distractions. For instance, Subject 1 reported that the tool was distracting, particularly when the interpreter fell behind and needed to refocus to catch up. Additionally, he expressed dissatisfaction with the real-time transcription of words, suggesting that a complete sentence transcription, akin to subtitles in films, would be more useful. Nevertheless, Subject 1 acknowledged the tool's utility in interpreting specific names and numbers. Subject 2 also found the tool confusing, particularly when it was unclear what to focus on. She mentioned that she looked away from the text to concentrate on the interpretation. Furthermore, she reported a case of a homophone (die/dye) being mistyped, which led to confusion. Similarly, subject 4 noted the tool's distracting nature, although he found it occasionally helpful for interpreting vernacular terms. Subject 5 highlighted a similar issue, stating that he was distracted by the text, which hindered their ability to focus on the speaker's voice. Notwithstanding, he found the tool useful for recognizing unfamiliar words, numbers, and proper names. Last, subject 12 mentioned that he was distracted while using the tool and he could have performed better without it. He emphasized that if the ASR showed a larger segment of the text, not line by line, that would be more helpful.

On the other hand, seven participants provided positive feedback about the tool's utility. Subject 3 suggested that the tool could expedite the mental analysis or decoding of the intended message. Subject 6 appreciated how the tool alleviated some cognitive load and praised its dynamic, real-time display, in contrast to the static nature of subtitles. Subject 7 appreciated how the tool alleviated some cognitive load and praised its dynamic, real-time display, in

contrast to the static nature of subtitles. Subject 8 noted that the tool helped reduce overthinking but expressed concern that it might impede the interpreter's speed. Subject 9 considered the tool as a significant aid, mentioning that it helped in some cases find the term you doubt you had heard. Subject 10 mentioned that the tool allowed for better focus on the cohesion of interpreted sentences by reducing cognitive load. Subject 11 described the tool as handy, accessible, and useful, emphasizing its clarity and ease of use in real-time interpretation.

When analyzing the mean of concentration changes in HbO₂ in the left temporal region (LTC) which was significantly active in this experiment, an intriguing discrepancy emerged between participants' subjective perceptions and their actual cognitive load during the interpreting process (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). The data revealed that participants' self-reported experiences did not always align with the objective measures of their cognitive effort. For example, subjects 1, 2, 4 and 5, who expressed a critical stance toward the use of automatic speech recognition (ASR) tools in interpreting, exhibited a higher cognitive load when performing interpreting without ASR compared to when they had access to it. Conversely, subjects 7, 9, and 11 who expressed positive attitudes toward the tool displayed a higher cognitive load while using it, as reflected in the mean of HbO₂ concentration changes.

4. Discussion

This study is one of the first to use functional Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (fNIRS) to compare the cognitive load experienced by interpreters when using a Computer-Assisted Interpreting (CAI) tool, specifically Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR), versus interpreting without it. Additionally, it explores interpreting between English and Persian in this context, which has not been widely studied. Interpreters in the study performed two distinct tasks consecutively, each repeated four times. Task 1 involved interpreting with the use of ASR (ASR-SI), while task 2 required interpreting without ASR (NoASR-SI). fNIRS neuroimaging was employed to monitor the interpreters' neural activity during the tasks. The results of the fNIRS data revealed activation in the left temporal cortex (LTC) during simultaneous interpreting from English to Persian, a finding that aligns with previous neuroimaging studies, which have also reported activation in this region of the brain during interpreting tasks (Kurz 1995; Rinne et al. 2000; Ahrens et al. 2010; Hervais-Adelman et al. 2014). However, the results of a study by He and Hu (2022) on Mandarin-to-English interpreters showed activation in the right dorsolateral prefrontal hub, highlighting some variation in brain activation patterns depending on the language pair and the interpreter's task.

In practical terms, the results of the fNIRS data suggest that interpreting without ASR imposed a greater cognitive demand on linguistic processing compared to interpreting with ASR, leading to increased neural activity in this area. The absence of significant effects in the other four regions could be due to task-specific demands, individual variability, or the possibility that these regions were not as critically engaged in the cognitive processes required by the tasks. It is likely that LTC region was more involved during the SI process compared to the other four regions.

Furthermore, understanding which brain regions are activated during a specific task can provide valuable insights for designing targeted activities, tasks, or training programs that strengthen those areas for future cognitive demands. In the context of interpreter training, these findings can be used to develop classroom activities that enhance the neural mechanisms

essential for interpreting, ultimately improving cognitive efficiency and performance in professional settings.

Beyond the neural activation patterns, the primary objective of this study was to determine whether the use of CAI tools, specifically ASR, impacted the cognitive load of interpreters. This question had not previously been explored using fNIRS, and the existing literature on the relationship between CAI tools and cognitive load is limited. One of the earliest researchers to address this issue, Prandi (2018), examined the connection between CAI tools and cognitive load, primarily from a theoretical perspective. More recently, Mellinger (2023) emphasized the importance of considering how the integration of technology in interpreting affects cognitive processes. In her doctoral thesis, Frittella (2024) explores the cognitive impacts of CAI tools on interpreting and delivers practical, research-supported strategies for their integration into interpreter training programs.

The analysis of changes in the concentration of oxygenated hemoglobin (HbO₂) in this study indicated that the use of ASR resulted in lower levels of HbO₂ compared to interpreting without ASR. This suggests that the use of ASR facilitated the interpreting process, significantly reducing the cognitive load required by the interpreters. These findings are consistent with those of Defrancq & Fantinuoli (2021), who investigated the impact of ASR integrated into the InterpretBank tool. Their study, which assessed both interpreters' performance through an error matrix and their subjective perceptions via a questionnaire, found that ASR improved interpreter performance. This can further be interpreted as follows: A reduction in the cognitive load can lead to better performance which can further support the conclusion that CAI tools like ASR ease the cognitive demands of interpreting tasks.

Furthermore, a comparison of the participants' opinions on ASR's contribution to the interpreting process with the average brain activity revealed a discrepancy. This finding showed that participants' perceptions of ASR did not fully correspond to the objective neural activity recorded during simultaneous interpreting with and without ASR support. For instance, the results of fNIRS data showed a decrease in the cognitive load of those who expressed a negative stance toward the use of ASR. This finding suggests that, despite their skepticism, the ASR tool effectively reduced their cognitive burden. However, these participants subjectively perceived the tool as imposing a greater cognitive strain, which may indicate a psychological or attitudinal barrier to its adoption rather than an actual increase in cognitive effort. One possible explanation for this discrepancy is the lack of familiarity or training in using the tool efficiently. If participants were provided with structured guidance on how to integrate the ASR system into their workflow, their subjective experience might improve, allowing them to better recognize and appreciate its benefits. On the contrary, those three participants who expressed positive attitudes toward integrating the tool into the interpreting process, displayed a higher cognitive load while using it, as reflected in the mean of HbO₂ concentration changes. This finding suggests that while these individuals were receptive to the tool, its use may have required additional cognitive resources, potentially due to the complexity of multitasking or the challenge of integrating the tool effectively within the interpreting process.

Overall, these findings underscore the inherently subjective nature of self-reported experiences, highlighting the limitations of relying solely on personal perceptions to assess the tool's effectiveness. Instead, objective physiological measures, such as changes in HbO₂ concentration, offer valuable insights into the cognitive demands associated with different interpreting conditions. Ultimately, the results suggest that proper training and increased familiarity with ASR technology could enhance both the subjective experience and the actual

cognitive efficiency of its use, thereby maximizing its potential benefits in the interpreting process.

In conclusion, the results of this study provide novel insights into the relationship between the use of CAI tools, specifically ASR, and cognitive load in interpreters. The results indicate that the use of ASR can significantly reduce cognitive load, as evidenced by lower HbO₂ levels in the brain. We might propose that, intuitively, a lower cognitive load *could* facilitate faster and more accurate interpretation. This assumption aligns with common sense, as reduced cognitive load may free up mental resources for more efficient processing. However, without empirical evidence to support this claim, further research would be necessary to substantiate it. These findings contribute to the growing body of research on the integration of technology in interpreting and highlight the potential benefits of CAI tools for improving interpreter performance while reducing mental effort. Future research should continue to explore these dynamics across different language pairs and interpreting contexts to further validate and expand upon these results.

5. Conclusion

While this study provides valuable insights into the cognitive load of interpreters using automatic speech recognition (ASR), several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the laboratory setting, while necessary for controlled experimentation, may limit the generalizability of the findings to real-world interpreting scenarios. Participants' behavior in a controlled environment may not fully reflect their natural responses in professional settings, potentially influencing the study's external validity. Additionally, controlled conditions can sometimes induce artificial responses, which may not entirely capture the complexities of real-time interpreting.

Second, the sample size of 12 participants, although justified by the demanding nature of data collection and analysis in fNIRS studies, remains a limitation. Larger sample sizes are typically preferred for statistical analyses to enhance the reliability and generalizability of findings. However, practical constraints, such as the time-intensive nature of data processing and the challenges in recruiting interpreters with our desired criteria, influenced the feasibility of a larger participant pool. Future studies could aim to include more participants to strengthen statistical power and further validate the results.

Despite these limitations, this study contributes to the ongoing discourse on interpreter training and technology integration. Future research could explore several directions to expand on these findings. One potential avenue is investigating the impact of ASR in different interpreting modes and across diverse language pairs, which could provide a more comprehensive understanding of its applicability across varied contexts. Additionally, future studies could assess different computer-assisted interpreting (CAI) tools beyond ASR, examining how various technologies influence cognitive load and interpreter performance.

Further research could also incorporate additional variables, such as gender differences, text complexity, modality, efficiency, and accuracy, to assess their impact on cognitive load. These factors could provide deeper insights into how different elements interact with interpreters' cognitive processes. Moreover, applying alternative measurement techniques alongside fNIRS could enhance the robustness of findings by offering a multi-method perspective on cognitive load assessment.

Overall, by acknowledging these limitations and exploring new research directions, future studies can build upon these findings to develop more tailored, effective, and cognitively sustainable interpreting technologies. This could ultimately contribute to optimizing interpreter performance and improving the efficiency of language interpretation in both professional and training contexts.

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